

**SURVIVING THE CHALLENGES OF 21ST CENTURY RETAILING -
PROPOSING A WAY FORWARD FOR INDEPENDENT DIY
RETAILERS IN THE UK USING E-COMMERCE.**

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Abstract:

The number of independently owned brick-and-mortar DIY retailers in the UK is falling year on year due to the rise of online retailing and less footfall on the high street and town centre. This online retailing is dominated by the big retailers B&Q, Homebase, Toolstation and others. Independent DIY retailers' participation in e-commerce is marginal though, e-commerce provides many benefits to resource-constrained and geographically niched retail SMEs, connecting sellers and customers from across the world.

Researchers emphasised e-commerce adoption for the small retail business to tackle the challenges of 21st century retailing to survive and grow. However, very few independent DIY retailers adopted online retailing. Moreover, what affects independent DIY retailer's e-commerce adoption is largely unknown. Therefore, this exploratory study aimed to investigate independently owned DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges, practices and opportunities to propose e-commerce adoption strategies. By employing a qualitative in-depth interview method, using convenience and purposive sampling, this study interviewed 20 independent DIY retailers; ten retailers are non-e-commerce adopters, and the rest are e-commerce adopters.

This empirical study found that the current e-commerce adoption models for retail SMEs are impractical for the independent DIY retailers that hinder their participation in e-commerce and proposes a practical model, 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model'. This model suggests that independent DIY retailers first adopt e-marketplaces to sell locally and internationally, progressing onto creating their e-commerce channels and offer simultaneously through all the channels.

Dedication

*To my parents Md Abu Taher and Rahima Begum,
and my gorgeous daughter Aleena Ashraf Hossain.*

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It is my immense pleasure to have Dr Julia Fallon as my supervisor. I would like to express my heartfelt gratitude for her care, support, and guidance throughout the journey.

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Finally, I like to express my deepest gratitude to my beautiful wife Samanta for her sacrifice and support in the last few years. Without her ample support, I could not have made it this far.

Declaration

I declare that the work in the thesis has not been submitted for any other degree or qualification in any university or institute of learning.

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Signed:

Date:

List of Abbreviations

Acronyms	Definition
A	Adopters
CRR	Centre for Retail Research
DIT	Department for International Trade
DTI	Digital Transformation Index
DIY	Do-It-Yourself
DOI	Diffusion of Innovations
EC	Electronic Commerce
EU	European Union
IR	Independent Retailing
IS	Information System
IT	Information Technology
MNC	Multi-National Company
NA	Non-Adopters
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
ONS	Office for National Statistics
SME	Small and Medium Enterprise
RBV	Resource-Based View
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TAM2	Technology Acceptance Model Version 2
TOE	Technology–Organization–Environment Framework
TPB	Theory of Planned Behaviour
TRA	Theory of Reasoned Action
UK	United Kingdom
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
UWS	University of the West of Scotland

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter outlines the whole thesis at a glance. Firstly, it briefly discusses the study background and provides a problem statement to justify the need for this research. Furthermore, it outlines the following chapters and key findings, limitations, and future research direction.

1.1. Background

Working over 15 years in independent Do-It-Yourself (DIY) retailing in the high street, I have seen many DIY stores closures. That led me to one central question why independently owned DIY stores are closing? What can be done?

1.1.1. Importance of this study

Small DIY stores are an integral part of high streets and town centres across the UK. These independently owned DIY stores serve the community with great care and customer service offerings. Though big-box DIY retailers offer many products, they lack the personal touch and care for the customers that require face to face interactions and DIY advice from the experienced seller (CRR,2020; Mintel, 2021). Furthermore, these businesses are often family-run and employ people from the local communities. Therefore, it is crucial to protect these independently owned DIY stores for the heritage and diversity of the British high streets and town centres and the local community (Parker *et al.*, 2017).

1.1.2. Declining small independent brick and mortar retailing in the UK

Research published by Deloitte (2021) on independent retailing on high street and town centres suggests that independent DIY retailing is one of the largest declining categories along with fashion shops, newsagents and bookmakers in high streets across the UK.

The Centre for Retail Research (2021) suggests that 16,045 brick-and-mortar stores had been closed in 2020 despite the government employee retention scheme, business rates rebate, grants and other facilities during the pandemic. The number of store closures increased significantly. In 2020 compared to 2018, 14583 stores closed across the UK (CRR,2021; KSA,2021). Furthermore, Deloitte (2021) estimates 30,000 more independent stores will be

out of business by 2022. These data indicate that small independent retailers' future in many categories is at risk, as does the small DIY retailers, one of the fast-declining retail categories across the UK.

1.1.3. Online retailing

Figure 1: Forecast of total online retail spending in the UK.

Source: Adapted from Statista (2019)

In the UK, the share of online retailing was 19% in 2019 and predicted that by 2024, it would reach 33.8% before reaching an astonishing figure of 53% in 2028 (McCarthy, 2019) [figure 1]. However, pushed by the pandemic and the lockdown, online retail sales reached 36% of total retailing in February 2021 (ONS,2021) and continue to grow even after the lockdown eases. This acceleration of online retail sales creates unprecedented challenges for high-street retailers that are already suffering (Appendix 7).

1.1.4. DIY retailing in the UK

The DIY retail market is highly fragmented in the UK (Mintel,2020; Statista,2020; BIRA,2021). A majority share of the market is captured by big-box retailers such as B&Q, Screwfix, Homebase, Toolstation (Mintel,2020; Statista,2020). Moreover, non-DIY specialists or grocery retail chains – Argos, Sainsbury and Tesco- invested heavily in the DIY segment, making the DIY market more competitive across all the distribution channels (Mintel 2018, 2019, 2020,

2021). As a result of intense competition, independent DIY retailers are suffering significantly (CRR,2021; BIRA,2021). Moreover, less footfall on the high street (Deloitte,2021), having no or limited parking on the high street (Parker *et al.*, 2017; CRR,2021), unfavourable rent and rates contributed to the decline of independent DIY retailers (PwC, 2021). In addition, the rise of e-commerce where the specialist, non-specialists, online pure player DIY retailers dominate the market, having the know-how, capacity and financial resources (Deloitte, 2021; Clement, 2020a; Cooper, 2021). Failure to adapt to e-commerce can be attributed to the decline of independent DIY retailers. Perkins, Geddes and Harrap (2020) and Scutto *et al.* (2021) suggested that independent retailers need to reinvent themselves to adapt to the changing customer habit of buying online, which have propounded even more during the pandemic lockdown. McCarthy (2019) argued that brick and mortar retailers need to integrate online and offline to offer a more meaningful customer shopping experience that provides discovery, entertainment, and escapism. It is more important when more and more young generations are accustomed to the internet and online shopping, accounting for over half of the UK's population (Appendix 10.9).

1.1.5. Online DIY Market

DIY is one of the least mature categories in e-commerce in the UK compared to other consumer categories (Intel,2020; Statista,2020). Online DIY turnover crossed £2.1 billion in 2020 (latest available data) and grew by 14.7% like-for-like (Intel,2020). However, DIY retailing is gaining substantial development in the UK. Significantly, the lighter end of the market is top-rated and popular online across the channels due to the delivery suitability. It is speculated that the bigger-ticket items that are not suitable for delivery hinder DIY online retailing. Customers are intended to purchase bigger-ticket items in-store (Intel, 2020; Statista,2020). However, this does not justify when other large consumer items such as home appliances and furniture that are even larger have more online market penetration, 18% (Appendix 10.10).

Advances in information technology, e-commerce, and online shopping have drastically changed the retail landscape, structure, and strategies (Kim *et al.*, 2018; Hånell *et al.*, 2019). However, this shift has created new opportunities for SMEs and micro retailers to adapt to the new and changed online retail ecosystem (Knight and Kim, 2009). Furthermore, EC

opened a new gateway for small and micro retailers to sell beyond their geographical niche and sell across the country and globally (Kacen, Hess and Kevin Chiang, 2013; Yrjölä, Saarijärvi and Nummela, 2018; OECD,2020; DIT,2021).

All the leading market research organisations (PwC, 2021; Deloitte, 2021; EY,2021; Mintel, 2020; CRR,2021; Statista,2021) emphasised the digital transformation for the small independent retailer to survive in the changing retail landscape. Independent DIY retailers need to embrace this massive channel shift in the last decade and recently forced by the pandemic. Importantly, this online shopping trend will continue even after the lockdown eases (Rigby,2021; PwC,2021). These reports and scholars stressed redesigning retail stores, enhancing digital transformations, and personalising the multichannel experience to customers to tackle the new retailing.

However, a recent report in June 2021, published by the Open University in collaboration with 'Be the Business', found that 77% of SMEs owners do not have the required technical skill to adopt and implement new technology. In addition, SMEs owners acknowledge the need for technology adoption for productivity and competitiveness, yet they fail to adopt new technology such as e-commerce. (Paul, Impey and Stewart, 2021).

1.1.6. The current state of IT adoption among small independent retailers

Leading tech company Dell Technology introduced the Digital Transformation Index (DTI) in 2016, and they publish DTI report every two years, last published in 2020. This highly sophisticated report is based on more than 4300 companies in 13 different categories, including companies from the retail and consumer category and 18 other countries from America, Asia Pacific, and the EU.

The report found that lack of resources and budget, 30% of businesses surveyed, lack of skill and in-house expertise (24%) and slow economic growth are the critical reasons for digital transformation and technology adoption. Furthermore, government regulations and legislative changes (23%) and lack of institutional or government support (17%) for digitalisation hinder digitalisation and e-commerce adoption. However, in 2020, pandemic related disruption pushed businesses to embrace technology at least to some extent, which

raises the concern for data privacy and security (31%), and strong government legislation regarding GDPR, limiting the technology adoption and digitalisation as many small businesses are not able to comply with the regulations for data protection (Appendix 10.6).

Figure 2: Digital technology adoption Index in 2020.

Source: Author's construct, data derived from DTI (2020).

The figure 2 illustrates the digital technology adoption stage in different countries in 2020. Traditionally, it was believed the developed countries are ahead of IT adoption. However, British SMEs participation in technology adoption is significantly low (32%) compared to the global average (39%) (DTI, 2020). On the other hand, the figure shows that SMEs in India (55%), Brazil (50%) and Mexico (52%) are ahead in digital technology (e-commerce) adoption. Remarkably, this report supports the findings from OECD (2019,2020).

This can be seen among the independent DIY retailers as their e-commerce presence is significantly low (Mintel, 2021). Moreover, the number of independent DIY retailers is shrinking yearly (Mintel,2018,2019,2020,2021; CRR,2021). Therefore, retail SMEs are losing to harness the opportunities to sell at the local and cross-border markets.

1.1.7. Cross-border e-commerce trade

Cross border e-commerce is the trade between different countries using the internet via e-commerce through the website or intermediary platforms (Deng and Wang, 2016; Huang and Chang, 2019; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020). The figure 3 shows the percentage of online

orders UK SMEs (over ten employees) received geographically through websites (ONS, 2021; Eurostat (2021). Reports from ONS (2021) and Eurostat (2021) highlighted those British businesses received a significant number of orders from Europe and the rest of the world. Furthermore, over 48% of sales made in the UK through e-commerce platforms eBay and Amazon came from abroad (DIT,2021; eBay,2021). This clearly shows that online retail gained substantial customers from the international markets (Appendix 10.11).

Analysing eBay and Amazon sales shows that some small independent DIY retailers are already selling their products in the UK and offering globally (Eurostat, 2019, Cambridge Econometrics, 2020). But nothing has been done to understand why most DIY retailers are not adopting e-commerce through websites or intermediary e-commerce platforms (Amazon, eBay) and take the opportunity of selling beyond their geographical niche area. This gap in understanding requires further investigation of how small independent retailers can harness these opportunities of selling internationally using e-commerce.

Figure 3 Share of UK business making website sales geographically, 2018.

Source: Adapted from ONS (2021)

However, small independent DIY retailers that are geographically confined cannot harness the opportunity of selling at cross border markets. E-commerce adoption could elevate the chance for independent DIY retailers. Though, this is not the primary objective of e-commerce

adoption. Primarily, DIY retailers would reach more customers at-home market through the e-commerce adoption. Furthermore, they will have the opportunity to expand to the cross-border markets through e-commerce platforms, facilitating the market opportunity and logistical and other related support.

1.2. Problem Statement

Independent DIY retailers play a vital role in the diversity of the high street and town centres and serve the local community with better customer service. However, their participation is marginal in e-commerce. Leading market research firms and overwhelming academics stressed small independent retailers' e-commerce adoption. However, being an essential and significant retail segment, very little attention has been paid to DIY retailing in academia (Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019). Recent market research (Mintel,2020; Statista,2020; CRR,2020; Deloitte, 2021; PwC,2021) highlights a significant shift in customers shopping behaviour and channel choice. In addition, academics (Zahra, 2020; Effendi, Sugandini and Istanto, 2020; Amasanti, 2020; Skeldon, 2021; Rigby, 2021c; Sousa *et al.*, 2021; Paul, Impey and Stewart, 2021) emphasised integrating to online channels from brick-and-mortar stores in the post COVID world.

The retail researcher stressed that the survival and success of small independent retailers would be determined by the ability to integrate different retail channels in the coming days with the emergence of new channels and touchpoints such as websites, mobile apps, social media are already inhabited in the way customers purchase today (Sorescu *et al.*, 2011; Chen, Cheung and Tan, 2018; Jin and Shin, 2020). However, previous research shows that small retailers are in their infancy of channel integration, where large retailers dominate online retailing in most countries (Beck and Rygl, 2015; Verhoef, Kannan and Inman, 2015; Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019; Thaichon, Phau and Weaven, 2020; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Therefore, it is imperative to study small retail business and their e-commerce adoption challenges.

However, existing research on SMEs e-commerce adoption is multidisciplinary and unable to address the category-specific understanding. Retail SMEs are unique and differs in many ways from one to another. Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) and Van Looy (2021) argued that businesses are made of people and processes, and small business owners exert a significant

influence and control the decision making. Therefore, it needs to be investigated how the owner's characteristics, the firm's specific aspects, and other environmental factors affect independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption.

Furthermore, little is known about the market expansion at the cross border for DIY retailers. Scholars emphasised the further research exploring the CBeC opportunity, practice and challenges (Valarezo *et al.*, 2018; Lee, 2020; Hånell *et al.*, 2020; Tolstoy *et al.*, 202). Therefore, this study investigates the e-commerce adoption challenges, practices and opportunities for independently owned DIY retail in the UK.

1.3. Gaps in the Literature

Existing literature extensively focused on SMEs e-commerce adoption. However, most of the studies are multidisciplinary and their findings are generic and unable to address category-specific challenges and warranted category-specific research. In addition, no academic studies have been published yet, examining the e-commerce adoption challenges of independent DIY retailers in the UK or anywhere in the world. Furthermore, it is yet to identify whether the current e-commerce adoption models are practical for the independent DIY retail sector in the UK. Finally, no studies explore the challenges, practices, and opportunities of cross-border e-commerce (CBeC) for independently owned DIY retailers in the UK.

1.4. Research Aim

To examine the e-commerce adoption challenges, practices and opportunities to develop strategies for e-commerce adoption and market expansion for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

1.5. Research Objectives

1. To investigate the individual characteristics and capabilities of independent DIY retail business owners to explore the challenges of e-commerce adoption.
2. To examine other micro and macro challenges that affect e-commerce adoption of independent DIY retailers in the UK.
3. To explore cross border e-commerce for independent DIY retailers in the UK by examining the existing literature and current practice.
4. Critically analysing the findings to reveal the challenges in practice to develop a model for e-commerce adoption and cross border e-commerce.

5. To recommend an e-commerce adoption strategy for the future success of independent DIY retailing in the UK.

1.6. Research Questions

- What are the existing market research and relevant literature to inform the identification of e-commerce adoption challenges for British independent DIY retailers?
- How independent DIY retail owner's individual characteristics and capabilities affect e-commerce adoption?
- What technological, organisational, and environmental challenges affect e-commerce adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK?
- What are the current practice, challenges, and opportunities of selling internationally using e-commerce?
- What are the current challenges in practice for e-commerce adoption and implementation?

1.7. Contribution to the theory

- This empirical study contributes to the body of knowledge by adding an in-depth understanding of British independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges and market expansion opportunities at cross border using e-commerce.
- This research contributes to the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework by including unique elements.

1.8. Contribution to the Practice

- This study contributes to the practice by adding a 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and market expansion model'.
- This study further contributes to the practice by providing a 'step-by-step' e-commerce strategy for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

1.9. Limitations of the study

Generalisation and Sample size: This study employs a small sample size for non-e-commerce adopters from London due to the convenience. Therefore, it was not known whether

independently owned DIY businesses outside of London encounter similar challenges. Therefore, this cannot be generalised as the complete scenario of independent DIY retailing in the UK. Though, e-commerce adopters represent different cities and ethnicity.

Lack of women representation: Furthermore, the findings are based on the interviews from the male respondents as the DIY industry is heavily male dominated. Therefore, women perspectives could not be included in this research. The researcher strongly believes a women perspective would have added more value to the understanding of the adoption challenges.

1.10. Thesis Structure

Chapter 1: Introduction

This chapter introduces the background and study context that justify the need for the research. Furthermore, this chapter outlines the research aim, objectives and questions. Finally, it presents the critical elements of this thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature review: DIY retailing and e-commerce.

This chapter critically discusses the key research areas related to this study. First of all, it critically analyses the DIY retailing and existing research in DIY retailing and identify the research gaps in DIY retailing. In addition, this chapter discusses the e-commerce related issues that are significant for this research.

Chapter 3: Literature Review: Theories and frameworks for technology adoption.

This chapter critically discusses the four critical theoretical frameworks for evaluating e-commerce adoption. The frameworks are the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Resource-Based View (RBV), Diffusion of Innovation theory (DOI) and Technology-Organisation-Environment framework (TOE). In addition, this study adapted TOE as the theoretical lens and further discusses e-commerce adoption challenges under the TOE framework. Finally, this chapter presents the current e-commerce adoption model.

Chapter 4: Literature Review: Cross-Border e-commerce (CBeC)

This chapter critically discusses the traditional internationalisation model and justifies their unsuitability for small independent DIY retailers' internationalisation. Furthermore, this chapter discusses the current state of cross-border e-commerce (CBeC) from different contexts. Finally, it presents the gap in the literature.

Chapter 5: Methodology

This chapter discusses the methodology and methods used in this research. This exploratory research adapted in interpretivist inductive research approach by employing qualitative in-depth interview method. This study undertook 20 in-depth interviews using convenience and purposive sampling with e-commerce adopters and non-e-commerce adopters. This chapter presents the data collection and analysis techniques.

Chapter 6: Research Findings

This chapter presents the research findings in four themes according to the research objectives. The four themes are e-commerce adoption challenges, adoption practice, CBeC, and opportunities.

Chapter 7: Analysis and discussion

This chapter critically analyses the findings and triangulates them with the existing literature. In addition, it proposes the piggyback e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model, an e-commerce strategy for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

Chapter 8: Conclusion

This chapter reflects on the research process and concludes this research. Moreover, this chapter addresses the study limitation and suggest the implication and future research.

1.11. Key Definitions

DIY: Acronym for "Do It Yourself", which denotes the non-profit activity reflected in improving one's own home through the actions that involve building, electricity, carpentry, plumbing etc.

Brick and mortar store:

A Brick-and-mortar store refers to a physical shop that can range from less than 1000 SFT to 120,000 SFT. In the UK, shop and store refers to the same meaning, though the definitions of shop and store may vary in other countries (CRR, 2021). In this thesis, shop and store are used interchangeably.

Independent Retailer:

According to the Centre for Retail Research (2021), "An independent retailer is mainly one-shop businesses also can refer to the companies with up to five stores". This study addresses independent retailers with less than five independently owned and not a part of any large corporation. (See appendix 10.1)

Online Retailers:

Online retailers are those who operate their business online.

Pure online or e-tailers: Pure online retailers are those who sell online only and deliver products to the door, such as Ocado, Boohoo, Amazon, Etsy.

Big-Box Retailer:

A speciality retailer (sells one or more categories of products) is a company that is directly involved in the sale of goods or services to end-users for personal, non-commercial use (Kotler & Armstrong, 2013) in stores with more than 4,000 square feet in size, which are generally located in the outskirts of large, populous cities.

Click-and-Mortar Retailers:

These retailers have the operation both online and offline, such as B&Q, Screwfix, Toolstation.

It should be noted that internet shopping, electronic shopping, internet retailing, e-tailing, online retailing, and online commerce are used interchangeably throughout this study because these terms are employed in the existing literature research reports.

Furthermore, e-commerce platforms, e-commerce marketplaces, and online platforms are used interchangeably throughout this study.

Cross border e-commerce (CBeC):

Cross border e-commerce is the trade between different countries using the internet via e-commerce through the website or intermediary platforms (Deng and Wang, 2016; Huang and Chang, 2019; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020).

UK: The UK includes all four countries in the United Kingdom.

Great Britain: Although Great Britain includes England, Scotland and Wales, not Northern Ireland, commonly business registered in England, Wales, Scotland, and Northern Ireland are widely known as British business.

Throughout the studies, British, Great Britain and the UK are used interchangeably as these terms are used interchangeably in reports published by ONS, Mintel, Statista.

Piggybacking:

A low-cost market entry strategy in which two or more firms represent one another's complementary (but non-competing) products in their respective markets.

1.12. Conclusion

This chapter established the study background and justified the rationale for this study. Furthermore, this chapter provided a structure of the entire thesis.

Chapter 2: Literature Review: DIY retailing and e-commerce

2.1. Introduction:

As discussed in the previous chapter, this study investigates e-commerce adoption challenges for independent DIY retailers in the UK. Furthermore, it examines the current practice and opportunities for e-commerce adoption. Finally, this study explores the market expansion at cross-border through e-commerce.

In the following three chapters, relevant literature will be critically discussed. This chapter outlines the critical issues around independent DIY retailing and e-commerce.

The next chapter will highlight the challenges of e-commerce adoption and theories and frameworks for e-commerce adoption related to this study. This chapter will also present the current e-commerce adoption model for small independent retailers.

Finally, the third chapter of the literature review will critically discuss the current state of cross-border e-commerce (CBeC), including challenges and opportunities.

2.2. What is DIY retailing?

DIY is the abbreviation for Do-It-Yourself. According to the Oxford Learners Dictionary (2021), "DIY is the activity of making or repairing things yourself, especially in your home". In addition, Cambridge Dictionary (2021) defines "DIY as the activity of decorating or repairing your home, or making things for your home by yourself, rather than paying someone else to do it for you. Furthermore, Wolf and McQuitty (2011) "Activities in which individuals engage raw and semi-raw materials and component parts to produce, transform, or reconstruct material possessions, including those drawn from the natural environment (e.g., landscaping)."

However, the term 'DIY' has taken a broader meaning covering a wide range of skill sets, leading to the widespread use of the term DIY in 'self-made-culture' of designing, creating, and repairing things without any special training (Hui and Chow, 2011). In addition, it is widely used in the term 'value co-creation,' which is a social concept of sharing ideas, design, techniques, methods, and finished projects with one another either online or in-person (Xie,

Bagozzi and Troye, 2007; Lusch, Vargo and O'Brien, 2007; Breidbach, Smith and Callagher, 2013).

Following Wolf and McQuitty (2011) definition, this study defines DIY as building, repairing, and maintaining the households, including gardening, painting, electricals, and plumbing works without expert or professional help. In the UK, DIY stores are called those that sell paint, hardware, tools, ironmongery, gardening, electricals, household items, such as B&Q, Screwfix, Homebase, and many high-street traditional hardware retailers.

Once DIY is defined, it is essential to discuss what is known in DIY retailing and why this study is critical. Therefore, the following section critically examines the current research in DIY retailing.

2.3. Research in DIY Retailing

Being an essential and significant retail and customer segment, very little attention has been paid to DIY retailing in academia (Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019). However, a few studies have investigated DIY retailing on both consumers and retailers. (Bush, Menon and Smart, 1987; Swartzlander and Bowers, 1989; Bogdon, 1996; Williams, 2004, 2008; Wolf and McQuitty, 2011; Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019). Scholars argued that DIY household and gardening purchase behaviour is different from grocery, fashion or electrical appliances purchase behaviour (Wolf and McQuitty, 2011; Amasanti, 2020). Therefore, retailers need to address that behaviour and position themselves by improving their value proposition to meet the customers' needs and expectations (Gebhardt, Carpenter and Sherry, 2006; Wolf and McQuitty, 2011).

Furthermore, to survive and thrive in the fragmented DIY market, independent retailers need to adopt the technology-based retail channel in the new digital retail landscape when brick-and-mortar retailing is shrinking due to various micro and macro factors (Amasanti, 2020; Mintel, 2020). Table 1 illustrates the previous research in DIY retailing. Surprisingly, in academia, scholars have paid little attention to DIY retailing. Existing studies have focused on the customer motivation side of DIY retailing and largely ignored the retailer's perspective (Wolf and McQuitty, 2013). This largely unexplored area requires further investigation to

understand the challenges and opportunities and practice, particularly in the age of e-commerce (Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019).

Table 1: Previous research and context in DIY retailing.

Author (s)	Research Area
Bush, Menon and Smart (1987)	Profiling the DIY segment to non-DIY segment.
Bogdon (1996)	Customer DIY decision making.
Swartzlander and Bowers (1989)	Relationship between consumer behaviour and DIY behaviour.
Williams (2004)	DIY Motives.
Williams (2008)	Rethinking of consumers DIY motives and behaviour.
Watson and Shove (2008)	DIY product and DIY practice.
Mărginean (2012)	Private label in the DIY market in Romania.
Wolf and McQuitty (2013)	Marketplace motivation from the customer perspective.
Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019)	DIY SMEs owners digital marketing adoption for success.

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

Wolf and McQuitty (2011, 2013) argued that lack of product availability and quality influenced consumers' DIY purchase and marketplace choice and proposed a conceptual model (Figure 4) for DIY motivation and channel choice.

Figure 4. A conceptual model of the motivations and outcomes of DIY behaviour.

Source: Adapted from Wolf and McQuitty (2011).

This model demonstrates customer's marketplace choice is motivated by the lack of quality products and availability. Furthermore, customisation, economic benefits, and uniqueness drive customer channel choice for DIY purchases. However, this motivation model does not reflect on the DIY retailers.

More recently, in 2019, Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) investigated the small DIY businesses owners' motivation towards digital marketing adoption using the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and DIY motivation behavioural model (Wolf and McQuitty, 2011), presented in the table 1. Their DIY behavioural model was designed to understand consumer DIY motivation and channel choice. In addition, they used the model to investigate the owner's motivation, considering the owners as a person who has the same motivation as the DIY customers. However, they found that the perceived technological benefit may motivate DIY retail businesses owners. But they failed to confirm other factors that affect the adoption of digital marketing.

It is essential to mention that most of the studies (Bush, Menon and Smart, 1987; Bogdon, 1996; Swartzlander and Bowers, 1989; Williams, 2004, 2008; Watson and Shove, 2008; Wolf and McQuitty, 2013; Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty, 2019) are conducted in the US context except for Mărginean (2012) who studied the role of private label in the DIY market in the Romanian context.

The above discussions clearly highlight a lack of understanding in DIY retailing. Remarkably, little is known about DIY retailing in the UK; furthermore, how DIY retailers react to those changes in customer channel choice and position themselves is mainly unknown. Therefore, it is crucial to address this knowledge gap, and the next section highlights the significance of the channel extension for DIY retailers.

2.4. Channel extension and online retailing

Why do independent DIY retailers need to adopt e-commerce for survival and growth?

Recent market research (Intel,2020; Statista,2020; ONS,2021) highlights a significant shift in customers shopping behaviour and channel choice. In addition, academics (Zahra, 2020; Effendi, Sugandini and Istanto, 2020; Amasanti, 2020; Skeldon, 2021; Rigby, 2021c; Sousa *et al.*, 2021) emphasised on moving to online channels from brick-and-mortar stores in the post COVID world. The current data from ONS (2021) justifies this call for online channel adoption, when online retail sales reached 36.1% in February 2021 (Appendix 10.10), exceeding the prediction for 2024.

However, the necessity of expanding online is not a new concept; it has been a long practice by the large businesses where most large retailers operate in multichannel and omnichannel driven by the emergence of the internet and pure online retail platforms eBay and Amazon (Herhausen *et al.*, 2015; Verhoef, Kannan and Inman, 2015; von Briel, 2018; Thaichon, Phau and Weaven, 2020; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, this rise of online retailers contributed to the change of customer shopping behaviour, browsing the product in the store and buying from online channels (Balakrishnan, Sundaresan and Zhang, 2014; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). This spread of online retailing and e-commerce generates many opportunities and severe threats

to small retailers (Mele, 2013; Mazzarol, 2015). the opportunities and threats rely on the retailers' ability to embrace e-commerce, otherwise become uncompetitive.

The retail researcher stressed that the survival and success of retailers would be determined by the ability to integrate different retail channels in the coming days with the emergence of new channels and touchpoints such as website, mobile apps, social media are already inhabited in the way customers purchase today (Sorescu *et al.*, 2011; Chen, Cheung and Tan, 2018; Jin and Shin, 2020). However, previous research shows that small retailers are in their infancy of channel integration, where large retailers dominate online retailing in most countries (Beck and Rygl, 2015; Verhoef, Kannan and Inman, 2015; Thaichon, Phau and Weaven, 2020; Sousa *et al.*, 2021). This can be seen in the independent DIY retailing in the UK. The reports published by Mintel (2020) and Statista (2020) shows that only 3% of customers bought DIY items from independent retailers where the online DIY market is dominated by traditional 'big-box' retailers B&Q, Homebase, Argos and pure e-tailers Amazon and eBay.

The online channels provide many substantial advantages for small retailers operating in the small geographic area (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Sorescu *et al.*, 2011; Hutchinson and Quinn, 2012). First of all, it enables small businesses to sell beyond their geographic area and target different target customer groups that are not possible from the brick-and-mortar store (Gao, Agrawal and Cui, 2021; Prasetyo *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, it allows businesses to sell at cross border through the website (Tolstoy, Jonsson and Sharma, 2016; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Effendi, Sugandini and Istanto, 2020) or third-party platforms (Zheng, 2014; Guo *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, it empowers businesses with customer knowledge that can be utilised in-store to offer better customer service resulting in more customer retention and generating more revenue (Verhoef, Kannan and Inman, 2015; Chen, Cheung and Tan, 2018; Hänninen, Kwan and Mitronen, 2020). In addition, it empowers small businesses with a competitive advantage over large retailers (Quaye and Mensah, 2018; Xuhua, Chosniel Elikem and Akaba, 2019). Small businesses are able to integrate online within the brick-and-mortar store that incurs less cost for a separate establishment.

In contrast, there is criticism that multichannel retailing is costly and online channel extension cannibalises the offline businesses and expensive to create and maintain a separate channel

(Gensler, Dekimpe and Skiera, 2007; Stojkovic, Lovreta and Bogetic, 2016; Breugelmans and Campo, 2016). Herhausen *et al.* (2015) and Prasetyo *et al.* (2021) contended that for small businesses expanding online channel, e-commerce offsets the offline store and provide a competitive synergy if they can integrate the online and offline and utilise their offline customer knowledge in the online channel. Furthermore, some scholars raised concern that gaining competitive advantage is getting increasingly difficult for small businesses as e-commerce is saturated in most of the developed countries, particularly in the UK (Lewis, Whysall and Foster, 2014; Fornari *et al.*, 2016), while others affirmed that offering a greater value and seamless shopping experience allows gain and retain customers (Yrjölä, Saarijärvi and Nummela, 2018; Patten *et al.*, 2020; Gorji *et al.*, 2021).

Overall, the discussion substantiates the significance of small and independent DIY retailers adopting and expanding e-commerce channels.

The following section will outline the e-commerce for small DIY retailers.

2.5. What Electronic Commerce (EC) means for small DIY retailers

Electronic commerce (EC) is buying and selling products or services using electronic devices such as computers and mobile through the internet (Ramanathan, 2010; Parvinen, Oinas-Kukkonen and Kaptein, 2015; Riccardo Resciniti and Federica De Vanna, 2019; Tran,2021). EC is another way of purchasing and selling like the traditional physical stores. However, EC is a small spectrum of the total e-world and e-businesses (Turban *et al.*, 2018). Electronic businesses have broader applications in today's digital world, including providing e-logistics, customer service, delivering e-learning, providing e-healthcare, maintaining e-governance and many more, not only limited to buy and sell of goods and services. (Kalakota and Whinston, 1997; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Turban *et al.*, 2018).

There has been a significant shift in the role of EC, especially during the COVID-19, in all aspects of life (Tran,2021). That shift has created the need for businesses to change their existing businesses model and adopting e-commerce. Figure 5 illustrates the EC model in e-tailing businesses. The enterprise models (Turban *et al.*, 2018) show how an e-tailing organisation can maintain relationships with suppliers, partners, employees, and customers

to increase service effectiveness and sales and maintain relationships with stakeholders, where e-commerce is part of e-businesses.

Figure 5: E-tailing as an enterprise EC system model.

Source: Adapted from Turban *et al.* (2018).

The following section discusses the types of EC activities.

2.6. E-commerce Activity Types

EC involves three fundamental activities ordering and making payment, logistics and order fulfilment and delivery to the customers. Based on that, electronic commerce can be either pure EC, partial EC (Vizard, 2013; Turban *et al.*, 2018). If all these major activities are conducted digitally, that refers to the pure EC, and at least one of these three dimensions is undertaken online, its partial EC. However, if none of the activities is conducted online, it would not consider as electronic commerce. For example, buying any software from a company that delivers electronically is deemed pure EC.

In contrast, purchasing something from Amazon and receiving a physical delivery would not be considered pure EC, rather partial EC as at least one dimension is done physically. Therefore, it is crucial to understand whether the industry is in pure EC or partial EC as a part of this research. E-commerce and e-businesses are confusing terms and often used interchangeably. However, e-commerce is a part of e-businesses (Turban *et al.*, 2018; Abdullah *et al.*, 2018).

It is essential to acknowledge that this research is focusing on the e-commerce part of e-businesses. Thus, it aims to determine how the small independent DIY retailers can convert brick-and-mortar stores to click-and-mortar stores, combining traditional high street retailing and e-commerce. Despite the exponential growth of e-commerce and call for EC adoption by scholars, it is mainly the larger businesses that reaped the benefits of e-commerce while the rate of e-commerce adoption in the small retail businesses sector has remained relatively low (Ajmal and Yasin, 2012; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Abdul Hamid and Aliman, 2020; Marolt *et al.*, 2020; Paul, Impey and Stewart 2021; Mkansi, 2021; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). Furthermore, the retail researcher argued that small retailers' unique features are limiting their ability of e-commerce adoption (Dennis, 2000; Riquelme, 2002; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Mndzebele, 2016; Wu and Gereffi, 2019; Patten *et al.* 2020; Paul, Impey and Stewart 2021).

The following sections discussed the small independent, unique features that affect their e-commerce adoption.

2.7. Features unique to independent retailers

SMEs are unique and differs in many ways from one to another. Because SMEs are not a scale down version of the large businesses (MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Ajmal and Yasin, 2012), and all SMEs are not the same categorically (Olatokun and Bankole, 2011). For example, manufacturing SMEs, service SMEs and retail SMEs differs in many ways in their characteristics and activities (Hutchinson, Quinn and Alexander, 2005; Hånell *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, retail SMEs challenges are different, mainly independently owned small retail SMEs. Thus, scholars argued that it is crucial to understand small businesses' unique features to address their challenges (Quayle, 2002; Al-Qirim, 2007).

SMEs e-commerce adoption has gained tremendous attention in academia and researched widely in different countries and contexts. Two significant studies paved the way for our understanding of small retailers' unique features and their challenges in the twenty-first century of retailing and EC adoption (Quayle, 2002; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005). First,

Quayle (2002) examined the unique features and challenges of small retailers in 298 small UK businesses in order to examine their e-commerce adoption. Another critical study carried out by MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005) investigated the EC adoption barriers among 477 small retailers in Sweden and Australia and developed a basic EC adoption model for small retailers. Subsequently, many scholars have studied EC adoption among businesses from different countries and contexts. However, both the studies were conducted among the various categories of small businesses and unable to address the category-specific understanding and warranted further category-specific investigation. Furthermore, they emphasised further research on how these unique features can be converted into a strength that can be utilised to tackle the challenges of 21 century retailing.

These two studies still guide the research in the small retail businesses for the unique features that differ small businesses from large businesses, contributing to the understanding of the unique characteristics of small retail businesses. The tables 2 and 3 outline the unique features of small businesses.

Table 2: Internal unique features of small retail businesses.

Internal or micro-features: Related to the resource and capabilities, planning process, decision-making, and management.	Related literature
Small retailers often have extensive product lines and a selection of brands in their area, unlike manufacturing SMEs with limited product lines. However, compared to large retailers, they still have limited lines.	Avermaete <i>et al.</i> (2003), Pearson and Grandon (2005), Nikolaeva (2006), Herhausen <i>et al.</i> (2015) and Breugelmans and Campo (2016).
Small retail owners have greater control over the businesses and often sole decision-maker, and they withhold information from the staff. Thus, they may exert control over the company but are often deprived of the team's shared knowledge.	Dennis (2000), MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005), Kartiwi and MacGregor (2007) and Marolt <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Small retail owners often lack trust in the staff and have no system for staff management that limits their ability to expand businesses.	Nikolaeva (2006) Abdul Hamid and Aliman (2020)
In small businesses, the decision-making process is short term and intuitive rather than strategic based on detailed planning. Therefore, they may be unable to achieve many opportunities.	Dennis (2000) Beckinsale, Ram and Theodorakopoulos, (2010)
Small retailers exhibit a need for independence and often avoid collaborating with other businesses that may affect their dominance.	Riquelme, (2002), Kartiwi and MacGregor (2007)
Owners' family value influences their businesses operation and decision making. Many small retail businesses owners are in the same trade for generations, and their family values and traditions affect their decision-making.	Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011), Riemenschneider and McKinney (2016) and Tarafdar and Vaidya (2006)
Informal record and account keeping limit their ability to gather detailed customer information to help data-driven decisions.	Brooksbank, Kirby and Kane (1992), Dennis (2000), and Pearson and Grandon (2005).
Small retailers have a lack technological knowledge. This lack of knowledge affects their decision to learn and adapt to rapidly changing new technology in retailing.	Riquelme (2002), Nikolaeva (2006), Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011), Marolt <i>et al.</i> (2020), Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) and Chau, Deng and Tay (2021).
Resource related features	
Small retailers often suffer from the lack of capital and face challenges obtaining finance and other resources; thus, they have resource limitations.	Kaynak, Tatoglu and Kula, (2005) Saffu, Walker and Hinson (2008) Elbanna, Child and Dayan (2013)

Having resource constraints limits their ability to gain capabilities in terms of products, logistics and market.	Daniel, Wilson and Myers (2002), Kartiwi and MacGregor (2007), Oliveira and Martins (2010), and Beynon-Davies (2013)
Small retailers often desire quick return on investment due to the resource limitation	Sutanonpaiboon and Pearson (2006), Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, (2011) and Herhausen <i>et al.</i> (2015).
They are more reluctant to invest in technology, therefore, have limited use of technology.	Riemenschneider and McKinney (2016) Zhen <i>et al.</i> , (2019) and (Marolt <i>et al.</i> , (2020).
They are resistant to change driven by their individual beliefs and other internal and external factors.	Oliveira and Martins (2010), Riemenschneider and McKinney (2016).
Small retailers are often unable to hire specialist staff and provide little importance on staff training.	Acilar and Karamaşa (2010), Ajmal and Yasin (2012) Abdul Hamid and Aliman (2020) Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021),

Source: Author's construct, drawn from the literature.

Table 3: External features of small independent retailers.

External/macro features	Related literature
They are geographically confined in a niche area that leads to relying heavily on fewer customers.	Quayle (2002), Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason (2009), Hutchinson and Quinn (2011,) Peltier, Zhao and Schibrowsy,

	(2012) and Beynon-Davies, (2013)
Small retailers have limited market share and control over the market that therefore, they are vulnerable to the change in the industry.	MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005), Acilar and Karamaşa (2010), and Zhen <i>et al.</i> (2019)
They are unable to compete with the large businesses in the area they serve.	MacGregor and Vrazalic, (2005), Mndzebele (2016) Wu and Gereffi (2019) and Patten <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Small businesses are product-oriented; on the other hand, a large company is customer-oriented.	Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg, (2015) and Gorji <i>et al.</i> (2021)
The failure rate is exceptionally high for small retailers compared to large retailers.	Peltier, Zhao and Schibrowsky, (2012), Gavrilă and de Lucas Ancillo (2021)
They are risk averted and, therefore, more reluctant to take the risk.	Dennis (2000), MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005), Dew <i>et al.</i> , (2009) and Liu <i>et al.</i> (2021)

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

The above table highlights the unique features that scholars argued as weaknesses for e-commerce adoption. The following section will highlight the small retailers EC adoption barriers, considering the unique features of independent retailing.

2.8. E-commerce adoption barriers

Quayle (2002) and MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005) argued that the unique features of small businesses are their strength and challenges depending on the ability to utilise those unique factors. The opportunity comes from quick decision-making control over the businesses and processes. On the other hand, challenges come from the lack of resources and skills and the inability to adapt to the new technology.

Though it is unknown what e-commerce adoption barriers and challenges exist in small independent DIY retailing in the UK, there is no previous research on DIY retailers' e-

commerce adoption challenges. However, SMEs EC adoption barriers received considerable attention in EC research (Coca-Stefaniak *et al.*, 2005; Acilar and Karamaşa, 2010; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam, 2014; Awiagah, Kang and Lim, 2016; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021). In addition, many scholars have studied the adoption drivers and barriers in different contexts and settings (MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Al-Qirim, 2007; Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Kurnia *et al.*, 2015; Badi *et al.*, 2020, Tan and Wu, 2021 Scuotto *et al.*, 2021; Zhang and Zheng, 2021).

First, the cost of EC related technology- including the adoption, implementation and maintenance cost, and uncertainty of return on investment affects EC adoption in small businesses (Avermaete *et al.*, 2003; Lertwongsatien and Wongpinunwatana, 2003; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Gavrilă and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021; Mkansi, 2021). In addition, the complexity of the EC technology usage (Grandón, Nasco and Mykytyn, 2011; Joubert and Jokonya, 2021), lack awareness of EC benefits (Saffu, Walker and Hinson, 2008; Kurnia *et al.*, 2015; Sin *et al.*, 2016), wiliness to implement EC technology due to the organisational resistance and familiarity of the traditional way of doing businesses (Parvinen, Oinas-Kukkonen and Kaptein, 2015; Badi *et al.*, 2020).

Moreover, lack of technical skills among the owner (Ramanathan, 2010; Rebiazina, Smirnova and Daviy, 2020; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021; Paul, Impey and Stewart, 2021) and a shortage of skilled staff (Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Ajmal and Yasin, 2012; Mazzarol, 2015) have a negative effect on EC adoption in small businesses.

Similarly, many small retail owners assume that their products are not suitable for e-commerce (Avermaete *et al.*, 2003; Pearson and Grandon, 2005; Nikolaeva, 2006; Herhausen *et al.*, 2015; Breugelmans and Campo, 2016). Finally, unfavourable rules and regulations and lack of institutional and government support affect EC adoption of small businesses (Simpson and Docherty, 2004; Gomez-Herrera, Martens and Turlea, 2014; OECD, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2021; Gavrilă and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021). How owner's individual characteristics, firm's resource and capabilities, and EC technology itself and other external factors of s e-commerce adoption for independent DIY retailers are discussed in detail in the next chapter (chapter 3).

The above discussions highlighted the adoption barriers, and it is crucial to evaluate what opportunity e-commerce can facilitate to the DIY retailers. Therefore, the following section discusses the EC adoption benefits for independent retailers.

2.9. E-commerce adoption benefits

Innovation and technology bring new opportunities and challenges (Abdullah *et al.*, 2018; Kickert, 2019). However, whether businesses can utilise those opportunities depends on how quickly they can adapt to the change in the macro-environment in which it operates. (Xia and Zhang, 2010; Sinkovics, Sinkovics and Bryan-Jean, 2013; Valarezo *et al.*, 2018).

Scholars argued that benefits drive SMEs e-commerce adoption (Kaynak, Tatoglu and Kula, 2005; Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam, 2014). First of all, EC enables small bricks and mortar retailers to expand beyond their geographic niche, reaching millions of more customers through e-commerce at home and cross border markets (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Sinkovics, Sinkovics and Bryan-Jean, 2013; Qi *et al.*, 2020). Although, the rise of EC cannibalised many bricks and mortar retail sectors such as books, music, electronics stores and provided many potentialities for the small businesses. Existing studies have highlighted some expected benefits for e-commerce adoption for small businesses. Table 4 presents the key benefits of e-commerce adoption.

Table 4: EC adoption benefits for small retailers.

Contexts	Details	Existing research
Economy of scale	EC adoption reduces operating costs for the retail store by integrating online and offline stores and brings productivity.	Simpson and Docherty (2004), Gregory, Karavdic and Zou (2007) Lendle <i>et al.</i> (2012) Herhausen <i>et al.</i> (2015) Alcácer, Cantwell and Piscitello (2016).
Customer service	EC adoption allows small businesses to provide improved customer service, providing customers more value.	Ajmal and Yasin (2012) Bart <i>et al.</i> (2005), Cheung and Thadani (2012), Glavas and Mathew, (2014).

Convenience	EC increases the availability of products and services to customers convenient for both the sellers and buyers.	Daniel, Wilson and Myers (2002), Gavrilă and de Lucas Ancillo (2021)
Reach	EC allows small businesses to reach beyond their geographic niche area.	Bianchi and Mathews (2016), Gomez-Herrera, Martens and Turlea (2014), Guo <i>et al.</i> (2020)
Competition	Small businesses often face competition from large companies. However, they cannot compete with those opponents having limited resources. Therefore, EC allows them to compete in online platforms through their website or third-party sites.	Prasad, Ramamurthy and Naid (2001) and Doherty and Ellis-Chadwick (2010), Kumar, Tiffany and Vaidya (2014)
Access to information	Through EC, small businesses able to achieve significant insight into customers and the market.	Saffu, Walker and Hinson (2008), Lertwongsatien and Wongpinunwatana (2003), Mathews, Healy and Wickramasekera (2012) Guo <i>et al.</i> (2020).

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

The previous sections highlighted the need for e-commerce adoption and its potential benefits. However, it is important to discuss ways of e-commerce entrance for small independent retailers. The following sections discuss the e-commerce adoption channels.

2.10. E-commerce channels

There are many channels considered as a part of the online channel, such as own website, third-party e-commerce platforms, social media marketplaces and apps. The following sections discuss the three common e-commerce channels: website, e-platforms, and social media marketplaces.

2.10.1. Website as an online channel

Website is the most traditional channel of e-commerce and widely used for e-commerce entrance. It allows businesses to connect with large customers locally and globally (Bart *et al.*, 2005; Di Fatta, Patton and Viglia, 2018; Huang and Chang, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020). Especially for small retailers who do not have a strong presence through offline establishments, the website provides a unique opportunity to reach millions of potential customers beyond the area they can serve by the physical store (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Tolstoy *et al.*, 2020). However, the success of an e-commerce website as a sales channel is complex, requires skill to develop and maintain (Bart *et al.*, 2005; Di Fatta, Patton and Viglia, 2018). Furthermore, it requires upfront and continuous investment to drive traffic to the website (Gensler, Neslin and Verhoef, 2017; Feldman, 2019). In addition, converting website visitors into active buyers is challenging for any business that operates in an online channel (Patel, 2012; Riaz *et al.*, 2020; Lăzăroiu *et al.*, 2020).

Some argued that the upfront cost of creating and maintaining a website and the poor conversion rate limits small businesses' success in e-commerce. SMEs are often unable to sustain such ventures, therefore, lagged the big companies (Gensler, Neslin and Verhoef, 2017; Feldman, 2019). In comparison, others contended that the website presentation, loading speed, and the seamless navigation affect the e-commerce website's success (Ramanathan, 2010; Thimm, Rasmussen and Gohout, 2016; Feldman, 2019).

In the next section, website presentation and negotiations are discussed critically.

2.10.1.1. Presentation and navigation

Presentation of a website refers to the appearance, layout, and sequence of the website's images as customers view a website as a storefront, unlike the brick-and-mortar store (Bart *et al.*, 2005; Ramanathan, 2010; Work, 2011). For example, Ramanathan (2010) examined 484

e-commerce websites and found that customers use various criteria to judge the website quality before making a purchase decision and suggested that a good website should have a simple design, with helpful product information and correctly displayed price with all the relevant product and service descriptions in details along with after-sales service and terms and condition for returns and refunds. Others echoed the same and added that comparative price information, easy filtering option, products photos influence customer purchase intention (Chen, Lu and Wang, 2017; Lăzăroiu *et al.*, 2020).

Thimm, Rasmussen and Gohout (2016) examined success determinants of e-commerce websites, investigating 1000 websites based in Germany and Sweden and found that website quality and speed motivate customers to purchase the site. Similarly, Gensler, Neslin and Verhoef (2017) argued that the loading speed affects sales conversion rate and the bottom line, and customers are unlikely to return to the sites. A study found that customers customer buying behaviour and preference are constantly changing, and they prefer loading speed more than the aesthetic look of the website (Work, 2011). Because customer buying behaviour and web page are scattered, they often multitask while browsing (Feldman, 2018). This is supported by Patel (2021), who branded e-commerce customers as a moving target as they continuously switch to other websites, social media, and messaging apps.

Therefore, an organised and user-friendly website that offers swift and easy navigability contributes to customers' purchase intention leading to a higher conversion rate and increased bottom. However, customer trust in a website plays a crucial role in their purchase intention. The following section discusses customer trust on SME websites.

2.10.1.2. Website trust

Customer trust is a crucial factor for an e-commerce website as the conversion rate heavily depends on customers' trust on the website (Molinillo *et al.*, 2021). As discussed in the previous section, website quality and navigation affect customer purchase intention and conversion (Thimm, Rasmussen and Gohout, 2016). All those factors are found to have a direct co-relation to build initial trust on the website. Customers evaluate some more criteria when they make their purchase (Wu, 2019).

Fulfilment and the delivery option provided on the website influence customer trust (Ritala, Golnam and Wegmann, 2014). In addition, brand strength of the website, absence of error in the product information, order fulfilment option and confidence affect customer trust (Phaneuf, 2021). After-sales service is another crucial factor for customer trust in the e-commerce website. Customers cannot physically inspect the product and rely on the seller to send their expected orders. If any dispute happens during the order and delivery, customers expect sellers to resolve the conflict. This factor has a significant influence on customer trust in the e-commerce website. Therefore, providing a detailed description of the after-sales service a substantial role in the customer purchase decision.

Most importantly, customers are concerned about their data privacy, considering the risk of their details such as name, address, phone number and email and financial information such as bank details. Therefore, assurance on the website plays a vital role in customer trust on the website, resulting in sales (Feldman, 2019).

The discussion, as mentioned earlier, shows the success of e-commerce as a sales channel depends on the website design, ease of use, responsiveness, and retailers' capabilities of providing comparative price, quick delivery, and providing after-sales service as assuring customer data privacy. However, all these factors limit small retailers' ability to compete with the large retailers in the e-commerce channel. And therefore, lagged the e-commerce adoption (Di Fatta, Patton and Viglia, 2018).

The following sections discuss third-party e-commerce platforms.

2.10.2. E-commerce platforms as an online channel

An E-commerce platform is another e-commerce channel like website and social media marketplaces (Saffu, Walker and Hinson, 2008; Balakrishnan, Sundaresan and Zhang, 2014). As e-commerce progressed with the rise of the internet, so did the third-party e-commerce platforms, often called e-platforms and e-marketplaces, interchangeably (Goldsby and Eckert, 2003; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). These platforms offer businesses to businesses (B2B), businesses to consumers (B2C) (Fornari *et al.*, 2016). For example, Alibaba is a leading B2B marketplace, while AliExpress, eBay and Amazon are the top B2C platforms. Researchers argued that the importance of e-platforms and contribution to e-commerce is

undeniable (Awiagah, Kang and Lim, 2016; Wagner, Schramm-Klein and Steinmann, 2018). E-platforms are a parallel channel of companies own websites. Interestingly many large companies adopted e-commerce platforms despite having their own established website. For example, Curry's PC World and Argos, the most renowned brands in the UK, which has vast offline and online channels-website, apps, adopted e-marketplaces (Argos, 2021; Outlet | eBay, 2021). Similarly, DIY retail giants Homebase (Homebase,2021) and Toolstation (Toolstation, 2019) are actively selling on eBay and Amazon along with their own online and offline channels.

Furthermore, this practice is established in the UK and many other countries (Zhen *et al.*, 2019). For instance, Walmart China has a strong offline and online presence in China. Still, they adopted JD.com, one of the biggest Chinese e-commerce platforms, and sell through JD.com (Walmart, 2021).

As discussed in the previous section, a website as an online channel encounters many challenges: creating and maintaining, driving traffic (Riaz *et al.*, 2020), poor conversion rate (Chen, Lu and Wang, 2017), payment gateway (Lăzăroiu *et al.*, 2020), logistics and fulfilment (Ritala, Golnam and Wegmann, 2014), and achieving customer trust (Ritala, Golnam and Wegmann, 2014). In contrast, e-marketplaces have many loyal, active customers in the local market and across the world (Rebiasina, Smirnova and Daviy, 2020; Reuschke and Mason, 2020; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021). In addition, e-platforms provide support to those who sell on the platforms, which is essential for small businesses. For example, e-platforms have their payment gateway (PayPal, 'eBay Managed Payment'), fulfilment and logistical service (Amazon FBA) and many others that are crucial for e-commerce (Matina Stevis-Gridneff, 2018; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021).

However, despite the aforementioned benefits, e-marketplaces as an adoption channel are neglected in academia (Kacen, Hess and Kevin Chiang, 2013; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). Many scholars have seen e-marketplaces as a part of multichannel for channel extension for both the large and small retailers rather itself as a primary online channel (Chen and Chen, 2017; Zhang, He and Shi, 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Zhen *et al.*, 2019; Zhang and Zheng, 2021). Furthermore, existing literature emphasised e-platforms as the way for market

expansion at the cross border (Wang *et al.* 2015; Valarezo *et al.*, 2018; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020; Guercini, Ranfagni and Runfola, 2020; Tolstoy *et al.*, 2021).

Zhen *et al.* (2019) examined the timing of starting e-commerce channels. They recommended that businesses adopt third-party channels only if they have their website and dare discouraged from adopting e-platforms if they do not have their own online channel. Such adoption would bring little benefits to agency fees and intense competition. This supports the previous study by Chen and Chen (2017) Chen *et al.* (2018), who investigated the agency fees and competition effect on e-marketplace adoption. However, all these studies argued that the relationship between own online and e-marketplaces is complementary (Chen and Chen, 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2018; Zhen *et al.*, 2019).

The above discussions show that e-marketplaces can provide many benefits for small retailers, but the feasibility of those channels' adoption is still a point of argument. Therefore, the current state of e-platforms use needs to be investigated among the independent DIY retailers in the UK.

The following section will discuss the social media marketplaces as an e-commerce channel.

2.10.3. Social Media Marketplaces as e-commerce channel

Social media has become a necessary foundation of communication and marketing tools (Liang and Turban, 2011; Wang and Wang, 2020; Fraccastoro, Gabrielsson and Chetty, 2021). Researchers argued that it enables small businesses to harness the opportunity locally and internationally that was never possible before the rise of social media (Andersson and Wikström, 2017; Drummond, McGrath and O'Toole, 2018). Social media (Facebook, Twitter, Instagram and LinkedIn) as a communication and marketing tool and their impact on businesses of all sizes are largely known. On the other hand, the role of the social media marketplace as a selling platform for small retailers is relatively unexplored (Wang and Wang, 2020; Fraccastoro, Gabrielsson and Chetty, 2021). Although social media marketplaces, such as Facebook Marketplace, Instagram, is relatively new, it has gained popularity in some retail categories, such as beauty and fashion.

Existing studies identify that the social media marketplace is primarily driven by the interaction of like-minded people who interact with each other in the social media, particularly groups, blogs, that share common interest thus involve in the exchange of goods or services (Han, Xu and Chen, 2018; Molinillo *et al.*, 2021). Some argued that the difference between the seller and buyer based on the interaction on social media platforms through the exchange in the community where buyers and sellers build trust, but in traditional e-commerce channels, such as websites, buyers often have confidence in the seller (Yahia, Al-Neama and Kerbache, 2018; Hyun, Thavisay and Lee, 2021).

While others argued that trust is the most significant factor in social media as an e-commerce channel, having regulations in place. the opportunist can often deceive customers through fake reviews, comments. (Horng and Wu, 2019; Pham, Shancer and Nelson, 2019; Bhattacharyya and Bose, 2020)

However, it is yet to understand the current practice of social media marketplace in independent DIY retailing in the UK. Furthermore, it also needs to explore that whether social media marketplaces are suitable for DIY products.

2.11. Emerging issues in e-commerce practice

2.11.1. Return, cancellation, and Refund

Online return is a challenge for e-commerce across Europe; on average, 30% of total online shopping has returned. A customer has the right to cancel or change mind within 14 days of receiving the order with or without any reason, which is guaranteed by the EU law (European Union, 2021). This EU law applies in the UK until any new law comes in place.

Customers are highly habituated with the free return, especially many who use Amazon Prime and enjoy free returns on anything bought from the platform. Moreover, for most prominent brands, free return is the norm. Therefore, a return policy is crucial for customer decision making, as the study found that 92% of customers intend to make a repeat purchase if the seller offers a free return (Lazar, 2018). The same survey also found that 60% of customers review shipping and return policies before making a purchase decision. From the seller

viewpoint, this can be problematic as profit margin varies from category. However, the fashion clothing category has the most significant return.

2.12. Conclusion:

This chapter critically discussed the existing research in DIY retailing that highlighted little understanding of DIY retailing in academia. Furthermore, it examined how the small retailers' unique features limit their ability to adopt e-commerce along with the barriers to e-commerce entrance. Finally, it critically discussed the e-commerce channels to enter e-commerce for small businesses. However, it can be drawn from the discussion that there is a knowledge of the understanding of DIY retailing and its e-commerce adoption challenge. The next chapter discusses the theoretical frameworks related to this study.

Chapter 3: Literature Review: Theories and frameworks for technology adoption

3.1. Introduction

Many theories and frameworks are used in order to evaluate innovation and technology adoption. For example, researchers have used Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), Resource-Based View (RBV), Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) and Technology- Organisation- Environment (TOE) framework extensively. This chapter discusses these four vital theoretical frameworks for small retailers' e-commerce adoption. Finally discusses the adopted framework (TOE framework) in detail.

3.2. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

TAM is the widely used theoretical framework for determining user technology acceptance (Turban *et al.*, 2018). Davis (1989) first proposed TAM model of how users accept the new technologies based on the Fishbein and Ajzen (1975) Expectancy Value Theory and the Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) by Ajzen and Fishbein (1980) that were widely practised in the field of psychology (Venkatesh, 2000).

The TRA framework posits that individual behaviour intention is guided by attitudes and subjective norms influenced by normative beliefs and motivation (Hendrickson, Massey and Cronan, 1993). Thus, individual behaviour is the function of beliefs and attitudes. Figure 6 shows the TRA framework, which is the foundation of the TAM.

Figure 6: The Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA).

Source: Adapted from Turban *et al.* (2018).

Meanwhile, based on TRA, TAM proposes that individual perceived usefulness and ease of use shapes the personal attitude that leads to the intention to accept the technology. In Figure 7, TAM framework is presented. TAM consists of two variables: perceived usefulness and perceived ease of the technology.

Figure 7: First modified version of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

Source: Adapted from Davis (1989).

The two critical variables are perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use (Davis, 1989). Perceived usefulness refers to the user's perception of the usefulness of the new technology usage (Venkatesh and Davis, 2000, p.187), while 'perceived ease of use' refers to the perception of how easy and user-friendly the technology is (Davis, 1989). In the initial TAM model, Davis (1989) argued that these two factors influence an individual acceptance of new technology that led to the actual system use.

Since the inception of TAM, it has been widely used to evaluate technology adoption in various fields at an individual level. For instance, MS word processor (Davis, Bagozzi and Warshaw, 1989), e-collaboration (Dasgupta, Granger and McGarry, 2002), e-service (Taherdoost, 2018) and electronic voting (Okediran *et al.*, 2020)

Although TAM has been widely used to evaluate the extent of user acceptance of the new technology, it has several limitations (Casey, Pennington and Mireles, 2020). It only counts potential users' perception of the usefulness and the technology and does not consider other

micro and macro factors that may influence their perception (Moore and Benbasat, 1991; Lucas *et al.*, 2007; Kimiagari and Baei, 2021).

Furthermore, Lucas *et al.* (2007) criticise that the TAM was developed to consider voluntary individual participation of computers, word processors, and spreadsheets. Still, the marketplace has moved the bundle-solution such as CRM, SCM and so on. In addition, the rapid change of those systems added complexity to the adoption, and TAM fails to address those complexities (Baker, Al-Gahtani and Hubona, 2010).

Baker, Al-Gahtani and Hubona (2010) argued that the TAM model does not consider the institutional influence. Therefore, it is not suitable to use in the organisational context. Many researchers, however, applied TAM in organisational use and rejected it (Hu *et al.*, 1999; Lee, Kozar and Larsen, 2003; King and He, 2006; Williams *et al.*, 2009).

More recently, Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) used TAM for examining DIY SME owners' digital marketing adoption in the USA. They combined TAM (Davis, 1989) and the DIY behaviour model (Wolf and McQuitty, 2011) and considered DIY owners as individuals who have greater control over the businesses. However, they concluded that, though the owner is an individual, their attitude and perception are vastly different regarding technology adoption for the businesses, driven by the micro and macro factors. Therefore, as they hypothesised, the owner's perception and attitude towards digital marketing adoption are more likely to be influenced by other factors.

Ever since, researchers independently attempted to update the original TAM having limitations to address the innovation and technology adoption in the rapidly changing technology field (Baker, Al-Gahtani and Hubona, 2010). Consequently, Venkatesh and Davis (2000) proposed TAM-2 as an extended version of TAM, adding six more contemporary elements of technology adoption. Figure 8 shows the TAM-2.

Figure 8: TAM-2, an extension of Technology Acceptance Model (TAM).

Source: Adapted from Venkatesh and Davis (2000).

However, researchers believed that TAM-2 became obsolete (Duffy, 2001; Lin, 2007). Therefore, Venkatesh and Bala (2008) proposed TAM-3, adding more relevant features to the original TAM and TAM-2 model.

Since this study considers the EC adoption in independent DIY retailers' context, which involves owners' characteristics and organisational and macro-environmental factors, TAM has not been selected for the EC adoption framework. However, the two essential contexts will not be avoided; instead, they will be included in the chosen TOE framework.

3.3. Resource-Based View (RBV)

Resource-based view is a managerial framework that has been widely used to evaluate the competitive advantage using all the tangible and intangible strategically (Hoopes, Madsen and Walker, 2003; Sheshdari, 2013). Though it is a managerial framework, it has been widely used to understand how the technology, information system adoption challenges in a different context, considering the resource as crucial for the technology and EC adoption (Galan, Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020). RBV is mainly used for and compatible with the large organisation context with separate IT resources (IT infrastructure). The researcher argued that RBV could not address the challenges for small businesses, considering that this

model only focuses on the resource, ignoring other micro and macro factors (Taher, 2012; Ruivo, Oliveira and Neto, 2015).

3.3.1. RBV Consideration

Resources is the primary consideration of RBV (Taher, 2012). The resource can be defined as all the tangible and intangible things that can be utilised in producing a product or service for the company (Barney, 1991; Collis, 1994; Wade and Hulland, 2004). Wade and Hulland (2004) highlighted the critical resource characteristics such as value, rarity, appropriability, imitability (brand loyalty), and non-substitutability. They argued that these resource characteristics bring a competitive advantage. Barney (1991) examined the relationship between resource and sustained competitive advantage and found that imitability, rareness, value, and sustainability assure the competitive advantage. However, their focus was on the field of strategic management.

Others contended that RVB has a narrow focus on employing resources to achieve a sustainable competitive advantage that does not consider other factors that influence technology adoption (Aziz and Samad, 2016; Quaye and Mensah, 2018). In the case of retail SMEs, very few small retailers can fulfil those criteria that RBV explains as rarity and imperfect imitability, and therefore RBV cannot reflect the SMEs (Taher, 2012; Galan, Mashenene and Kumburu, 2020). Remarkably, the small retailers cannot achieve a sustainable competitive advantage as their primary businesses model sells many brands (Boateng *et al.*, 2011). Moreover, small independent retailers compete in a market where many competitors offer their customers the same products and brands. Therefore, RVB has minimal practical implication in the case of retail SMEs as finding resources or capabilities that are rare, inimitable is extremely difficult, if not impossible (Hu and Liu, 2013; Collins, 2020).

3.4. The Diffusion of Innovation (DOI)

The DOI (the Diffusion of Innovation) framework also assesses technology adoption at an organisation level. DOI explains why and at what rate an innovation, a new idea, and technology spread through the organisation, society, or country (Roger, 1962,2003). DOI

consists of five elements: relative advantage, perceived usefulness, compatibility, image, visibility, and voluntariness.

Roger (1962) believed that any new ideas, innovation, or technology adoption depend on the individual's characteristics as perception and motivation set the likelihood of adopting the latest technology. However, the ability and motivation vary significantly depending on the context; at the individual level, an individual could make a necessary adjustment if they deemed the new technology useful, but it is more complex at an organisational level (Al-Mamary *et al.*, 2016). This echoed the same as Roger (1962) argued that technology adoption at an organisational level is more complicated than the individual level because the organisation combines both people and a system with a set of norms and procedures.

Since the introduction of the DOI theory by Roger (1962), many scholars have used this theory. However, researchers have used slightly different parameters in every study to meet their objectives (Hsu, Ray and Li-Hsieh, 2014). Some criticise that this lack of cohesion and consistency has left the DOI stagnant over the years and does not offer any consistent parameter that can measure the new idea and technology diffusion, unlike other frameworks (Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo, 2009; Ilin, Ivetić and Simić, 2017; Lai, 2017). For example, the TOE (Technology, Organisation and Environment) framework offers three broad categories that allow flexibility to add new elements under those significant categories.

The following sections discuss the TOE framework.

3.5. The Technology- Organisation- Environment (TOE) Framework

The TOE is a theoretical framework that describes innovation and technology adoption at the organisational level and explains the technology adoption and implementation process influenced by the technological, organisation and environmental factors. The TOE framework first introduced by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990), explaining in detail the technology and innovation adoption starting from the technology developed by the engineers, adopted by the entrepreneurs and businesses and implementations by the users (Baker, 2011).

Figure 9 shows the critical contexts of the TOE that influence the adoption of innovation and technology.

Figure 9: Technology- Organisation- Environment framework.

Source: Adopted form Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990)

TOE framework is a commonly used framework to understand the adoption of innovation and technology acceptance barriers at the organisational level regardless of multinational companies (MNCs) or SMEs (Chandra and Kumar, 2018; Baker, 2011; Badi *et al.*, 2020; Mkansi 2021).

3.5.1. Technological context

Technological context refers to the factors related to the technology itself. In this study, technological context refers to e-commerce and EC related technology. Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) argued that a firm's existing technology usage determines the capability to use industry-specific technology available in the market. In addition, the complexity of the Technology, compatibility, trialability are the critical determinants for technology adoption (Baker, 2011; Badi *et al.*, 2020; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). Most importantly, perceived relative advantage of technology usage (Grandon and Pearson, 2004; Al-Qirim, 2007; Baker, 2011; Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016; and the cost of acquiring the Technology affect the adoption of any new application (Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Schmitt

et al., 2019; Mkansi, 2021). However, factors are not static; instead, researchers have used a unique set of elements based on their research field.

Tushman and Nadler (1986) argued that the advancement of technology could be competence-enhancing and competence-destroying. Businesses need to adapt to the changes in the new technology to maintain their competitive stance. Competence enhancing Technology enables businesses to further their reach in the market proposition. In contrast, businesses that fail to adapt to the change in technology can destroy the businesses' competence.

It is important to note that technological change is a continuous process (Barney, 1991; Quaye and Mensah, 2018). Therefore, businesses that achieved a high level of expertise in the current technology in their field and gained a competitive advantage may no longer be a source of competitive advantage in the coming days (Watson and Shove, 2008; Das Nair, 2017). Therefore, updating the change is imperative for the businesses (Xuhua, Chosniel Elikem and Akaba, 2019; Aziz and Samad, 2016; Jin and Shin, 2020).

In SMEs research, there is a consensus that technological challenges limit SMEs e-commerce adoption. However, it is yet to identify what technological factors affecting independent DIY retailer's e-commerce adoption.

3.5.2. Organisational context

Alongside the technological aspects, a firm's organisational elements play a vital role in technology adoption. Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick (2004) explained that the organisational factors refer to the firm's microelements under its control. Meaning that organisational factors are firms' characteristics and internal resources, capabilities including the link between the employees, communication process within intra-firm, firms' size and the number of slack resources (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990; Abed, 2020). However, these factors were considered in the case of a large organisation when Tornatzky and Fleischer developed the TOE framework in 1990 (Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Abdul Hamid and Aliman, 2020; Stjepić, Pejić Bach and Bosilj Vukšić, 2021).

These factors are not valid in small retail businesses, having no separate departments proposed in the initial TOE framework. However, Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) and Van Looy (2021) argued that businesses are made of people and processes, and therefore, organisational factors should include the factors involving people and the process.

As small retail businesses are often managed and controlled by the owner (Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007; Mackay and Perkins, 2016), and therefore their traits such as awareness, perception, attitude, and motivation towards the technology along with firms' size and tangible and intangible resources, firm's technological readiness, organisational culture affect technology (EC) adoption.

However, our understanding of the EC adoption challenges for independent DIY retailers in the UK is infancy. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate what organisational factors affect independent DIY retailer's e-commerce adoption.

3.5.3. Environmental context

Environmental factors refer to the macro issues that are outside the firm's control but have a significant impact on the firms and the market they operate (Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Baker, 2011; Mboli, Thakker and Mishra, 2020).

Environmental context includes macro or external factors, such as the presence or absence of the technology vendors, competition, rules, and regulation related to the industry, professional body affiliation that can positively or negatively affect the adoption (Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Haryanti and Subriadi, 2020). In addition, many other industry-specific technological factors have been used under the TOE framework to assess technology adoption. For example, support from the technology providers, government support, pressure from the customer, suppliers (Ajmal and Yasin, 2012; Abualrob and Kang, 2016) are a few of them. However, how these environmental factors affect the e-commerce adoption for the independent DIY retailers in the UK yet to be identified.

3.5.4. Existing research on technology adoption using TOE framework

Many studies have used the TOE as the theoretical framework while examining innovation and technology adoption (Grover, 1993; Chau and Tam, 1997; Thong, 1999; Kuan and Chau, 2000; Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, 2003; Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick, 2004; Zhu *et al.*, 2006; Lee and Shim, 2007; Mishra, Konana and Barua, 2007; Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo, 2009; Baker, 2011; Grandón, Nasco and Mykytyn, 2011; Hsu, Ray and Li-Hsieh, 2014; Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016; Awiagah, Kang and Lim, 2016; Resciniti and De Vanna, 2019; Schmitt *et al.*, 2019; Abed, 2020; Badi *et al.*, 2020; Mkansi, 2021; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). A detailed table 5 is given below with more details of the studies, including the subject and types.

Table 5: Existing key research using the TOE framework.

Citation	Context	Methodology
Grover (1993)	Firm's size and compatibility of IT adoption.	Quantitative
Chau and Tam (1997)	Open systems, perceived barriers, satisfaction with the existing system and uncertainty.	Quantitative
Thong (1999)	IT adoption based on firms' size and employees and owner's knowledge of IT.	Quantitative
Kuan and Chau (2001)	Electronic data interchange (EDI) in SMEs using TOE.	Quantitative
Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, (2003)	E-businesses adoption in the EU.	Quantitative
Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick (2004)	E-businesses adoption in the financial service industry.	Quantitative
Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, (2006)	E-businesses firm from different countries.	Quantitative

Lee and Shim (2007)	RFID adoption in the healthcare industry.	Quantitative
Mishra, Konana and Barua (2007)	Manufacturing firms' procurement digitalisation.	Quantitative
Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo (2009)	SMEs' adoption of enterprise systems.	Qualitative
Olatokun and Bankole (2011)	Businesses owner's EC awareness, size, nature of businesses and perceived benefits.	Quantitative
Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh (2016)	Mobile marketing adoption intention: multi-perspective framework including TOE.	Quantitative
Schmitt <i>et al.</i> (2019)	Adopting smart contracts by SMEs.	Qualitative
Badi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Smart contract adoption in the construction sector in the UK.	Quantitative
Marolt <i>et al.</i> (2020)	SCRM adoption by SMEs and Microbusinesses.	Mixed method
Van Looy (2021)	The link between businesses process management and digital innovation.	Mixed method
Mkansi (2021)	Influence cost of e-commerce adoption: Microbusinesses in South Africa and the United Kingdom.	Qualitative
Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021)	Market expansion and internationalisation through e-commerce platforms.	Qualitative

Source: Author's construct, drawn from the literature.

It is essential to acknowledge that the above table does not illustrate the findings of those research mentioned in the table because this is presented to show the usage of TOE in research and their methodology rather than the outcomes of the studies.

3.5.5. Criticism of TOE as a theoretical framework

TOE is criticised for lacking development and change since the initial inception (Chau and Tam, 1997; Beckinsale, Ram and Theodorakopoulos, 2010) and branded as a generic theory (Zhu, Kraemer, and Xu, 2003) of innovation adoption at an organisation level. This criticism appears to be appropriate since the three primary contexts remain the same since the development of the TOE framework.

However, having the freedom to vary the measures and factors for the suitability of each research context makes the TOE highly flexible and adaptable (Baker, 2011; Chandra and Kumar, 2018). Therefore, researchers have seen little need for the evolution of the TOE. Furthermore, TOE has been viewed as aligned with other adoption theories instead of offering competing explanations (Badi *et al.*, 2020; Haryanti and Subriadi, 2020). Therefore, the TOE framework is helping researchers to understand the information system, information technology, innovation including and e-commerce adoption process and challenges at an organisational level in all sorts of fields. However, some criticise that TOE is the alternative of DOI (Baker, 2011).

Use of TOE from methodological perspective:

TOE has been used in empirical studies, as shown in the table 5. However, in the beginning, TOE was used for quantitative studies over the decades, mainly for a large organisation, using the initial three main factors proposed by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990).

However, scholars started using TOE as a theoretical framework for SMEs in various technological and innovation contexts. As SMEs have a different set of unique features and challenges, discussed in section 2.7, that require an in-depth understanding, and therefore it has been used in exploratory qualitative studies (Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo, 2009; Schmitt *et al.*, 2019; Effendi, Sugandini and Istanto, 2020; Mkansi, 2021; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). For example, Ramdani, Kawalek and Lorenzo (2009) SMEs enterprise system adoption and Schmitt *et al.* (2019) how construction SMEs adopt smart contracts using the internet. Similarly, Mkansi, (2021) Used the TOE framework to examine the influence of the cost of e-commerce adoption and Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) explored the market expansion and internationalisation through online platforms using the TOE framework.

It has also been used in mixed-method research. For instance, Marolt *et al.* (2020) used TOE as a theoretical framework for the mixed-method research on SCRM adoption SMEs. In addition, Van Looy (2021) used TOE as a theoretical lens while examining the link between businesses process management and innovation.

These are just a few examples of the use of TOE in qualitative research. Finally, many researchers use the TOE framework, adding elements that suit the study field and help achieve the research objectives.

3.5.6. Justification of the Use of TOE

Grandón, Nasco and Mykytyn (2011) emphasised using TPB (Theory of Planned Behaviour) and TAM (Technology Acceptance Model) to understand SMEs information technology adoption based on the manager's or owner's attitudes and beliefs. However, in 2016, Riemenschneider and McKinney (2016), who studied the SMEs website adoption by examining owner's attitudes and beliefs using TPB and TAM and concluded that TAM and TPB could not provide the answer for technology, website, adoption as such adoption decision not solely relied on the owner's characteristics rather their decision is influenced by other micro and macro factors. This is supported by Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019), who concluded the same.

Here, TOE plays a significant role in offering three broad aspects (Technological, Organisational, Environmental) that allow more comprehensive options for considering all factors included in the three main categories.

However, TAM, TPB, could have been used separately if only owners' attitudes, beliefs, and perceptions were examined from the user's perspective. Unfortunately, those models are used only for individual-level technology adoption. Therefore, the TOE framework is used in this research. However, owners' attitudes and perceptions towards e-commerce adoption are not ignored here but in the organisational context as in this model; the owner mainly controls independent retail; therefore, considering their attitudes towards IT adoption is essential.

Some scholars (Hsu, Kraemer and Dunkle, 2006; Abualrob and Kang, 2016) used DOI and TOE separately. However, Resciniti and De Vanna (2019) studied the extent of literature published in e-commerce adoption and internationalisation. They affirmed that leader characteristics and firms' internal characteristics better fit the TOE framework rather than multiple frameworks. Therefore, a different theoretical framework is deemed unnecessary.

As discussed above, scholars have used different elements under the technological, organisational, and environmental context to examine e-commerce adoption challenges. The following section will justify the inclusion of various aspects in the TOE framework for this study.

3.6. Factors selected for this study

As discussed above, previous studies have used different technological, organisational, and environmental factors to examine the e-commerce adoption challenges.

Figure 10 illustrates the factors used in the study conducted by Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011)

Figure 10: Usage of different elements in TOE framework.

Source: Adapted from Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011).

Moreover, figure 11 shows that a different set of factors used in the study conducted by Olatokun and Bankole (2011).

Figure 11: EC adoption challenges considered in the existing research.

Source: Adapted form Olatokun and Bankole (2011).

Figure 12 demonstrates that a unique set of factors used in the study conducted by Van Looy (2021).

Figure 12: EC adoption challenges considered in the existing research.

Source: Adapted from Van Looy (2021).

Existing literature in figure 10, 11 and 12 demonstrates that three different studies have used three different sets of factors to examine the challenges of technology adoption. In addition, it highlights that under the three main categories proposed by Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990), many subcategories can be used for the suitability of the study.

This study adopts a set of factors based on the existing literature (discussed in chapter 2) and the relevance of the DIY retail industry to examine e-commerce adoption challenges for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

Figure 13: Selected e-commerce adoption factors for this study.

Source: Author's construct.

The following sections will discuss these selected factors in detail.

3.6.1. Technological Factors

3.6.1.1. Firm's usage of existing Technology

Existing technology used in a firm is crucial as it sets the benchmark of technological usage capabilities that indicates whether a business would be able to adopt new technology (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990; Collins, Hage and Hull, 1988; Baker, 2011; Maduku, Mpanganjira and Duh, 2016; Stjepić, Pejić Bach and Bosilj Vukšić, 2021). However, for typical retail SMEs introducing innovations a complex task as they often lack the technological skill (Avermaete *et al.*, 2003; Li *et al.*, 2011; Kurnia *et al.*, 2015).

In this context, technology computer, printer, internet, or any management software DIY retailers are currently using would indicate whether independent retailers have the technological capabilities to adopt e-commerce depending on their usage of current technology.

3.6.1.2. Complexity /ease of usage EC related technology

User-friendliness of the technology is the key for the new technology adoption regardless of the country and context (Nikolaeva, 2006; Stroud, Minahan and Sabapathy, 2009; Gavrila and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021). The complexity of the EC technology has a direct influence on e-commerce adoption among SMEs. Interestingly, whether it is developed or developing countries, SMEs face difficulties to adopt e-commerce due to the perceived complexity of the EC technology. Many studies, for example, Seyal and Rahman (2003) in Brunei and Pakistan, Grandon and Pearson (2004) in Chile, Tarafdar and Vaidya (2006) in India, Sutanonpaiboon and Pearson (2006) in Thailand, Kim (2006) and Kim and Pae (2007) in South Korea, Al-Qirim, (2007) in New Zealand, Li *et al.* (2011) in the USA, Shemi and Procter (2013) in Botswana, Kurnia *et al.* (2015) in Malaysia, Badi *et al.* (2020) in the UK, Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, (2021) in Bangladesh examined the perceived complexity of new technology adoption in various sectors. They affirmed that perceived complexity is one of the most influential factors of e-commerce adoption. Though businesses are aware of EC technology adoption, most SMEs often find it challenging to use that Technology for being complex. Similarly, Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) studied 1500 SMEs in Scotland and affirmed that perceived complexity negatively affects technology adoption.

The discussion signifies the need to investigate how the owner's perceived ease of use affects the e-commerce adoption of DIY retailing in the UK.

3.6.1.3. Perceived relative advantages of e-commerce

Perceived relative advantage can be defined as a set of anticipated advantages the technology can provide to the adopting businesses (Rogers, 2003; Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Sin *et al.*, 2016; Gavrila and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021). Some scholars argued that perceived relative benefits of e-commerce adoption are directly related to EC adoption decisions in SMEs (Pearson and Grandon, 2005; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011). Similarly, Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) examined in their qualitative study and confirmed that perceived relative advantage directly influences e-commerce adoption decisions. However, this study was conducted in the context of a developing country and cannot generalise that perceived relative advantage affects EC adoption.

However, others contended that SMEs owners measure relative advantage in the monetary term rather than a holistic benefit of EC use (Riquelme, 2002; Quayle 2002; Mkansi,2021); therefore, perceived advantage play a minor role in EC adoption. This supports the findings of Al-Qirim (2007), who found that relative advantage has little influence on technology adoption. More recently, Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) found that owners value the need for technology adoption, but financial resources and time limitations limit their ability to adopt e-commerce.

The above discussion indicates that the perceived relative advantage of technology may not always affect EC adoption. It is crucial to understand how perceived relative advantage influences DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption in the UK.

3.6.1.4. EC adoption Cost

The high initial establishment cost and recurring implementation cost influence technology adoption decisions in resource-constraint SMEs (Riquelme, 2002; Quayle, 2002; Mkansi, 2021). Most scholars who examined SMEs e-commerce adoption acknowledge that the cost of adoption is a significant challenge for SMEs and micro-businesses (Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2011; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Tan and Wu, 2021).

Mkansi (2021) examined the EC adoption cost and found that cost can be three types: initial establishment cost, maintenance cost, and up-gradation or concurring cost. Initial EC establishment costs such as computers, reliable internet connection, access to network facilities and telecommunications hinder EC adoption (Gavrila and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021).

Furthermore, complementary cost such as payment gateway, ensuring online security, data protection, legal issues, subscriptions and updates and maintenance cost such as skilled and trained staff also influences SMEs EC adoption (Mkansi, 2021). However, they argued that the cost determines whether it is merely a web presence or a successful EC operation.

Therefore, it is necessary to investigate whether EC adoption costs impact independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption.

3.6.2. Organisational Factors

Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) and Van Looy (2021) argued that businesses are made of people and processes. Therefore, organisational factors should include the elements involving people and the process. Therefore, owners' traits are considered under the organisational context. The following sections will discuss retail owner's characteristics that may affect EC adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

3.6.3. Owner's individual traits on e-commerce adoption

How owner's individual characteristics, such as perception¹ about the e-commerce, motivation to adopt e-commerce, age, technical skill and education, affect e-commerce adoption are discussed below.

3.6.3.1. Owner's awareness and perception of EC adoption

Owners' individual beliefs toward technology promote and accelerates e-commerce adoption in SMEs. A behavioural belief can be defined as the perceived relation between performing the behaviour and achieving a specific result (Lee and Shim, 2007; Riemenschneider and McKinney, 2016).

Figure 14: e-commerce adoption factor.

Source: Adapted from Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam (2014).

¹ Footnote: Perception is a process by which individuals organize and interpret their sensory impressions in order to give meaning to their environment. However, what we perceive can be substantially different from objective reality (Robbins *et al.*, 2017).

Figure 14 shows that the owner's awareness along with organisational readiness promotes e-commerce adoption. Owners and managers play an essential role in deciding any change or adoption for small and micro businesses; therefore, their awareness and perception about the technology and innovation influence EC adoption (Kuan and Chau, 2001; Al-Qirim, 2007; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam, 2014; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021)

Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam (2014) argued that owners' lack of awareness creates a cognitive barrier for EC adoption among SMEs owners. This lack of understanding is driven by the lack of IT familiarity and literacy, lack of language and communication skills, unawareness of the owner about the potentiality of EC adoption. (Quayle, 2002; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Molla and Licker, 2005; Kshetri, 2007; Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2011). Al-Qirim (2007) studied SMEs internet adoption in New Zealand and found that perceived relative advantage significantly influences the adoption.

Cyert and March (1992) argued that SME owners prefer to be in their comfort zone and are reluctant to 'think outside of the box and adopt new technology, despite being aware of the e-commerce technologies that offer the strategic potentiality to grow. Gary (2003) echoed the similar stance and added that whether the market drives the adoption, competition or technology pushed owner's awareness, positive relative perception promotes technology adoption. Other researchers have supported this view (Venkatesh & Brown, 2001; Sarosa & Zowghi, 2003; Ala-Mutka, 2011)

Furthermore, the owner's perception the of privacy and security of EC related technology affects EC adoption (Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Haryanti and Subriadi, 2020). Sestino *et al.* (2020) added that having a lack of technical skill among the small retail businesses owners is often scared to deal with e-commerce.

However, Abdul Hamid and Aliman (2020) argued otherwise. In 2020, they studied the e-commerce adoption of small and micro businesses in Malaysia among 361 respondents (175 adopters and 186 non-adopters). They found that entrepreneurs' awareness and perception do not play any role, but their age significantly. They found that most EC adopters below 40

years of age and concluded that younger 'digital natives' SMEs are highly likely to adopt e-commerce opportunities.

However, contradictions among the scholars regarding the influence of e-commerce adoption of owner's awareness and perception are noticeable. Some believe owner's awareness and perception about EC affects adoption significantly for small retail businesses (Kuan and Chau, 2001; Al-Qirim, 2007; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam, 2014 Scutto *et al.*, 2021), while others contradict as it has a little significance (Abdul Hamid and Aliman, 2020; Paul, Impey and Stewart, 2021).

Therefore, it is imperative to understand whether owners' awareness and perception about e-commerce affect their e-commerce adoption in independently owned DIY retailing in the UK.

3.6.3.2. Owner's willingness and motivation on e-commerce adoption

Motivation and willingness are different from awareness and perception (Hill, Fishbein and Ajzen, 1977). As someone may be aware of certain things or possess positive or negative perceptions, motivation and willingness create the difference between performing the task or not performing it. Here EC adoption may depend on the owner's willingness and motivations.

Interestingly, EC adopters tend to have a strong belief about the perceived advantage of EC; therefore, they initiated the EC. On the other hand, non-adopters have little motivation than adopters (Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016). Tumolo (2001) argued that the owner's motivation and willingness to adopt e-commerce directly influences EC adoption.

On the other hand, Stroud, Minahan and Sabapathy, (2009) and Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) found no significance between owners' motivation and willingness to e-commerce adoption; instead, owner's and potential customers education are vital for e-commerce adoption. As they put it, if the owner is educated and so do the customers, the businesses will adopt e-commerce regardless. Although this study was done in a developing country and

the interview carried out among Bangladeshi SMEs where IT literacy among customers is relatively low, e-commerce is still in the early stage.

Considering the current debate whether the owner's perception or motivation are more important than others create a need for understanding. Therefore, it is crucial to identify whether the owner's motivation and willingness affect e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing in the UK.

3.6.3.3. Owner's age and education

It is argued that the owner's education and age significantly influence e-commerce adoption in SMEs. Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) argued that SME owners in the UK, aged over 35 up to 45, are generally knowledgeable about the current technology such as e-commerce, cloud computing and online accounting, contrary to the popular belief that the young generation is more tech-savvy. However, owners aged 18-34 are more knowledgeable about digital marketing, Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) software. This young group of SME owners are more receptive to receiving the training and highly likely to adopt e-commerce or any new technology. In addition, Hsu, Ray and Li-Hsieh, (2014), Cragg and Zinatelli (1995) suggested that businesses failing to adopt new technology are those with the leader who has little or no technological knowledge or skill. Others supported this view (Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021). A detailed study by Scuotto *et al.* (2021) from a sample of 2.2 million European SMEs found that the owner's digital skill and capabilities determine EC adoption in the European SMEs.

It is essential to highlight that among the researcher there is a minor disagreement about owners' capabilities that affect EC adoption, especially looking at the work of Scuotto *et al.*, (2021) that used a large sample can be concluded that owners' digital capabilities have a direct correlation with the EC adoption. However, the question remains whether the owner's education has any impact on the EC adoption. It creates a gap in whether traditional education promoted digital capabilities and influenced EC adoption.

3.6.3.4. *Perceived Return on Investment (ROI)*

SMEs owners are cautious about investing and spend little on the technology, often desire a quick return on investment (Pearson and Grandon, 2005). In addition, the researcher highlighted those small businesses have limited capital, skilled staff, time, management (Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007). Lawrence (2002) argued that these limitations put the owners in a preferential choice between the traditional way of doing business and e-commerce and often deter SMEs from gaining advantages of initiating e-commerce channels.

They often focus on short-term survival using the available resources at their disposal. Therefore, they shy away from investing in the long-term viability EC can offer (Akkeren and Caraye, 2000). This resource limitation and uncertainty of ROI affects their EC adoption.

3.6.4. *Businesses Size*

Size and slack are widely studied in the literature. There is little conclusive evidence that businesses size contributes to innovation or technology adoption; instead, slack of resources influences EC adoption (Baker, 2011). However, others argued that a firm's size is important for SMEs' innovation, technology, and EC adoption (Lertwongsatien and Wongpinunwatana, 2003; Al-Qirim, 2007; Shemi and Procter 2013; Xuhua, Chosniel Elikem and Akaba, 2019; Susanty *et al.*, 2020).

3.6.5. *Years of operation in businesses*

Some scholars argued that firms' years of operation in businesses promote e-commerce adoption as long years of operation allow firms to adopt the technology (Freeman, Hannan and Carroll, 2003; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011). For example, Freeman, Hannan and Carroll (2003) argued that older businesses have more market knowledge, reliability and accountability and fewer failure rates than new businesses. Furthermore, Mishra, Konana and Barua (2007) often added that businesses grow in resources and capabilities that allow companies to try a new venture with the years of operation. Thus, these factors help enterprises to adopt new technology.

In contrast, Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick, (2004) contended that businesses are operating in the market for a long year hardly interested in entering e-commerce as most owners are not updated with the new technology arrival in the industry. Similarly, Reuschke and Mason

(2020) studied 994 SMEs from Scotland and found no significant relationship between the firms' age and years of operation with e-commerce adoption. Instead, they emphasised that newly established businesses are more likely to enter e-commerce than that older firms.

3.6.6. Resources and capabilities

There is a consensus among scholars that SMEs' resource constraints deter them from EC adoption. For example, purchasing EC-related technology such as computers, printers, and the internet lacks the ability to hire skilled people, providing training to employees, or outsourcing the service. (Pearson and Grandon, 2005; Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011)

Technology adoption is dependent firm's tangible and intangible resources and capabilities (Sutanonpaiboon and Pearson, 2006; Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011). Resource refers to the firm's capital, product, or service they sell, skilled staff (Zhu, Kraemer, and Xu, 2003; Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick, 2004; Baker 2011). In contrast, capability is a conceptual and subjective term (Eposto,2008). It is challenging to define what comes in the capabilities as it varies from context to context (Eposto, 2008; Scuotto *et al.*, 2021). In this case, SMEs' capabilities can be categorised in three ways: informational, operational, and strategic. businesses that have these capabilities are more likely to adopt e-commerce (Pearson and Grandon, 2005). Informational capabilities refer to the ability of businesses owners and employees to search, assess, select, and process the new formation for EC adoption. And, operational capabilities refer to the ability to perform day-to-day activities such as managing logistics, picking and packing, and generating labels for the fulfilment. Strategic capabilities can be defined as the owner's ability to think and plan for the future.

3.6.7. Suitability of DIY products for e-commerce

The products and services businesses offer to the customer to have found affects EC adoption (Haluk Köksal and Kettaneh, 2011). As SMEs often relies on third-party fulfilment facilities, that may not be suitable for every consumer category to sell online (Yu *et al.*, 2017). For example, perishable items require quick fulfilment and delivery time. On the other hand,

fashion, toys, and different categories don't need that sensitivity (Susanty *et al.*, 2020). However, big companies are capitalising on the fulfilment factors offering same-day delivery or within-hour delivery. For instance, traditional retailers Asda, Sainsbury, Tesco and pure online retailer Ocado, Amazon offering fresh groceries as they have the capabilities and infrastructure to provide a seamless experience for customers. However, for DIY retailers, most products are suitable for e-commerce (Intel, 2020).

3.6.8. Logistical capabilities

Logistics and fulfilment are an integral part of e-commerce as the customer wants a quick and seamless experience (Bart *et al.*, 2005; Ramanathan, 2010). Customers are accustomed to receiving services from large e-commerce businesses (Tinashe Kahiya and L. Dean, 2014; Niu *et al.*, 2019). That expectation of quick delivery became pertinent with the Amazon Prime one-day delivery; now, most large companies are boosting their investment in logistics using automation and artificial intelligence (Intel, 2020; Statista, 2021). However, this is often challenging for SMEs, having to deal with fulfilment manually (Susanty *et al.*, 2020). Online sales fulfilment requires accurate picking, appropriate packaging and secure delivery.

It is important to understand whether logistics and fulfilment capability affects DIY retailers' EC adoption.

3.6.9. Environmental or Macro Factors

3.6.9.1. Competition

Tornatzky and Fleischer (1990) argued that intense competition stimulates innovation. Although many external or macro factors drive technology adoption, competition has been portrayed as one of the most prevailing and influential dynamics in shaping markets and determining the EC adoption (Hånell *et al.*, 2019).

In the context of small businesses, researchers found that intense competition from the direct competitors drives EC adoption (Al-Qirim, 2007; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Hånell *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, this competitive

rivalry stimulates technology and EC adoption (Mboli, Thakker and Mishra, 2020). This stance also affirmed by other researchers and argued that EC adopting firms have a strong desire to stay competitive for their survival and not to lose out (Al-Qirim, 2007; Balakrishnan, Sundaresan and Zhang, 2014).

Pressure from the competitors poses a threat to the businesses, and this intense competition is regarded as the driving factor of EC adoption (Zhu, Kraemer and Xu, 2003; Zhu, Kraemer and Dedrick, 2004; Baker 2011).

As the competitive landscape frequently changes in retailing, EC allows SMEs to avoid 'catch up disadvantage' and directly compete with large and established businesses by changing the rules of competition and structure. In the typical competitive setting in small brick-and-mortar retailers often far behind compared to the big retailers (Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Sin *et al.*, 2016).

3.6.9.2. Institutional and government support

EC adoption for small businesses not only affected by the owner's individual and firm characteristics but macro also environmental factors in the industry has a direct effect on EC adoption for small businesses (Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Molla and Licker, 2005; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Badi *et al.*, 2020). For example, EC related infrastructure, telecommunication and internet access, road and transport facilities, direct or indirect support from the technology vendors, rules and regulations of privacy and consumer rights influence e-commerce adoption for small businesses.

Government policy and legislation affect technology adoption and can positively or negatively affect EC adoption for small businesses (Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Baker, 2011). For example, Reuschke and Mason (2020) studied e-commerce adoption using a survey among 994 SMEs in Scotland. They found that the e-commerce adoption rate is the lowest in rural Scotland, with poor EC infrastructure and broadband internet access. In most countries, big companies are the beneficiaries of direct and indirect government support, and only a tiny fraction of small businesses engage in e-commerce supported by the government (Abed, 2020; Badi *et*

al., 2020; Joubert and Jokonya, 2021). For example, in the UK e-commerce industry is in an advanced stage in terms of infrastructure and users experience (Badi *et al.*, 2020). Though there are still geographic areas where accessing the internet is still challenging.

Support from the technology providers promotes e-commerce adoption. Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) investigated 1500 SME businesses owners. They revealed that 25% of SME owners seek help from the direct technology vendors for support in all the stages, including objective setting, adoption, implementation, and maintenance. However, more than 65 % of respondents rely on the internet for such support in their studies.

Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, (2021) found that government initiatives for digitalisation in Bangladesh through the 'Digital Bangladesh' campaign has seen a significant e-commerce adoption among SMEs. This can be observed in India, where most 55% of SMEs adopted e-commerce regardless of the challenges (OECD,2018; Mboli, Thakker and Mishra, 2020).

The above discussion clearly shows that e-commerce adoption for retail SMEs is influenced by owners' individual traits, organisation resources and capabilities and other environmental factors. However, it is yet to investigate what affects independently owned DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption. This led to the question of what existing e-commerce adoption models are there for SMEs to adopt e-commerce. Therefore, the following section discusses the current e-commerce adoption models for SMEs.

3.7. Current EC adoption Models for SMEs

3.7.1. EC adoption capability stage models

EC adoption is not a straightforward process for small businesses, having micro and macro challenges that affect adoption. Researchers argued that EC adoption happens in stages in a 'step-by-step' process, where small businesses achieve adoption capabilities (Molla and Licker, 2005; Sin *et al.*, 2016; Abdullah *et al.*, 2018; Chava *et al.*, 2018). Subsequently, some scholars developed a stage model for EC adoption in small businesses (Thomas *et al.*, 2009,2013; Beynon-Davies, 2013; Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg, 2015; Mporu, Milne and

Watkins-Mathys, 2015; Abdullah *et al.*, 2018). Table 6 illustrates the EC adoption level at a different stage.

Table 6: E-businesses adoption stage model.

Stages	Descriptions
Stage 0	At this stage, businesses do not have internet access.
Stage 1	Businesses do not have any websites but able to communicate through email via the internet.
Stage 2	Businesses have a presence in social media platforms, like Facebook, where they publish their contact details on their businesses page and sometimes advertise their products and services.
Stage 3	Website: Businesses has their own website that includes their contact details and information about their businesses. But this website is not e-commerce-enabled.
Stage 4	E-commerce Websites: at this stage, businesses develop their e-commerce websites where customers can access more detailed product and service information and purchase from this website.
Stage 5	Mobile Apps: Businesses can develop a mobile app with similar features to their websites. Customers can access apps and websites and experience a seamless experience.
Stage 6	E-businesses: successful e-commerce adoption leads to the e-businesses model where they integrate ordering, logistics and fulfilment, accounting, Human resource management (HR) and other services.
Stage 7	Transformed Digital organisation: All internal and external activities are digitalised, and the businesses are entirely transformed.

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

Data derived from Thomas *et al.* (2009,2013), Beynon-Davies (2013), Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg (2015), Mpofo, Milne and Watkins-Mathys (2015) and Abdullah *et al.* (2018).

They argued that businesses start with no digital activities and no internet and operate in a traditional setting at stage zero and gradually progress towards EC adoption using the internet and email at stage one. Then, businesses start using social media platforms such as Facebook and Instagram by creating a free business page with the products and services they offer and contact details to communicate with the businesses (Thomas *et al.*, 2009; Mpofu, Milne, and Watkins-Mathys, 2015). In the next step, the businesses can create an essential website with rudimentary businesses information such as the product and service and contact details (Beynon-Davies, 2013). However, this site is not an e-commerce site. Finally, small businesses can create an e-commerce website (Beynon-Davies, 2013; Abdullah *et al.*, 2018).

However, Abdullah *et al.* (2018) added two more stages in their EC adoption stage model, suggesting mobile apps, all fulfilment functions and logistical integration before transforming the businesses into a digitally enabled firm where all internal and external activities are automated. Thus, small businesses transformed themselves into technology-enabled organisations.

However, it is a general understanding of SMEs' broader context, and it is not confirmed how different retail sectors adopt EC in practicality, considering the micro and macro challenges. Hence, there is a significant gap in understanding whether independent DIY retailers follow the similar stage outlined by the previous studies.

3.7.2. Current e-commerce adoption model

Above mentioned stage model explains how SMEs gain capabilities of EC technology to adopt e-commerce and become technology-driven organisations.

The detailed investigation of existing literature on SMEs and small retailers suggests the below mentioned-commerce adoption model, figure 15.

Figure 15: E-commerce adoption model for retail SMEs.

Source: Author's construct.

Adopted from MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005), Kaynak, Tatoglu and Kula (2005), Ngai and Gunasekaran (2007), Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado (2011), Olatokun and Bankole (2011), Hajli, Sims and Shanmugam (2014), Kurnia *et al.* (2015), Al-Somali, Gholami and Clegg (2015), Mpofu, Milne and Watkins-Mathys (2015), Sin *et al.* (2016), Awiagah, Kang and Lim (2016), Ramdansyah and Taufik (2017), Di Fatta, Patton and Viglia (2018), Taherdoost (2018) Strzelecki (2019), Cuellar-Fernández, Fuertes-Callén and Serrano-Cinca (2021) and Chau, Deng and Tay (2021).

Figure 15 shows the current e-commerce adoption model, drawn from the literature. An overwhelming majority of e-commerce researchers suggest websites as the recommended e-commerce entry point for resource-constraint retail SMEs. Despite the fact retail SMEs have limited resources to invest upfront and technical skills to create and manage websites for e-commerce. However, retail SMEs' participation in e-commerce remained low. This can be argued that whether this current e-commerce practical for retail SMEs. Therefore, this study aims to investigate the current practice of e-commerce adoption among independently owned DIY retailers in the UK.

3.8. Conclusion

This chapter discusses the technology adoption frameworks that are used in evaluating technology adoption. Furthermore, a critical analysis of e-commerce adoption is presented in this chapter, where e-commerce adoption challenges are critically discussed in the TOE framework. Finally, this chapter gave the current e-commerce adoption model.

As stated in the introduction chapter, this study also explores the market expansion opportunity at cross-border for DIY retailers. Therefore, this next chapter critically discusses the current practice, challenges, and opportunities of cross-border-e-commerce.

Chapter 4: Literature Review: Cross-border e-commerce (CBeC)

4.1. Introduction

Previous chapters critically discussed the DIY retailing and e-commerce adoption challenges. Furthermore, the current e-commerce model is presented in chapter two. This chapter discusses the market expansion in the international market through e-commerce.

4.2. Retail SMEs' internationalisation

Retail SMEs' internationalisation is categorically different from other SME businesses' internationalisation (Tiessen, Wright and Turner, 2001; Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Knight & Liesch, 2016). Though SMEs internationalisation gained considerable attention in international entrepreneurship, one area is understudied: retailing (Hånell *et al.*, 2019), especially small and independently owned retailing. More importantly, before the emergence of e-commerce, selling in a cross-border market was beyond imagination for small independent retailers (Tiessen, Wright and Turner, 2001; Wang, 2014).

It is important to note that the traditional way of internationalisation such as exporting, franchising, appointing agents, dealership, investing in other countries through foreign direct investment (FDI), opening wholly-owned subsidiaries may not be suitable for the small independent retailers, hence DIY retailers (Li *et al.*, 2011). However, those internationalisation methods have their own merits and challenges (Zheng, 2014; Ojala, Evers and Rialp, 2018; Qi *et al.*, 2020). In the following sections, traditional internationalisation methods will briefly discuss and justify their unsuitability for DIY retailers' internationalisation.

Traditional modes of internationalisation:

Figure 16: Traditional internationalisation methods.

Source: Adapted from Wach, (2014, p.136).

The figure 16 summarises the traditional way of internationalisation. There are three broader modes in traditional internationalisation: exporting modes, contractual modes, and investment modes. Although, these modes have their own challenges and advantages (Cullen and Parboteeah, 2010; Wach, 2014). The figure 17 outlines the strategic determinants of entry mode choice.

Figure 17: Strategic determinants of entry mode choice.

Entry modes		Indirect export	Direct export	Licensing and/or franchising	Joint venture subsidiary	Wholly-owned subsidiary
Exporter's situation						
Strategic intent	Immediate profit	✓✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓
	Learn the market			✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
Need for control	High				✓✓	✓✓✓
	Low	✓✓✓	✓✓	✓		
Company resource	International expertise		✓		✓✓✓	✓✓✓
	Strong financial position				✓✓	✓✓✓
Product	Easy to adopt		✓✓	✓✓	✓	✓✓
	Difficult to adopt				✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Transport	Easy to transport	✓✓		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
	Difficult to transport		✓✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Local government	Favourable regulatory environment		✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓✓
	Unfavourable regulatory environment	✓✓✓	✓			
Geography	Long distance between markets			✓✓	✓✓	✓✓
	Short distance between markets	✓✓	✓✓✓			
Culture	Large cultural distance	✓✓	✓	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓
	Small cultural distance	✓✓✓	✓✓✓		✓	✓✓✓

Source: Adopted from Cullen and Parboteeah (2010, p.296).

The figure 17 illustrates different entry modes and their strategic determinants.

Among all the entry modes exporting are the commonly used entry mode choice for SMEs (Kahiya, Dean and Heyl, 2014). The following section discusses exporting as an entry mode.

4.2.1. Exporting

Exporting allows businesses to expand rapidly in a foreign market (Barnes, Chakrabarti and Palihawadana, 2006; Arteaga-Ortiz and Fernández-Ortiz, 2010; Tinashe Kahiya and L. Dean, 2014), that contributes to less dependency on one market and require less investment (Barney, 2001; Freeman, Edwards and Schroder, 2006; Bianchi and Wickramasekera, 2013). Thus, it helps businesses achieve economies of scale and profitability (Greenhalgh *et al.*, 2005; Hakan Altıntaş, Tokol and Harcar, 2007; Johanson and Vahlne, 2009). However, in this form of internationalisation, the businesses have less control in host countries. Exporting firms have to depend heavily on the distributor, leading to the lack of power in the host market (Julian and Ahmed, 2005; Kahiya, 2013). Moreover, the host country often relies on

importers; therefore, developing the host market is difficult for exporting (Pinho and Martins, 2010). Finally, this dependency and lack of involvement hinder gaining knowledge about the host market for further development and growth (Kahiya, Dean and Heyl, 2014; Ribau, Moreira and Raposo, 2016).

However, the traditional cooperative exporting method, piggybacking, can play a significant role in international retail SMEs. Piggybacking is the entry mode where a small entrepreneur (rider) from exporting country utilises the facilities of a large business (often called the carrier) at host country who has established a distribution network at host country (Terpstra and Chwo-Ming, 1990; Cullen and Parboteeah, 2010; Wach, 2014). The carrier carries out businesses in foreign markets, offering its own distribution network for a commission to a rider. This form of export is beneficial to both parties as it enables a small entrepreneur to enter a foreign market without needing significant investment. This mode is particularly recommended for micro and small businesses that cannot make their foreign investment.

Small independent retailers such as DIY retailers may not be capable of exporting in foreign countries, having no leverage in their product line as they do not produce merchandise. Instead, they sell goods from many established brands in their industry. Therefore, they do not have the resource or capabilities to export any specific product or product lines businesses to businesses (B2B).

However, this piggybacking may offer a unique opportunity for DIY retailers to reach millions of customers in the international market. DIY retailers can use the e-commerce platforms, eBay, and Amazon, as a carrier who have established market in most developed countries.

The next section discusses the cross-border e-commerce (CBeC).

4.3. Cross Border eCommerce (CBeC)

Market expansion at cross borders.

CBeC is an emerging trend of internationalisation, especially among SMEs following the emergence of the internet, subsequently website and e-commerce platforms. (Wang *et al.*,

2015) CBeC is the new model that combines traditional internalisation methods and e-commerce (Hånell *et al.*, 2019). It could revolutionise the internationalise practice and renew the conceptual understanding of entry mode selection, opening the path for small and micro independent retailers' new opportunities. Having a predominant online shopping demand and established e-commerce channels. Many small businesses adopted those platforms and expanded globally through e-commerce. One successful example of CBeC is china who are leading the CBeC market through Alibaba.com for B2B, Aliexpress.com for B2C.

4.3.1. Cross border e-commerce

Cross border e-commerce can be defined as the trade between different countries using the internet via e-commerce through the website or intermediary platforms (Deng and Wang, 2016; Huang and Chang, 2019; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020). There are different CBeC models such as businesses to businesses (Alibaba.com), businesses to consumer (Aliexpress.com eBay.com Amazon.com), consumer to consumer, and businesses to businesses to consumer. However, the B2C model is the most appropriate for small retailers as they have a wide range of products that can attract more customers from cross-border (Hånell *et al.*, 2020; Tolstoy *et al.*, 2021).

Peng, Wang and Jiang (2008) and Wang (2014) have identified several key characteristics of CBeC, suggesting CBeC is less complex than traditional exporting and require less formality and fewer or no distributors. Furthermore, CBeC usually is higher in frequency but small in volume in B2C through websites or e-marketplaces. However, trust in the foreign website, tax, import duty, cross border logistics, payment security and guarantee affect the CBeC (Cardona and Martens, 2014; Valarezo *et al.*, 2018; Lee, 2020).

In addition, CBeC provides small retailers international opportunities cost-effectively. In CBeC, businesses do not require to have a physical store in the host countries. Instead, transactions are made on the website or e-commerce platforms, and they ship the order to the recipient from their home country (Valarezo *et al.*, 2018).

A comparison between the traditional exporting method and CBeC

The process and challenge of traditional internationalisation limit the small retailers' ability to sell on a global scale. Many scholars argue that exporting is the typical way of SMEs internationalisation (Barnes, Chakrabarti and Palihawadana, 2006; Arteaga-Ortiz and Fernández-Ortiz, 2010; Adu-Gyamfi and Korneliussen, 2013; Tinashe Kahiya and L. Dean, 2014; Bjarnason, Marshall and Eyjólfsson, 2015). However, exporting has its challenges; figure 18 depicts a typical exporting supply chain between two countries.

Before reaching the customer, many parties such as importers, distributors, and retailers are involved in the traditional exporting process. That creates difficulties in the flow of information and products, and such involvement increases the customer price.

On the other hand, figure 19 illustrates the CBeC model of businesses to customer (B2C) with only one intermediary between customers and sellers that speed up the process for both sellers and buyers. Furthermore, sellers can offer relatively cheaper to cross-border customers (Qi *et al.*, 2020).

Figure 18: A typical businesses model of traditional exporting mode for internationalisation.

Source: Adopted from Wang *et al.* (2015) Qi *et al.* (2020).

Figure 19: CBeC through e-platforms.

Source: Adopted from Wang *et al.* (2015) Qi *et al.* (2020).

Traditionally, internationalisation barriers such as physical and psychic distance, cultural, language barriers, lack of customer and market knowledge, and logistical challenges impacted SMEs' internationalisation ability. However, with the advancement of digital technology and e-commerce platforms, those traditional barriers are less likely to impact selling to an international market.

4.3.2. Existing research in CBeC

In recent decades research in internationalisation has explored how manufacturing and service providing SMEs can enter a foreign market and their drivers and barriers (Oviatt and McDougall, 2005; Cavusgil and Knight, 2015). However, with the rise of e-commerce and intermediary's platform, this focus has shifted towards CBeC. Despite that, knowledge about small retailer internationalisation is a very early stage. Considering the current state of CBeC, research scholars argued that the exploitation of CBeC remains an unexplored area (Chandra, Styles and Wilkinson, 2009; Knight and Liesch, 2016; Reuber *et al.*, 2018). Furthermore, scholars argued that how this shift of cross border e-commerce works in practice among the small independent retailers is mainly unknown.

In light of that, Resciniti and De Vanna (2019) examined the existing literature in the CBeC. They categorised the knowledge of CBeC in the three-component framework, antecedents, modalities and performance and consequences. Figure 20 illustrates the framework on the existing expertise of CBeC.

4.3.3. CBEC research framework

Figure 20: Cross border e-commerce (CBeC) research framework.

Source: Adapted from: Resciniti and De Vanna (2019).

This integrative framework of CBeC consists of three aspects. Firstly, antecedents are referring to why firms chose CBeC for market expansion. Secondly, Modalities, how small businesses possibly expand the global market—finally, performance and consequences of using EC for small retail businesses. Three components are discussed below.

4.3.3.1. *Antecedents*

Motivation for Cross border e-commerce:

There is a consensus among the retail researchers that retail SMEs can exploit opportunities through e-commerce facilitated by the internet and intermediaries' platforms.

The CBeC enabled small retail businesses to harness the opportunity in a foreign market. Brouthers, Geisser and Rothlauf (2015) argued that competing in the home market where competition is high allows little room for growth for small businesses. Therefore, a company should look for opportunities abroad (Jean, Kim and Cavusgil, 2020).

Mathews, Healy and Wickramasekera, (2012) and Peltier, Zhao and Schibrowsky (2012) argued that antecedents of e-commerce adoption and CBeC is driven by the firm's degree of innovation and management capabilities. In contrast, other researchers contended that CBeC is driven by the market and competition rather than the firm's internal strategic management capabilities, decision or technological capabilities (Guercini and Runfola, 2015; Guercini, Ranfagni and Runfola, 2020). Moreover, it allows small businesses to utilise the existing store capabilities to expand into more markets. Cost-saving is another motivation of CBeC as the overall cost of maintaining an online store significantly low than the physical store. Thus, e-commerce adoption and CBeC simultaneously contributes to the cost reduction for small

retailers as CBeC allow the opportunity to utilise the existing facilities (Verhoef, Kannan and Inman, 2015; Qi *et al.*, 2020).

4.3.3.2. Modalities

How the retailers use e-commerce for CBeC

As stated earlier, the development and diffusion of the internet and e-commerce have facilitated businesses with the opportunity beyond their geographic area (Bianchi and Mathews, 2016; Guercini, Ranfagni and Runfola, 2020). IT created a new distribution channel for small businesses (Resciniti and De Vanna, 2019).

Firstly, a website offered the opportunity to reach potential customers in the international market at a reduced cost compared to investing in the physical store in the foreign market (Chandra, Styles and Wilkinson, 2012). However, discoverability on the internet is the main issue small retail businesses face. Because reaching the right customer requires a digital marketing campaign, and a large company can run a digital marketing campaign. However, small businesses that limited resources in terms of capital and skill facing challenges in a foreign market. Furthermore, Customer trust on cross-border websites is an essential issue along with the payment method.

However, the rise of e-marketplaces such as eBay, Amazon, and Alibaba have significantly contributed to eradicating those challenges. Scholars have stressed that intermediary's e-commerce platforms contribute to CBeC by bringing customers and sellers from different continents (Guo *et al.*, 2020; Zhichao *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, they emphasised the e-platforms as the best way for CBeC for small retailers. Those e-marketplaces have the capabilities and knowledge of different countries, cultures, and languages that are often challenging for SMEs to tackle. Furthermore, standardisation of communication in terms of culture and language does not work for international trading. e-platforms bridge the cultural and language gap by adapting to the host market. (Colton, Roth and Bearden, 2010)

Table 7: Differences between retailer's own website and e-platforms in CBeC.

Context	Retailer's Website	CBeC platforms
Website design and maintenance	Businesses must design and maintain their own website	Intermediaries design and maintain their websites (Qi <i>et al.</i> , 2020).

	(Brouthers and Hennart, 2007; Qi <i>et al.</i> , 2020).	
Culture and language	Businesses face language and cultural challenges in the host country(s). Conveying Product description and communication in the host market is often difficult (Brouthers, Brouthers and Werner, 2003; Bembom and Schwens, 2018).	In contrast, CBeC platforms provide all the information, including product descriptions and terms and conditions in the local language (Gessner and Snodgrass, 2015; Aparicio, Audretsch and Urbano, 2021).
Currency conversion	Currency conversion challenges (Chandra, Styles and Wilkinson, 2009).	Comply with local rules and regulations. (Chandra, Styles and Wilkinson, 2009).
Payment gateway	Retailers' need to arrange a payment gateway for the international payment (Guercini and Runfola, 2015; Colton, Roth and Bearden, 2010; Chetty, Ojala and Leppäaho, 2015).	E-platforms provide a secure payment gateway (Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2021).
Logistics and fulfilment	Retailers need to arrange logistics and fulfilment for CBeC (Kim, Dekker and Heij, 2017).	e-commerce platforms provide logistical support, so sellers have limited responsibilities (Maekelburger, Schwens and Kabst, 2012; Nguyen, de Leeuw and Dullaert, 2016). For example, eBay' Global Shipping Programme' (eBay, 2021)

Conflict Resolution	In case of a CBeC transaction conflict, businesses need to resolve themselves.	e-platforms mediate disputes between buyers and sellers in return and refunds (Liu <i>et al.</i> , 2021).
Site visitor	Driving international traffic is upon the retailer.	Intermediary platforms have millions of existing customers from all over the world.
Customer Trust	Customers experience trust issues on the foreign website (Hutchinson, Quinn and Alexander, 2005; Hoffmann, Neumann and Speckbacher, 2010; Poppo, Zhou and Li, 2014).	Customer trust more e-platforms (Wang and Wang, 2020; Qi <i>et al.</i> , 2020).

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

4.3.3.3. Performance and Consequences

After deciding to adopt e-commerce and selecting the ways to enter cross-border, the question arises what the consequences of foreign market entry are and how the businesses are performing in the foreign market. However, antecedents and modalities are driven by the demand argued by Brouthers, Geisser and Rothlauf (2015) and technological and management capabilities affirmed by (Mathews, Healy and Wickramasekera (2012) and Peltier, Zhao and Schibrowsky (2012), the performance depends on the firm's core competency such as brands, products, price, logistical capabilities, customer service, and the ability to provide customers with the seamless experience (Elbanna, Child and Dayan, 2013; Preston, Chen and Leidner, 2008; Bianchi and Mathews, 2016)

Hånell *et al.* (2020) investigated a Swedish small fashion retailer that operates in cross-border markets through e-commerce. They argued that the use of intermediaries plays a significant role in the success of the studied case. What they called 'piggy-back style internationalisation'. They emphasised using such methods as foreign market entry tools, given the small retailer inherent inability to expand internationally. This supports the previous studies that advocated that small retailers could compensate for resource shortage that inhabits growth at the

international market by leveraging the knowledge, capabilities of the external partners (Hutchinson, Quinn and Alexander, 2005; Hutchinson *et al.*, 2009; Tolstoy, Jonsson and Sharma, 2016; Tolstoy *et al.*, 2020; Qi *et al.*, 2020).

4.3.4. Methodological aspects of CBeC research

SME's internalisation through the traditional ways is widely researched using quantitative and qualitative and other methods. However, retail CBeC research has been using qualitative methodology, especially case study research through semi-structured interviews. The suitability of qualitative research that uses semi-structured in-depth interviews helps understand and interpret the understudied research areas such as retailers CBeC (Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Alexander and Doherty, 2010; Resciniti and De Vanna, 2019; Hutchinson; Hånell *et al.*, 2020). However, all these studies warranted further exploratory research in different sectors and contexts in the cross-border research, mainly how small retail businesses can utilise this global opportunity using e-commerce.

Table 8: Use of methodology in CBeC research.

	Field	Methodology	
Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, (2009)	Initial barriers of internationalisation using e-commerce: UK SMEs	Qualitative	Multiple case study
Qi <i>et al.</i> (2020)	Motivation for selecting CBeC as an entry mode among Chinese businesses.	Qualitative	Multiple case study
Tolstoy <i>et al.</i> (2021)	Retailers' internalisation through e-commerce in Swedish retail SMEs context	Qualitative	Single case study through in-depth interview.

Source: Author's construct, drawn from literature.

4.3.5. Country context of CBeC research

In the CBeC field, China is undoubtedly leading the market, having some of the largest e-commerce platforms (Alibaba, JD and AliExpress) and significant domestic online demand with millions of active e-commerce users who buy from home and abroad (Qi *et al.*, 2020; Liu

et al., 2021). Furthermore, Chinese businesses of all sizes harnessed the e-commerce opportunity through those platforms (Deng and Wang, 2016). Subsequently, this led to e-commerce, and cross-border e-commerce flourished significantly. Given the rise of e-commerce and CBeC, academics from all over the world and china have focused on the Chinese market. Many CBeC research generated from china or in the Chinese context (Luo, Hongxin Zhao and Du, 2005; Zheng, 2014; Deng and Wang, 2016; Mou *et al.*, 2019; Huang and Chang, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020; Guo *et al.*, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2021). What is known about cross border e-commerce is about the Chinese businesses and their perspectives, such as motivation of selecting CBeC (Deng and Wang, 2016; Qi *et al.*, 2020), drivers and barriers (Zhichao *et al.*, 2020).

On the other hand, other researchers have explored the European context. For example, Valarezo *et al.* (2018) examined individual motivation for purchasing from the cross border in the Spanish context. Guercini, Ranfagni and Runfola (2020) investigated the top eight luxury fashion brand internationalisation through e-commerce in Europe. Hutchinson, Quinn and Alexander (2005, 2006), Hutchinson *et al.* (2009) and Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, (2009) explored the CBeC for British SME retailers. Furthermore, Nordman and Melén (2008), Hagberg, Sundstrom and Egels-Zandén (2016) and Tolstoy *et al.* (2021) investigated Swedish retail SMEs internationalisation through e-commerce.

The above discussion demonstrates that those small retailers are now able to sell globally through e-commerce using their own website or third-party platforms. If the retailer has the capabilities, using a website, small retailers are able to harness the international opportunities. However, that comes with many challenges regarding discoverability, customer trust, payment security, logistics. On the other hand, e-commerce platforms bring geographically distanced customers and sellers together. Furthermore, these platforms ease the physics distance, provide logistical support for small businesses.

However, there is a gap in the research on how country and category-specific retailers can utilise the CBeC. Furthermore, literature has a severe lack informing the current practice among the retailers. Therefore, it is crucial to investigate the current practice of CBeC among the independent DIY retailers to promote the CBeC for the DIY retailers.

4.4. Gaps In the Literature

After a critical evaluation of the literature in chapters two, three and four, bellow mentioned gaps are clearly identified.

Although existing literature extensively focused on SMEs e-commerce adoption, most of the studies are multidisciplinary and generic and unable to address category-specific challenges and warranted category-specific research.

In addition, no academic studies have been published yet, examining the e-commerce adoption challenges of independent DIY retailers in the UK or anywhere in the world. Therefore, this study aims to fill the knowledge gap in understanding DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges.

Furthermore, it is yet to identify whether the current e-commerce adoption models are practical for the independent DIY retail sector in the UK.

Finally, no studies explore the challenges, practices, and opportunities of CBeC for independently owned DIY retailers in the UK.

This study aims to fulfil these gaps in knowledge.

4.5. Conclusion:

This chapter critically discussed the CBeC (cross-border e-commerce) and highlighted the current state of CBeC in academia and practice. Finally, gaps in the literature are outlined. The following chapter discusses the research methodology and methods employed in the study to conduct the research.

Chapter 5: Research Methodology

5.1. Introduction

After identifying relevant research themes and gaps in the previous chapters, this chapter discusses the choice of research methodology, design, methods, and tools used to achieve the research objectives. This exploratory study adopted an interpretivist inductive research approach and used convenience and purposive sampling to conduct 20 qualitative in-depth interviews. Furthermore, this study adopted the thematic analysis technique to analyse and present collected data.

The following section represents the chapter structure at a glance.

5.2. Chapter structure

The figure 21, below illustrates the structure of this chapter and the flow of information.

Figure 21: Chapter structure.

Source: Author's construct.

5.3. Research Paradigm and Philosophy

Research philosophy refers to a system of assumptions and beliefs about developing knowledge in a specific field (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Burrell and Morgan (2016) argued that we make assumptions during the research about the reality we encounter (ontological assumption) about human knowledge (epistemological assumption) and how far the research value influences the research process (axiological belief). We set knowingly or unknowingly, and these assumptions dictate our understanding of the research problem and how we interpret the solution (Crotty, 1998; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Gill, Johnson and Clark (2014) argued that a well-crafted and consistent set of assumptions to establish a reliable research philosophy underpins the choice of research approach, strategy, methodology data collection, analysis techniques, and interpretations of the result.

Figure 22: Foundation of the research process.

Source: Adapted from Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019).

Figure 22 illustrates how our assumptions, beliefs, and philosophical stance are interrelated to the research design. Therefore, it is essential to highlight the paradigms based on their ontological, epistemological, and axiological assumptions. Many research paradigms are used in research, such as positivism, interpretivism, pragmatism, constructivism, and postmodernism. The following sections outline the four commonly used research paradigms in business and management research and provide justifications.

5.3.1. Positivism

Positivism is an epistemological, philosophical stance that advocates the application of the methods of the natural sciences to the study of social reality and beyond (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Malhotra, 2020).

In this paradigm, it is assumed that objective facts offer the best scientific evidence that can be tested and confirmed objectively by collecting measurable, quantifiable data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Moreover, in positivism, researchers often use the existing theories to develop hypotheses and test them using the quantitative method (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). As a justification, positivists believe that the use of highly structured quantitative methodology facilitate replication (Uma Sekaran and Bougie, 2019)

However, this law-like generalisation is also less likely to offer a rich and complex understanding of the realities, unlike the subjective view of the knowledge that appreciates the differences in individual contexts and experience and tries to understand the phenomena in the natural settings (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013).

As this aims to gather a rich understanding of the independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption, practice and opportunities, a positivist research paradigm would not be appropriate for this study. Furthermore, having no previous research or reference that can be tested and confirmed in order to generalise the findings validate the unsuitability of positivism.

5.3.2. Critical Realism

In critical realism, reality is the most crucial philosophical consideration, a structured and layered ontology (Fleetwood 2005). It considers reality as external and independent but not directly accessible through observation. Instead, what we experience is sensations, which are manifestations of the things in the real world rather than the real things (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Bhaskar and Hartwig (2011) argued that the fact could only be understood if we understand the social structures that have given rise to the phenomena we are trying to understand. However, critical realism philosophy shares some features with positivism but emphasises the reality that is separate from our descriptions of it (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013). Due

to this focus, much of critical realist research takes the form of an in-depth historical analysis of social and organisational structures and how they have changed over time (Reed 2005).

Therefore, critical realism has not been chosen for this study.

5.3.3. Interpretivism

Interpretivism is taken to denote an alternative to the positivist assumptions. It is predicated upon the view that a strategy is required that respects the differences between people and the object of the natural sciences, and it emphasises that humans are different from physical phenomena because they create meanings (Smith-Doerr, Lounsbury and Ventresca, 2003; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

Researchers argued that human beings and their social worlds could not be studied in the same way as physical phenomena. Therefore, it requires a subjective approach to understand the social realities (Leitch, Hill and Harrison, 2009; Zikmund *et al.*, 2013). Furthermore, as different people of different cultural backgrounds, under different circumstances and at different times, make different meanings, and so create and experience different social realities (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). However, these differences cannot be generalised objectively and be ignored either (Rosenow-Williams and Kortmann, 2013; Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Burrell and Morgan, 2016). Therefore, it is necessary to take an interpretivist approach to create new, richer understandings and interpretations of social worlds and contexts to generate new knowledge. This approach is particularly suitable for business and management research as the different groups of people in an organisation have a different experience of reality from their perspective. Therefore, a subjective approach can appropriately understand the complex and diverse realities profoundly.

However, this philosophical stance often criticised for the biasness of the selectivity and interpretation of reality (Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

This study adopts the interpretivist stance because the challenges of e-commerce adoption of independent DIY retailers cannot be generalised at this stage, with no previous studies informing the challenges they face to adopt to e-commerce or expand to the international

market using EC. Furthermore, the small independent retailers (Dennis, 2000; Quayle, 2002; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005) require a subjective approach to understand and interpret the complex situation.

5.3.4. Pragmatism

Pragmatism asserts that concepts are only relevant where they support action, reconciling both objective (facts) and subjective assumptions (values) (Kelemen and Rumens, 2008). This comprises both philosophical stances, unlike positivism that only considers objective law like generalisation and interpretivism, which considers gaining an in-depth understanding of the social realities. Furthermore, it believes that there are many ways of interpreting the world and undertaking research. No single point of view can ever give the entire picture, and that there may be multiple realities (Rosenow-Williams and Kortmann, 2013; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Therefore, it considers theories, concepts, ideas, hypotheses, and research findings not in an abstract form but terms of their roles as instruments of thought and action and their practical consequences in specific contexts (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). Therefore, this stance utilises various methods and instruments in order to obtain functional outcomes of the problem (Leitch, Hill and Harrison, 2009).

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) argued that if a research problem does not suggest unambiguously that one particular type of knowledge or method should be adopted, this only confirms the pragmatist philosophical stance that it is perfectly possible to work with different kinds of knowledge and methods.

However, this study did not adopt the pragmatic philosophical stance as Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019) argued that pragmatism should not be treated as an escape route from the challenge of understanding other philosophies. The goal of the study to understand the complex realities of independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges, practices, and opportunities. This clearly suggests an interpretivist qualitative approach and does not require an objective approach, positivist or combination of both. Since interpretivism is chosen for this study, pragmatism seems unnecessary for this study.

5.4. Research Approach

This section highlights the different research approaches and gives justification for the chosen research approach for this study.

This study adopts an inductive research approach as inductive reasoning allows generating new theories or conceptual frameworks from the collected data. Because the understanding of DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges and practice is unknown academically, it is imperative to investigate the challenges, practice, and opportunities of e-commerce adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK to propose strategies for adoption and internationalisation.

Deductive reasoning usually tests, verifies and validates the theory-driven hypothesis, while abductive reasoning offers interactions between the inductive and deductive (Suddaby 2006; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). Therefore, deductive and abductive research approaches are unsuitable for this study and do not fit the research goals.

The table 9 outlines the key perspectives of the deductive, inductive, and abductive research approach that further justifies the adopted research approach and the unsuitability.

Table 9: Presentation of research approaches.

	Deductive	Inductive	Abductive
Meaning	It usually begins with a theory-driven hypothesis, which guides data collection and analysis.	This approach starts with a research question and empirical data collected to generate hypotheses and theories.	The abductive approach moves back and forth, combining both deduction and induction, instead of moving from theory to data (deduction) or data to theory (induction).
Logic	Logically and realistically valid.	Logically valid but may or may not be realistically accurate.	Known premises are used to generate testable conclusions.

Generalisability	General to specific.	Specific to general.	Generalising from the interactions between the general and specific.
Theory	Theory testing or verification.	Theory generation and building.	Theory generation or modification to build new theory or modify the existing theory by incorporating existing theory where appropriate.
Use of data	Data collection is used to evaluate propositions or hypotheses related to an existing theory.	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns to create a conceptual framework.	Data collection is used to explore a phenomenon, identify themes and patterns, locate these in a conceptual framework and test this through the subsequent data collection and so forth.

Source: Adapted from Suddaby (2006), Cameron and Price (2009), Bell, Bryman and Harley (2019), Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), Ghauri, Kjell Grønhaug and Strange (2020) and Malhotra (2020).

This section highlighted the research approach selected for this study, and the following section will outline the research design.

5.5. Research Design

This section first illustrates the different aspects of the three research designs, followed by the justification for the selected research design.

Table 10: Presentation of exploratory, descriptive and causal research design.

	Exploratory	Descriptive	Causal
Key research statement	Research questions.	Research questions.	Research Hypothesis.
Research stage	The early stage of decision making in any research field.	Intermediary stage of decision making of any research field.	Later stages of decision making of any research field.
Typical research approach	Highly unstructured.	Structured.	Highly structured.
Results	This type of research is discovery-oriented and productive but speculative at times. Often further research needed to justify the outcomes of the study.	This can be confirmatory, but further research may need sometimes. Findings can be actionable managerially.	Confirmatory oriented fairly conclusive. Often obtained results managerially actionably.

Source: Source: Adopted from Zikmund *et al.* (2013), Bell, Bryman and Harley (2019), Babin *et al.* (2019) and Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019).

5.5.1. Justification for chosen research Design

After examining the literature, it was established that the understanding of the e-commerce adoption challenges, practice and opportunities (perceived and actual) for independent DIY retailing in the UK is understudied and lack empirical research. Therefore, the exploratory research design is chosen for this study. Exploratory research design is considered appropriate for several reasons. First, the exploratory research design is suitable where the existing knowledge base is poor and clarifies the situation and discover potential business opportunities (Yin, 1994; Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Babin *et al.*, 2019). Here, what affects e-commerce adoption and market expansion through e-commerce for independent DIY retailers in the UK are unknown, having no previous studies. Secondly, whether the current

e-commerce adoption model suggested in the literature for small retail businesses is practical and fit for the independently owned DIY retailers in the UK is largely unknown.

Finally, in the review of prior empirical studies in SMEs e-commerce adoption in different countries and contexts, there has been increasing recognition and adoption of exploratory qualitative research design in SMEs e-commerce adoption. For example, Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) adopted a similar approach while investigating e-commerce adoption and internationalisation through e-marketplace in Bangladesh. Moreover, Mkansi (2021) adopted the exploratory research design to examine the cost of e-commerce adoption for micro-businesses in South Africa. Furthermore, Patil (2019) studied SMEs internationalisation through digitalisation and adopted an exploratory research design. This approach further advocated by various other researchers (Hutchinson, Quinn and Alexander, 2006; Alexander and Doherty, 2010; Parvinen, Oinas-Kukkonen and Kaptein, 2015; Resciniti and De Vanna, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020; Tolstoy *et al.*, 2021.)

This section highlighted the research designs and given the rationale for the selected design exploratory research design. The following section will highlight the research methods and justify the chosen method for this study.

5.6. Research Method

Table 11: comparison of different methods.

	Qualitative Method	Quantitative method	Mixed method
Objectives	Gaining an in-depth understanding of the underlying reason and motives (Patton, 2002; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).	To quantify and generalise the outcomes from the representative sample of the populations (Rich, 2018; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).	A mixed-method allows a better understanding of the problem and yields more conclusive evidence covering depth and breadth (Wedawatta and Ingirige, 2016).

<p>Advantages</p>	<p>Provide an in-depth understanding of the subject matter (Silverman, 2016).</p> <p>Quality of collected data-rich (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).</p> <p>Requires little structure (Gupta, 2015).</p> <p>It can be done with a small sample (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).</p>	<p>Less time consuming (Malhotra, 2020).</p> <p>High validity as the analysis of collected data is straightforward and free from subjective bias (Cameron and Price, 2009; Rich, 2018).</p>	<p>Allows triangulation of data that strengthen the findings (Nyanga, 2012).</p>
<p>Disadvantages</p>	<p>It is too subjective and cannot be generalised.</p> <p>Difficult to duplicate.</p> <p>Often criticised for a sample bias (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).</p> <p>Lack of transparency (Gupta, 2015).</p>	<p>Time consuming (Malhotra, 2020).</p> <p>Highly structured.</p> <p>Require a large sample size (Rich, 2018).</p> <p>It can be misleading, having no insight into the findings (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).</p>	<p>Time-consuming and requires more resources than other methods (Cameron and Price, 2009).</p> <p>Require the skill of both quantitative and qualitative methods (Cooper and Schindler, 2014).</p> <p>Require two different sampling techniques</p>

	Time-consuming (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).		and samples (Wedawatta <i>et al.</i> , 2011).
Types of data	The qualitative method uses mainly words and represents the participant's point of view (Evert Gummesson, 2001; Silverman, 2016).	Quantitative uses numbers and represent the researcher point of view (Cooper and Schindler, 2014).	Use both quantitative and qualitative data (Zakari, 2020).
Purpose	Often used in exploratory research to discover ideas with general research objectives. Theory generating from natural settings (Evert Gummesson, 2001).	To test a hypothesis or specific questions in an artificial setting (Gill, Johnson and Clark, 2014). Often used in descriptive and causal research design (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019).	Combining both inductive and deductive approaches that allow theory building and testing in the same study (De Silva, 2011; Wedawatta and Ingrige, 2016)
Approach	Observe and interpret (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013).	Measure and test (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013).	Generate and test (Zikmund <i>et al.</i> , 2013).

Source: Author' construct.

5.6.1. The rationale for the selected method

As mentioned in the section 4.4, little is known about the e-commerce adoption challenges and practice of independent DIY retailers in the UK. This study endeavours to establish an initial in-depth understanding of e-commerce adoption challenges, practice, and opportunities of the independent DIY retail sector in the UK to propose a way forward.

Having no previous empirical studies on independent DIY retailing and their e-commerce adoption challenges require a deep understanding through in-depth discussion with independent DIY retailers. In this early stage, generating any hypothesis that can be numerically and statistically tested seems unrealistic (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009). Furthermore, upon reviewing existing empirical studies in the e-commerce adoption field, there has been increased recognition and use of qualitative in-depth interview techniques.

Many previous empirical studies adopted the qualitative method. For example, Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) examined SMEs marketplace adoption challenges in Bangladesh, Mkansi (2021) investigated the cost of e-commerce adoption in South Africa. In addition, Brenda (2019) examined retailers' internationalisation through digitalisation, Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason (2009) studied initial barriers to internationalisation, Tolstoy *et al.* (2021) investigated Swedish SMEs internationalisation through e-commerce. All those empirical studies adopted the qualitative in-depth interview method and advocated that this method allows rich understanding.

The qualitative method is often criticised for not being representative and ungeneralisable (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Silverman, 2016; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). It is contended that the richness and quality of data offset the deficiencies of limited generalisability and representativeness (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Silverman, 2016; Hånell *et al.*, 2019).

Therefore, any positivist-quantitative approach would only be hypothetical that would not have any credibility at this early stage to investigate the challenges of e-commerce adoption and internationalisation. The quantitative method could not adopt having any previous reference of the EC adoption challenges of DIY retailing in the UK or anywhere in the world that can be tested using an extensive data set or business.

Mixed method: Previous studies have used mixed methods to understand the challenges of EC adoption in various SME categories; MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005) used six in-depth interviews to validate the challenges and further generalised those challenges through a quantitative survey of 477 small businesses. Furthermore, Galanakis (2016) have used a

similar method for their exploratory research while examining export effectiveness in Greek SEMs. However, this method only allows generalisation but does not provide an in-depth understanding or recommend a practical solution based on the in-depth insight of the subject matter. The mixed-method could have been better suited if only e-commerce adoption challenges were to investigate and generalise. However, as stated earlier, this study aims to examine the e-commerce adoption challenges and examine e-commerce practice and CBeC to recommend a way forward for the DIY retailers that can be achieved through the use of the qualitative method. Therefore, the mixed method was not chosen for this study. These sections discussed the research methods and provided the rationale for selecting the qualitative research method. The following section will outline the research population.

5.7. Research Population

A research population is the total of all elements that share some common features, comprising the universe for the research problem (Malhotra, 2020). The term 'population' does not mean people in sampling. Instead, it represents the complete set of relevant cases in the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). Figure 23 illustrates the research population, sample and individual cases.

Figure 23: representation of research population, sample, and individual cases.

Source: Adapted from the Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019).

This exploratory research aims to provide an e-commerce adoption strategy for independent DIY retailers in the UK. Therefore, the research population automatically be the independent

DIY retailers in the UK. However, not all DIY retailers are the research population in the study. Instead, independent retailers are not part of any large corporation (agent or franchise) instead of run and managed by the independent owner with up to five branches (CRR,2021; ONS, 2021).

As shown in the figure 23, in this context, the research population refers to all independent DIY retail owners in the UK. Therefore, every single independently owned DIY retailer is the population element. In comparison, the selected participants for this study represents the research sample.

The following sections first highlight the various sampling methods followed by the rationale of sample selection, including the sampling criteria and techniques.

5.8. Sampling

As shown in the figure 23, a sample is a selective representation of the entire research population (Van Maanen, Sørensen and Mitchell, 2007; Malhotra, 2020). Due to the resource and time constraints often, it is impractical to study the entire population unless the research population is relatively small and manageable (Babin *et al.*, 2019; Rich, 2018; Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). Therefore, selecting a sample that either represents or serves the research purpose (Cameron and Price, 2009; Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Sampling can be both probability and non-probability. Both types of sampling are discussed in the next section.

5.8.1. Probability sampling

Probability sampling refers to the technique of selecting where each property of the research population has a certain probabilistic chance of being chosen to make the research representative (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Malhotra, 2020). The table below highlights the different probability sampling and their different aspects.

Table 12: Probability sampling methods and their advantage and disadvantages.

Sampling type	Meaning	Advantages	Disadvantages
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Simple random sampling or random sampling	Selecting the sample using a sample frame, where each sample case has an optimum chance of being selected.	Easily understood, and results are predictable.	Sampling frame construction is complicated. Expensive if the sample size is large and not computerised. The likelihood of representation is not assured.
Systematic sampling	Each unit of sample size is selected randomly at a fixed interval point using a sampling frame.	High likelihood of being representative. Implementation is relatively easy.	Systematic sampling is often complex.
Stratified sampling	Samples are selected from the different parts of the research population.	Includes all significant subpopulations More likelihood of being representative. Relatively less expensive given the	Selecting relevant stratification variables is difficult Difficult to explain.

		relevant list of strata available.	
Cluster sampling	Sampling requires the population to be divided into a group then sampled.	Relatively easy to implement. Cost-effective.	Maintaining precision is difficult. Not easy to compute and interprets the results.

Source: Adapted from Cameron and Price (2009), Zikmund *et al.* (2013), Cooper and Schindler (2014), Bell, Bryman and Harley (2019), Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2019), Ghauri, Kjell Grønhaug and Strange (2020) and Malhotra (2020).

5.8.2. Non-probability sampling

A non-probability sampling technique where the researcher uses subjective judgement to select the sample to answer the research questions (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). A non-probability, often called non-random sampling that doesn't require a statistical sampling frame. Different types of non-probability sampling are discussed below.

5.8.2.1. Quota sampling

Quota sampling is a non-random sampling technique, usually used for interview surveys based on the assumptions that the sampling would represent the research population (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019). Malhotra (2020) clarified that quota sampling selection technique that two-stage restricted judgmental sampling where developing control quotas of population elements followed by the convenience and judgmental sampling selection. As it does not require a sampling frame, quota sampling is often used as a quick alternative to probability sampling, where the research budget is limited and time-constrained. In addition, the likelihood of being representative is relatively high compared to other non-probability sampling techniques as samples are selected considering different quota variables of the research population (Zikmund *et al.*, 2013).

However, quota sampling is often subject to selection bias as researchers use their judgment based on their accessibility (Denzin and Lincoln, 2018). Furthermore, it is also criticised for measuring the margin of error as it is based on non-probability (Bell, Bryman and Harley, 2019; Uma Sekaran and Bougie, 2019).

5.8.2.2. Snowball sampling

A snowball sampling method is often used when gaining access to the unit of the research population (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019; Malhotra, 2020). Therefore, researchers need to select a primary group of respondents then ask for further referrals. This referral continues until the optimum level is reached. However, this method, sampling bias and the probability of selecting homogenous samples are highly likely as respondents may refer to other respondents like themselves (Kvale and Corbin, 2009; Cooper and Schindler, 2014; Ghauri, Kjell Grønhaug and Strange, 2020). Despite the criticism, this may be the best-suited way to access the population, where identifying the population is challenging.

5.8.2.3. Self-selection Sampling

Self-selection sampling happens when the researcher allows each case that expressed their interest to participate in the research. It is mainly used for research is limited and required fundamental exploratory study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

5.8.2.4. Purposive sampling

As the name suggests, purposive sampling is when the researcher believes the respondents are well informed that their responses would suit the research objectives. The sample selected using purposive sampling usually small, but they provide rich data as this is mainly used for the relatively understudied area (Hutchinson, Fleck and Lloyd-Reason, 2009; Gupta, 2015; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019). Therefore, this study adopts purposive sampling. Justifications of the purposive sampling selection are given in the section 5.9.

5.8.2.5. Convenience Sampling

Convenience sampling is a sampling technique where researcher selects their sample based on their accessibility to the research population (Babin *et al.*, 2019). The selection of sampling units is often upon the researcher as the samples are either accessible, cooperative, and less expensive. This allows the researcher to select the sample relatively easily. However, this is

not representative of the research population, and therefore the outcome of the research cannot be generalised (Rich,2018; Malhotra, 2020). Therefore, this study adopts convenience sampling along with purposive sampling. Justifications of the purposive sampling selection are given in the chapter 1, section1.3.

Previous sections outline the probability and non-probability sampling techniques, and purposive and convenience sampling was chosen for this study. The following section justifies the preferred sampling methods.

5.9. The rationale for sampling

Since this study aims to examine the e-commerce adoption challenges, practice and opportunities, this research undertook the convenience and purposive sampling techniques to select a respondent independent retail business who has experience of running DIY stores in the UK and are willing to participate in this study. There are several reasons for selecting such an approach.

First, it is common in exploratory business research to select the sample element that the researcher deemed appropriate to achieve the research objectives (Corbin and Strauss, 2008 Zikmund *et al.*, 2013; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

Furthermore, many previous studies adopted a similar approach and advocated for this sampling technique where the subject is understudied to establish a rich insight. For example, MacGregor and Vrazalic (2005) examined EC adoption challenges in Sweden and Australia and used purposive and convenience sampling where they segmented selected samples into adopters and non-adopters to create a basic model of EC adoption and advocated this approach suits better to understand the problem and practice. Similarly, Riemenschneider and McKinney (2016) in the USA assess website adoption in small businesses and used adopters and non-adopters. In addition, Kurnia *et al.* (2015) investigated the e-commerce adoption for small grocery retailers in the Malaysian context and adopted a similar approach. Therefore, the sampling criteria adopted in this study guided by the other studies also supported many scholars (Lincoln and Denzin 2003; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Abdul Hamid and Aliman, 2020).

As discussed above, purposive and convenience sampling methods are suitable for exploratory qualitative research, guided by previous studies in a similar field. Therefore, the following section outlines the sampling criteria.

5.9.1. Criteria for sample selection

Once the research population is selected, a sampling criterion was set for selecting the respondents to choose the sample for this study using convenience and purposive sampling methods.

Three different sample selection criteria were produced. Firstly, a basic set of criteria was determined for all respondents. Then, a separate second set of criteria was made for adopters and non-adopters. Finally, they were validated by the SIC codes 47520 and 47910. Respondents' selection criteria are given below.

The following section presents the sampling criteria.

Basic selection criteria

- The business must be DIY stores, not a convenient store, pound plus shop that sell DIY products such as handy tools and light bulbs as traditional DIY stores sell paints, hardware, tools, ironmongery products that convenience stores do not sell.
- The DIY retail business must be independently owned, or family run business and has less than five stores, following the definition of independent retailing by (ONS 2021; CRR,2021).
- Retailers must have at least one physical DIY store.
- They must not have more than five branches.
- They should be listed in the Company House under the Standard Industrial Classification (SIC) code either,
47520 - Retail sale of hardware, paints and glass in specialised stores (non-adopters).
and
47910 - Retail sale via mail order houses or via the internet (adopters).

Selection criteria for non-e-commerce adopters: SIC code 47520

- Non-adopters must not have an e-commerce website or sell on eBay, Amazon or social media marketplaces, such as Facebook Marketplace or Gumtree. However, they may have a simple DIY-made² web page with a 'contact us' page as the e-commerce, and ordinary websites are vastly different (Patel, 2021).
- They are based in London so that the researcher can visit the store due to convenience.
- Selection criteria for e-commerce adopters: SIC code 47520 and 47910.
- Along with all the essential criteria stated in section 5.9.1.
- They must have a presence at least in one e-commerce platform (eBay and Amazon or others, if any), own an e-commerce website, or have a presence on all platforms.
- They must be based in the UK. This can be verified through the registered address listed on e-commerce platforms (eBay and Amazon) that publicly available to access.

5.9.2. The rationale for sampling criteria

This selection approach, categorising the selected sample into adopters and non-adopters, is adapted, guided by the previous studies in the retail SMEs e-commerce adoption field (Lincoln and Denzin 2003; MacGregor and Vrazalic, 2005; Olatokun and Bankole, 2011; Kurnia *et al.*, 2015; Riemenschneider and McKinney, 2016; Abdul Hamid and Aliman, 2020).

As discussed in the literature, technology (e-commerce) adoption challenges are mostly perceived among non-adopters. Therefore, the responses from non-adopters established the e-commerce adoption challenges. Thus, the first two objectives of this study are to examine how the independent DIY retail owner's individual traits and other organisational and environmental factors affect e-commerce adoption. However, objectives three and four cannot be achieved only by interviewing the non-e-commerce adopters as objectives three and four examined the CBeC (cross border e-commerce) and the current practice of e-commerce in DIY retailing, respectively. Therefore, the businesses are already adopted e-commerce needed to be interviewed to investigate the current practice of e-commerce adoption and CBeC.

² A simple website can be a DIY-made website but, an e-commerce site requires advanced skill and many other factors, including advanced designing, optimizing, payment gateway, instant messaging, data security measures are involved in an e-commerce website.

Finally, the last objective of this study is to propose strategies for e-commerce adoption and market expansion that can only be done by developing an in-depth understanding of the perceived (non-adopters) and actual challenges and practices (adopters). Furthermore, this approach allowed data triangulation between the perceived and actual obstacles to making informed suggestions.

The above discussion justified the selection of different sampling criteria. Based on the selection criteria, the following section describes the sample collection technique.

5.9.3. Sampling Technique

Once the research population was selected, and sampling criteria were determined, the extensive search was conducted using Google search. Using the term 'independent DIY stores near me' and 'independent DIY store in London', the Google search presented a list of DIY retailers based on their location on Google Map. Furthermore, using the search term 'DIY stores' was conducted on eBay and Amazon. As mentioned in the section 5.9.1, DIY retailers were categorised into adopters and non-adopter; those businesses that did not meet the sampling criteria were removed from the list. After initial screening and processing based on the sampling criteria, 50 DIY retailers were contacted using their phone number, found on Google, eBay and Amazon, and a participant information sheet and a consent form were emailed to the prospects, detailing the purpose and procedure of the study (see the appendix 1 and 2). Among all 50 prospects, 30 DIY retail owner expressed their interest to participate in the research during the telephone conversation. With their permission, a store visit was arranged in order to explain the research purpose and procedure, to familiarise with the owner and to build trust between the owner and the researcher. A similar approach was taken by Kurnia *et al.* (2015), and Qi *et al.* (2020) for their data collection and advocated that the interaction and familiarity before the interview develop trust between the interviewer and respondents. This trust assures the respondents reply uninterruptedly that increase the richness of respondents' answer.

For the data analysis and presentation non -adopting businesses are labelled as 'NA' (non-adopter), and e-commerce adopters are marked as 'A' (Adopter).

Table 13 and 14 illustrate the respondent business and their number of store and under the appropriate SIC codes.

Selected respondents under SIC (Standard Industrial Classification) code 47520 – Retail sale of hardware, paints and glass in specialised stores (non-adopters).

Table 13: Selected respondents (non-adopters) and their number of stores.

Respondents	NA 1	NA 2	NA 3	NA4	NA5	NA6	NA 7	NA 8	NA 9	NA 10
Number of Stores	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
e-commerce presence	No	No	No	No, but it has a basic website	No	No	No	No	No	No

Source: Author's construct.

The table 13 demonstrates that ten businesses were selected that sell DIY materials, paints hardware in a store (SIC code – 47520). In addition, it indicates that all the samples chosen for this had one store only and no e-commerce presence. Thus, all the selected samples fulfilled the sampling criteria. It is essential to acknowledge that respondent NA4 has a simple DIY-made website with only a contact information page and is not classified as an e-commerce site in the selection criteria.

Table 14: Presentation of the selected sample (e-commerce adopters).

Respondents	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Years in e-commerce	7	3	10	4	7	12	4	3	2	8
Number of Stores	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
E-commerce website	No	Yes	Yes	No	yes	yes	No	No	no	yes
E-commerce platform	EB AZ	EB AZ	EB AZ	EB	EB AZ	EB	EB	EB	EB	EB AZ

Social Media	yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Marketplace										

Amazon = AZ, eBay =EB.

Source: Author's construct.

The table 14 illustrates that the selected sample that is registered at the Company House under the SIC code 47520 (selling paints and hardware in-store and 47910 (retail sale via the internet). 8 Selected samples have one DIY store, and one of the samples has two stores, and one has 3 DIY stores. In addition, it shows that five of them have an e-commerce website, and the rest of the five selected sample does not have an e-commerce website.

The above sections outlined the sampling techniques, and the next section will discuss the data collection procedure.

5.10. Data Collection

Data collection refers to data gathering to meet the research goals (Cooper and Schindler, 2014). Data can be primary data collected by the researcher and secondary data collected by other researchers or organisations (Babin *et al.*, 2019). However, in this research, only primary data was collected through the semi-structured interview to understand the e-commerce adoption challenges and the current practice in independent DIY retailing.

5.10.1. Interview guide structure

The gap was informed and guided by the literature, stated in section 4.4, along with the researcher experience working in DIY retailing, an interview guideline was formulated.

The interview questions mainly concentrated on the five key areas:

- DIY retail owner's awareness, perception and towards the e-commerce adoption.
- Other firms' specific factors such as resource (capital, skilled worker) and capabilities that affect e-commerce adoption.
- Macro or environmental factors such as competition, rules and regulations, institutional and government support affect their e-commerce adoption.
- CBeC (Cross-border e-commerce) practice, challenges and opportunities.

- E-commerce platform choice, practice and challenges.

Above mentioned three themes (1-3) were asked to both the non-adopters and adopters as it helped to understand the perceived challenges and the challenges. To clarify, non-adopters said they could not adopt e-commerce for so and so reasons, but adopters state how they adopted e-commerce and what challenges they faced and overcame those challenges. Because this study aims to investigate the challenges of EC adoption and current practice to recommend a practical strategy for the DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption and implementation.

5.10.2. Pilot interview

A pilot study serves some of the functions of previous research, but more precisely for objectives, any research wants to achieve (Maxwell, 2012). In addition, a pilot study helps to understand the feasibility of the ideas, theories, possible interview techniques, style, and others (Uma Sekaran and Bougie, 2019).

An initial consultation about the interview was taken among four independent DIY retailers in London as a part of the pilot interview. Among the selected sample for the pilot interviews, two independent DIY retailers are non-e-commerce adopters who neither have a presence in any e-commerce platforms and social media marketplaces nor have any websites. Similarly, two e-commerce adopters, who are selling on eBay and Amazon, were interviewed. The pilot interviews aimed to check whether the researcher communication skill and styles are understandable among the respondents. Furthermore, it was aimed to check the viability of the interview structure and objectives this study aims to achieve after the interview respondents were asked about their opinion on the overall process and asked for their criticism about the researcher's communication style and research questions in line with the research objectives.

After the initial pilot interview, three significant corrections were made, including their suggestion on how they perceive the overall questionnaire and the interview process.

Firstly, it was raised that the questionnaire was full of technical terms, academic jargon that is often difficult to understand for the retailers. For example, perceived advantages are replaced with the word benefits, ease of use replaced by how easy to use.

Moreover, the questions were complex and hard to understand. Therefore, following their suggestion, all the technical terms and academic words were replaced with everyday plain language so that interviewees understand the question comfortably. For example, the question 'do you sell at cross border markets?' was hard to grasp, as suggested by the respondents. Therefore, it was replaced with a simple language (are you selling to the international markets?) and asked during the actual interviews.

Furthermore, it was identified that non-adopters are limited in the EC knowledge and highlighted the need to triangulate the perceived challenges and opportunities and actual challenges and opportunities. Thus, adopters played a significant role in the research, as they overcame those challenges and adopted e-commerce

Secondly, the interviews' structure initially was problematic as the researcher wanted to ask questions sequentially following the themes. However, during the interview, it was observed that the participants find it difficult to follow at times. For example, respondents added many logistical, organisational, and environmental challenges while asking about technological challenges. However, this was addressed during the actual interviews, allowing participants to answer freely whatever they thought appropriate. Later supplementary questions were asked to gain their insight where it was appropriate.

Thirdly, in the pilot interviews, it was observed that some respondents (two out of four) hesitated or struggled to answer questions on the record. In their opinion, they simply could not remember or not accustomed to being interviewed. However, it was noticed that some respondents are more comfortable discussing while asking about any subject matter while they are performing the job. Therefore, during the actual face to face interview, detailed notes were taken in those circumstances and later added to the interview transcript. That allowed the researcher to obtain a great deal of insight into the challenges DIY retailers are facing.

5.11. Data collection procedure

Semi-structured interview refers to a non-standardised interview technique where researcher asks their respondents open-ended predetermined questions. Cooper and

Schindler (2014) argued that semi-structured in-depth interviews are crucial to understanding what is happening and gaining new insight into an understudied field. For the qualitative method, there can be three types of interviews: structured, semi-structured and unstructured. However, a semi-structured in-depth interview is the most common way of collecting data for qualitative exploratory research.

As there is little research and theory on general DIY retailing, this research examines the insights through in-depth interviews. A similar approach has been adopted by Wolf and McQuitty (2011) while conducting early research on DIY consumers' purchase behaviour and motivation. Moreover, this study integrates the multidisciplinary review of the relevant research and literature to establish the knowledge gap (Crittenden *et al.*, 2010).

After careful consideration of the research objectives, and semi-structured interview was selected as the primary data collection method. With a pre-arrangement and agreement with the respondents, 20 recorded interviews were conducted among ten non-adopters and ten adopters of the DIY business.

Although, the target number of respondents was open-ended until the data saturation was achieved. After interviewing 20 respondents, the researcher stopped interviewing more cases, believing information redundancy and theoretical saturation were achieved (Lincoln and Guba, 1985; Lincoln and Denzin, 2003; Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2019).

All the interviews were recorded with the participants' verbal consent. Table 15 and 16 depict the length of the interviews conducted with the 20 respondents. A total of 900 minutes or 15 hours of the interview was recorded with 20 respondents. Interview with the -e-commerce adopting business amounted to 580 minutes or on average 58 mins. With the non-adopting business, it accounted for 320 minutes, averaging 32 minutes with each respondent.

Table 15: Interview duration with the e-commerce adopters.

Adopters	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	-----------	------------

Interview Duration in minutes	55	34	66	57	64	68	73	45	52	66
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Source: Author's construct.

Table 16: Interview duration with the non-adopters.

Non-adopters	NA 1	NA 2	NA 3	NA 4	NA 5	NA 6	NA 7	NA 8	NA 9	NA 10
Interview Duration in minutes	20	28	24	40	32	36	35	28	40	37

Source: Author's construct.

The above section discussed the data collection procedure, and the next section will highlight the data analysis procedure.

5.12. Data analysis procedure

The thematic analysis method was employed in this study as this qualitative data analysis method allows flexibility to analyse and present a rich and complex account of the data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; O'Connor and Joffe, 2020). Thematic analysis refers to the process of identifying patterns or themes within qualitative data (Braun and Clarke, 2006; Corbin and Strauss, 2008; Denzin and Lincoln, 2018).

It is essential to acknowledge that special attention was paid to assessing relevance rather than measuring prevalence while analysing the data. Measuring prevalence is the process of counting the frequency of the word or idea. Instead, this is focused on the detailed description of data at the expense of presenting detailed accounts of the respondents (Braun and Clarke, 2006, 2019).

Therefore, the researcher emphasised the relevant data rather than the data set in its entirety in all its empirical breadth, as Braun and Clarke (2006, 2019) suggested. This approach is suitable for themes that have not emerged from the data set but are constructed by the

researcher in a six-stage process (Braun and Clarke, 2019). Using NVIVO-12 and MS Excel, data were prepared, organised, and analysed. A six-stage data processing are given below.

Familiarising with the data:

It is essential to highlight that the interview and data went hand in hand (Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021). The recorded interview was transcribed on the same day of the interview and the researcher's important notes. A total of 313 pages of transcripts were produced from the 900 minutes of recording. A breakdown of the recording is shown in table 15 and 16. To familiarise with the meaning of the interview transcript, the researcher first read the transcript more than once before starting indexing.

Generating initial codes:

After familiarising with the transcript, the researcher open-mindedly labelled the descriptive data based on what they deemed relevant. Thus, a total of 49 initial codes were created at the first phase of coding under different names.

Searching for themes:

After labelling the data into the initial codes, the second grouping layer was created before generating the theme. Then based on this group of data, the researcher developed the first layer of themes. However, it is essential to acknowledge that the researcher organised and restructured the themes throughout the process. A total of 27 themes is created at this stage, grouping the relevant themes under each theme.

Reviewing themes: At this stage, 27 themes are transformed into 17 themes which later organised into four major themes.

Defining and naming themes:

Finally, four main themes (challenges, practice, opportunities and CBeC) were created for data presentation.

Presenting the findings: Finally, these four themes with 17 subthemes and their relevant properties are discussed in the chapter six in line with the research objectives.

5.13. Ensuring trustworthiness and authenticity

Qualitative research is often criticised for its ability of generalisability and transferability, unlike quantitative research (Babin *et al.*, 2019). However, Guba and Lincoln (1994) suggested four alternatives that ensure the trustworthiness and authenticity of qualitative research.

- Credibility, which parallels internal validity.
- Transferability, which parallels external validity.
 - Dependability, which parallels reliability.
 - Confirmability, which parallels objectivity.

The following sections discuss how this research ensured credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

5.13.1. Credibility

Credibility is the ability to show that the social realities have been truly represented and enhanced when the researcher selects appropriate methods. Below mentioned measures have been assured to ensure the credibility of this research.

5.13.1.1. *Reference from the previous research*

In this research 20 semi-structured in-depth interviews were conducted, guided by the previous studies (Ajmal and Yasin, 2012; Qi *et al.*, 2020; Hossain, Azam and Quaddus, 2021; Mkansi, 2021). This data collection method is well established in exploratory research and advocated by many scholars in a similar field. This strengthens the credibility of the study using appropriate data collection methods.

5.13.1.2. *Triangulation*

Data triangulation ensures the credibility of the research findings (Silverman, 2016). this study collected data from 20 independent DIY retailers representing different business sizes and backgrounds to ensure the account of realities. Furthermore, the data collected from the non-adopters were triangulated with the adopters' accounts.

5.13.1.3. *Member validation*

The interview transcripts were presented to the respondents to validate their accounts. However, it is essential to acknowledge that one respondent further added to their statement.

5.13.1.4. *Peer debriefing*

External views were obtained from the research colleagues and the supervisors throughout the research that helped remove ambiguous expressions and repetition and present the finding in an orderly manner (Guba and Lincoln, 1985).

5.13.2. Transferability

Transferability is the degree to which a study can be replicated. The researcher acknowledges that it is implausible to 'freeze' a social setting and the circumstances of initial research to make it replicable in the sense in which the term is usually employed. Therefore, this study

cannot be replicated like for like. However, the use of purposive sampling ensured the appropriateness and the relevance of the collected data as the selected respondents have knowledge about DIY retailing, having been in business for many years. The researcher believes an approach can be adapted to research other retail categories in order to find their e-commerce adoption challenges, practice and opportunities.

Furthermore, the findings of this research are only valid for the cases of this study, and a broad generalisation cannot be made for the whole independent DIY retailing in the UK. However, the researcher believes that the data from 20 different retailers represent a fair amount of representation of the understanding in the field, and the propositions made in this study can be transformed into testable hypotheses; these can be investigated in future studies.

5.13.3. Dependability

Dependability of this research achieved through providing the entire recording, transcript and notes taken during the interviews. The length of the interview recordings is presented in the table 15 and 16.

5.13.4. Confirmability

It is advocated that auditing can ensure confirmability. However, it has not been possible to appoint external auditors due to resource limitations. However, the supervisors looked over the transcripts and expressed their opinions about the data collection and presentation. As a result, the presented data represents the respondents' point of view and is free from subjective biasness to the extent possible. Thus, confirmability has been achieved in this research.

5.14. Ethical considerations in this research

The researcher maintained a strict ethical practice set out by the UWS ethics committee throughout the research process.

Ethics form approval:

It is important to acknowledge that the researcher obtained the necessary permission for the UWS ethics committee. [Appendix 10.3]

Anonymity and confidentiality:

All the respondents were informed about the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses through the participant information sheet, detailing the purpose of the research

and how their responses will be stored and processed before the formal store visit or interview. Furthermore, during the store visit, where applicable, the interview respondents were assured and reminded about the confidentiality and anonymity of the data collected.

Respondents' wellbeing:

During the interview or store visit, the researcher has caused no harm to the respondents or their business. The respondents were informed through the participant information sheet what is expected from them during the store visit and interview. So, therefore, there no mental or emotional pressure on the respondents.

As store visits took place during the COVID-19 lockdown, government guidelines followed using a face mask and hand gloves, and social distancing was maintained from the respondents.

Consent:

An informed consent obtained from every respondent during the recorded interview.

Data protection:

Collected data were securely stored in the Apple devices, encrypted, and locked with the researcher's fingerprint, and only the researcher has access to those devices. Thus, respondent's data protection rights were respected.

Assurance:

Respondents were assured about their voluntary participation, right to refuse to answer, and withdrawal from participation without any reason or justification. Furthermore, respondents were made aware that they can reach the researcher's supervisor and their contact details if they have any concerns about the researcher or data collected.

Inclusiveness:

Respondents were selected solely based on the business types (e-commerce adopters and non-e-commerce adopters), NOT based on their gender, race, ethnicity, religion or social class.

Age and qualification-related questions:

Before the interview, respondents were made aware and assured that they could refuse to answer anything they did not feel like answering. To avoid an uncomfortable situation for the respondents, they were asked what age group they belong to, keeping ten years such as 30-

40. However, all respondents provided a straight answer about their age, stating the exact age.

The same protocol was maintained while asking about the qualification. Although, respondents willingly replied about their educational qualifications. Interestingly, those who did not have any formal training or degree emphasised their motivations and willingness to start e-commerce and expressed their confidence about the day-to-day e-commerce practice, despite having no formal training. Furthermore, one respondent proudly said that their lack of institutional education makes them 'Street Smart'.

5.15. Conclusion

In this chapter, the methodological aspects and methods are discussed. First, this exploratory study adopted an interpretivist research paradigm to understand multiple social realities subjectively. Second, through inductive reasoning, this study adopted a qualitative in-depth interview research method. Subsequently, 20 independent DIY retailers were selected using convenience and purposive sampling techniques. Third, using semi-structured interviews, a total of 900 minutes of conversation recorded and later transcribed. Finally, data were analysed using thematic analysis to answer the research objectives.

The following chapter will present the research findings.

Chapter 6: Research Findings

6.1. Introduction:

This chapter presents the research findings. Findings are presented in four themes with relevant sub-themes. the main four themes are challenges, practices, CBeC and opportunities.

For the purpose of the presentation of the findings, respondents are labelled as NA and A.

- **NA is non-adopters, respondents who have no e-commerce presence.**
- **A is an adopter who adopted e-commerce and selling on e-commerce channels.**

Throughout this chapter and following chapters, 'NA' and 'A' would be used interchangeably instead of non-adopters and adopters.

6.2. Demography of the respondents

The flowing table 17 presents respondents' demography. The discussions will be provided in the appropriate section.

E-commerce adopters:

Table 17: Adopters' demography.

Respondent	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
A-Adopters										
Existing Technology	CPI									
Years in Business	7	3	10	14	13	25	8	3	6	9
Years in e-commerce	7	3	10	4	7	12	4	3	2	8
Number of Stores	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Number of Employees	13	8	12	4	5	8	6	3	5	3

Website	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
E-commerce Platforms	eBay Amazon	eBay Amazon	All	eBay	All	eBay	eBay	eBay	eBay	All
Social Media	Yes	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No	No
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male
Education	Self- educated	Bachelor	O Level	Bachelor	A Level	O level	Bachelor	Bachelor	High	A level
Owner's Age	40	36	52	38	43	52	35	32	40	39
Reviews on eBay	13405+	2372+	262276+	5348+	153843+	63366+	6397+	4032+	2838+	66214+
Products on eBay	2559	389	3921	742	1345	1969	756	342	431	1890
CBeC	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No

Note: C-Computer, P-Printer, and I- Internet.

Source: Author's construct.

E-commerce non-adopters:

Table 18: Non-adopters' demography

Respondent	NA1	NA2	NA3	NA4	NA5	NA6	NA7	NA8	NA9	NA10
Existing Technology	Non e	CI	CPI	CPI	C	CPI	CPI	CI	CPI	CPI
Years in Business	10	12	8	9	18	22	19	14	8	22

Years in e-commerce	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Number of Stores	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Number of Employees	3	4	6	3	2	16	6	3	3	9
Website	No	No	No	Yes	No	No	No	No	No	No
E-commerce Platforms	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Social Media	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No
Gender	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male	Male
Education	Self-educated	High School	High School	High School	Self-educated	Self-educated	self-educated	Primary School	O level	O level
Owner's Age	46	40	38	42	58	60	52	57	38	56
Review eBay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Products on eBay	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
CBeC	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No	No

Note: C-Computer, P-Printer and I- Internet.

Source: Author's construct.

6.3. Theme 1: E-commerce adoption challenges

This section discusses e-commerce adoption challenges, technological, organisational and environmental challenges.

6.3.1. Technological challenges

The following sections discusses technological challenges of e-commerce adoption.

6.3.1.1. Firm's existing technology

The existing literature explicitly suggests that a firm's usage of existing technology determines the new technology (EC) adoption. Therefore, respondents were asked about what technology they use in their retail business. The table 19 illustrates the current technology used in businesses among non-adopters. While the table 20 demonstrates the types of EC related technology used by the e-commerce adopting retailers.

It was found that most non -adopters use computers and printers except for respondent NA1, who does not have any computer printer and internet connection. In contrast, all adopter has a computer, printer and internet. Significantly, respondents A2, A3 and A6 uses other specialised software. Therefore, it can be argued that current technology usage does not promote e-commerce adoption.

Table 19: Existing technology used by non-e-commerce adopters.

Non-Adopters	NA 1	NA 2	NA 3	NA 4	NA 5	NA 6	NA 7	NA 8	NA 9	NA 10
Existing Technology	None	C	CPI	CPI	CI	CPI	CPI	CP	CPI	CPI

Note: C- Computer, P- Printer and I-Internet.

Source: Author's construct.

Table 20: Existing technology used by e-commerce adopters.

Adopters	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Existing Technology	CPI	CPI+	CPI+	CPI	CPI	CPI+	CPI	CPI	CPI	CPI

C- Computer, P- Printer, I-Internet and the plus (+) sign is for any other technology such as inventory and integration software.

Source: Author's construct.

6.3.1.2. Complexity with e-commerce technology on EC adoption

It is argued that perceived ease of technology usage affects e-commerce adoption. Therefore, respondents were asked what they think about EC technology and how they affect e-commerce adoption. This study found that the perceived ease of use or the complexity significantly impacted EC adoption. Most non-adopters stressed that they find e-commerce challenging, while adopters claimed they overcame the challenges by motivation and self-learning. It is not only independent retail owner's perception of ease of use, but some retailers also attempted to start e-commerce adoption. However, they have failed to initiate selling online successfully.

Perceived complexity:

Some non-adopters perceived e-commerce as complex and claimed that,

"I cannot even use the smartphone properly; how I am going to use this difficult computer and internet?" (Respondent NA1)

The respondent above perceived the e-commerce technology and process complex based on their ability to use smartphones.

"I know a little bit about computers, but this internet, eBay and amazon would be extremely difficult for me. I do not understand the system." (Respondent NA3)

"Of course, I do not know this computer and all, this (e-commerce) is not for me."
(Respondent NA8)

The statements clearly state that the non-adopters perceive EC technology as difficult and complex that impacts their EC adoption decision. However, it is not only a perceived challenge. For example, some respondents expressed that they have taken initiatives to start selling on eBay or Amazon and found it challenging. The following section highlights retailers hands-on experience of EC technology challenges.

Hands-on experience of complexity:

Some non-adopters also stated that they had hands-on experience of complexity that deterred them from selling online. They have tried to learn the e-commerce process to sell online but experienced the difficulties of EC technology.

"I searched on google how to start selling on e-bay, and I found some videos and some documents explained to me some of that. I saw the video, and I found it extremely difficult.

Honestly, I lose my interest in it (selling on e-commerce)."

(Respondent NA10)

"Therefore, I have tried it by myself, but I failed on both eBay and Amazon. Little did I know that they are not so easy." (Respondent NA7)

"Challenging, I just did not know exactly what certain things I need to do, although I watched a lot of videos, in practical, so many simple things I got to do. I thought, no, I cannot do this." (Respondent NA4)

Similarly, respondents NA 2 and NA 6 explained,

'I have taken initiatives a couple of times to learn; it seems extremely difficult for me. In my own calculation, selling on eBay and Amazon is challenging for me.'

(Respondent NA 2)

*"I would say the using computer and internet is manageable for me, but the total online business process is **difficult**. I have tried a couple of years ago and kind of lost interest."*

(Respondent NA 6)

While the complexity of e-commerce affects the adoption for non-adopters, respondent A3 who recalled their journey and said,

"Technology is always complex. When I first started with my website, we didn't have things like Wix or Shopify or reg123.com or anything like that. We literally had to build the website from the ground up. It wasn't just a case of dragging and dropping pictures into placeholders and cutting and pasting text into a placeholder like it is these days on Shopify. You have got all your cart shopping carts integrated, and all

the SEO is done for you. If you want to expand, you have to learn how the system works."

The above discussion suggests that the non-adopters respondents perceive EC as challenging, impacting their EC adoption. On the other hand, one adopter took a positive stance on the EC technology and emphasised the willingness to learn the process.

The following section presents the influence of perceived advantages of e-commerce adoption.

6.3.1.3. Perceived advantages of E-commerce technology adoption

It is argued that the possible advantage of e-commerce accelerates the adoption in SMEs. Therefore, respondents were asked what advantages they perceive of e-commerce and how that affect their adoption decision. It was found that the majority of respondents are aware of the benefits of e-commerce adoption. However, that perceived advantage has little effect on e-commerce adoption among the independent DIY retailers in this study.

Respondents NA1, NA3 and NA7 claimed,

"I very much know what this (e-commerce adoption) can do, but I cannot do it because I do not know the system, how all this work, too difficult for me." (Respondent NA7)

"I have thought about it and know this would be good for us, but not yet."

(Respondent NA3)

"People are selling, they must be doing good, but I cannot do this at this age. People across the road are selling a lot online, I can see, they send so many bags to post office."

(Respondent NA1)

A similar proposition is supported by other respondents, NA8, NA6 and NA2.

The following section highlights the influence of EC cost on e-commerce adoption.

6.3.2. Cost of e-commerce adoption

According to the literature, e-commerce costs affect e-commerce adoption. Therefore, respondents were asked their opinion about the cost of e-commerce technology and how that cost influences their adoption decision.

Remarkably, it was found that respondents highlighted three types of cost. First, initial or EC establishment costs such as the cost of computer printer and internet and creating a website, maintenance cost, and operating cost. Second, maintenance and implementation costs, such as recruiting skilled staff and their salary. Finally, operating costs as e-commerce platforms commission, payment gateway for the website. Though initial cost does not affect e-commerce adoption, implementation and concurring cost play a significant role in EC adoption. Furthermore, concern about return on investment (ROI) is an essential factor for e-commerce adoption. Remarkably, respondents claimed that initial EC adoption cost does not significantly affect e-concern for independent DIY retailers studied in the research.

6.3.2.1. Establishment and implementation cost:

Some respondents expressed that

"I do not mind paying for the initial settings, but you need people to run it, which is costly; the minimum salary you must pay is £1400- £1500 at this moment. I have to pay from my pocket until business picks up. I don't think so it would be a good idea."

(Respondent NA 10)

"I can invest initially, I have that much money, but I do not have a budget for extra staff to keep this going." (Respondent NA 8)

A similar opinion was given by respondent NA 2, who said,

"I do not have that extra money that I will employ someone for that purpose only because I am not sure whether I will be making money until then I have to pay for that, I don't even know how long I can return my money from there."

It is evidenced that non-adopters are willing to pay and have the ability to pay for the initial cost of EC related setup. However, the EC implementation and the operating cost that they

deem challenging for EC adoption. The following section discusses the implementation and operating cost of EC adoption.

6.3.2.2. Implementation and operating cost

Most non-adopters perceived that maintaining and operating cost of e-commerce is the high cost that affected their e-commerce adoption decision. Respondent NA3 claimed that selling commission on e-commerce platforms, eBay, and Amazon is high.

"It is (selling commission) roughly 22 per cent of my sales would go to them (e-platforms), then what is left for us?" (Respondent NA 3)

A similar concern expressed by the respondent NA 4 and said,

"I am thinking I'm investing there, and Amazon will keep my money! I will get it after one month. So basically, Amazon is playing with my money."

They went on and further explained,

"I got to post, I got to prepare, I got to pay eBay, PayPal and then once sell is done, then I will get money after two weeks or sometimes even months because it has a certain period of time for releasing funds."

However, it is not only for non-adopters, but a similar proposition expressed by the adopters who are already selling on e-commerce through e-commerce platforms but when it comes to adopting another channel, such as a website. Respondent A1 who is an established seller on eBay and Amazon (have 2559 products listed on eBay at the time of writing, and have been selling for over seven years), stressed that,

"To just create a decent e-commerce website for my business, this will cost me 13-14 thousand given the range of products I have. I am happy to invest, but who is going to manage the website? What guarantee I have that the website will work?"

(Respondent A1)

However, Respondent A3 and A7 expressed different opinions regarding the initial and operating costs.

Respondent A3 argued,

"These days, e-commerce costs peanut. You can literally buy any software cheaper than your iPhone, but when we started ten years ago, it was a different ball game, and we made that decision it worked well for us." (Respondent A3)

A similar stance suggested by respondent A7 who contended,

It is like your rent and rates if you have a store. Likewise, you have to pay commission the eBay and Amazon. It is their platform and their customer, and you are selling to them."

While both the adopters and non-adopters suggested that they are willing to pay for the initial establishment cost but expressed concern for the maintenance cost, however, almost all respondents claimed that return on investment is one of the biggest concerns for the e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing, interviewed in this study.

The following section presents the ROI and how that affect e-commerce adoption.

6.3.3. Perceived return on investment (ROI)

Interestingly, all the non-adopters claimed that they are concerned about their investment in e-commerce, and this uncertainty of ROI affects e-commerce adoption.

Respondent NA3, NA7 and NA1 explained,

"I am concerned about my investment, I can invest money, but there is no guarantee that I will have my money back; at the end of the day, my money would be gone."

(Respondent NA3)

"I think money is no problem, I can invest, but I am concerned when I will get my money back." (Respondent NA7)

"I do not think whether they are expensive or not, but If I want to sell online, I am ready to invest if it brings money, but there is no guarantee that I will have my money back."

(Respondent NA1)

Respondent NA5 and NA10 argued that,

"I do not have that extra money that I will employ someone for this purpose only because I am not sure whether I will be making money until then I have to pay from my pocket, I don't even know how long and when I can return me." (Respondent NA5)

"Obviously, as a businessman, I have to count every single penny. I think in this tough moment, I got to think that the return I would get, I do not have idle cash that I can spend on that (e-commerce) wait for years to get a return." (Respondent NA10)

The above sections highlighted the technological challenges of e-commerce adoption. The table, 21, below summarises the technological difficulties of EC adoption.

Table 21: Summary of the findings of the technological challenges.

Challenges	Findings
The perceived complexity of e-commerce	The owner's perceived ease of use affects e-commerce adoption significantly.
Perceived advantages of e-commerce.	Perceived advantages of e-commerce have little significance in e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing as most respondents claimed they are aware of the benefits of EC adoption.
Cost of e-commerce adoption.	Initial cost: Respondents claimed they are not concerned about the initial establishment cost and willing to invest.
	Maintenance and operating cost: EC implementation costs have a detrimental effect on e-commerce adoption among the independent DIY retailers in this study.
Perceived ROI of EC investment.	Perceived ROI significantly affects EC adoption.

Source: Author's construct.

The following section discusses the organisational challenges of e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing in the UK.

6.3.4. Organisational challenges of e-commerce adoption

This section presents the findings of organisational challenges of e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing in the UK. Ritz, Wolf and McQuitty (2019) and Van Looy (2021) argued that businesses are made of people and processes. Therefore, organisational factors should include the elements involving people and the process. Therefore, owners' traits are considered under the organisational context.

6.3.5. Owner's Characteristics on EC adoption.

Following section discusses how the owner's traits influence EC adoption

6.3.5.1. Owner's awareness and perception

In section 6.3.1.3, it was shown the perceived advantages of e-commerce adoption is less significant for e-commerce adoption. However, this aspect only highlighted only the perceived advantages. Furthermore, perception is limited to the positive aspects; it can be multidimensional (Robbins *et al.*, 2017). Therefore, this section presents how the DIY retail owner's perception affect EC adoption.

Respondents were asked what they think about e-commerce and how that affects their adoption decision. It was observed that most of the respondents perceive EC adoption as necessary, but this doesn't promote EC adoption. Respondent NA1 said that,

"I see everyone talks about this eBay and amazon. People must be doing good; otherwise, why people would get there? But this is not for me. I am happy in my business."

A similar response was given by other non-adopters and stated,

"I thought a couple of times, some of my friends influenced me, they are doing well in their business, they are selling on eBay, and Amazon I can see by myself that they are doing well." (Respondent NA3)

"I occasionally buy from eBay or Amazon. I sometimes thought that other people are selling online, why not give it a try but never managed to start."

(Respondent NA9)

However, a negative perception of e-commerce affects EC adoption significantly.

Respondents argued that,

"People are selling on eBay and Amazon, but I have heard there are a lot of issues there."

(Respondent NA10)

"I do not think customers will be happy to pay £3 for a pack of small screw that I sell in the store for £1. I don't want to upset my customer with the postage cost and all fees."

(Respondent NA6)

"Competition is huge people fight for a penny."

(Respondent NA5)

A similar stance was seen for social media marketplace adoption as respondent NA3 argued,

"I do not think it is (selling on the Facebook marketplace) worth it, why someone going to spend £50 on Facebook, I wouldn't buy, and I think you would not buy either." (Respondent NA3)

However, it is not only the non-adopters; one adopter who is actively selling on eBay and Amazon expressed their opinion regarding social media marketplace adoption.

"These are absolutely fraud (Facebook marketplace), I think. There are so many things on the FB marketplace, but who knows who they are? Why is someone going to buy from them? What guarantee customers or I will have about the payment if they do not send the payment. At least on eBay and Amazon, you have some sort of guarantee here no chance, and they are not approved, the seller."

(Respondent A5)

The above discussions show that the owner's positive perception does not substantially influence e-commerce adoption. In contrast, negative perception affects e-commerce adoption significantly. The following sections present how owner's motivation and willingness affect e-commerce adoption.

6.3.6. Motivation and willingness

The previous sections presented that most DIY retail owners in this study expressed a positive perception of e-commerce adoption. However, this positivity towards e-commerce did not play a key role in their e-commerce adoption decision. However, it was found that the motivation to adopt e-commerce play a significant role in e-commerce adoption. Most adopters who are already selling one e-commerce argued that it the willingness that helped them to start selling on e-commerce. A similar stance was found among the non-adopters. Therefore, it can be argued that motivation and willingness of e-commerce adoption are vital determinants. Conversely, lack of motivation and willingness affects e-commerce adoption negatively.

Lack of motivation and willingness:

When respondents replied that they are aware of the e-commerce benefits, they were asked what is stopping them from selling on e-commerce?

Non-adopters replied,

*"I am not thinking of selling on eBay and Amazon as I think I cannot manage time for that have to recruit extra people I have heard there are a lot of difficulties. **I do not want to go to all these troubles.**" (Respondent NA5)*

*"My friend is doing extremely well on eBay all the time, picking and packing eBay orders. He tried to teach me how to do eBay. I **got scared** and gave me a **dizzy head**. I never think I would like to be in that situation, so many things to do." (Respondent NA2)*

A similar response was given by other non-adopters that highlights their lack of willingness to adopt e-commerce.

*"No plan at this moment, I have no time, it is **very hard** I cannot do anything different than what I have now." (Respondent NA1)*

*"I see many people are doing well in their business, selling on eBay and amazon I can see by myself. But **never managed to start.**" (Respondent NA9)*

However, this further substantiates that the lack of motivation affected e-commerce adoption when adopters claimed that their willingness helped them adopt e-commerce.

One respondent explained,

"I think [...] there is no excuse not to learn anything, [.....] pretty much with YouTube all sorts of resources out there [.....] there's pretty much you can learn what you need to set your business up and to develop it. All you need is the willingness to learn. [.....] I have learned everything from YouTube for free; these days, I learn things on YouTube.

(Respondent A3)

The same respondent further went and stressed that,

"In internet business, the sale is dramatic. In-store I can sell only the time I keep the store open. But on e-bay, I make money even when I am sleeping. That's really good. The money you make is huge than store sell. Most importantly, I return my investment very quickly."

A similar proposition made by other adopters,

"I knew about people selling on eBay and amazon, and I learned by myself everything on YouTube." (Respondent A1)

"I did not know anything about e-commerce, but my friends used to sell on eBay and amazon. I got some help from them, but I had to do everything by myself."

(Respondent A9)

"I have seen a lot of videos on YouTube and google and tried myself. I made so many mistakes in the beginning and learned slowly. Now it's fine. I can do everything by myself. Now before starting anything or any problem, I first go online and try to watch some videos and read from google and get some ideas from the internet, especially during the corona I have watched a lot of videos about e-commerce learned a lot."

(Respondent A8)

The above discussion illustrates that motivation and willingness to start e-commerce are the keys to e-commerce adoption. As adopters are self-motivated, often inspired by friends and learned the adoption process from the internet for free. Though most respondents who do not have an e-commerce presence explained their lack of motivation, lack of skill and technical knowledge is one of them. The following section presents the lack of skill on e-commerce adoption.

6.3.6.1. Lack of skills

The previous section highlighted that most independent DIY retailers in this study are aware of the e-commerce adoption benefits and have a positive perception of the e-commerce adoption. However, their lack of technical skills is affecting their motivation and willingness to adopt e-commerce.

The owner's technical skill is the crucial determinant of e-commerce adoption. Respondents highlighted that,

"I want to do it (sell on e-commerce), but I do not know how the system (EC) works, as you can see I have so many kinds of stuff here, got computer sitting idle in my shop and the post office is next door, but I cannot sell because I don't have any experience of e-commerce and kids are not interested." (Respondent NA7)

"I know little about computer, but these internet and eBay and amazon would be difficult for me I do not understand the system." (Respondent NA1)

Other respondents echoed the same stance on e-commerce adoption and expressed that,

"I know I have to do it and want to do it, but neither have skill nor experience."
(Respondent NA10)

"If I knew this, I would have done it long ago."
(Respondent NA8)

"Of course, I don't know this computer and all, this (e-commerce) is not for me."
(Respondent NA6)

The above findings show that the owner's lack of technical skill is detrimental to e-commerce adoption. The following section outlines another critical challenge of e-commerce adoption for independently owned DIY retailing in the UK.

6.3.6.2. Lack of Trust

Previous sections highlighted that the respondents' lack of technological ability affects e-commerce adoption. Subsequently, respondents were asked about hiring skilled staff or training their existing employees to start e-commerce.

In response to that, respondents argued that,

"You cannot trust people. They may leave at any time for a good or bad reason; if they get a good opportunity, they may go somewhere, as you know we pay minimum wages what they can get the same payment working anywhere."

(Respondent NA10)

"I need to learn first to train them. And you cannot rely on staff, because today they are with you and tomorrow, they could be somewhere else. I need to have some experience to train them so that I know what they are doing. If they are not here, I can manage everything. If you do not know the business, you cannot reply to the staff completely."

(Respondent NA2)

Other respondents expressed the same opinion and said,

"I do not have the knowledge to do this (e-commerce). I would have hired someone, but the main challenge for me is trust. I got to expose all my business details to my staff, like, my bank details, PayPal, account password, everything. I think this is risky, and anything can happen. If they want to do anything fraudulent, I will not have any control over that."

(Respondent NA4)

Furthermore, respondent NA10 shared their negative experience with the staff and justified,

"If a staff has all the details, they can start the same next day, one of our staff tried the same, he contacted the suppliers for the products using our name, but luckily company informed me then I had to sack him. But, how to trust people these days? So, I do whatever I can."

However, this lack of trust in staff can be seen among the adopters. Respondent A7, who is in the DIY business for over eight years and selling on eBay for four years and do not have an e-commerce website, stressed regarding outsourcing the service from the technology vendors,

"I personally look after my business, and I have control over my staff and overall business. If I hire a third party, I have to provide them with my personal data and know my business information. This would be risky."

(Respondent A6)

Respondent A1 is one of the biggest DIY retailers on eBay and Amazon, and in the DIY business for over seven years and selling on e-marketplaces from the beginning, but do not have an e-commerce website. Respondent A1 contended regarding opening an e-commerce website and said,

"I cannot do it (creating and maintaining the website) by myself, and I do not trust anybody with my business. For example, if I give all the information to them to create a website. Then I must give all the products and prices to the web developer. So how can I trust that they would not pass it to others, or they can start themselves the same business that will create more competition."

Respondent A1 further explained,

"Then the security issue. So, I wouldn't ever open websites, not in a million years. So many big businesses got hacked. I do not want to take that chance. You need only one chance. If I get hacked, I will be on the street. So, for me, it is all about trust."

A similar response was given by the respondent A9 and stated

"My concern is trust, whether it is in the UK or other country as I will have to give all my data about my all-payment details to link with my account, but what guarantee I have? If anybody wants to do anything with my account, they can do it if they want. Because I do not know much about the system and structure of the account, but they do. So, if you do not know anything, you should stay away from it."

However, in response to the lack of trust in the staff and outsourcing service, respondent A3 was asked about their opinion on the perceived trust in the staff and website security. The

respondent A3 is the biggest e-commerce retailer in this study who employ 12 people and sells on eBay, Amazon, and owns a website with nearly 4000 listings on all platforms.

They suggested a positive approach and explained,

"I do not think there is much to worry about because there are no card details stored on our website as we only use PayPal. Furthermore, the products that we sell at a fairly low value we have never had any fraud committed, you know people using stolen cards, or whatever on our site or anything like that, if you've stolen some credit card details, you're probably going to go and buy a 50-inch Tele rather than, DIY tools sort of thing. So, we have not had any issues. And we use the best website security service for our website, and never stressed about hacking, technology is pretty good these days and reasonably cheap."

And further added,

"We do want to grow our business, and as an owner, I can do only so much. If you have that mentality, you cannot grow or expand the business, and I have to trust people. So, no, I don't have any concerns about my employees."

The above findings highlight that the lack of trust affects e-commerce adoption significantly in independently owned DIY retailing in studied cases. The following section highlights the owner's age and education on e-commerce adoption.

6.3.6.3. Owner's Age

Existing literature stressed that the owner's age has a significant co-relation with e-commerce adoption. Table 22 and 23 outlined the age of the respondents. The table 23 illustrates the age of the e-commerce adopters, and table 22 demonstrates non-adopters' age.

Table 22: Respondents' age: non-adopter.

Respondents (Non-adopters)	NA 1	NA 2	NA 3	NA 4	NA 5	NA 6	NA 7	NA 8	NA 9	NA 10
Owner's Age	46	40	38	42	58	60	52	57	38	56

Source: Author's construct.

Table 23: Respondents' age: e-commerce adopter.

Respondents (Adopters)	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Owner's Age	40	36	52	38	43	52	35	32	40	39

Source: Author's construct.

The table above shows the respondents' age. Among non-adopters, the two youngest owners are 38 years old, and one respondent is 40, while four respondents are in their 50s. In comparison, the youngest respondent is 32 years old and started selling on e-commerce three years ago. Therefore, it can be seen that most adopters were comparatively younger when they started selling on e-commerce. However, this cannot be concluded that the young owners are more likely to adopt e-commerce as the two largest retailers in this study is 52 years of age.

6.3.6.4. Owner's education

A significant body of researchers argued that owner's education plays a substantial role in the e-commerce adoption for small retailers. This study wanted to investigate whether an owner's education affects a DIY retailer's e-commerce adoption. Table 25 depicts the age of the business those who have no e-commerce presence. While the table 24 presents the age of the non-adopters.

Table 24: Respondents Education level (Adopters).

Respondents (Non-adopters)	NA 1	NA 2	NA 3	NA 4	NA 5	NA 6	NA 7	NA 8	NA 9	NA 10
Education	Self-educated	High School	High School	High School	Self-educated	Self-educated	Self-educated	Primary School	O level	O level

Source: Author's construct.

Table 25: Respondents Education level (non-adopters).

Respondents (Adopters)	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A 10
Education	Self-educated	Bachelor	O Level	Bachelor	A Level	O level	Bachelor	Bachelor	High School	A level

Source: Author's construct.

From the tables above, this can be seen that most non-adopters do not have a university degree, and five out of ten respondents introduced themselves as self-educated. On the other hand, four out of 20 adopters have a university degree. Interestingly, one of the largest retailers (A1) introduced themselves as self-educated. Therefore, this cannot be interpreted that the owner's education affects e-commerce adoption. Although, it is more likely that education attainment helps to learn new knowledge to some extent.

Owner's characteristics on EC adoption summary

The above section discussed how independent DIY retail owner's individual traits affect EC adoption. The table, 26, below summarises the findings.

Table 26: Owners characteristics on EC adoption findings summary.

Organisational challenges:	Owner's specific challenges:	<p>Owner's awareness and perception of EC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ owner's positive perception has less significance among the non-adopters for EC adoption. ○ The owner's negative perception significantly affects EC adoption. ○ A similar pattern is seen among the adopters for channel extension.
		<p>Motivation and willingness to adopt EC:</p> <p>The owner's motivation and willingness for EC adoption is a crucial determinant for EC adoption.</p>
		<p>Owner's lack of Skills:</p> <p>Lack of technical skill affects EC adoption significantly.</p>
		<p>Lack of trust:</p> <p>The owner's lack of trust on staff and technology provider, affect EC adoption significantly.</p>
		<p>Owner's Age:</p> <p>EC adopters are relatively younger in their 40s, while most non-adopters are who are in their 50s. However, two of the largest DIY retailers in this study is 52 years old.</p>
		<p>Owner's education:</p> <p>Some EC adopters have university degrees, while most non-adopters are self-educated. However, two adopters who are the largest in terms of business size in this study are self-educated.</p>

Source: Author's Construct.

6.3.7. Resource related challenges

Previous sections presented the influence of DIY retail owner's characteristics on EC adoption. This section outlines the firm's specific challenges.

6.3.7.1. Capital

Existing literature explicitly suggests that retail SMEs lack resources that affect their ability to adopt new technology, hence e-commerce. In the previous section, it was discussed how retail owners lack of ability affects e-commerce adoption. Furthermore, those determinants are influenced by the organisation's level of capital. Therefore, respondents were asked how necessary the capital is for EC adoption and how it affects their EC adoption.

Respondents claimed,

"I think money is no problem, I can invest, but I am concerned when I will get my money back." (Respondent NA4)

"I have money if it (ROI) is good, I can put money in, I do not mind".
(Respondent NA7)

"I do not think you need a lot of money to invest. I have that much money. Moreover, I have stocks at this moment I can sell online. If this (EC) investment brings money, I am happy to invest."
(Respondent NA1)

However, another respondent argued that,

"At this moment, I cannot invest more in the business as we hard hit by the pandemic. we had a hard time moneywise to survive."
(Respondent NA10)

This can be seen among the adopters as respondents A1, A3, A6, A7, and A8 supported a similar stance, saying they have enough capital to invest. Respondent A3 stated,

"We were quite lucky, the business model that we have is an excellent positive cash flow model, we are not selling a product, and then waiting for our customers to pay us in a month, you know, everything is paid at the point of order."
(Respondent A3)

6.3.7.2. Skilled staff

Respondents were asked about their current staff's technological capability and how that affects EC adoption decisions. Respondents claimed that it is significant as it would help them to start EC. Unfortunately, though, most of the respondents have a lack of trust in the staff. It affects EC adoption. As most non-adopters said, they do not have the technical knowledge, and therefore, a skilled team would help their EC adoption.

Respondent A7 explained that,

"You have to have the right people, the staff working for me do not know, this and I do not know either." (Respondent NA7)

This can be seen from respondent A2, who stated that how their staff supported their EC.

"Luckily, my staff know about it. We do everything together. In the beginning, I was doing everything by myself, but during the pandemic, our business boomed and had to train staff now, my staff can do eBay and Amazon."

(Respondent A9)

Although non-adopters expressed that they lack trust in staff as the owners know little about the EC process, adopters stated they rely on a team and experienced a positive experience selling on e-commerce.

The following section highlights the finding of Logistical capabilities that affect EC adoption.

6.3.7.3. Logistical Capabilities

It was found that among non-adopters, a perceived lack of logistical capabilities affects EC adoption. As the respondent, A2 stated that

"I have seen my friends doing a lot picking and packing, and I do not think I can do all these".

A similar expression was given by the respondent NA8, stating,

"You need to know how to fulfil the online order, and I do not have any idea about it."

The above statements indicate that non-adopters have perceived EC-related logistics as complicated, another contributing factor affecting EC adoption.

6.3.7.4. Years in business

The literature suggests that year of operation affects AC adoption as they gain capabilities and market knowledge with time. Table 27 below presents the respondents year of operation and years of e-commerce adoption for adopters. Furthermore, table 28 shows the non-adopters respondents' years in business.

Table 27: Years of operation of EC-adopters.

Respondent Adopters	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Years in business	7	3	10	14	13	25	8	3	6	9
Years in e-commerce	7	3	10	4	7	12	4	3	2	8

Source: Author's construct.

Table 28: Years of operation of non-adopters.

Respondent Non-adopters	NA1	NA2	NA3	NA4	NA5	NA6	NA7	NA8	NA9	NA10
Years in business	10	12	8	9	18	22	19	14	8	22
Years in e-commerce	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

Source: Author's construct.

The tables above show that firm years of operation has no co-relation with the EC adoption as most non-adopters' respondents are in operation for 8-22 years but still could not manage to adopt E-commerce. On the other hand, EC adopters are relatively new except for respondent A6b, who is in business for over 25 years and selling online for 12 years.

Therefore, it can be concluded that the year of business does not affect EC adoption for independent DIY retailers in this study.

6.3.7.5. Organisation size

Table 29: Organisation size determinants, adopters.

Respondent Adopters	A1	A2	A3	A4	A5	A6	A7	A8	A9	A10
Number of Stores	3	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1
Number of employees	13	8	12	4	5	8	6	3	5	3
Review eBay	13405+	2372+	262276+	5348+	153843+	63366+	6397+	4032+	2838+	66214+
Products on eBay	2559	389	3921	742	1345	1969	756	342	431	1890

Source: Author's construct.

Table 30: Organisation size determinants, non-adopters.

Respondent Non-Adopters	NA1	NA2	NA3	NA4	NA5	NA6	NA7	NA8	NA9	NA10
Number of Stores	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
Number of employees	3	4	6	3	2	16	6	3	3	9

Source: Author's construct.

The above table shows that most adopters and non-adopter are one store retailers with one to ten employees. However, it was not examined how many products non-adopters have to explore the size in terms of product line wise. For adopters' their listing on eBay was examined with their customer reviews. Remarkably, it shows that businesses of all sizes sell on e-

commerce as respondent A8 has 342 listings at the time of data collection. In contrast, the biggest retailer in this study, respondent A3 had 3921 products listed on eBay. Therefore, it can be concluded that organisation size does not affect EC adoption.

The above sections highlighted the findings of organisation factors that affect EC adoption. The table 31 summarises the findings of the firm’s specific challenges.

Table 31: Firm’s specific changes summary.

Resource	Capital: Respondents believe that they have enough capital to invest in EC. And it does not affect their EC adoption decision
	Skilled staff: Lack of skilled staff significantly affects EC adoption.
	Logistical capabilities: The owner’s perceived capabilities affect EC adoption.
Years of business operation:	It does not have any significance on EC adoption.
Size of the business	Size does not affect EC adoption.

Source: Authors, construct.

The next sections present the environmental challenges of EC adoption.

6.3.8. Environmental Factors

Literature suggests that the macro-environmental factors affect EC adoption for SMEs. The following sections present the findings of environmental factors.

6.3.8.1. Competition

It was found that the pressure from direct competitors does not affect EC adoption. However, a negative perception of EC competition affects EC adoption among non-adopters.

Respondent NA3 stated that,

“I see other people are selling on eBay, but it does not bother me. I can do only whatever I can if they make progress, good luck to them. It does not mean that I have to do it.”

On the other hand, most respondents claimed that competition in e-commerce is extremely high, affecting their EC adoption decision.

"I do not have any capacity to compete with big businesses online."

(Respondent NA9)

"There are too many people (sellers) are there, I am afraid that I will be able to sell."

(Respondent NA1)

"I am thinking my goodness because it's like hassling with a big elephant; I am like a mosquito here because they do what they want to do with the seller."

(Respondent NA4)

"Very little space for me to play in that field (online). So, I thought, let it go and focus on my stores." (Respondent NA8)

"Very competitive, I have heard eBay ad Amazon is a tough place for business." (Respondent NA5)

A similar stance is supported by some adopters and provided a different explanation of competition,

"It is true the competition is really high because there are plenty opportunities that is why competition is increasing more."

(Respondent A2)

"The whole idea of selling on Amazon and eBay is the margin. It is competitive, but that is business and that what business is about; you have competition on high streets as well."

(Respondent A3)

Another adopter further explained,

“Businesses born with competition, so there is no way to get rid of it. However, I think you got to know how to minimize the competition. So obviously, customer retention is a big part that helps to minimize competition, because if you keep good quality product and provide a quality customer service, customers would love to come back to you.”

(Respondent A7)

The above findings show that actual competition from direct competitors has a minor role in EC adoption. However, perceived competition plays a significant role and affect EC adoption negatively.

The following section discusses the role of support from technology vendors and the government on EC adoption.

6.3.8.2. Institutional and government support

Respondents were asked whether they require any support or are aware of any support available that promotes e-commerce adoption. Most non-adopters expressed that they are not aware of such facilities available and warranted training support.

One respondent said that,

“I need practical support, not academics support, I do not have time for reading and learning at this age given how busy I am.”

(Respondent NA8)

Furthermore, respondent NA4 explained that,

“I know there are videos on YouTube, but to be honest I do not have time for that I need someone to show me hands-on experience. If someone trains me for a week, I am sure I can do this (sell online).”

In addition, other respondents stated that they are not aware of any support that would help them to learn and adopt e-commerce.

“I do not know whether any institutional or government support available. If anything, available I will definitely accept that, if it is free.”

(Respondent NA3)

“I do not know exactly if there is any specific support for small businesses like me to go online.”

(Respondent NA4)

The above statements clearly show that non-adopters require institutional support and training for the EC adoption and are unaware of any available support. However, it is not only non-adopters, but adopters in this study also warranted further support for channel extension.

Respondent A4 who is selling on eBay and do not have a presence on Amazon suggested that,

“If I get support from somewhere to get started with Amazon. It would be helpful for me. Because I know it’s a big platform. So, I would like to get training for Amazon.”

Another respondent shared their experience how support from the technology vendors helped them to start selling on Amazon.

“I talked to customer service, and they are quite good and fast communication and resolved the problem I had with account opening.”

(Respondent NA5)

The above findings show that independent DIY retailers require institutional support to adopt e-commerce and channel extension. The following section discusses the role of rules and regulations on EC adoption.

6.3.8.3. Rules and regulations

EC related rules and regulations affect e-commerce adoption. One respondent explained that selling at cross-border,

“I am not getting involved in this because who knows the taxman will create problem.” (Respondent A2)

“I do not know what this GDPR is, but this would be a big problem.”

(Respondent A9)

Another respondent stressed

"I am exhausted with the Amazon return policy; they always take customer side."

(Respondent A3)

Above findings show that EC related rules and regulation affect EC adoption and channel extension. The following section summarises the environmental challenges.

Table 32: Summary of the environmental challenges.

Environmental challenges	Competition	Direct competition: Competition for the high street competitors is less significant.
		Perceived Competition: Perceived competition of EC significantly affects EC adoption.
	Institutional support	Support from technology vendors and government has a significant influence on EC adoption.
	Rules and regulations	E-commerce rules and regulations affects EC adoption.

Source: Author's construct.

The above sections presented the theme one, EC adoption challenges. The next section presents the theme two, EC practice.

6.4. Theme 2: EC adoption Practice

Among the 20 respondents in this study, ten respondents sell on e-commerce at least in one channel. For example, respondents A1 and A2 sell on eBay and Amazon, while respondents A3, A5 and A10 sell on three channels, eBay, Amazon and their own website. In contrast, five respondents (A4, A6, A7, A8 and A9) sell only on Amazon. And three respondents have a presence in the Facebook marketplace (A1, A6 and A7). One objective of this research to examine the challenges in the current practice of e-commerce in independently owned DIY retailing in the UK.

This section outlines the findings in EC practice.

6.4.1. Channel Choice

Adopters were asked how they started selling online and how those channels are performing now. The largest retailer, A3, in this study who sells on three e-commerce channels contributed significantly to the understanding of the channel choice, and they explained that,

*“It’s been a bit of a journey. Initially, we just set the website up. That was **a mistake for us**. I would say we have done all the hard work and received little return. We then started selling products on eBay. And then we started selling products on Amazon.”*

The respondent further explained the reason for such choice,

“Because with eBay and our own website, creating a product is quite time-consuming. Getting the pictures right putting the titles in, putting the descriptions in, the barcodes in, the weights, the postage, but on Amazon, it is just easy to list.”

(Respondent A3)

The respondent A3 also explained,

“We did a million on Amazon, and we did 1.6 million on eBay and 100 thousand on our website. So, if we took eBay and Amazon out of the mix, business would not stand up as a viable business just running the website on its own.”

Interestingly, a similar statement made by the respondent A2, who sell on eBay, Amazon and the website and said,

“I have tried to sell on the website, but it’s not generating any business, and now I am focusing on eBay and Amazon and trying to learn everything. eBay and Amazon are more established, and they have all the facilities, and my website does not have anything; there are millions of websites for websites. So, I do think it will take time for people to know my website.”

The above statements show that the conflicting argument about website adoption. Adopters preferred e-commerce platforms over a website. Therefore, respondents were asked what their recommendation for the other business is. Respondents shared recommended that e-commerce platform should be the starting point for the business that would like to start e-commerce.

Respondent A2 suggested,

I would say initially everyone should start on e-commerce platforms, as we did and of course for the long term they should invest in own websites.”

Respondent A3 suggested a similar approach,

*“I think at the end of the day, eBay and Amazon are the two biggest marketplaces; you cannot ignore them. So, **it is a good place to start**. But ultimately, what you should be trying to do is to build our own website, and build our own customers, and not be over-reliant on Amazon and eBay for our business.”*

Respondent A3 further clarified and emphasised on eBay adoption,

*“So, without the seller, eBay is nothing. But Amazon, without the third-party sellers, is still a massive business. They do not really need third-party sellers. eBay **cares about their sellers**. And whilst they make many decisions, you raise your eyebrows and wonder what they are up to. But, but all day long, **I prefer eBay** to Amazon. **100% eBay is the best to start.**”*

In addition, respondent A7 suggested

*“eBay should be the priority for the new seller. It has **little formality** to start with, people with little knowledge can start, but **Amazon is complex** and require many formalities. Plus, **selling abroad is easy on eBay.**”*

However, respondent A1 encouraged to start on e-commerce platforms but discouraged the website adoption.

“I can only suggest eBay and Amazon, not a website. As I am happy with eBay and Amazon though they charge money and control many things, still, it is good for me because I do not have to do anything, there are plenty people on eBay, and Amazon I can sell to them.”

However, all adopters mentioned some challenges with e-commerce practice. The following section presents the challenges of e-commerce practice.

6.4.1.1. Challenges with website

One respondent emphasised the downside of the website as an e-commerce channel for DIY retailers,

“I will never have a website, not in a million years. Although I know if I get to a website, I can save at least 25% of that I pay to eBay and Amazon, but still, I do not think it will make any difference to my business as I am doing very good on eBay and Amazon.”

(Respondent A1)

Respondent A1 further clarified,

“I sell a lot of branded products. If I sell on eBay and Amazon, I can get away with the formalities. However, I will have to get permission from every brand to sell them on my website for branded products when I promote their products. There are many compliance issues with the branded products that require a lot of documentation, such as proof of stock purchase date, copyright of their photos and description. Furthermore, people do not trust new websites.”

However, respondent A3 affirmed that,

“We are selling on our website. It is the most comfortable for us because we have full control over the whole process. selling on eBay and Amazon, we do not have control over a lot of that process.”

It can be claimed from the above statements that a website provides greater control to the seller and avoid EC platforms challenges, but some businesses are reluctant to create a website due to the difficulties related to website creation and operations. The following sections discuss the challenges with e-commerce platforms.

6.4.1.2. Challenges with e-marketplaces

Adopters who are already selling on e-commerce mentioned some challenges. Some of them are generic, while others are for eBay or Amazon and social media marketplace. This section discusses the challenges in general.

Respondent stated that e-commerce platforms charge high commission and competition is high,

“Amazon and eBay are very competitive and charge unrealistic commissions. Especially Amazon, they charge a lot of money for everything, listing charge selling fees, FBA (fulfil by amazon) when we send product there. that’s why we cannot make enough money.

(Respondent A2)

“I think this charge is unrealistic as I have sourced the product, invested money, but they are taking a lot of it” (Respondent 10)

Regarding the dispute on platforms, one respondent stated,

“The problem is eBay and Amazon are too customer-centric. some customers take advantage of this system.” (Respondent A5)

Other respondents supported this and said,

“Amazon and eBay have both taken the view and change their policies over time, to make it very easy for customers to return products customers to say they have not received the order and get a refund, they probably may have received the item.”

(Respondent A6)

In conclusion, adopters believe that e-marketplaces charge high commissions and impose other restrictions on the seller. That can be challenging for businesses. The following section presents the advantages and disadvantages of Amazon.

6.4.1.2.1. Amazon

Being the most prominent e-commerce marketplace in the UK, Amazon has the largest customer base in the UK among other competitors. Independent DIY retailers can benefit from utilising the Amazon marketplace. Though, it offers many benefits for the sellers and is not free of challenges.

The respondent A3 suggested that,

“It was almost too easy listing on Amazon. You just type the barcode of the product into Amazon. And you could have that product listed for sale within minutes.”

However, the same respondent expressed that,

“Amazon is horrible. Suppose I could, if I would not sell on Amazon, and run my business. They are almost impossible to deal with. They don't care about their sellers. But they are the biggest player in the entire world, and you have to include them in your mix of platforms; you cannot ignore them. So, I just cannot bear dealing with them. And I take every opportunity not to have to deal with them. They are impossible.” (Respondent A3)

Another respondent suggested malpractice by amazon and claimed that,

*“I can tell you Amazon is r*****. They are extremely greedy sell all the top brands by themselves once we establish the market, and they closed my account for no reason. I am doing fine with eBay. They are different because eBay is just media. They do not sell. I will never sell again on Amazon.”* (Respondent A6)

It is seen that adopters find it challenging to comply with Amazon's authoritative policies, excessive charges, and other restrictions, though it is easy to start selling and listing on Amazon.

6.4.1.2.2. eBay

Most adopters expressed a positive stance regarding eBay. One respondent argued about the listing allowance on eBay and said,

“I tried to list my item, and eBay allow me to sell only ten products to start with. it took time to increase the selling allowance.” (Respondent A4)

Most adopters expressed that among all other marketplaces, eBay is relatively seller-friendly, but selling limits, in the beginning, is a challenge for new entrants. The following section discusses the issues with social media marketplaces.

6.4.1.2.3. Social media marketplaces

Social media marketplaces are the new trends in e-commerce. Some categories, such as beauty and fashion, are gaining market on social media, Facebook, Instagram. However, in the DIY category, it seems still in the early stage.

One respondent explained

“It’s not worth it; I tried; it does not work. I have 5000 plus followers of my business page, and we put the advert on Facebook and Instagram, but people like it but don’t buy it, for DIY products it doesn’t work you may be able to sell clothes.”

(Respondent A7)

Another respondent stated,

“Customers get information on social media and buy from eBay and Amazon. For example, I have been advertising on Facebook for a long but have not sold a single pc; on the other hand, I am getting around 400 orders every day on eBay and Amazon.” (Respondent A6)

The above discussion shows that adopters prefer e-commerce platforms over their own websites for e-commerce. However, between eBay and Amazon, they suggested eBay.

Table 33: Theme 2: EC practice summary

Theme 2: e-commerce practice	Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Most adopters do not prefer website as a starting point. ○ Difficulties with driving traffic. ○ Security concern.
	eBay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Easy to start with. ● Require fewer formalities. ● Respondents suggest eBay over all the platforms. ● Respondents believe the commission is high. ● Customer-centric. ● Seller friendly. ● Easy to sell internationally.
	Amazon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ More formalities. ▪ Easy to create a listing. ▪ Customer-centric. ▪ Conduct malpractice. ▪ Pressure sellers to subscribe to FBA. ▪ Many fees and charges.
	Social Media Marketplace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Lack of trust. ○ Not suitable for DIY products.

Source: Authors Construct.

6.5. Theme 3: Cross border e-commerce

This study explores the current state of cross border e-commerce in independently owned DIY retailing in the UK. Therefore, the respondents were asked whether they sell at cross-borders using e-commerce. It was found that six adopters are selling cross-border through the internet (A1, A4, A5, A6, A7 and A8).

6.5.1. The current state of CBeC:

E-marketplaces offer a tremendous opportunity of selling at cross-border for interdependent DIY retailers. Although, selling online through a website can transcend the national boundary, as stated previously, selling through a website is challenging, lacking customer trust on a small foreign website and lack of website reach and conversion.

Respondents A1 explained,

“I just list on eBay and Amazon, and I pay extra to eBay and Amazon to sell on the global marketplaces. 10% of our total sales come from all over the world. Sale is like before, but only the profit is less now after Brexit.”

Another respondent claimed that,

“We get orders from the whole world. My items sell most in Germany, I do not know why. I charge postage cost so product price getting high. But still people buy from here. Maybe people love UK item.” (Respondent A4)

Respondent A7 said

“We mostly sell tools and locks in the international market; we get orders mostly from the EU and Canada.”

Overall, the above statements suggest that e-commerce adopters already sell at cross-border markets using eBay and Amazon and receive orders from across the world.

6.5.2. Challenges of CBeC in practice

Selling at international markets through e-marketplaces has some challenges. Respondent A1 explained the challenges with the CBeC after Brexit,

“We must declare everything manufacturing country materials and others, find commodity code (SIC) you have to declare but finding the commodity code for every product. I don’t know how tax works, but we have to pay taxes on both sides.”

Furthermore, respondents mentioned that they receive missing parcel cases frequently. The respondent A4 stated,

“Product not accepted rate is high. It frequently happens for international orders. Maybe a flight issue or closed border nowadays.”

In conclusion, Brexit has added some new challenges for CBeC, selling in the EU markets. However, these rules and regulations were in place for destinations outside of the EU.

Summary of the CBeC:

Table 34: CBeC summary.

Theme 3: CBeC	Worldwide selling opportunity through eBay and Amazon.
	Customers buy from British sellers.
	It is challenging after Brexit.
	Transaction dispute is high for CBeC.
	Customs declaration is challenging.

Source: Author’s construct.

The following section discussed the opportunity of e-commerce adoption.

6.6. Theme 4: Opportunities

The adopters were asked how selling on e-commerce help their stores. It was found that e-commerce brings many benefits for DIY retailers. Those benefits are discussed below.

6.6.1. Maximisation of existing resources and employment

Respondents claimed that selling on e-commerce help keeps their staff employed.

“We are working with the same staff as we had before though our business doubled on eBay and amazon over the time.” (Respondent A2)

Another respondent claimed that,

“Our turnover increased on e-commerce sites, but our overall cost remained the same as we do not need any extra storage or staff for online sales.”

(Respondent A7)

The above statements suggest that e-commerce adoption for independents DIY retailers helps utilise existing resources.

6.6.2. Generating revenue

As stated in the previous section that adopting e-commerce allows maximum utilisation of resources and employees. Furthermore, it helps businesses generating more revenue.

Respondent A1 claimed,

“At the moment, online is helping in everything, eBay and Amazon are paying my wages, rents and rates. If it is not online - eBay and Amazon, I would’ve closed the business long ago. In the shop, we are not making even 20 % of our business. I am earning my living through eBay and Amazon.”

6.6.3. Employment and staff retentions

E-commerce adoption supports staff retention and more employment for small independent businesses. Most DIY e-commerce adopters interviewed in this study claimed that selling on eBay and Amazon helps retain their staff and leads to further employment.

Respondent A6 claimed that,

“Fortunately, I can keep people working for me for long. The good thing is we do eBay and Amazon (Picking and packing) when the shop is quiet. We do not need four people otherwise, and you know how business is these days.”

(Respondent A6)

Respondent A4 supported this stance and stated that,

“Before I had only one staff, now I have five staff, including me. My sales are going up and getting more busier day by day. I am planning to be recruiting two more part-time staff.

People are getting a job. It is a good sign.” (Respondent A4)

Similarly, respondent A3 claimed that,

“I certainly wouldn't be able to employ 11 people, and you know, be a local employer. That's the other thing that I kind of pride myself on. If you like is that we are based in a tiny village. And we provide jobs for 11 people that they only have to travel to three miles to every day.”

(Respondent A3)

The above statements suggest that selling on e-commerce platforms provides a significant advantage for independent DIY retailers in staff retention and allow additional employment.

6.6.4. Economy of scale and bulk buying

As small retailers mainly buy their stock from manufacturers and suppliers, they often receive less competitive prices due to their purchase capacity. However, selling on e-commerce platforms allows them to buy more and gain bulk-buy discounts. Due to this, non-adopters are often less competitive in the price offerings to the customers. Respondents A5, A8 and A9 claimed that,

“Number of items selling in eBay is way more than store and selling price is also higher.

It's also helping me when I buy from the supplier because they offer bulk purchase discounts. So, it leads to more profit”

(Respondent A8)

“You have to remember; my costing price depends on the quantity I buy. If I buy only for the shop, I will have to pay at least 30-35% more and buy from cash and carry (wholesaler) because big suppliers do not sell small quantities.”

(Respondent A9)

“I have to buy from the cash and carry which is 30-40% more expensive. How I am going to run my business if my costing price is 30% higher. It is online (eBay and Amazon) clears my 80% products.”

(Respondent A5)

6.6.5. Recycling

E-commerce allows retailers to recycle most of the cardboard that has twofold benefits. First, it saves recycling costs and then packaging materials costs.

“I mean, we recycle in that every single piece of cardboard that comes into this building get shredded, we've got a big cardboard shredder. So that saves our packaging cost for online.”

(Respondent A3)

Interestingly, e-commerce adoption helps businesses recycle most of the cardboard and use them for online packaging. Otherwise, companies have to pay for recycling to dispose of cardboard.

6.6.6. Positive cashflow

Selling on e-commerce platforms provides a greater cash flow. As Respondent A3 said,

“We were quite lucky, the business model that we have is an excellent positive cash flow model, we are not selling a product, and then waiting for our customers to pay us in a month, you know, everything is paid at the point of order.”

(Respondent A3)

6.6.7. Working capital and credit

Having a positive cash flow selling on e-commerce platforms allows retailers to capitalise on the suppliers' 30-45 days credit. Respondent A6 put it,

“We sell many brands and buy from many suppliers. Before, I had to pay for my order within the time; even if the stock was on the shelf, I struggled to pay all these

companies. Now the situation is much better because my stock rollover is much frequent. I get my money back from eBay before even I have to pay back."

"I have a credit account with all the suppliers and have 45 days credit term, I pay them after 45 days I get the bills, but in the meantime, I can roll at two times that products. I don't have to invest anything literally for many suppliers. cos I get paid instantly but pay them 45 days later."

(Respondent A2)

The above discussion highlights the benefits of e-commerce adoption that are often overlooked. These advantages could significantly impact the survival and growth of independent DIY retailers.

Summary of theme four

Table 35: An overview of the theme four.

Theme 4: Opportunity	Maximise the utilisation of existing resources.
	Generate revenue for the store.
	Helps staff retention and employment.
	Allow gaining economy of scale through bulk buy.
	Recycling facility and cost-saving.
	Positive cash flow model.
	Allows using working up capital and credit.

Source: Author's construct.

6.7. Conclusion:

This chapter presented the research findings in four themes. First, the challenges of e-commerce adoption were introduced, followed by the e-commerce practice. Furthermore, the results of the current state of CBeC were presented. Finally, the opportunities for EC adoption presented in this chapter.

The next chapter presents the analysis and the discussion.

Chapter 7: Analysis and Discussion

7.1. Introduction:

This chapter critically analyses the research findings in line with the research question and objectives. The chapter begins with the research questions and the results summary. Furthermore, this chapter critically discusses the findings in line with the existing literature. Moreover, this chapter proposes a conceptual framework for e-commerce adoption and internationalisation.

Research Objectives:

1. To investigate the individual characteristics and capabilities of independent DIY retail business owners to explore the challenges of e-commerce adoption.
2. To examine other micro and macro challenges that affect e-commerce adoption of independent DIY retailers in the UK.
3. To explore cross border e-commerce for independent DIY retailers in the UK by examining the existing literature and current practice.
4. Critically analysing the findings to reveal the challenges in practice to develop a model for e-commerce adoption and cross border e-commerce.
5. To recommend an e-commerce adoption strategy for the future success of independent DIY retailing in the UK.

Research Questions:

- What are the existing market research and relevant literature to inform the identification of e-commerce adoption challenges for British independent DIY retailers?
- How independent DIY retail owner's individual characteristics and capabilities affect e-commerce adoption?
- What technological, organisational, and environmental challenges affect e-commerce adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK?
- What are the current practices, challenges, and opportunities of selling internationally using e-commerce?
- What are the current challenges in practice for e-commerce adoption and implementation?

The following section presents the summary of the findings.

Table 36: Summary of the theme 1.

Theme 1: EC adoption challenges.	Technological challenges	The perceived complexity of e-commerce.	Affects e-commerce adoption significantly.
		Perceived advantages of e-commerce.	Less important.
		Cost of e-commerce adoption.	Initial cost does not affect EC adoption
			Concurring costs significantly affect EC adoption.
	Perceived ROI of EC investment.	Perceived ROI is one of the most influential factors of e-commerce adoption.	
	Organisational challenges	Owner's specific challenges	<p>Owner's awareness and perception of EC:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ owner's positive perception has less significance among the non-adopters for EC adoption. ➤ The owner's negative perception significantly affect EC adoption ➤ A similar pattern is seen among the adopters for channel extension.
			<p>Motivation and willingness to adopt EC:</p> <p>The owner's motivation and willingness for EC adoption is a crucial determinant for EC adoption.</p>
			<p>Lack of Skill:</p> <p>The owner's lack of technical skill affects EC adoption significantly.</p>
			<p>Lack of trust:</p>

			The owner's lack of trust on staff and technology provider, affect EC adoption significantly.
			<p>Owner's Age: EC adopters are relatively younger in their 40s, while most non-adopters are who are in their 50s. However, two of the largest DIY retailers in this study is 52 years old.</p> <p>Owner's education: Some EC adopters have university degrees, while most non-adopters are self-educated. However, two adopters who are the largest in terms of business size in this study are self-educated.</p>
		Resource:	<p>Capital: Respondents believe that they have enough capital to invest in EC. And its capital does not affect their EC adoption decision</p>
			<p>Skilled staff: Lack of skilled staff significantly affects EC adoption.</p>
			<p>Logistical capabilities: The owner's perceived capabilities affect EC adoption.</p>
		Years of business operation:	It does not have any significance on EC adoption.
		Size of the business	Size does not affect EC adoption.

	Environmental challenges	Competition	Direct competition: Competition for the high street competitors is less significant.
			Perceived Competition: Perceived competition of EC significantly affects EC adoption.
		Institutional support	Support from technology vendors and the government has a significant influence on EC adoption.
		Rules and regulations	E-commerce rules and regulations affect EC adoption.

Source: Author's construct.

Table 37: Theme 2: EC practice summary.

Theme 2: EC practice summary

Theme 2: e-commerce practice	Website	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Most adopters do not prefer a website as a starting point. ➤ Difficulties with driving traffic. ➤ Security concern.
	eBay	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Easy to start with. ➤ Require fewer formalities. ➤ Respondents suggest eBay over all the platforms. ➤ Respondents believe the commission is high. ➤ Customer-centric. ➤ Seller-friendly. ➤ Easy to sell internationally.
	Amazon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ More formalities. ➤ Easy to create a listing. ➤ Customer-centric. ➤ Conduct malpractice.

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Pressure sellers to subscribe to FBA. ➤ Many charges.
	Social Media Marketplace	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Lack of trust ➤ Lack of secure payments.

Source: Author's construct.

Table 38: Theme 3, CBeC summary.

Theme 3: CBeC	Worldwide selling opportunity through eBay and Amazon.
	Customers buy from British sellers.
	It is challenging after Brexit.
	Transaction dispute is high for CBeC.
	Customs declaration is challenging.

Source: Author's construct.

Table 39: An overview of the theme four.

Theme 4: Opportunity	Maximise the utilisation of existing resources.
	Generate revenue for the store.
	Helps staff retention and employment.
	Allow gaining economy of scale through bulk buy.
	Recycling facility and cost-saving.
	Positive cash flow model.
	Allows using working up capital and credit.

Source: Author's construct.

The following section discusses objective one.

7.1.1. Objective 1

To investigate the individual characteristics and capabilities of independent DIY retail business owners to explore the challenges of e-commerce adoption.

In small retail, SMEs owners play a pivotal role as they often single headedly manage the business. Therefore, small businesses' e-commerce adoption decision depends on how the owner perceives the e-commerce. Furthermore, their motivation plays a critical role in e-commerce adoption. However, this perception and motivation are driven by owners' other traits such as age, education, technical skills.

The following sections discuss how owner's perceptions on EC affect EC adoption for independently owned DIY retail businesses.

7.1.2. Owners' perception

This study found owners perception is crucial for EC adoption. They expressed different perceptions on various aspects. However, this cannot be concluded that the perception is independent. Instead, their perception is influenced by many other factors. The following sections discuss those aspects.

7.1.3. Perceived complexities of e-commerce

In this study, DIY retail owners perceived ease of use affects e-commerce adoption significantly. Most non-adopters perceived that EC related technology such as using computers, printers, and managing e-commerce would be complicated. This is significant because those who adopted e-commerce expressed that they faced those difficulties, but their willingness to learn the technology, supported their EC adoption. These findings support the results of previous studies (Nikolaeva, 2006; Stroud, Minahan and Sabapathy, 2009; Gavrilu and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021). The following section discusses the influence of owners' perceived advantage of EC adoption.

7.1.4. Perceived advantages of e-commerce

Interestingly, all the respondents in this study are aware of the EC benefits, and they perceive that EC adoption will bring benefits for their business. However, only one retailer attempted to learn though they found the process challenging, therefore, could not adopt the EC. At the same time, the majority did not take any initiatives for EC adoption. Consequently, it can be concluded that the perceived advantages of EC do not play a significant role in EC adoption for independent DIY retailers interviewed in this study. Interestingly, this can be seen in many previous studies (Riquelme, 2002; Quayle, 2002; Al-Qirim, 2007; Mkansi, 2021; Paul, Impey

and Stewart, 2021). Although, this finding contradicts with a large body of researchers who found that perceived advantages of EC adoption affect technology adoption (Rogers, 2003; Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Pearson and Grandon, 2005; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Sin *et al.*, 2016; Gavrilu and de Lucas Ancillo, 2021).

7.1.5. Motivation and willingness to adopt EC

This study found that owners' motivation and willingness to adopt e-commerce is crucial. As the adopter explicitly stated that they have self-educated themselves to learn from the internet or friends. Therefore, it can be concluded that the owner's motivation and willingness affect EC adoption significantly. This supports the findings of Tumolo (2001) and Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh (2016) and contradicts the findings of Stroud, Minahan and Sabapathy (2009) and Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021) and who argued that motivation is less significant for the EC adoption in SMEs.

7.1.6. Perceived ROI

This study found that owners perceived ROI as one of the most influential e-commerce adoption factors in independent DIY retailing. As all the non-adopters respondents claimed, they are willing to invest but expressed concern for return on investment. This justifies the previous studies (Pearson and Grandon, 2005; Kartiwi and MacGregor, 2007), who argued that SMEs owners often desire quick returns with limited resources.

7.1.7. Perceived Competition

This interesting finding in this study is that direct competition does not somewhat influence DIY retail owners. However, they are discouraged by the perceived competition of e-commerce. This finding contradicts almost all the previous studies (Al-Qirim, 2007; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Balakrishnan, Sundaresan and Zhang, 2014; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Mboli, Thakker and Mishra, 2020) who argued that intense competition stimulates EC adoption. Respondents in this study expressed a similar concern on perceived logistical capabilities. Non-adopters retailers deemed that they do not have the capabilities of EC fulfilments.

7.1.8. Owners Lack of trust in staff

Surprisingly most non-adopters and adopters claimed their lack of trust in staff affect EC adoption. This is a unique finding for this study. No previous study to have found this in retail SMEs. This is a significant factor as most non-adopters lack technical skills simultaneously; they lack trust in the staff.

7.1.9. Owner's age

EC adopters are relatively younger, in their 40s, while most non-adopters are in their 50s. However, two of the largest DIY retailers in this study is 52 years old. Therefore, it cannot be concluded owner's age affect EC adoption. However, Paul, Impey and Stewart (2021) found that SMEs below 40 are more likely to adopt EC.

7.1.10. Owner's education and technical skill

This study found no significance of education with the EC adoption. This contradicts the findings of Hossain, Azam and Quaddus (2021). However, owners lack of technical skill is crucial for EC adoption as most non-adopters explicitly claimed their inability to operate EC related technology affects EC adoption decisions. This result supports the study of Scuotto *et al.* (2021).

The following sections discuss objective two.

7.2. Objective 2

To examine other micro and macro challenges that affect e-commerce adoption of independent DIY retailers in the UK.

Many micro and macro factors influence retail SMEs EC adoption decisions. The following sections critically analyse those factors that play a critical role in EC adoption.

Existing technology usage does not influence EC adoption as most non -adopter businesses have computers and printers. Other previous studies found a similar result in their investigation (Avermaete *et al.*, 2003; Li *et al.*, 2011; Kurnia *et al.*, 2015). Although, a large number of researchers found otherwise (Tornatzky and Fleischer, 1990; Collins, Hage and

Hull, 1988; Baker, 2011; Maduku, Mpinganjira and Duh, 2016; Stjepić, Pejić Bach and Bosilj Vukšić, 2021).

The initial cost of EC does not play a role in EC adoption; instead, implementation and maintenance costs affect EC adoption decisions among the DIY retailers in this study. Most respondents claimed they are willing to pay for the initial cost, but they don't have enough resources to hire skilled staff to manage EC operations. However, existing literature (Ghobakhloo and Tang, 2011; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Tan and Wu, 2021) suggests otherwise.

Business size and year of operation do not play any role in e-commerce adoption among the DIY retailers in this study. Remarkably, this contradicts a large body of research (Lertwongsatien and Wongpinunwatana, 2003; Al-Qirim, 2007; Shemi and Procter, 2013; Xuhua, Chosniel Elikem and Akaba, 2019; Susanty *et al.*, 2020). Similarly, competition from direct competitors is less significant. This also contradicts the studies (Al-Qirim, 2007; Oliveira and Martins, 2010; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Hånell *et al.*, 2019). However, rules and regulations of EC affect adoption. Furthermore, DIY retailers in this study warranted institutional support for EC adoption. This result supports the following studies (Seyal and Rahman, 2003; Molla and Licker, 2005; Ghobakhloo, Arias-Aranda and Benitez-Amado, 2011; Badi *et al.*, 2020).

The following section discusses objective three.

7.3. Objective 3

To explore cross border e-commerce for independent DIY retailers in the UK by examining the existing literature and current practice.

Surprisingly, some DIY retailers sell at the cross border using eBay and Amazon. Respondents claimed that they receive regular orders from worldwide, around 10% of their online sales. However, it was found that before Brexit, retailers enjoyed free market benefits and now face customs declaration related difficulties. However, there is a tremendous opportunity for DIY retailers to sell internationally using e-commerce platforms, eBay and Amazon. Many

researchers (Deng and Wang, 2016; Huang and Chang, 2019; Hånell *et al.*, 2019; Qi *et al.*, 2020) made this proposition and urged small retailers to use EC platforms to sell globally. The following section discusses objective four.

7.4. Objective 4

Critically analysing the findings to reveal the challenges in practice to develop a model for e-commerce adoption and cross border e-commerce.

This study found that for most non-adopters, e-commerce means eBay and amazon. On the other hand, those selling online most of them sell on either eBay or Amazon. Based on the findings of this study with the recommendation of the adopters this study, proposes a 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model'.

Figure 24: Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model.

Source: Author's construct.

This study proposes a conceptual framework, piggyback e-commerce adoption and internationalisation based on the study result.

This model suggests that retailers should adopt to e-commerce platform first to offer at the home market and simultaneously, at the cross border. Then gradually extend to own website and social media marketplaces.

The Piggyback e-commerce adoption model can be successful for independent retailers. One such success story can be seen in the food and hospitality retail sector. Most restaurants adopted a similar model through food delivery service provider platforms, such as Just Eat, Uber Eats, Deliveroo. Establishing own restaurants is difficult for many such restaurants, but through adopting those platforms, most restaurants can access millions of customers locally and beyond their geographical area. Even big chain restaurants like MacDonald's, KFC are forced to adopt such a model. Though, they have their own online channels. It can be seen that it is all about reaching the target customer regardless of their usage of platforms.

Justification for e-commerce platforms over website:

Customer trust on the internet and online is not the same as website trust (Bart *et al.*, 2005). In Traditional ways, customers trust the Brick-and-mortar store, but online shopping is the website and the information provided (Jarvenpaa, Tractinsky and Vitale, 2000). Customers develop their perception through website navigation, the information provided, and many other antecedents that influence customer perception. Bart *et al.* (2005) argued that customer trust in websites heavily influenced many factors: financial risk, personal information and data privacy, payment details, uncertainty over the delivery. However, in the beginning, any business starts from scratch and build up customer trust over time through customer service. All the concerning factors that influence customer trust, e-commerce platforms assure the customers and customers are accustomed to those sites. Therefore, adopting e-commerce sites first and gaining experience on online shoppers' expectations and behaviour would benefit DIY retailers. Independent retailers can work on their website and build customer trust over time with the acquired knowledge and expertise.

It is tempting to suggest websites as many studies indicated that websites as the way to enter e-commerce operation. However, creating and maintaining an e-commerce website is not straightforward as it seems. Many independent DIY retailers lack technical and digital skills and cannot hire skilled staff due to resource limitations and lack of trust and security. Furthermore, it requires expensive SEO for discoverability and continuous digital marketing campaign to bring traffic to the websites. Therefore, creating a website cannot be suggested to begin with; instead, adopting e-commerce platforms such as eBay and Amazon is preferable for DIY retailers. This study shows that e-commerce platforms are the ideal starting

point for the e-commerce journey for independent DIY retailers as these platforms are well-established and have millions of active users and buyers.

Moreover, these platforms gained trust among the users and enhanced security for customers' purchases and flexible payment methods. Therefore, DIY retailers can capitalise from these platforms, which will allow businesses with customer knowledge, market knowledge, logistical knowledge and capabilities. This knowledge and abilities will enable retailers to open their own websites and offer domestic and global markets through e-commerce. Furthermore, this model does not require any upfront investment, as most respondents claimed they are concerned about their investment. This model can bring a positive cash flow to the business that can further be invested for channel extension. The following section discusses objective five.

7.5. Objective 5

To recommend an e-commerce adoption strategy for the future success of independent DIY retailing in the UK.

This study investigated many challenges and practices, and opportunities of e-commerce adoption. Based on the findings, this study suggests the below-mentioned strategies for future e-commerce success of the independent DIY retail sector.

7.5.1. Online entry strategies

7.5.1.1. Setting up 'My Business' page in search engines

The foundation of e-commerce has a detailed Google business page that offers customers essential information about the business, such as contact details, opening and closing hours. Furthermore, the google my business page allows business to showcase their products and services to potential customers. Though Google automatically lists the business address on the google map based on the publicly available data from a different source, do not update the contact information.

An increasing number of internet users uses Google to find out about the business before visiting the store. Having the updated contact details on Google or other search engines can attract more customers. Looking at the google trend in the UK, most search words in the DIY category are, 'DIY stores near me', 'Best DIY store near me' and 'Hardware store near me' (Google Trends, 2021).

However, it was observed during the research most of the non-e-commerce adopters of small independent DIY businesses do not have updated information on Google pages. Therefore, they have fewer reviews on Google. In contrast, adopters who have a website have an updated and detailed Google page. This is important because it suggests those businesses to strong SEO users based on relevancy, appropriateness, and reviews. People do not do DIY every day and only search for the stores when needed, unlike other shops, such as groceries and coffee shops. Therefore, businesses must have updated information on the google page.

Business owners can update their details through their google account or using Google's 'My Business' app and claim their business page for free. This will allow the customer to find the shop, eventually, bring more customers to the shop.

7.5.1.2. Listings business in directories

Having business listed on the business directories, such as Yell.com, yelp.com reg.123.com, has many benefits. First of all, it allows a business with more visibility to the directory users. Furthermore, it will enable search engines and digital devices to recommend the information and location to internet users.

Search engines are integrated into these directories and collect business data when users search for information. Many of these directories offer a small business with free tools and subscription-based SEO and website maintenance services. For example, Yell.com provide businesses with many user-friendly free tools. For instance, free DIY website, website health scanner, online reputation scanner, digital marketing guide, Yell business app and free messaging service. (See appendix 10.12)

Yel.com is the number one business directory in the UK (Similarweb, 2021a), ranked by the leading website traffic ranking provider Similarweb, and has over 2.1 million monthly unique

visitors. In addition, yell is the crucial data providing the partner with Apple maps and spotlight search through iPhone and iPad, Microsoft Bing maps and virtual assistant Cortana, Google, Facebook, digital home device- Amazon Alexa. Therefore, it is essential to have a business listed on the directories like yell.com in order to gain more visibility to millions of potential customers.

DIY retailers who have not adopted e-commerce expressed that lack of experience and support affecting e-commerce adoption can begin with this service. Most basic services can be used for free, and additional benefits can be used for a £10 monthly fee.

7.5.2. Strategy for selling on e-marketplaces

Generally, eBay is easy to start selling as they are flexible in listing requirements for new entrants and have a wide range of tutorials videos on the overall process. Including account opening and other transactional procedures. However, all the platforms are highly customer-centric. Therefore, these platforms maintain the buyer interest first policy in their terms and conditions. In addition, though, they have various seller-protection measures to protect seller interest that prevents scammers and opportunity hunters.

Selling on eBay and Amazon requires registration. Only registered sellers can sell on the platforms. Then like any other e-commerce business, it needs to list its products on the site. eBay allows the registered seller to sell up to £80,000 yearly as a private seller. Above this threshold, a seller needs to be registered as a business seller and buy store subscriptions. Both the business models have pros and cons. However, expert sellers suggest that small businesses start as a private seller and slowly learn the business process, then progress to the business seller. However, if sellers wish to be registered as business sellers, they can do so, to begin with. A business account requires a company registration number from the Company House. A private seller business does not need to be VAT registered for business sellers; VAT registration is mandatory. It is believed that DIY stores are registered as a company, and therefore Independent DIY retailers have the opportunity to open an account with eBay. A guideline for the DIY retailer is provided below.

Product Listing: Process

- **Product Title:** Appropriate product title is vital for selling on e-commerce as it allows the search engine to recognise the products and recommend them to the customers. As eBay suggests that relevant and appropriate keywords help the seller to reach more customers. It is also important because the wrong title may mislead the customers and result in the return of the order. This will affect seller performance negatively as eBay promotes a better service better customer service. It is important to note that eBay allows 80 characters for the listing title. However, a seller may add a sub-title for a fee. But adding a subtitle is not a common practice.
- **Selecting the appropriate categories:** Selecting the appropriate category is important for greater visibility on eBay. Moreover, selecting the wrong category may cause problems for the seller account as outlined in the eBay term and conditions. Major categories are divided into many subcategories depending on the appropriateness of the product. For instance, Home, Furniture & DIY > DIY Materials> Paint, Stain and Varnishes > interior and exterior paint. However, sellers can select the category as they seem appropriate for the particular product.
- **EAN Number:** Adding EAN (European Article Numbering) codes, commonly known as barcode numbers, is a good practice as it allows greater product visibility. When customers search for a product using a barcode, google quickly finds the products listed with EAN numbers. Having a barcode allows gaining traffic from outside the eBay platforms. Furthermore, EAN will enable eBay to add existing product reviews on its sites, benefiting a new seller as customers would be better informed before making a purchase.
- **Creating Variations:** eBay allows the sellers to create a variation in a single listing. The seller can make any variation they deem appropriate as colour, size, price and many more. The number of products DIY retailers sell is astonishingly high as paint and varnishes come in different sizes (250ml, 500ml, 1litre, 2.5 litres), shades (white, magnolia, black, red) and finishing (gloss, satin, matt). This is a valuable tool for the DIY products category as it saves time for the seller to list all the variations in one place rather than creating a single listing for every single variant.
- **Selecting product Condition:**
It is essential to mention the product condition as buyer has the right to know the state of the product so that they can make an informed decision. There are few categories of

products, such as brand new with labels and tags. If a box is damaged or any fault in the product, it should be listed under that specific category. This will decrease the product return and refund, as most respondents selling on e-commerce that return and refund is one of the biggest challenges of e-commerce of sale.

- **Product images:**

Photos are crucial for e-commerce as customers only able to see the images of the products. Therefore, providing the customer with a lot of explicit photos from a different angle is crucial. Furthermore, a product video is an emerging trend. Many well-known brands that sell on e-commerce display a 360-degree product video. For example, JD sports, Curry's PC World, Argos. Most e-commerce platforms such as eBay and Amazon allow displaying up to 12 photos and one video. Retailers can showcase their products in the photo section in order to attract customers' attention.

- **Adding item specifications and features:**

Most search engine and SEO work on the relevance of the customer search before showing to the customers. Adding as many as possible applicable product specifications help search engine to find the product.

- **Adding item description:**

Detailed product description helps customers know about the product as customers only can learn about the product through the description provided by the seller. Furthermore, giving correct products information is mandatory according to the trading standard regulations.

- **Choosing price format:**

Price is essential in e-commerce as many sellers compete in the same category, and most customers are price sensitive. Therefore, setting up a competitive price is crucial as buyers can compare prices within a click. And there is many prices comparison software available on the internet. Furthermore, most search engines, including Google shopping, allow customers to filter the search according to the price. Furthermore, offering discounts, coupons and tempting promotions enhance the sell-through rate and customer loyalty. eBay suggests sellers allow customers to make an offer and recommends that product listing with the 'best offer' option perform better than non-offering product listing.

- **Adding the product quantity:**

The sellers need to add appropriate product quantities as DIY independent retailers use their store stock for online listing.

- **Postage:**

Sellers have the opportunity to charge for the postage or offer free shipping depending on seller strategies.

For Amazon:

Amazon maintains strict account operations that strictly maintain and monitors account activities. As a buyer, opening an account and buying is much easier than the seller's account to maintain the platform's integrity. Therefore, only company House registered businesses are only allowed to sell on a business account in total capacity. A private seller can sell few items on Amazon, but that is not feasible for the independent DIY retailers as any average independent DIY retailer in the UK have thousands of products in their brick-and-mortar store that require a varied and approved business account before start selling. Moreover, DIY retailing involves selling paints, solvents, adhesives, sharp tools and many other restricted products.

7.5.3. Other strategies

7.5.3.1. *Ways to reduce Return*

1. Detailing the description accurately clearly can reduce return significantly as 88% of returns were made because the product was not as described. Moreover, accurate product details can help a customer make an informed decision that will reduce the recovery for change of mind.
2. The product must be displayed with many explicit photos from every possible angle, if possible, with a 360-degree video. Many big retailers are already using short videos with images (Callarman, 2021).
3. Secure and appropriate packaging: in 2020, 22% of returns were made due to damage during shipment. Therefore, adequate packaging materials, including double corrugated cardboards, air pillows, bubble wrap, and other protective materials, should be used to control damage during shipment.

7.5.3.2. Leaflet marketing through e-commerce platforms

E-commerce platforms can pave the marketing for own websites. Leaflet marketing is one of the affordable traditional marketing tools these days. Many large companies and SMEs still practise this leafleting marketing. Most importantly, it has been observed that high street retailers still maintain leaflet marketing through the leaflet distributor, newspaper, or shopfront. However, this small-scale leafletting covers only a specific geographic area that targeted and served by the business. An e-commerce platform enables a business to sell across the country and internationally. This allows businesses to reach many customers across the country. Retailers can run promotional campaigns, including coupons, promotional vouchers, and business cards to attract customers to their websites. Happy customers will be confident to shop from their websites as they already bought from the retailers through e-marketplaces. Thus, SMEs have the opportunities to utilise those platforms.

7.5.3.3. Gathering customers database

E-commerce platforms allow a business to save and download customers data with all the details, including name, address, contact number, email address items bought from the retailers. These customers data would be beneficial to the business when they launch their websites. Retailers will have the opportunity to run a digital marketing campaign for those existing customers, especially an email campaign. Though GDPR and ethical issues arise at this point, retailers need to make sure that they deal with customers' privacy with care. This is not only for the data they collected from e-commerce platforms but also for any customer data privacy should be respected equally regardless of the offline and online channel.

7.5.3.4. Click and collect offerings and fulfilment

Big DIY retailers, B&Q, Screwfix, Toolstation, Homebase and Argos, have been practising click and collect models to drive customers in-store. (Sillitoe, 2020). Independent retailers can utilise social media and e-commerce platforms to their advantage, offering click and collect, which means buying on social media or eBay and amazon and collecting locally. This can drive customers to brick and mortar stores that may drive more sales. Furthermore, unused store space can be used for online inventory warehousing, which reduces overall business costs and eventually contributes to profitability.

7.5.3.5. Hybrid store strategy

High street retail space is always expensive, and independent retailers struggle to meet per SQF. However, independent DIY retailers can utilise existing store space as the Warehouse for the online inventory if they sell anything online that is not in store.

7.5.4. Skill enhancing strategies

Independent DIY retail owners warranted institutional support. There are many supports available. Some of them are given below.

7.5.4.1. Support from technology vendors

In May 2021, Vodafone UK, in partnership with 'Enterprise Nation', has declared a digital training programme for British SMEs and offering basic training on e-commerce for technology and EC adoption, implementation, maintenance of 100,000 SMEs for free. SMEs can register for free through this link <https://www.vodafone.co.uk/business/sme-business/business-connected>.

7.5.4.1.1. Amazon small Business Accelerator programme

Another free support programme funded by Amazon and organised and provided by Enterprise Nations is the Amazon small business accelerator programme, offering free online training for small businesses to grow online. This free educational programme is open for anyone planning to open a new online or existing business that wants to grow and expand in digital platforms.

Interestingly, this course is designed and tailored for users experience level and need. This comprehensive online course covers creating a website, selling online, social media marketing, selling on amazon locally and internationally, managing cash flow, search engine optimisation (SEO), data analytics. Furthermore, it allows participants to attend many other events, seminars, digital intensive boot camps organised by Amazon and Enterprise Nation's affiliated organisation. This programme can be registered through this link <https://enterprisenationportal11.microsoftcrmportals.com/accelerator/>.

7.5.4.2. Government support for CBeC

Although many independent retailers are not aware of such facilities provided by the British government to sell internationally, Department for International Trade (DIT) runs many online and offline informational and educative events conducted by industry experts throughout the year. Most of the event is free to join for the business. Exporting is Great campaign offers in-depth knowledge about the twenty-two industry and category wise A complete list of categories are given below) E-commerce platforms in all the countries across the world. Retailers can access that information through this link, <https://www.great.gov.uk/selling-online-overseas/>. This website simplifies market insight about the prospective market using e-commerce sites popular in the host country business want to export. This is an excellent opportunity for the DIY retailers to capitalise as many retailers cannot gather market intelligence, culture, consumer behaviour and preferences about the host country. Businesses can get tailor-made expert advice about opportunities in the target market and get an e-commerce export strategy and the right marketplace for their products and industry. Furthermore, these DIT initiatives offer affiliation benefits through the DIT sites for the business. The offers include reduced or free registration fees, no or less listing fees and commission for a certain period, varying from country to country. DIT offers support from the beginning until retailers can set up a business operation on the target market e-commerce sites. In addition, there are plenty of case studies; success stories retailers can learn from to grow further.

List of categories: Alphabetically

<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Arts, crafts, and hobbies○ Baby and toddler○ Books, music and film○ Business, industrial and science○ Cameras, lenses and photography○ Celebration and ceremonial○ Clothing and accessories○ Computer software and games○ DIY, Tools and Hardware.○ Electronics, computing and communications	<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Furniture○ Garden and Outdoor○ Health and beauty○ Home and Lifestyle○ Luggage and bags○ Mature○ Pet care○ Religious and ceremonial○ Sports and leisure○ Stationery and office supplies○ Toys and Games
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○ Food and Drink	○ Vehicle parts and accessories.
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7.6. Concusion

This chapter critically analysed the findings in line with the research objectives.

In addition, it suggested a practical e-commerce adoption model. Finally, it provided e-commerce strategies. The following chapter will present the conclusion of this thesis, including future recommendations.

Chapter 8: Conclusion, Recommendations, and Implications

8.1. Introduction

This chapter provides a summary of this thesis in line with the research aim and objectives. Furthermore, it includes the implication of the research findings, study limitations, and future research directions. Therefore, the chapter starts with reiterating the research objectives and questions in order to guide the research outcomes.

8.2. Research aims, objectives and questions

Research aims:

To examine the e-commerce adoption challenges and opportunities to develop strategies for e-commerce adoption and market expansion for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

Research Objectives:

1. To investigate the individual characteristics and capabilities of independent DIY retail business owners to explore the challenges of e-commerce adoption.
2. To examine other micro and macro challenges that affect e-commerce adoption of independent DIY retailers in the UK.
3. To explore cross border e-commerce for independent DIY retailers in the UK by examining the existing literature and current practice.
4. Critically analysing the findings to reveal the challenges in practice to develop a model for e-commerce adoption and cross border e-commerce.
5. To recommend an e-commerce adoption strategy for the future success of independent DIY retailing in the UK.

Research Questions:

- What are the existing market research and relevant literature to inform the identification of e-commerce adoption challenges for British independent DIY retailers?
- How independent DIY retail owner's individual characteristics and capabilities affect e-commerce adoption?
- What technological, organisational, and environmental challenges affect e-commerce adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK?

- What are the current practice, challenges, and opportunities of selling internationally using e-commerce?
- What are the current challenges in practice for e-commerce adoption and implementation?

The following sections summarise the research questions this study aimed to answer.

8.3. Research question One

The first research question was, what are the existing market research and relevant literature to identify e-commerce adoption challenges for British independent DIY retailers?

This study clearly highlighted in chapter one (background) that the number of interdependent DIY retailers in sharp decline, research published by Mintel (2020), Statista (2020) and BIRA (2021). These market research clearly highlighted that the rise of online retailing, less footfall on the high streets, low profitability contributed to the decline of small independent DIY retailers across the UK. Many other leading market research organisations (CRR,2020; Deloitte, 2021; PwC, 2021) expressed similar concerns for independent brick-and-mortar DIY retailers. Academics emphasised e-commerce adoption for retail SMEs. However, Mintel (2020) suggests that independent DIY retailers' online participation is significantly low.

Chapter two clearly established that the small retailers' unique features are often limiting their ability to adopt e-commerce. However, it was also established potential benefits of e-commerce adoption guided the existing research. And found that no current literature examined the e-commerce adoption challenges of small independent DIY retailers in the UK. Chapter three clearly established the e-commerce adoption challenges using the TOE framework. However, it was also identified that most existing knowledge of SMEs e-commerce adoption is multidisciplinary and therefore unable to address the obstacles independent DIY retailers' encounter. In addition, the current e-commerce adoption model (figure below) suggested a website as the way to offline to the online channel.

Figure 25: Current e-commerce adoption model for retail SEMs.

Source: Author's construct.

Chapter four highlighted the cross-border opportunities for small retailers through e-commerce for resource-constraint DIY retailers, which is almost impossible in the traditional way of internationalisation. It was also established that e-commerce platforms connect customers worldwide with geographically niched small retailers. However, it was not known how the current state of CBEC practices among the independent DIY retailers.

8.4. Research question two

Guided by the literature, it was found that e-commerce adoption for independent retail SMEs is heavily dependent on the owner's characteristics. Therefore, it was imperative to investigate how independent DIY retail owner's individual characteristics and capabilities affect e-commerce adoption.

This study found that owners perceptions of EC significantly affect EC adoption. Remarkably, the owner's perceived advantages of EC do not play a significant role in EC adoption because of the lack of technical skill and motivation to adopt EC. On the other hand, their negative perceptions affect EC adoption significantly. This study also found that owners' lack of trust

in staff affects EC adoption as most DIY retail owners lack technical knowledge and are unwilling to hire EC staff. Furthermore, it was also found that the direct competition did promote EC adoption, but perceived EC competition significantly affected EC adoption. Finally, lack of institutional support affects EC adoption. Most retailers in this study urged for training support and affirmed that such training on EC adoption would support them in integrating online channels. However, owners age and education does not play any role in EC adoption in independent DIY retailing, studied in this thesis.

8.5. Research question three

Existing literature suggested that other micro and macro factors influence EC adoption for small independent retail businesses apart from owner's traits. Therefore, this study examined what technological, organisational, and environmental factors affect EC adoption for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

This exploratory study found that EC complexity affects EC adoption significantly as some independent DIY retailers in this study attempted to learn the EC process and failed to launch the EC channel successfully. In addition, this study found that the initial cost of EC adoption is less significant for EC adoption. However, EC implementation costs and operating costs, such as recruiting staff and paying eBay and Amazon commission, significantly affect EC adoption in independent DIY retailing. This is a crucial finding because the existing literature categorises the EC costs instead of generalising the costs in a broader term. This understanding would help the policymakers to address the EC adoption challenges. Finally, it was found that unfavourable EC regulations affect EC adoption, as retailers who sell at cross border stated that after Brexit selling to EU is complicated having to declare SIC code for every product, and new VAT for international sales added more complexity to CBeC.

8.6. Research Question four

Existing literature suggested that EC adoption provides multifaceted benefits for small retailers to sell locally and internationally. Therefore, this study explored the current practice, challenges, and opportunities of selling internationally using e-commerce. Interestingly, this was found that British DIY tools and accessories are popular across the world. Five retailers in

this study sold globally through eBay and Amazon and claimed that 10% of the total online sales come from the cross-border. One significant finding of this study that DIY retailers do not use their own website for CBeC; instead use piggybacking for internationalisation. This is because of the discoverability of the website in a foreign market, international customers' lack of trust in unfamiliar websites. Therefore, eBay and Amazon offer tremendous opportunities to sell globally by facilitating traffic, payment gateways and fulfilments.

8.7. Research question five

Understanding the current practice of e-commerce adoption in independent DIY retailing in the UK was apparent to understand the challenges and opportunities to make informed suggestions. Therefore, this study examined the current e-commerce adoption practice among independent DIY retailers.

It was found that independent DIY retailers prefer e-commerce platforms over their own websites, as it doesn't require a substantial upfront investment. In addition, these platforms have millions of active customers across the world that small retailers can reach instantly. However, these platforms charge excessive fees and exert strict control over the third-party sellers, as stated by the retailers in this study. Still, the overwhelming majority reiterated that they prefer eBay and Amazon. Furthermore, these retailers affirmed that selling on e-commerce platforms offered them many benefits, such as gaining economy of scale through bulk-buying, utilising the existing store and staff. In addition, this approach provides a positive cash flow to the business that support their survival in a brick-and-mortar store and allow more employment and staff retention. Finally, it will enable the opportunity to sell globally without any significant investment. Therefore, this study proposes a 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model' (figure below) for the independent DIY retailers in the UK.

Figure 26: Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model.

Source: Author's construct.

This conceptual model proposes retailers should enter e-marketplaces to utilise the opportunity to reach customers locally and globally, as this will enable independent DIY retailers to learn e-commerce processes, fulfilments and gain e-commerce capabilities. Furthermore, this will allow independent DIY retailers to gain market knowledge and bring revenue to invest in the own online channel and strengthen their survival and sustainable growth.

The researcher believes the e-commerce platforms are the way forward for the independent DIY retailing industry in the UK. It enables SMEs to initiate the e-commerce entrance, given these platforms have millions of active customers at home and millions of potential customers internationally. Although this study cannot generalise the result having a limited sample size, the in-depth understanding gained in this study justifies the viability of this model.

Following the findings of this study, this thesis recommends e-commerce strategies for the future success of independently owned DIY retailing in the UK, which fulfils objective five, which is to recommend e-commerce adoption strategies for future success.

These strategies address many challenges independent DIY retailers are facing at this moment. First of all, retailers stated that they lack understanding of the EC adoption process, and this study provides a step-by-step strategy that guides the independent retailers' online entrance. In addition, retailers claimed that they require institutional support and are unaware of any such support. Therefore, this study recommends many such facilities by the technology vendors, and governments and other organisations. For instance, Enterprise Nation', 'Amazon small Business Accelerator Programme' and Google Digital Garage' offers free digital training for SMEs and DIY retailers can gain knowledge and capabilities by utilising those programmes. Finally, this study recommends that DIY retailers use the CBeC service DIT (Department for International Trade).

8.8. Research recommendations for DIY retailers

Independent DIY retailers in the UK can follow the findings of this study and suggestions to successfully integrate online sales channels to offer their products in the UK and across the world. Especially, they can adopt the 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and internationalisation model' for future survival and success.

8.9. Implication for policymakers

- SME foundation should focus on digitalisation and supporting small businesses to adopt e-commerce as it was observed from the various government sources that the government has few initiatives for small independently own companies to help grow e-commerce.
- Department for International Trade: DIT offers many pieces of training to help SMEs to internationalise. However, due to the lack of communication, independent retailers are unable to utilise those services, and therefore, DIT should communicate through the proper channel to inform retail SMEs.
- Industry body: BIRA (British Independent Retail Association) and other trade associations lack promoting e-commerce. Therefore, they can encourage e-commerce so that independent retailers can adopt e-commerce and harness the opportunities EC offers.

- For e-commerce platforms: E-platforms can promote this Piggyback e-commerce adoption model and make seller-friendly policies to attract more independent retailers.

8.10. Contribution to the theory

- This empirical study contributes to the body of knowledge by adding an in-depth understanding of British independent DIY retailers' e-commerce adoption challenges and market expansion opportunities at the cross border using e-commerce.
- This research contributes to the Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE) framework by including unique elements.

8.11. Contribution to the Practice

- This study contributes to the practice by adding a 'Piggyback-style e-commerce adoption and market expansion model'.
- This study further contributes to the practice by providing a 'step-by-step' e-commerce strategy for independent DIY retailers in the UK.

8.12. Research limitations

- Generalisation and Sample size: This study considers a small sample size for non-e-commerce adopters from London due to the researcher's convenience. Therefore, it was not known whether independently owned DIY businesses outside of London encounter similar challenges. Therefore, this cannot be generalised as the complete scenario of independent DIY retailing in the UK. In addition, though, e-commerce adopters represent different cities and ethnicity.
- Lack of women representation: Furthermore, based on the interview from the male respondents, the industry is heavily male-dominated. Therefore, women perspectives could not include in this research. The researcher strongly believes a women perspective would have added more value to our understanding of the adoption challenges.

8.13. Future research directions

As stated, this study is the first of its kind. It combines many unexplored key research areas, such as independent DIY retailing, category-specific e-commerce adoption challenges and cross-border e-commerce (CBeC). Therefore, any particular focus could not be paid in any specific area. However, this study lays the foundation for many future research prospects. Therefore, these three key areas deserve to be investigated separately.

- Based on the findings of this study, e-commerce adoption challenges among independent DIY retailers can be investigated further, considering a larger sample size from the different parts of the UK.
- This study proposes a piggyback style e-commerce adoption and market expansion model. However, it could not be tested among a large sample. Therefore, future studies can test the viability among the large sample size.
- This model can be tested in other categories.

8.14. Concluding remarks

The claims made in this study are valid for the independent DIY retailers interviewed in this study. However, this understanding of independent DIY retailing could open the path for independently-owned retailers across the UK.

Chapter 9: References:

- Abdul Hamid, A. K. and Aliman, N. K. (2020) The Characteristics of Adopters and Non-Adopters of Digital Marketing Application among Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMES). Asian Journal of Business and Management. Vol.8 (5).
- Abdullah, A., Thomas, B., Murphy, L. and Plant, E. (2018) An Investigation of the Benefits and Barriers of e-business Adoption Activities in Yemeni SMEs. Strategic Change. Vol.27 (3), pp.195–208.
- Abebe, M. (2014) Electronic Commerce adoption, Entrepreneurial Orientation and small- and medium-sized Enterprise (SME) Performance. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.21 (1), pp.100–116.
- Abed, S. S. (2020) Social Commerce Adoption Using TOE framework: an Empirical Investigation of Saudi Arabian SMEs. International Journal of Information Management. [Online] Vol.53, p.102118. Available: <https://0-www-sciencedirect-com.lispac.lsbu.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0268401219314549> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Abualrob, A. A. and Kang, J. (2016) The Barriers That Hinder the Adoption of e-commerce by Small Businesses. Information Development. Vol.32 (5), pp.1528–1544.
- Acedo, F. J. and Jones, M. V. (2007) Speed of Internationalization and Entrepreneurial cognition: Insights and a Comparison between International New ventures, Exporters and Domestic Firms. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.42 (3), pp.236–252. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1090951607000375> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Acılar, A. and Karamaşa, Ç. (2010) Factors Affecting the Adoption of E-Commerce by Small Businesses: a Case Study. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Agnihotri, A. (2015) Can Brick-and-Mortar Retailers Successfully Become Multichannel Retailers? Journal of Marketing Channels. Vol.22 (1), pp.62–73.
- Ajmal, F. and Yasin, N. M. (2012) Model for Electronic Commerce Adoption for Small and Medium Sized Enterprises. International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology. Vol.3 (3), pp.90–94.

- Ajzen, I. (1991) The Theory of Planned Behavior. Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes. [Online] Vol.50 (2), pp.179–211. Available: <https://0-www-sciencedirect-com.lispac.lsbu.ac.uk/science/article/pii/074959789190020T> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Akhromeeva, T. S., Malinetskiy, G. G. and Posashkov, S. A. (2020) Limits and Risks of Digital Transformation. Digital Transformation. (2), pp.51–57.
- Al-Azawei, A., Parslow, P. and Lundqvist, K. (2016) Investigating the Effect of Learning Styles in a Blended e-learning system: an Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM). Australasian Journal of Educational Technology.
- Al-Qirim, N. (2007) The Adoption of eCommerce Communications and Applications Technologies in Small Businesses in New Zealand. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. [Online] Vol.6 (4), pp.462–473. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S1567422307000178?token=96EE1646D9519BA43D1FE89C45349C99D4DA4D944030B7C1542D781F4E9CC839C943E336F093C0CACF9D4BB6CADD5EFB&originRegion=eu-west-1&originCreation=20210508030238> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Al-Somali, S. A., Gholami, R. and Clegg, B. (2015) A stage-oriented Model (SOM) for e-commerce adoption: a Study of Saudi Arabian Organisations. Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management. Vol.26 (1), pp.2–35.
- Alcácer, J., Cantwell, J. and Piscitello, L. (2016) Internationalization in the Information age: a New Era for places, firms, and International Business networks? Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.47 (5), pp.499–512. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/jibs.2016.22> [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Ale Ebrahim, N., Abdul Rashid, S. H., Ahmed, S. and Taha, Z. (2011) The Effectiveness of Virtual R&D Teams in SMEs: Experiences of Malaysian SMEs. Industrial Engineering and Management Systems. Vol.10 (2), pp.109–114.
- Alexander, N. and Doherty, A. M. (2010) International Retail research: focus, Methodology and Conceptual Development. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.38 (11/12), pp.928–942.
- Ali, A. B., Miao, J.-J. and Tran, Q. D. (2018) Study on E-Commerce Adoption in SMEs under the Institutional Perspective. International Journal of E-Adoption. Vol.10 (1), pp.53–72.
- Amasanti, M. (2020) DIY Retailing: Inc Impact of COVID-19 - UK - May 2020 - Market Research Report [Online]. Mintel.com. Available:

- <https://reports.mintel.com/display/988726/?fromSearch=%3Ffreetext%3DUK%2520DIY%2520Retailing%2520Market%2520Report%25202020> [Accessed 20 Feb 2021].
- Andersson, S. and Wikström, N. (2017) Why and How Are Social Media Used in a B2B context, and Which Stakeholders Are involved? Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing. Vol.32 (8), pp.1098–1108.
- Aparicio, S., Audretsch, D. and Urbano, D. (2021) Why Is export-oriented Entrepreneurship More Prevalent in Some Countries than others? Contextual Antecedents and Economic Consequences. Journal of World Business. Vol.56 (3), p.101177.
- APPSSG (2017) High Street Britain : 2015. London: London: All-Party Parliamentary Small Shops Group, House of Commons.
- Augustine, B. (2008) Want to Lease Space at Staten Island Ferry Terminal? [Online]. Silive. Available:
https://www.silive.com/news/2008/03/want_to_lease_space_at_staten.html
[Accessed 4 May 2021].
- Avermaete, T., Viaene, J., Morgan, E. J. and Crawford, N. (2003) Determinants of Innovation in Small Food Firms. European Journal of Innovation Management. Vol.6 (1), pp.8–17.
- Awiagah, R., Kang, J. and Lim, J. I. (2016) Factors Affecting e-commerce Adoption among SMEs in Ghana. Information Development. Vol.32 (4), pp.815–836.
- Aziz, N. N. A. and Samad, S. (2016) Innovation and Competitive Advantage: Moderating Effects of Firm Age in Foods Manufacturing SMEs in Malaysia. Procedia Economics and Finance. Vol.35, pp.256–266.
- Babin, B. J., Zikmund, W. G., Quinlan, C., Carr, J. C. and Griffin, M. (2019) Business Research methods. Andover: Cengage Learning.
- Badi, S., Ochieng, E., Nasaj, M. and Papadaki, M. (2020) Technological, Organisational and Environmental Determinants of Smart Contracts adoption: UK Construction Sector Viewpoint. Construction Management and Economics. [Online] Vol.39 (1), pp.36–54. Available:
<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/epub/10.1080/01446193.2020.1819549?needAccess=true> [Accessed 1 Mar 2021].
- Bahl, M., Lahiri, S. and Mukherjee, D. (2021) Managing Internationalization and Innovation Tradeoffs in Entrepreneurial firms: Evidence from Transition Economies. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.56 (1), p.101150. Available:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S109095162030078X>

[Accessed 6 Jun 2021].

- Baker, E. W., Al-Gahtani, S. S. and Hubona, G. S. (2010) Cultural Impacts on Acceptance and Adoption of Information Technology in a Developing Country. Journal of Global Information Management. Vol.18 (3), pp.35–58.
- Baker, J. (2011) The Technology–Organization–Environment Framework. Information Systems _____ Theory. [Online] pp.231–245. Available: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-1-4419-6108-2_12 [Accessed 1 Mar 2021].
- Balakrishnan, A., Sundaresan, S. and Zhang, B. (2014) Browse-and-Switch: Retail-Online Competition under Value Uncertainty. Production and Operations Management. Vol.23 (7), pp.1129–1145.
- Barney, J. (1991) Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. Journal of Management. [Online] Vol.17 (1), pp.99–120.
- Barney, J. B. (2001) Is the Resource-Based “View” a Useful Perspective for Strategic Management Research? Yes. The Academy of Management Review. Vol.26 (1), p.41.
- Baron, S., Harris, K., Leaver, D. and Oldfield, B. M. (2001) Beyond Convenience: the Future for Independent Food and Grocery Retailers in the UK. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research. Vol.11 (4), pp.395–414.
- Bart, Y., Shankar, V., Sultan, F. and Urban, G. L. (2005) Are the Drivers and Role of Online Trust the Same for All Web Sites and Consumers? a Large-Scale Exploratory Empirical Study. Journal of Marketing. [Online] Vol.69 (4), pp.133–152. Available: https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1509/jmkg.2005.69.4.133?casa_token=8jABxGZ8WMwAAAAA%3AQuvXUoLj_ZGYGjCt1fKgXUY7PDt5AvpMrxUBwhZILOJw8bICBRs8ialxDo0tbMFT9BZJIFD2HWZdvg [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Bashir, S., Khwaja, M. G., Mahmood, A., Turi, J. A. and Latif, K. F. (2021) Refining e-shoppers’ Perceived risks: Development and Validation of New Measurement Scale. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.58, p.102285.
- Beck, N. and Rygl, D. (2015) Categorization of multiple channel retailing in Multi-, Cross-, and Omni-Channel Retailing for retailers and retailing. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.27, pp.170–178. Available:

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698915300199> [Accessed 14 Jun 2021].
- Beckinsale, M., Ram, M. and Theodorakopoulos, N. (2010) ICT Adoption and Ebusiness Development. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.29 (3), pp.193–219.
- Bell, E., Bryman, A. and Harley, B. (2019) Business Research Methods. 5th ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Bembom, M. and Schwens, C. (2018) The Role of Networks in Early Internationalizing firms: a Systematic Review and Future Research Agenda. European Management Journal. [Online] Vol.36 (6), pp.679–694. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0263237318300306?token=3EBF595E13E1D33166B4F4D55CCBDD73A85F38C3D7DAD1D54EA2A15F2CFF649D765D88E07E7F3F3315F93EFD8CEF5314> [Accessed 28 Nov 2020].
- Beynon-Davies, P. (2013) EBusiness as a Driver for Regional Development | Emerald Insight. Journal of Systems and Information Technology. [Online]. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/13287261011032634/full/html> [Accessed 13 Jun 2021].
- Bhaskar, R. and Hartwig, M. (2011) Reclaiming Reality : a Critical Introduction to Contemporary Philosophy. London: Routledge.
- Bhattacharyya, S. and Bose, I. (2020) S-commerce: Influence of Facebook likes on purchases and recommendations on a linked e-commerce site. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.138, p.113383. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016792362030138X> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Bianchi, C. and Mathews, S. (2016) Internet Marketing and Export Market Growth in Chile. Journal of Business Research. [Online] Vol.69 (2), pp.426–434. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296315002799?casa_token=DpPaXfX0iR4AAAAA:fplf4mhfkp7hCH__fOqDliLEC6UzrH9uZj87iBDI5mHqtvw98csAtzvMsuQO1PQBA7apouzX1mU [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- BIRA (2020) Big Benefits and Support for Independent Hardware Businesses | Bira [Online]. Bira. Available: <https://bira.co.uk/sectors/diy-hardware/> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].

- Boateng, R., Hinson, R., Heeks, R. and Mbarika, V. (2011) A Resource-Based Analysis of E-Commerce in Developing Countries [Online]. AIS Electronic Library (AISeL). Available: <https://aisel.aisnet.org/ecis2010/137/> [Accessed 5 Jun 2021].
- Bogdon, A. S. (1996) Homeowner Renovation and Repair: the Decision to Hire Someone Else to Do the Project. Journal of Housing Economics. Vol.5 (4), pp.323–350.
- Bourne, V. (2020) Dell Technologies Digital Transformation Index [Online]. www.delltechnologies.com. Available: <https://www.delltechnologies.com/en-us/perspectives/digital-transformation-index.htm#scroll=off&pdf-overlay=//www.delltechnologies.com/en-us/collaterals/unauth/briefs-handouts/solutions/dt-index-2020-executive-summary.pdf> [Accessed 6 Apr 2021].
- Bradley, J. (2012) If We Build It They Will Come? the Technology Acceptance Model. In: Wade, M. R., Dwivedi, Y. K., and Schneberger, S. L. (eds.). Information Systems Theory. New York: Springer Science+Business Media.
- Brand Outlet products for sale | eBay. (2021) [Online]. eBay. Available: https://www.ebay.co.uk/b/Brand-Outlet/bn_7040700407 [Accessed 7 May 2021].
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2006) Using Thematic Analysis in Psychology. Qualitative Research in Psychology. [Online] Vol.3 (2), pp.77–101. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1191/1478088706qp063oa>.
- Braun, V. and Clarke, V. (2019) Reflecting on Reflexive Thematic Analysis. Qualitative Research in Sport, Exercise and Health. Vol.11 (4), pp.589–597.
- BRC (2021) British Retail Consortium [Online]. Brc.org.uk. Available: <https://www.brc.org.uk/> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- Breidbach, C. F., Smith, P. and Callagher, L. J. (2013) Advancing Innovation in Professional Service Firms: Insights from the Service-Dominant Logic. Service Science. Vol.5 (3), pp.263–275.
- Breugelmans, E. and Campo, K. (2016) Cross-Channel Effects of Price Promotions: an Empirical Analysis of the Multi-Channel Grocery Retail Sector. Journal of Retailing. Vol.92 (3), pp.333–351.
- Brooksbank, R., Kirby, D. and Kane, S. (1992) IT Adoption and the Independent Retail Business: the Retail Newsagency. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.10 (3), pp.53–61.

- Brouthers, K. D. and Brouthers, L. E. (2003) Why Service and Manufacturing Entry Mode Choices Differ: the Influence of Transaction Cost Factors, Risk and Trust*. Journal of Management Studies. Vol.40 (5), pp.1179–1204.
- Brouthers, K. D. and Hennart, J.-F. (2007) Boundaries of the Firm: Insights from International Entry Mode Research. Journal of Management. [Online] Vol.33 (3), pp.395–425. Available: [https://kclpure.kcl.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/boundaries-of-the-firm-insights-from-international-entry-mode-research\(d3bee491-c5f1-410e-97ce-39094d51347c\)/export.html](https://kclpure.kcl.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/boundaries-of-the-firm-insights-from-international-entry-mode-research(d3bee491-c5f1-410e-97ce-39094d51347c)/export.html).
- Brouthers, K. D. and Nakos, G. (2004) SME Entry Mode Choice and Performance: a Transaction Cost Perspective. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice. Vol.28 (3), pp.229–247.
- Brouthers, K. D., Geisser, K. D. and Rothlauf, F. (2015) Explaining the Internationalization of Ibusiness Firms. Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.47 (5), pp.513–534. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/jibs.2015.20> [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Brummer, A. (2021) Kingfisher Boss on How DIY Bloomed during Lockdown [Online]. This Is Money. Available: <https://www.thisismoney.co.uk/money/markets/article-9526557/How-DIY-bloomed-lockdown.html> [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Bukht, R. and Heeks, R. (2018) Defining, Conceptualising and Measuring the Digital Economy. International Organisations Research Journal. Vol.13 (2), pp.143–172.
- Burnett, G. and Lingam, G. I. (2012) Postgraduate Research in Pacific education: Interpretivism and Other Trends. PROSPECTS. Vol.42 (2), pp.221–233.
- Burns, P. (2016) Entrepreneurship and Small Business : start-up, Growth and Maturity. 4th ed. Basingstoke (Gb): Palgrave Macmillan Education, Cop.
- Burrell, G. and Morgan, G. (2016) Sociological Paradigms and Organisational Analysis : Elements of the Sociology of Corporate Life. London: Routledge.
- Bush, A., Menon, A. and Smart, D. (1987) Media Habits of the do-it-yourselfers. Journal of Advertising Research, 27(5). Vol.27 (5), pp.14–20.
- Callarman, S. (2021) Ecommerce Return Policies: Examples, Stats, Template [Infographic] [Online]. ShipBob. Available: <https://www.shipbob.com/blog/ecommerce-returns/> [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Cambridge Dictionary (2021) DIY [Online]. @CambridgeWords. Available: <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/diy> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].

- Cameron, S. and Price, D. (2009) Business Research Methods : a Practical Approach. London: Chartered Institute of Personnel and Development.
- Canabal, A. and White, G. O. (2008) Entry Mode research: past and Future. International Business Review. Vol.17 (3), pp.267–284.
- Cardona, M. and Martens, B. (2014) Supply-Side Barriers to Cross-Border E-Commerce in the EU Digital Single Market. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Casey, J. E., Pennington, L. K. and Mireles, S. V. (2020) Technology Acceptance Model: Assessing Preservice Teachers' Acceptance of Floor-Robots as a Useful Pedagogical Tool. Technology, Knowledge and Learning.
- Cavusgil, S. T. and Knight, G. (2015) The Born Global firm: an Entrepreneurial and Capabilities Perspective on Early and Rapid Internationalization. Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.46 (1), pp.3–16. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/jibs.2014.62> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Chaffey, D. (2015) Digital Business and e-commerce Management : Strategy, Implementation and Practice. 6th ed. Harlow: Pearson.
- Chaffey, D. (2021) E-commerce Conversion Rates 2021 Compilation - How Do Yours compare? [Online]. Smart Insights. Available: <https://www.smartinsights.com/ecommerce/ecommerce-analytics/ecommerce-conversion-rates/> [Accessed 2 Jun 2021].
- Chan, J. H. and Reiner, D. (2019) “Dominance by birthright”? Reconfiguration of Firm Boundaries to Acquire New Resources and Capabilities. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.119 (9), pp.1888–1907.
- Chandra, Y., Styles, C. and Wilkinson, I. (2009) The Recognition of First Time International Entrepreneurial Opportunities. International Marketing Review. Vol.26 (1), pp.30–61.
- Chandra, Y., Styles, C. and Wilkinson, I. F. (2012) An Opportunity-Based View of Rapid Internationalization. Journal of International Marketing. [Online] Vol.20 (1), pp.74–102. Available: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1509/jim.10.0147> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Chau, N. T., Deng, H. and Tay, R. (2021) A Perception-Based Model for Mobile Commerce Adoption in Vietnamese Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. Journal of Global Information Management. Vol.29 (1), pp.44–67.

- Chau, P. Y. K. and Tam, K. Y. (1997) Factors Affecting the Adoption of Open Systems: an Exploratory Study. MIS Quarterly. Vol.21 (1), p.1.
- Chava, S., Oettl, A., Singh, M. and Zeng, L. (2018) The Dark Side of Technological Progress? Impact of E-Commerce on Employees at Brick-and-Mortar Retailers. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Chen, A., Lu, Y. and Wang, B. (2017) Customers' Purchase decision-making Process in Social commerce: a Social Learning Perspective. International Journal of Information Management. [Online] Vol.37 (6), pp.627–638. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0268401216306107> [Accessed 19 Sep 2019].
- Chen, Y., Cheung, C. M. K. and Tan, C.-W. (2018) Omnichannel business research: Opportunities and challenges. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.109, pp.1–4. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923618300551> [Accessed 14 Jun 2021].
- Chetty, S., Ojala, A. and Leppäaho, T. (2015) Effectuation and Foreign Market Entry of Entrepreneurial Firms. European Journal of Marketing. Vol.49 (9/10), pp.1436–1459.
- Cheung, C. M. K. and Thadani, D. R. (2012) The Impact of Electronic word-of-mouth communication: a Literature Analysis and Integrative Model. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.54 (1), pp.461–470. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923612001911?casa_token=RfF5duuVvw0AAAAA:bQ5VEIkqeejDq5r--04dQc4ZDu3hUo7Cds9CCuVrf9p1MWU1lAtt88bDBxg6WhiW3p4tEbesMA [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Cho, H. and Tansuhaj, P. S. (2013) Becoming a Global SME: Determinants of SMEs' Decision to Use E-Intermediaries in Export Marketing. Thunderbird International Business Review. Vol.55 (5), pp.513–530.
- Choudhury, V. (2015) How Artificial Intelligence Is Changing the Face of eCommerce Industry [Online]. iamwire. Available: <http://www.iamwire.com/2015/09/artificial-intelligence-ecommerce-deep-learning-machine-learning/123423> [Accessed 6 Mar 2021].

- Clement, J. (2020a) Global Retail e-commerce Sales Growth [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/288487/forecast-of-global-b2c-e-commerce-growth/>.
- Clement, J. (2020b) Leading Online Shopping Categories Worldwide 2018 | Statista [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/276846/reach-of-top-online-retail-categories-worldwide/> [Accessed 17 Feb 2021].
- Coca-Stefaniak, A., Hallsworth, A. G., Parker, C., Bainbridge, S. and Yuste, R. (2005) Decline in the British Small Shop Independent Retail sector: Exploring European Parallels. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.12 (5), pp.357–371. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698904000943> [Accessed 10 May 2021].
- Collins, C. J. (2020) Expanding the Resource Based View Model of Strategic Human Resource Management. The International Journal of Human Resource Management. [Online] Vol.32 (2), pp.1–28. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/09585192.2019.1711442>.
- Collins, P. D., Hage, J. and Hull, F. M. (1988) Organizational and Technological Predictors of Change in Automaticity. Academy of Management Journal. Vol.31 (3), pp.512–543.
- Colton, D. A., Roth, M. S. and Bearden, W. O. (2010) Drivers of International E-Tail Performance: the Complexities of Orientations and Resources. Journal of International Marketing. Vol.18 (1), pp.1–22.
- Companies House (2017) Company Accounts Guidance [Online]. GOV.UK. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/life-of-a-company-annual-requirements/life-of-a-company-part-1-accounts#medium-sized-company-accounts> [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- Congressional Research Service (2021) Global Economic Effects of COVID-19 [Online]. Available: <https://fas.org/sgp/crs/row/R46270.pdf>.
- Cook, M., Duan, S. and Krivokapic-Skoko, B. (2021) SMEs Internationalization through Electronic Commerce. Rural Entrepreneurship and Innovation in the Digital Era. [Online] pp.80–102. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/smes-internationalization-through-electronic-commerce/266072> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Cooper, D. R. and Schindler, P. S. (2014) Business Research Methods. New York, Ny: Mcgraw-Hill/Irwin.

- Cooper, Z. (2021) Why Digital Transformation Is Essential for Business Growth [Online]. IT PRO. Available: <https://www.itpro.co.uk/strategy/29899/three-reasons-why-digital-transformation-is-essential-for-business-growth> [Accessed 1 Apr 2021].
- Corbin, J. M. and Strauss, A. L. (2008) Basics of Qualitative Research : Techniques and Procedures for Developing Grounded Theory. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Cordelia, A. (2006) Transaction Costs and Information Systems: Does IT Add Up? Journal of Information Technology. Vol.21 (3), pp.195–202.
- Cortés, P. and de la Rosa, F. E. (2013) BUILDING a GLOBAL REDRESS SYSTEM FOR LOW-VALUE CROSS-BORDER DISPUTES. International and Comparative Law Quarterly. Vol.62 (2), pp.407–440.
- Crittenden, V. L., Crittenden, W. F., Ferrell, L. K., Ferrell, O. C. and Pinney, C. C. (2010) Market-oriented sustainability: a Conceptual Framework and Propositions. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. [Online] Vol.39 (1), pp.71–85. Available: <https://danielsethics.mgt.unm.edu/pdf/Market-oriented%20sustainability.pdf> [Accessed 20 Jan 2020].
- Crotty, M. (1998) The Foundations of Social research: Meaning and Perspective in the Research Process. London Sage.
- Cuellar-Fernández, B., Fuertes-Callén, Y. and Serrano-Cinca, C. (2021) Survival of e-commerce entrepreneurs: The importance of brick-and-click and internationalization strategies. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. [Online] Vol.46, p.101035. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1567422321000077> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Cullen, J. B. and Parboteeah, P. (2010) International Business : Strategy and the Multinational Company. New York: Routledge.
- Dabija, D.-C. and Bejan, B. M. (2018) Green DIY Store Choice among Socially Responsible Consumer Generations. International Journal of Corporate Social Responsibility. [Online] Vol.3 (1). Available: <https://jcsr.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40991-018-0037-0> [Accessed 1 Mar 2021].
- Dalgleish, R. (2021) Retail sales, Great Britain [Online]. Ons.gov.uk. Available: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/retailindustry/bulletins/retailsales/february2021> [Accessed 20 Apr 2021].

- Daniel, E., Wilson, H. and Myers, A. (2002) Adoption of E-Commerce by SMEs in the UK. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.20 (3), pp.253–270.
- Das Nair, R. (2017) The Internationalisation of Supermarkets and the Nature of Competitive Rivalry in Retailing in Southern Africa. Development Southern Africa. Vol.35 (3), pp.315–333.
- Dasgupta, S., Granger, M. and McGarry, N. (2002) User Acceptance of E-Collaboration Technology: an Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model. Group Decision and Negotiation. [Online] Vol.11 (2), pp.87–100. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1023/A:1015221710638> [Accessed 5 Jun 2021].
- Datta, D. K., Hemmann, P. and Rasheed, A. A. (2002) Choice of foreign market entry modes: Critical review and future directions. Managing Transnational Firms: Resources, Market Entry and Strategic Alliances. [Online] pp.85–153. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0747792902140340> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Dave (2020) Huge Shift Emerging in Consumer Leisure Time Plans [Online]. eureka3. Available: <https://www.eurekaresearch.co.uk/post/2020/03/23/huge-shift-emerging-in-consumer-leisure-time-plans> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Davis, F. D. (1989) Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. MIS Quarterly. [Online] Vol.13 (3), pp.319–340. Available: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/249008?seq=1> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P. and Warshaw, P. R. (1989) User Acceptance of Computer Technology: a Comparison of Two Theoretical Models. Management Science. [Online] Vol.35 (8), pp.982–1003.
- Day One Team (2019) Amazon and Enterprise Nation kick off “Clicks and Mortar” with Manchester store for small business [Online]. UK Day One Blog. Available: <https://blog.aboutamazon.co.uk/supporting-small-businesses/amazon-and-enterprise-nation-kick-off-clicks-and-mortar-with-manchester-store-for-small-business> [Accessed 7 May 2021].
- Day, J. (2020) Simply Business UK [Online]. Simplybusiness.co.uk. Available: <https://www.simplybusiness.co.uk/knowledge/articles/2020/05/what-is-an-sme/> [Accessed 15 May 2021].

- De Cock, R., Andries, P. and Clarysse, B. (2020) How Founder Characteristics Imprint Ventures' Internationalization processes: the Role of International Experience and Cognitive Beliefs. Journal of World Business. p.101163.
- De Silva, T. (2011) Mixed methods: a Reflection of Its Adoption in Environmental Reporting. Qualitative Research in Accounting & Management. Vol.8 (1), pp.91–104.
- Deloitte (2021) Retail Trends 2021 | Deloitte UK [Online]. Deloitte United Kingdom. Available: <https://www2.deloitte.com/uk/en/pages/consumer-business/articles/retail-trends.html> [Accessed 13 Apr 2021].
- Deng, Z. and Wang, Z. (2016) Early-mover Advantages at cross-border business-to-business e-commerce Portals. Journal of Business Research. Vol.69 (12), pp.6002–6011.
- Dennis, C. (2000) Networking for Marketing Advantage. Management Decision. Vol.38 (4), pp.287–292.
- Denzin, N. K. and Lincoln, Y. S. (2018) The Sage Handbook of Qualitative Research. 5th ed. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Department for International Trade (2018) E-commerce for UK Small Businesses Selling Online to the USA [Online]. GOV.UK. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/e-commerce-for-uk-small-businesses-selling-online-to-the-usa/e-commerce-for-uk-small-businesses-selling-online-to-the-usa> [Accessed 30 Apr 2021].
- Department for International Trade (2020) Understanding and Measuring cross-border Digital Trade [Online]. GOV.UK. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/understanding-and-measuring-cross-border-digital-trade> [Accessed 30 Apr 2021].
- Dew, N., Read, S., Sarasvathy, S. D. and Wiltbank, R. (2009) Effectual versus Predictive Logics in Entrepreneurial decision-making: Differences between Experts and Novices. Journal of Business Venturing. [Online] Vol.24 (4), pp.287–309. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S088390260800027X> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Di Fatta, D., Patton, D. and Viglia, G. (2018) The determinants of conversion rates in SME e-commerce websites. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.41, pp.161–168. Available:

- <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698917306525> [Accessed 15 Jun 2021].
- Dickinson, H. (2021) BRC report: Footfall Goes from “bad to worse” in January | Bira [Online]. Bira. Available: <https://bira.co.uk/resource/brc-january-footfall/> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Dimitratos, P. and Jones, M. V. (2005) Future Directions for International Entrepreneurship Research. International Business Review. [Online] Vol.14 (2), pp.119–128. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0969593104000708> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Dishaw, M. T. and Strong, D. M. (2002) Extending the Technology Acceptance Model with Task–technology Fit Constructs. Information & Management. Vol.36 (1), pp.9–21.
- DIT (2021) Marketplace Details | eBay | Selling Online Overseas [Online]. Great.gov.uk. Available: <https://www.great.gov.uk/selling-online-overseas/markets/details/ebay/> [Accessed 4 May 2021].
- Doherty, A. M. (2000) Factors Influencing International Retailers’ Market Entry Mode Strategy: Qualitative Evidence from the UK Fashion Sector. Journal of Marketing Management. Vol.16 (1-3), pp.223–245.
- Doherty, N. F. and Ellis-Chadwick, F. (2010) Internet retailing: the past, the Present and the Future. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.38 (11/12), pp.943–965.
- Douglas, J. D. (1985) Creative Interviewing. Beverly Hills: Sage Publ.
- Drummond, C., McGrath, H. and O’Toole, T. (2018) The impact of social media on resource mobilisation in entrepreneurial firms. Industrial Marketing Management. [Online] Vol.70, pp.68–89. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019850117304157> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- DTI (2020) Dell Technologies Digital Transformation Index [Online]. Delltechnologies.com. Available: <https://www.delltechnologies.com/en-us/perspectives/digital-transformation-index.htm#scroll=off> [Accessed 6 Apr 2021].
- eBay (2021a) Advanced International Selling | UK Seller Centre [Online]. Ebay.co.uk. Available: <https://sellercentre.ebay.co.uk/global-sales/advanced-international-selling> [Accessed 26 Apr 2021].

- eBay (2021b) Selling | UK Seller Centre [Online]. Ebay.co.uk. Available: <https://sellercentre.ebay.co.uk/selling> [Accessed 7 May 2021].
- Economic Intelligence Unit (2021) Online retailing: How to Navigate the New Normal - the Economist Intelligence Unit [Online]. Eiu.com. Available: https://www.eiu.com/public/topical_report.aspx?campaignid=apr21onlineretailwp [Accessed 20 Apr 2021].
- Effendi, M. I., Sugandini, D. and Istanto, Y. (2020) Social Media Adoption in SMEs Impacted by COVID-19: the TOE Model. The Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business. Vol.7 (11), pp.915–925.
- Ekman, P., Hadjikhani, A. I., Pajuvirta, A. and Thilenius, P. (2014) Tit for Tat and Big steps: the Case of Swedish Banks' Internationalization 1961–2010. International Business Review. Vol.23 (6), pp.1049–1063.
- Elbanna, S., Child, J. and Dayan, M. (2013) A Model of Antecedents and Consequences of Intuition in Strategic Decision-making: Evidence from Egypt. Long Range Planning. Vol.46 (1-2), pp.149–176.
- European Commission (2016) SME Definition [Online]. European Commission. Available: https://ec.europa.eu/growth/smes/sme-definition_en [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- European Union (2021) Guarantees, Cancelling and Returning Your Purchases [Online]. Your Europe. Available: https://europa.eu/youreurope/citizens/consumers/shopping/guarantees-returns/index_en.htm [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Eurostat (2018) Final Report on Price and Volume Measures for Service Activities” Presented at the Meeting of Directors of Macroeconomic statistics, [Online]. Europa.eu. Available: https://circabc.europa.eu/d/a/workspace/SpacesStore/5e22faee-ad44-4e14-a919-%20e555615729c3/DMES_2018-06%20Item%2013%20-%20TF%20prices%20and%20volume%20final%20report.docx [Accessed 6 May 2021].
- Evert Gummesson (2001) Qualitative Methods in Management Research. Thousand Oaks, Calif. Sage Publ. [20]03.
- Feldman, S. (2019) Infographic: How Do Shoppers Bring Digital into Physical Stores? [Online]. Statista Infographics. Available: <https://www.statista.com/chart/18301/online-offline-consumer-behavior/> [Accessed 3 Jun 2021].

- Fillis, I. (2001) Small Firm internationalisation: an Investigative Survey and Future Research Directions. Management Decision. Vol.39 (9), pp.767–783.
- Fillis, I., Johansson, U. and Wagner, B. (2003) A Conceptualisation of the Opportunities and Barriers to E-business Development in the Smaller Firm. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.10 (3), pp.336–344.
- Fisher, B. (2021) UK Consumers Covet Sustainable Retail in 2021 [Online]. Insider Intelligence. Available: <https://www.emarketer.com/content/uk-consumers-covet-sustainable-retail-2021> [Accessed 2 Mar 2021].
- Fornari, E., Fornari, D., Grandi, S., Menegatti, M. and Hofacker, C. F. (2016) Adding Store to web: Migration and Synergy Effects in multi-channel Retailing. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.44 (6), pp.658–674.
- Forsgren, M. and Hagström, P. (2007) Ignorant and Impatient internationalization? Critical Perspectives on International Business. Vol.3 (4), pp.291–305.
- Forte, R. and Carvalho, J. (2013) Internationalisation through franchising: the Parfois Case Study. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.41 (5), pp.380–395.
- Fraccastoro, S., Gabrielsson, M. and Chetty, S. (2021) Social Media Firm Specific Advantages as Enablers of Network Embeddedness of International Entrepreneurial Ventures. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.56 (3), p.101164. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1090951620300924> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Franganillo, J. (2021) Bira Urges Government to Prioritise Independent Retail in Lockdown Exit Plan [Online]. www.retail-insight-network.com. Available: <https://www.retail-insight-network.com/news/bira-independent-lockdown-exit-plan/> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- Freeman, J., Styles, C. and Lawley, M. (2012) Does firm location make a difference to the export performance of SMEs? International Marketing Review. [Online] Vol.29 (1), pp.88–113. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/02651331211201552/full/pdf?title=does-firm-location-make-a-difference-to-the-export-performance-of-smes> [Accessed 4 Feb 2020].
- Galan Mashenene, R. and P. Kumburu, N. (2020) Performance of Small Businesses in Tanzania: Human Resources-Based View. Global Business Review. p.097215092092735.

- Galanakis, A. (2016) An Investigation into the Organizational Factors That Affect the Export Sales Effectiveness in Greek Exporting SMEs. Doctoral Dissertation. Heriot-Watt University.
- Gao, F., Agrawal, V. V. and Cui, S. (2021) The Effect of Multichannel and Omnichannel Retailing on Physical Stores. Management Science.
- Gavrila, S. G. and de Lucas Ancillo, A. (2021) Spanish SMEs' Digitalization enablers: E-Receipt Applications to the Offline Retail Market. Technological Forecasting and Social Change. [Online] Vol.162, p.120381. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162520312075> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- Gebhardt, G. F., Carpenter, G. S. and Sherry, J. F. (2006) Creating a Market Orientation: a Longitudinal, Multifirm, Grounded Analysis of Cultural Transformation. Journal of Marketing. Vol.70 (4), pp.37–55.
- Gensler, S., Dekimpe, M. G. and Skiera, B. (2007) Evaluating Channel Performance in multi-channel Environments. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.14 (1), pp.17–23.
- Gensler, S., Neslin, S. A. and Verhoef, P. C. (2017) The Showrooming Phenomenon: It's More than Just About Price. Journal of Interactive Marketing. [Online] Vol.38, pp.29–43. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1094996817300142> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Gessner, G. H. and Snodgrass, C. R. (2015) Designing e-commerce cross-border Distribution Networks for Small and medium-size Enterprises Incorporating Canadian and U.S. Trade Incentive Programs. Research in Transportation Business & Management. Vol.16, pp.84–94.
- GFK (2019) Whitepaper: The Pandemic Boost for E-Commerce in FMCG in Europe – Will it last? [Online]. Gfk.com. Available: <https://www.gfk.com/fmcg-e-commerce-whitepaper> [Accessed 20 Feb 2021].
- GFK (2020) Brits Console Themselves with DIY as They Settle in for Extended Stay at Home [Online]. Gfk.com. Available: <https://www.gfk.com/en-gb/press/brits-turn-to-diy-as-they-settle-in-for-extended-stay-at-home> [Accessed 20 Feb 2021].
- Ghauri, P. N., Kjell Grønhaug and Strange, R. (2020) Research Methods in Business Studies. New York: Cambridge University Press.

- Ghobakhloo, M. and Tang, S. H. (2011) Barriers to Electronic Commerce Adoption among Small Businesses in Iran. Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations. Vol.9 (4), pp.48–89.
- Gill, J., Johnson, P. and Clark, M. (2014) Research Methods for Managers. London ; Sage.
- Giorgini, M. (2020) 5 Digital Marketing Predictions for a post-pandemic Economic Recovery [Online]. Think with Google. Available: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-gb/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/post-pandemic-economic-recovery/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Glavas, C. and Mathews, S. (2014) How International Entrepreneurship Characteristics Influence Internet Capabilities for the International Business Processes of the Firm. International Business Review. [Online] Vol.23 (1), pp.228–245. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969593113000553?casa_token=6ritUAbIYoUAAAAA:1pwbgVV25w5r8rlvFwSR1fmVBOEffU3VV2HIDgM0u2hPQ2eWEfcc93TutE8SCvq1Jtfh4ENFSQ [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Global Reach (2020) The Death of Brick and Mortar Retail [Online]. Globalreach.com. Available: <https://www.globalreach.com/services/digital-marketing/digital-marketing-articles--resources/2020/06/17/the-death-of-brick-and-mortar-retail> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- GlobalData (2018) The UK DIY & Gardening Market 2018 - 2023 [Online]. GlobalData Report Store. Available: <https://store.globaldata.com/report/vr0154sr--the-uk-diy-gardening-market-2018-2023/> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Goldsby, T. J. and Eckert, J. A. (2003) Electronic Transportation marketplaces: a Transaction Cost Perspective. Industrial Marketing Management. Vol.32 (3), pp.187–198.
- Gomez-Herrera, E., Martens, B. and Turlea, G. (2014) The Drivers and Impediments for cross-border e-commerce in the EU. Information Economics and Policy. [Online] Vol.28, pp.83–96. Available: <https://0-www.sciencedirect-com.lispac.lsbu.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0167624514000171?via%3Dihub> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- Google Trends (2021) Google Trends [Online]. Google Trends. Available: <https://trends.google.co.uk/trends/explore?geo=GB&q=diy%20store%20near%20me,DIY%20store,hardware%20store%20near%20me> [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].

- Gorji, M., Grimmer, L., Grimmer, M. and Siami, S. (2021) Retail Store environment, Store Attachment and Customer Citizenship Behaviour. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print).
- GOV.UK (2021) Search Results | Selling Online Overseas [Online]. Great.gov.uk. Available: https://www.great.gov.uk/selling-online-overseas/markets/results/?category_id=632&country_id=307&commit= [Accessed 4 May 2021].
- Government Digital Service (2015) Prepare Annual Accounts for a Private Limited Company [Online]. GOV.UK. Available: <https://www.gov.uk/annual-accounts/microentities-small-and-dormant-companies> [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- Grandon, E. and Pearson, J. M. (2004) E-Commerce Adoption: Perceptions of Managers/Owners of Small and Medium Sized Firms in Chile. Communications of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.13.
- Grandón, E. E., Nasco, S. A. and Mykytyn, P. P. (2011) Comparing Theories to Explain e-commerce Adoption. Journal of Business Research. Vol.64 (3), pp.292–298.
- Graves, C. and Thomas, J. (2006) Internationalization of Australian Family Businesses: A Managerial Capabilities Perspective. Family Business Review. [Online] Vol.19 (3), pp.207–224. Available: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1111/j.1741-6248.2006.00066.x> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Gregory, G., Karavdic, M. and Zou, S. (2007) The Effects of E-Commerce Drivers on Export Marketing Strategy. Journal of International Marketing. [Online] Vol.15 (2), pp.30–57. Available: https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1509/jimk.15.2.30?casa_token=oGKCRbrqqtUAAAAA%3Ahvt9uqGpz8Gf1I0y5kvOaVB46HTpqdLuhchGfcgEsFmPf8GKdKHU3w_Zix0Nx5wzfwSK_f5fCcUkUg [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Griffin, R. W. and Pustay, M. W. (2020) International Business a Managerial Perspective. Boston Pearson Education.
- Guercini, S. and Runfola, A. (2015) Internationalization through e-commerce. the case of multibrand luxury retailers in the fashion industry [Online]. ResearchGate. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/283646096_Internationalization_through_e-commerce_the_case_of_multibrand_luxury_retailers_in_the_fashion_industry [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].

- Guo, X., Deng, H., Zhang, S. and Chen, G. (2020) Signals of Competence and Warmth on E-Commerce Platforms. Data and Information Management. Vol.4 (2), pp.81–93.
- Gupta, D. (2020) Digital Platforms and E-Commerce in India – Challenges and Opportunities. SSRN Electronic Journal. [Online]. Available: https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3577285 [Accessed 4 Mar 2021].
- Gupta, R. K. (2015) Qualitative Research in Management : Methods and Experiences. Los Angeles, Calif.: Sage.
- Hagberg, J., Sundstrom, M. and Egels-Zandén, N. (2016) The Digitalization of retailing: an Exploratory Framework. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.44 (7), pp.694–712.
- Hajli, N., Sims, J. and Shanmugam, M. (2014) A Practical Model for e-commerce Adoption in Iran. Journal of Enterprise Information Management. Vol.27 (6), pp.719–730.
- Han, H., Xu, H. and Chen, H. (2018) Social commerce: a Systematic Review and Data Synthesis. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. Vol.30, pp.38–50.
- Hånell, S. M., Nordman, E. R., Tolstoy, D. and ÖzbekN. (2020) “It’s a New Game out there”: e-commerce in Internationalising Retail SMEs | Emerald Insight. International Marketing Review. [Online] Vol.37 (3), pp.515–531. Available: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/IMR-03-2018-0107/full/html> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- Hänninen, M., Kwan, S. K. and Mitronen, L. (2020) From the Store to Omnichannel retail: Looking Back over Three Decades of Research. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research. [Online] pp.1–38. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09593969.2020.1833961>.
- Hargrave, S. (2019) How Can SMEs Succeed in exporting? [Online]. The Telegraph. Available: <https://www.telegraph.co.uk/business/challenges/sme-export-support/> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Hart, C., Stachow, G. and Cadogan, J. W. (2013) Conceptualising Town Centre Image and the Customer Experience. Journal of Marketing Management. Vol.29 (15-16), pp.1753–1781.
- Haryanti, T. and Subriadi, A. P. (2020) Factors and Theories E-Commerce Adoption: a Literature Review. International Journal of Electronic Commerce Studies. [Online]

Vol.11 (2), pp.87–105. Available:
[http://web.b.ebscohost.com/ehost/detail/detail?vid=12&sid=acd9f773-6e76-4ebd-8bbe-9f8c0f41d389%40pdc-v-
sessmgr03&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWZWhvc3QtG2ZQ%3d%3d#AN=146351849&db=bth](http://web.b.ebscohost.com/ehost/detail/detail?vid=12&sid=acd9f773-6e76-4ebd-8bbe-9f8c0f41d389%40pdc-v-
sessmgr03&bdata=JnNpdGU9ZWZWhvc3QtG2ZQ%3d%3d#AN=146351849&db=bth)
[Accessed 23 Oct 2020].

Herhausen, D., Binder, J., Schoegel, M. and Herrmann, A. (2015) Integrating Bricks with Clicks: Retailer-Level and Channel-Level Outcomes of Online–Offline Channel Integration. Journal of Retailing. Vol.91 (2), pp.309–325.

Hill, R. J., Fishbein, M. and Ajzen, I. (1977) Belief, Attitude, Intention and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research. Contemporary Sociology. Vol.6 (2), p.244.

Hoehle, H., Scornavacca, E. and Huff, S. (2012) Three Decades of Research on Consumer Adoption and Utilization of Electronic Banking channels: a Literature Analysis. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.54 (1), pp.122–132. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923612001066?casa_token=eDlz7XI--3gAAAAA:i8kNZIO9A6GeYsP9QXPPeSYFi94fmtEGQGLY7edRzvL7ox4-pAq5MLT7Y3vxB8FhnEL38htJoA [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].

Hoffmann, W. H., Neumann, K. and Speckbacher, G. (2010) The Effect of Interorganizational Trust on make-or-cooperate decisions: Disentangling opportunism-dependent and opportunism-independent Effects of Trust. European Management Review. Vol.7 (2), pp.101–115.

Holt, R. (2009) Effectuation: Elements of Entrepreneurial Experience 20091 Saras Sarasvathy. Effectuation: Elements of Entrepreneurial Experience. 2008. 368 pp., ISBN: 978-1-84376-680-3 £80, Hardback Edward Elgar Cheltenham. International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior & Research. Vol.15 (2), pp.232–236.

Holtgrave, M. (2017) Success through Trust, Control, and Learning? Contrasting the Drivers of SME Performance between Different Modes of Foreign Market Entry. Administrative Sciences. Vol.7 (2), p.9.

Hooker, L. (2021) PwC Comments on February 2021 ONS Retail Sales Figures [Online]. PwC. Available: <https://www.pwc.co.uk/press-room/press-releases/pwc-comments-on-february-2021-ons-retail-sales-figures.html> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].

Hong, S.-M. and Wu, C.-L. (2019) How Behaviors on Social Network Sites and Online Social Capital Influence Social Commerce Intentions. Information & Management. p.103176.

- Hossain, Md. I., Azam, M. S. and Quaddus, M. (2021) Small Firm Entry to e-marketplace for Market Expansion and internationalization: a Theoretical Perspective. Journal of International Entrepreneurship. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10843-021-00297-5> [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- Howel, T. (2020) 5 Digital Marketing Predictions for a post-pandemic Economic Recovery [Online]. Think with Google. Available: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-gb/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/post-pandemic-economic-recovery/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Hsu, P.-F., Kraemer, K. L. and Dunkle, D. (2006) Determinants of E-Business Use in U.S. Firms. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.10 (4), pp.9–45.
- Hsu, P.-F., Ray, S. and Li-Hsieh, Y.-Y. (2014) Examining Cloud Computing Adoption intention, Pricing mechanism, and Deployment Model. International Journal of Information Management. Vol.34 (4), pp.474–488.
- Hu, Y. and Liu, X. W. (2013) Information Technology in E-Commerce Capabilities and Firm Performance: Based on Resource-Based View. Advanced Materials Research. Vol.859, pp.527–530.
- Huang, S.-L. and Chang, Y.-C. (2019) Cross-border e-commerce: Consumers' Intention to Shop on Foreign Websites. Internet Research.
- Hui, L. S. and Chow, G. (2011) Vertical Greenery for Interior Spaces Made Easy: DIY Vertical Greenery at Home. CITYGREEN. Vol.01 (02), p.96.
- Hussey, L. K. (2010) . Library & Information Science Research. [Online] Vol.32 (1), pp.92–93. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0740818809001340?token=965014EFEF6E9AC0EE2FED3FEE6CD32CF5194612DE5BB276F8C398EACB008CCFE1BDBC277ABC9E250B73CC2B8D2DE0AC> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Hutchinson, K. and Quinn, B. (2012) Identifying the Characteristics of Small Specialist International Retailers. European Business Review. Vol.24 (2), pp.106–119.
- Hutchinson, K., Fleck, E. and Lloyd-Reason, L. (2009) An Investigation into the Initial Barriers to Internationalization. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.16 (4), pp.544–568.

- Hutchinson, K., Quinn, B. and Alexander, N. (2005) The Internationalisation of Small to Medium-Sized Retail Companies: Towards a Conceptual Framework. Journal of Marketing Management. Vol.21 (1-2), pp.149–179.
- Hutchinson, K., Quinn, B. and Alexander, N. (2006) SME Retailer internationalisation: Case Study Evidence from British Retailers. International Marketing Review. Vol.23 (1), pp.25–53.
- Hutchinson, K., Quinn, B., Alexander, N. and Doherty, A. M. (2009) Retailer internationalization: Overcoming Barriers to Expansion. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research. Vol.19 (3), pp.251–272.
- Hyun, H., Thavisay, T. and Lee, S. H. (2021) Enhancing the role of flow experience in social media usage and its impact on shopping. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] p.102492. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698921000588> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- ICO (2021a) SME Web Hub – Advice for All Small Organisations [Online]. Ico.org.uk. Available: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/sme-web-hub/> [Accessed 19 May 2021].
- ICO (2021b) Guide to the UK General Data Protection Regulation (UK GDPR) [Online]. Ico.org.uk. Available: <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/> [Accessed 19 May 2021].
- Ilin, V., Ivetić, J. and Simić, D. (2017) Understanding the Determinants of e-business Adoption in ERP-enabled Firms and non-ERP-enabled firms: a Case Study of the Western Balkan Peninsula. Technological Forecasting and Social Change. [Online] Vol.125, pp.206–223. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S004016251630662X> [Accessed 5 Jun 2021].
- Indie Retail. (2020) [Online]. Indie Retail. Available: <https://www.indieretail.uk/trade/appssg/> [Accessed 19 Mar 2021].
- Industria Conectada 4.0 - Página Principal. (2019) [Online]. Industriaconectada40.gob.es. Available: <https://www.industriaconectada40.gob.es/Paginas/index.aspx> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].

- Insights Hub. (2021) [Online]. Brc.org.uk. Available: <https://brc.org.uk/retail-insight/insighthub/?topic=Industry%20Briefings#9> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- IR (2021) Online Sales to Double Share of Total Retail to Account for a Fifth by 2025: Study [Online]. InternetRetailing. Available: <https://internetretailing.net/rxgeu/online-sales-to-double-share-of-total-retail-to-account-for-a-fifth-by-2025-study> [Accessed 20 Apr 2021].
- IRG (2021) DIY Latest Retail News & Market Data for the Home Improvement Retailers Sector | Do It Yourself [Online]. Insightdiy.co.uk. Available: <https://www.insightdiy.co.uk/> [Accessed 11 May 2021].
- Jean, R.-J. "Bryan", Kim, D. and Cavusgil, E. (2020) Antecedents and Outcomes of Digital Platform Risk for International New Ventures' Internationalization. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.55 (1), p.101021. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1090951618308502> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Johanson, M. and Kalinic, I. (2016) Acceleration and Deceleration in the Internationalization Process of the Firm. Management International Review. [Online] Vol.56 (6), pp.827–847. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11575-016-0304-9> [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Johnson, J. and Tellis, G. J. (2008) Drivers of Success for Market Entry into China and India. Journal of Marketing. [Online] Vol.72 (3), pp.1–13. Available: <http://www-bcf.usc.edu/~tellis/ChinaIndia.pdf>.
- Jones, B. (2021) Retail Volumes Continue to Fall but Record Online Sales Growth Provides Relief for Some Retailers | CBI [Online]. CBI. Available: <https://www.cbi.org.uk/media-centre/articles/retail-volumes-continue-to-fall-but-record-online-sales-growth-provides-relief-for-some-retailers/> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Jones, M. V., Coviello, N. and Tang, Y. K. (2011) International Entrepreneurship research (1989–2009): A domain ontology and thematic analysis. Journal of Business Venturing. [Online] Vol.26 (6), pp.632–659. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0883902611000395?via%3Dihub> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- Joubert, R.-L. and Jokonya, O. (2021) A Systematic Literature Review of Factors Affecting the Adoption of Technologies in Food Waste Management. Procedia Computer Science.

- [Online] Vol.181, pp.1034–1040. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050921003471> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Kabadayi, S. (2011) Choosing the Right Multiple Channel System to Minimize Transaction Costs. Industrial Marketing Management. Vol.40 (5), pp.763–773.
- Kacen, J. J., Hess, J. D. and Kevin Chiang, W.-Y. (2013) Bricks or Clicks? Consumer Attitudes toward Traditional Stores and Online Stores. Global Economics and Management Review. [Online] Vol.18 (1), pp.12–21. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S2340154013700033> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Kahiya, E. T. (2018) Five Decades of Research on Export barriers: Review and Future Directions. International Business Review. Vol.27 (6), pp.1172–1188.
- Kahiya, E. T. (2019) Context in International business: Entrepreneurial Internationalization from a Distant Small Open Economy. International Business Review. p.101621.
- Kartiwi, M. and MacGregor, R. C. (2007) Electronic Commerce Adoption Barriers in Small to Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Developed and Developing Countries. Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations. Vol.5 (3), pp.35–51.
- Kaynak, E., Tatoglu, E. and Kula, V. (2005) An Analysis of the Factors Affecting the Adoption of Electronic Commerce by SMEs. International Marketing Review. Vol.22 (6), pp.623–640.
- Kelemen, M. and Rumens, N. (2008) An Introduction to Critical Management Research. Los Angeles, Ca: Sage.
- Kervin, J. B. (1999) Methods for Business Research. 2nd ed. New York: Harper Collins.
- Kickert, C. (2019) What’s in store: Prospects and Challenges for American street-level Commerce. Journal of Urban Design. Vol.26 (2), pp.1–19.
- Kim, D., Jean, R.-J. B. and Sinkovics, R. R. (2018) Drivers of Virtual Interfirm Integration and Its Impact on Performance in International Customer–Supplier Relationships. Management International Review. Vol.58 (3), pp.495–522.
- Kim, N. and Pae, J. H. (2007) Utilization of New technologies: Organizational Adaptation to Business Environments. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. Vol.35 (2), pp.259–269.

- Kim, T. Y., Dekker, R. and Heij, C. (2017) Cross-Border Electronic Commerce: Distance Effects and Express Delivery in European Union Markets. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.21 (2), pp.184–218.
- Kimiagari, S. and Baei, F. (2021) Promoting e-banking Actual usage: Mix of Technology Acceptance Model and technology-organisation-environment Framework. Enterprise Information Systems. pp.1–57.
- Knight, G. A. and Cavusgil, S. T. (2004) Innovation, Organizational capabilities, and the born-global Firm. Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.35 (2), pp.124–141.
- Knight, G. A. and Kim, D. (2009) International Business Competence and the Contemporary Firm. Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.40 (2), pp.255–273.
- Knight, G. A. and Liesch, P. W. (2016) Internationalization: From incremental to born global. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.51 (1), pp.93–102. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1090951615000644> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Kodali, S. (2020) The Art and Science of Retail eCommerce [Online]. Forrester.com. Available: <https://www.forrester.com/report/The+Art+And+Science+Of+Retail+eCommer>
- Kotabe, M., Srinivasan, S. S. and Aulakh, P. S. (2002) Multinationality and Firm Performance: The Moderating Role of R&D and Marketing Capabilities. Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.33 (1), pp.79–97. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/palgrave.jibs.8491006> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- KSA (2021) KSA Group [Online]. KSA Group. Available: <https://www.ksagroup.co.uk/> [Accessed 8 Apr 2021].
- Kuan, K. K. Y. and Chau, P. Y. K. (2001) A perception-based Model for EDI Adoption in Small Businesses Using a Technology–organization–environment Framework. Information & Management. [Online] Vol.38 (8), pp.507–521. Available: <https://0-www-sciencedirect-com.lispac.lsbu.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0378720601000738?via%3Dihub> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Kumar, S., Tiffany, M. and Vaidya, S. (2014) Supply Chain Analysis of e-tailing versus Retailing Operation – a Case Study. Enterprise Information Systems. [Online] Vol.10 (6), pp.639–665. Available:

- <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2016EntIS..10..639K/abstract> [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- Kunday, Ö. and Şengüler, E. P. (2015) A Study on Factors Affecting the Internationalization Process of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.195, pp.972–981.
- Kurnia, S., Choudrie, J., Mahbubur, R. M. and Alzougool, B. (2015) E-commerce Technology adoption: a Malaysian Grocery SME Retail Sector Study. Journal of Business Research. [Online] Vol.68 (9), pp.1906–1918. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296314004251?casa_token=yIm1ocne8G8AAAAA:Md_m3dyT7W8CkR3d8Ga1xdICwZYw5Y0U5dWA_SO5QyRm5-UJM38-h-J16plksbr9VJPSmxuRDA [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Kvale, S. and Corbin, J. (2009) Basics of Qualitative Research 3rd Ed + Interviews 2nd Ed. Sage Pubns.
- Ladhari, R. (2010) Developing e-service quality scales: A literature review. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.17 (6), pp.464–477. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698910000615> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Lai, P. (2017) The Literature Review of Technology Adoption Models and Theories for the Novelty Technology. Journal of Information Systems and Technology Management. Vol.14 (1).
- Lambert, J., Tran, A. and Reiners, J. (2016) Digital Spillover [Online]. Oxford Economics. Available: <https://www.oxfordeconomics.com/recent-releases/digital-spillover> [Accessed 6 May 2021].
- Lazar, M.-J. (2018) Ecommerce Returns Statistics for 2018 [Online]. ReadyCloud. Available: <https://www.readycloud.com/info/ecommerce-returns-statistics-for-2018> [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Lăzăroiu, G., Neguriță, O., Grecu, I., Grecu, G. and Mitran, P. C. (2020) Consumers' Decision-Making Process on Social Commerce Platforms: Online Trust, Perceived Risk, and Purchase Intentions. Frontiers in Psychology. Vol.11.
- Leaver, D. and Al-Zubaidi, H. (1996) Challenging Conventional wisdom: a Reappraisal of the UK DIY Market. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.24 (11), pp.39–45.

- Lee, B.-M. (2020) Requirements for the Incorporation of Standard Terms in Cross Border e-Commerce under the CISG. THE INTERNATIONAL COMMERCE & LAW REVIEW. Vol.86, pp.1–23.
- Lee, C.-P. and Shim, J. P. (2007) An Exploratory Study of Radio Frequency Identification (RFID) Adoption in the Healthcare Industry. European Journal of Information Systems. Vol.16 (6), pp.712–724.
- Leitch, C. M., Hill, F. M. and Harrison, R. T. (2009) The Philosophy and Practice of Interpretivist Research in Entrepreneurship. Organizational Research Methods. [Online] Vol.13 (1), pp.67–84. Available: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1094428109339839?journalCode=orma>.
- Lendle, A. and Vézina, P.-L. (2015) Internet Technology and the Extensive Margin of Trade: Evidence from eBay in Emerging Economies. Review of Development Economics. [Online] Vol.19 (2), pp.375–386. Available: https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/epdf/10.1111/rode.12148?saml_referrer [Accessed 26 Dec 2020].
- Lendle, A., Olarreaga, M., Schropp, S. and Vézina, P.-L. (2012) There Goes Gravity: How eBay Reduces Trade Costs. Policy Research Working Papers. The World Bank.
- Leonidou, L. C., Katsikeas, C. S. and Coudounaris, D. N. (2010) Five Decades of Business Research into exporting: a Bibliographic Analysis. Journal of International Management. Vol.16 (1), pp.78–91.
- Lertwongsatien, C. and Wongpinunwatana, N. (2003) E-Commerce Adoption in Thailand: an Empirical Study of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Journal of Global Information Technology Management. Vol.6 (3), pp.67–83.
- Journal of Global Information Technology Management. Vol.6 (3), pp.67–83.
- Lewis, J., Whysall, P. and Foster, C. (2014) Drivers and Technology-Related Obstacles in Moving to Multichannel Retailing. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. [Online] Vol.18 (4), pp.43–68. Available: <https://core.ac.uk/display/30648657> [Accessed 11 Jan 2020].
- Li, X., Troutt, M., Brandyberry, A. and Wang, T. (2011) Decision Factors for the Adoption and Continued Use of Online Direct Sales Channels among SMEs. Journal of the Association for Information Systems. Vol.12 (1), pp.1–31.

- Liang, T.-P. and Turban, E. (2011) Introduction to the Special Issue Social Commerce: a Research Framework for Social Commerce. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.16 (2), pp.5–14.
- Lindstrand, A. and Hånell, S. M. (2017) International and market-specific Social Capital Effects on International Opportunity Exploitation in the Internationalization Process. Journal of World Business. Vol.52 (5), pp.653–663.
- Liu, X. and Wang, M. (2015) A Dynamic CPU Resources Scheduling Method for Xen Virtual Machine. 2015 4th International Conference on Next Generation Computer and Information Technology (NGCIT). [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/7527725> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Liu, X., Zhou, Y.-W., Shen, Y., Ge, C. and Jiang, J. (2021) Zooming in the Impacts of Merchants' Participation in Transformation from Online Flash Sale to Mixed Sale e-commerce Platform. Information & Management. [Online] Vol.58 (2), p.103409. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378720620303475> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Lo, F.-Y., Rey-Martí, A. and Botella-Carrubi, D. (2020) Research Methods in business: Quantitative and Qualitative Comparative Analysis. Journal of Business Research. [Online] Vol.115, pp.221–224. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0148296320302964?token=5F83402009FE91D6EE39AE163319F085A0A33F96D0D282959941E04DC45B8E7C40463E51872F4C28F209B1598013EBF8> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Lucas, T., Alexander, S., Firestone, I. J. and Baltes, B. B. (2007) Self-efficacy and Independence from Social influence: Discovery of an Efficacy–difficulty Effect. Social Influence. Vol.1 (1), pp.58–80.
- Luo, Y., Hongxin Zhao, J. and Du, J. (2005b) The Internationalization Speed of E-commerce companies: an Empirical Analysis. International Marketing Review. Vol.22 (6), pp.693–709.
- Lusch, R. F., Vargo, S. L. and O'Brien, M. (2007) Competing through service: Insights from service-dominant Logic. Journal of Retailing. Vol.83 (1), pp.5–18.
- Macchion, L., Moretto, A. M., Caniato, F., Caridi, M., Danese, P. and Vinelli, A. (2017a) International e-commerce for Fashion products: What Is the Relationship with

- performance? International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.45 (9), pp.1011–1031.
- Macer, T. (2017) DIY Research. Research World. Vol.2017 (66), pp.38–41.
- MacGregor, R. C. and Vrazalic, L. (2005) A Basic Model of Electronic Commerce Adoption Barriers. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.12 (4), pp.510–527.
- Mackay, M. and Perkins, H. C. (2016) The Globalising World of DIY House improvement: Interpreting a Cultural and Commercial Phenomenon. Housing Studies. Vol.32 (6), pp.758–777.
- Maduku, D. K., Mpinganjira, M. and Duh, H. (2016) Understanding Mobile Marketing Adoption Intention by South African SMEs: a multi-perspective Framework. International Journal of Information Management. [Online] Vol.36 (5), pp.711–723. Available: <https://0-www-sciencedirect-com.lispac.lsbu.ac.uk/science/article/pii/S0268401216300615> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Maekelburger, B., Schwens, C. and Kabst, R. (2012) Asset Specificity and Foreign Market Entry Mode Choice of Small and medium-sized enterprises: the Moderating Influence of Knowledge Safeguards and Institutional Safeguards. Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.43 (5), pp.458–476.
- Mainela, T. and Puhakka, V. (2008) Organising New Business in a Turbulent context: Opportunity Discovery and Effectuation for IJV Development in Transition Markets. Journal of International Entrepreneurship. Vol.7 (2), pp.111–134.
- Mainela, T., Puhakka, V. and Sipola, S. (2018) International entrepreneurship beyond individuals and firms: On the systemic nature of international opportunities. Journal of Business Venturing. [Online] Vol.33 (4), pp.534–550. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0883902617304664> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Malhotra, N. K. (2020) Marketing Research : an Applied Orientation. Harlow, England Pearson.
- Managing International Business in China. (2011) [Online]. Google Books. Available: https://books.google.co.uk/books?hl=en&lr=&id=U7ySDQAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PR13&ots=2VJBxj7pLj&sig=O3xuj4TDOOfFqKQ78VAJMLADxqQ&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q&f=false [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].

- Manion, M., Rothschild, V. and Zhu, H. (2020) Viral Politics: What a Public Health Crisis Reveals about Government Credibility in Authoritarian China. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Mărginean, S. (2012) Private Labels of the DIY Retailers against the Romanian Post-Recession Environment. Procedia Economics and Finance. Vol.3, pp.1208–1213.
- Marolt, M., Zimmermann, H.-D., Žnidaršič, A. and Pucihar, A. (2020) Exploring Social Customer Relationship Management Adoption in Micro, Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises. Journal of theoretical and applied electronic commerce research. [Online] Vol.15 (2), pp.38–58. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/0718-1876/15/2/12> [Accessed 19 Mar 2021].
- Martins, A. (2021) The Future of Retail: Trends for 2021 [Online]. Business News Daily. Available: <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/9836-future-of-retail.html> [Accessed 13 Apr 2021].
- Mathew, S. K. (2012) Adoption of Business Intelligence Systems in Indian Fashion Retail. International Journal of Business Information Systems. Vol.9 (3), p.261.
- Mathews, S., Bianchi, C., Perks, K. J., Healy, M. and Wickramasekera, R. (2016) Internet Marketing Capabilities and International Market Growth. International Business Review. Vol.25 (4), pp.820–830.
- Mathews, S., Healy, M. and Wickramasekera, R. (2012) The Internetalisation of information, knowledge, and Interaction Components of the firm's Internationalisation Process. Journal of Marketing Management. Vol.28 (5-6), pp.733–754.
- Matina Stevis-Gridneff (2018) Meet the Startup Building a Market from Scratch to Become Africa's Alibaba [Online]. WSJ. Available: <https://www.wsj.com/articles/with-c-o-d-and-goat-promotions-jumia-aims-to-be-africas-alibaba-1527073200> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Maxwell, J. A. (2012) A Realist Approach for Qualitative Research. Thousand Oaks, Ca: Sage.
- Mazzarol, T. (2015) SMEs Engagement with e-commerce, e-business and e-marketing. Small Enterprise Research. Vol.22 (1), pp.79–90.
- Mboli, J. S., Thakker, D. and Mishra, J. L. (2020) An Internet of Things-enabled Decision Support System for Circular Economy Business Model. Software: Practice and Experience.

- McCarthy, N. (2019) Infographic: Half of All UK Retail Sales Will Be Online in 10 Years [Online]. Statista Infographics. Available: <https://www.statista.com/chart/18637/forecast-online-retail-spending-in-the-uk/> [Accessed 3 Jun 2021].
- McCole, P. and Ramsey, E. (2005) A Profile of Adopters and Non-Adopters of Ecommerce in SME Professional Service Firms. Australasian Marketing Journal. [Online] Vol.13 (1), pp.36–48. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1441358205700665> [Accessed 23 May 2021].
- McKinsey (2018) The Rise of Digital Challengers. How Digitization Can Become the next Growth Engine for Central and Eastern Europe [Online]. Mckinsey.com. Available: <https://digitalchallengers.mckinsey.com/#:~:text=In%202017%20the%20Digital%20C hallengers,digital%20initiatives%20a%20head%20start.&text=We%20are%20on%20t he%20cusp,economy%20and%20the%20labor%20market.> [Accessed 6 May 2021].
- Megicks, P. and Warnaby, G. (2008) Market Orientation and Performance in Small Independent Retailers in the UK. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research. Vol.18 (1), pp.105–119.
- Mintel (2020) DIY Retailing: Inc Impact of COVID-19 - UK - May 2020: Online [Online]. Mintel.com. Available: <https://reports.mintel.com/display/1022307/?fromSearch=%3Ffreetext%3DUK%2520DIY%2520Retailing%2520Market%2520Report%25202020> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- MiQ (2021) MiQ - Research and Insights [Online]. MiQ. Available: <https://www.wearemiq.com/research-and-insights/> [Accessed 16 Apr 2021].
- Mir-Bernal, P., Guercini, S. and Sádaba, T. (2017) The Role of e-commerce in the Internationalization of Spanish Luxury Fashion multi-brand Retailers. Journal of Global Fashion Marketing. Vol.9 (1), pp.59–72.
- Mirhosseini, S.-A. (2019) Book Review. Tourism Management. [Online] Vol.74, pp.408–409. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0261517719300895?token=7BCC7C2472D742B92A9DB5846811CCFC20D4A0695B6E662D940A02A61988ED2F8C0AAD2B7958A0D74F101CA77F6CACD3> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].

- Mishra, A. N., Konana, P. and Barua, A. (2007) Antecedents and Consequences of Internet Use in Procurement: An Empirical Investigation of U.S. Manufacturing Firms. Information Systems Research. Vol.18 (1), pp.103–120.
- Mkansi, M. (2021) E-business Adoption Costs and Strategies for Retail Micro Businesses. Electronic Commerce Research. [Online]. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10660-020-09448-7#Sec11> [Accessed 17 Feb 2021].
- Mndzebele, N. (2016) The Relationship between e-Commerce Adoption and Competition in the Hotel Industry. International Journal of Information and Education Technology. Vol.6 (5), pp.394–397.
- Modern Retail (2018) Finance for Independent Retailers Explored | Modern Retail [Online]. Modernretail.co.uk. Available: <https://modernretail.co.uk/how-independent-retailers-can-benefit-from-retail-finance/> [Accessed 1 May 2021].
- Moen, Ø., Koed Madsen, T. and Aspelund, A. (2008) The Importance of the Internet in International Business-to-business Markets. International Marketing Review. Vol.25 (5), pp.487–503.
- Molinillo, S., Aguilar-Illescas, R., Anaya-Sánchez, R. and Liébana-Cabanillas, F. (2021) Social commerce website design, perceived value and loyalty behavior intentions: The moderating roles of gender, age and frequency of use. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] p.102404. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698920314120> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Molla, A. and Licker, P. S. (2005) Perceived E-Readiness Factors in E-Commerce Adoption: an Empirical Investigation in a Developing Country. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.10 (1), pp.83–110.
- Morganti, E., Dablanc, L. and Fortin, F. (2014) Final Deliveries for Online shopping: the Deployment of Pickup Point Networks in Urban and Suburban Areas. Research in Transportation Business & Management. Vol.11, pp.23–31.
- Morschett, D., Schramm-Klein, H. and Swoboda, B. (2010) Decades of research on market entry modes: What do we really know about external antecedents of entry mode choice? Journal of International Management. [Online] Vol.16 (1), pp.60–77. Available:

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1075425309000969>

[Accessed 6 Jun 2021].

- Mou, J., Cohen, J., Dou, Y. and Zhang, B. (2019) International Buyers' Repurchase Intentions in a Chinese cross-border e-commerce Platform. Internet Research. Vol.30 (2), pp.403–437.
- Mpofu, K. C., Milne, D. and Watkins-Mathys, L. (2015) ICT Adoption and Development of E-business among SMEs in South Africa - Buckinghamshire New University Repository. Guildhe.ac.uk. [Online]. Available: <https://bucks.repository.guildhe.ac.uk/id/eprint/9583/> [Accessed 13 Jun 2021].
- Mumdziev, N. and Windsperger, J. (2013) An Extended Transaction Cost Model of Decision Rights Allocation in Franchising: the Moderating Role of Trust. Managerial and Decision Economics. Vol.34 (3-5), pp.170–182.
- Musteen, M., Francis, J. and Datta, D. K. (2012) Corrigendum to “The Influence of International Networks on Internationalization Speed and performance: a Study of Czech SMEs [Journal of World Business 45 (2010) 197–205].” Journal of World Business. Vol.47 (2), p.327.
- Ngai, E. W. T. and Gunasekaran, A. (2007) A Review for Mobile Commerce Research and Applications. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.43 (1), pp.3–15. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923605000692?casa_token=IsKZS61-WoUAAAAA:H_IKctwy9KTIW3P6hPWhNKKqvrFZB6NcZeKOY5VKOCNif3hWT0dmPJfLiAyRLjxJlZ7QJ511lg [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Nguyen, D. H., de Leeuw, S. and Dullaert, W. E. H. (2016) Consumer Behaviour and Order Fulfilment in Online Retailing: a Systematic Review. International Journal of Management Reviews. Vol.20 (2), pp.255–276.
- Nikolaeva, R. (2006) E-commerce Adoption in the Retail sector: Empirical Insights. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.34 (4/5), pp.369–387.
- Niu, B., Wang, J., Lee, C. K. M. and Chen, L. (2019) “Product + logistics” Bundling Sale and co-delivery in cross-border e-commerce. Electronic Commerce Research. [Online] Vol.19 (4), pp.915–941. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10660-019-09379-y> [Accessed 11 Feb 2021].

- Nixon, G. (2019) Ebay Fraudsters Scammed Me 11,000 Separate Times and Cost My Business £54,000 [Online]. This Is Money. Available: <https://www.thisismoney.co.uk/money/beatthescammers/article-7332251/Ebay-fraudsters-scammed-11-000-separate-times-cost-business-54-000.html> [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Nordman, E. R. and Melén, S. (2008) The Impact of Different Kinds of Knowledge for the Internationalization Process of Born Globals in the Biotech Business. Journal of World Business. Vol.43 (2), pp.171–185.
- Nyanga, P. H. (2012) Factors Influencing Adoption and Area under Conservation Agriculture: a Mixed Methods Approach. Sustainable Agriculture Research. Vol.1 (2), p.27.
- O'Connor, C. and Joffe, H. (2020) Intercoder Reliability in Qualitative Research: Debates and Practical Guidelines. International Journal of Qualitative Methods. Vol.19, p.160940691989922.
- OECD (2020) OECD Digital Economy Outlook 2020 | En | OECD [Online]. Oecd.org. Available: <https://www.oecd.org/sti/ieconomy/oecd-digital-economy-outlook-2020-bb167041-en.htm> [Accessed 30 Apr 2021].
- OECD (2021) OECD Glossary of Statistical Terms - Small and medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) Definition [Online]. Oecd.org. Available: <https://stats.oecd.org/glossary/detail.asp?ID=3123> [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- Ojala, A., Evers, N. and Rialp, A. (2018) Extending the International New Venture Phenomenon to Digital Platform providers: a Longitudinal Case Study. Journal of World Business. Vol.53 (5), pp.725–739.
- Okediran, O. O., Oyediran, M. O., Sijuade, A. A. and Wahab, W. B. (2020) Modeling User Acceptance of Electronic Voting: an Extended Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) Approach. Current Journal of Applied Science and Technology. pp.141–153.
- Olatokun, W. and Bankole, B. (2011) Factors Influencing Electronic Business Technologies Adoption and Use by Small and Medium Scale Enterprises (SMES) in a Nigerian Municipality. The Journal of Internet Banking and Commerce. [Online] Vol.16 (3), pp.1–26. Available: <https://www.icommercecentral.com/open-access/factors-influencing-electronic-business-technologies-adoption-and-use-by-small-and-medium-scale-enterprises-smes-in-a-nigerian-municipality.php?aid=38283> [Accessed 11 May 2021].

- Oliveira, T. and Martins, M. F. (2010) Understanding E-business Adoption across Industries in European Countries. Industrial Management & Data Systems. [Online] Vol.110 (9), pp.1337–1354. Available: https://research.unl.pt/ws/portalfiles/portal/14731237/Toliveira_MFMartins_2010.pdf.
- ONS (2021) Retail Sales Index Time Series - Office for National Statistics [Online]. Ons.gov.uk. Available: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/businessindustryandtrade/retailindustry/datasets/retailsales> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- Oviatt, B. M. and McDougall, P. P. (2005) Defining International Entrepreneurship and Modeling the Speed of Internationalization. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice. Vol.29 (5), pp.537–554.
- Oxford Dictionary (2021) Diy Noun - Definition, pictures, Pronunciation and Usage Notes | Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary at OxfordLearnersDictionaries.com [Online]. Oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com. Available: <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/diy?q=DIY> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Paige, J. (2021) How Small Business Retailers Can Succeed in 2021: Oracle NetSuite [Online]. Retail-insight-network.com. Available: <https://www.retail-insight-network.com/features/how-small-business-retailers-can-succeed-in-2021-oracle-netsuite/> [Accessed 21 Feb 2021].
- Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N. and Hoagwood, K. (2013) Purposeful Sampling for Qualitative Data Collection and Analysis in Mixed Method Implementation Research. Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research. [Online] Vol.42 (5), pp.533–544. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10488-013-0528-y> [Accessed 19 May 2021].
- Pan, Y. and Tse, D. K. (2000) The Hierarchical Model of Market Entry Modes. Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.31 (4), pp.535–554. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/palgrave.jibs.8490921> [Accessed 21 Mar 2019].

- Park, E. J., Kim, E. Y., Funches, V. M. and Foxx, W. (2012) Apparel product attributes, web browsing, and e-impulse buying on shopping websites. Journal of Business Research. [Online] Vol.65 (11), pp.1583–1589. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296311000762> [Accessed 15 Jun 2021].
- Parker, C., Ntounis, N., Millington, S., Quin, S. and Castillo-Villar, F. R. (2017) Improving the Vitality and Viability of the UK High Street by 2020. Journal of Place Management and Development. Vol.10 (4), pp.310–348.
- Parvinen, P., Oinas-Kukkonen, H. and Kaptein, M. (2015) E-selling: a New Avenue of Research for Service Design and Online Engagement. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. [Online] Vol.14 (4), pp.214–221. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1567422314000775?casa_token=CAta65aT3UAAAAA:dhTnfgWZdvmPOuKcA8S51d9PMA5eitD0Q5lz4d2nzlnN5yNxEbShvb8QAYljP60M_73czR_DdQ [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Patel, N. (2012) What Customers Want in an eCommerce Site [Online]. Neil Patel. Available: <https://neilpatel.com/blog/what-ecommerce-customers-want/> [Accessed 2 Jun 2021].
- Patil, B. (2019) SME Internationalisation through Digitalisation : UK Specialist and Niche Retailers [Online]. Ethos.bl.uk. Available: <https://ethos.bl.uk/OrderDetails.do?did=1&uin=uk.bl.ethos.814221> [Accessed 1 May 2021].
- Patten, E., Ozuem, W., Howell, K. and Lancaster, G. (2020) Minding the competition: the Drivers for Multichannel Service Quality in Fashion Retailing. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. Vol.53, p.101974.
- Patton, M. Q. (2002) Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods. Sage.
- Paul, J., Impey, A. and Stewart, S. (2021) New Report Finds SME Leaders Lack Digital Tech Skills [Online]. Open University in Scotland. Available: <https://www.open.ac.uk/scotland/news/leaders-skills> [Accessed 10 Jun 2021].
- Paul, J., Parthasarathy, S. and Gupta, P. (2017) Exporting Challenges of SMEs: a Review and Future Research Agenda. Journal of World Business. Vol.52 (3), pp.327–342.

- Pearson, J. M. and Grandon, E. E. (2005) An Empirical Study of Factors That Influence E-Commerce Adoption/Non-Adoption in Small and Medium Sized Businesses. Journal of Internet Commerce. Vol.4 (4), pp.1–21.
- Pederzoli, D. and Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2015) Retail Companies' Internationalization Behavior and the 2008 Crisis. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.43 (9), pp.870–894.
- Peltier, J. W., Zhao, Y. and Schibrowsky, J. A. (2012) Technology Adoption by Small businesses: an Exploratory Study of the Interrelationships of Owner and Environmental Factors. International Small Business Journal: Researching Entrepreneurship. Vol.30 (4), pp.406–431.
- Perera, C. H., Nayak, R. and Long, N. V. T. (2019) The Impact of Electronic-Word-of Mouth on e-Loyalty and Consumers' e-Purchase Decision Making Process: a Social Media Perspective. International Journal of Trade, Economics and Finance. Vol.10 (4), pp.85–91.
- Perkins, B., Geddes, I. and Harrap, N. (2020) What next for the High street? [Online]. Deloitte United Kingdom. Available: <https://www2.deloitte.com/uk/en/pages/consumer-business/articles/what-next-for-the-high-street.html> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Perrini, F., Russo, A. and Tencati, A. (2007) CSR Strategies of SMEs and Large Firms. Evidence from Italy. Journal of Business Ethics. Vol.74 (3), pp.285–300.
- Petro, G. (2016) Amazon Vs. Walmart: Clash of the Titans. Forbes. [Online], August 25, 2016. Available: <https://www.forbes.com/sites/gregpetro/2016/08/25/amazon-vs-walmart-clash-of-the-titans/?sh=1f1756112884> [Accessed 6 Mar 2021].
- Pham, G. V., Shancer, M. and Nelson, M. R. (2019) Only Other People Post Food Photos on Facebook: Third-person Perception of Social Media Behavior and Effects. Computers in Human Behavior. Vol.93, pp.129–140.
- Phaneuf, A. (2021) Social Commerce 2021: Social media and ecommerce convergence trends brings growth opportunity for brands [Online]. Business Insider. Available: <https://www.businessinsider.com/social-commerce-brand-trends-marketing-strategies?r=US&IR=T> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Pinho, J. C. and Prange, C. (2016) The Effect of Social Networks and Dynamic Internationalization Capabilities on International Performance. Journal of World Business. Vol.51 (3), pp.391–403.

- Poppo, L., Zhou, K. Z. and Li, J. J. (2014) "When Can You Trust 'Trust'? Calculative Trust, Relational Trust, and Supplier Performance." Academy of Management Proceedings. Vol.2014 (1), p.10191.
- Pousttchi, K. and Hufenbach, Y. (2014) Engineering the Value Network of the Customer Interface and Marketing in the Data-Rich Retail Environment. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.18 (4), pp.17–42.
- Prasad, V. K., Ramamurthy, K. and Naidu, G. M. (2001) The Influence of Internet–Marketing Integration on Marketing Competencies and Export Performance. Journal of International Marketing. [Online] Vol.9 (4), pp.82–110. Available: https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1509/jimk.9.4.82.19944?casa_token=NmT8BZk-IQwAAAAA%3AejySyJnVhUg3LTymKiiybfw2ZliYTcpFKxRoRsPttrDuhrvPNigarwBxBdQE8tF2Hn-3BgTM6JauHg [Accessed 11 Feb 2021].
- Prasetyo, Y. T., Tanto, H., Mariyanto, M., Hanjaya, C., Young, M. N., Persada, S. F., Miraja, B. A. and Redi, A. A. N. P. (2021) Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty in Online Food Delivery Service during the COVID-19 Pandemic: Its Relation with Open Innovation. Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity. [Online] Vol.7 (1), p.76. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2199-8531/7/1/76> [Accessed 14 Jun 2021].
- Preston, D. S., Chen, D. and Leidner, D. E. (2008) Examining the Antecedents and Consequences of CIO Strategic Decision-Making Authority: an Empirical Study*. Decision Sciences. Vol.39 (4), pp.605–642.
- PwC (2021a) Retail Outlook 2021: Using M&A to Create Value [Online]. PwC. Available: <https://www.pwc.co.uk/industries/retail-consumer/insights/retail-outlook/using-m-and-a-to-create-value.html> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- PwC (2021b) Retail Outlook 2021: Reshaping Your Business around Your Consumer [Online]. PwC. Available: <https://www.pwc.co.uk/industries/retail-consumer/insights/retail-outlook/reshaping-your-business-around-your-consumer.html> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Qasem, Z. (2021) The Effect of Positive TRI Traits on Centennials Adoption of try-on Technology in the Context of E-fashion Retailing. International Journal of Information Management. [Online] Vol.56, p.102254. Available:

<https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0268401220314535?token=F29AE39674F1045150C25FBA6DC3DCDF4B3109B294C12E6354BCDA196FFBC5CFF6A0F8DC0449D8F0E25D8F5F18273FB4> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].

- Qi, X., Chan, J. H., Hu, J. and Li, Y. (2020) Motivations for Selecting cross-border e-commerce as a Foreign Market Entry Mode. Industrial Marketing Management. [Online] Vol.89, pp.50–60. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019850118308071> [Accessed 28 Nov 2020].
- Quaye, D. and Mensah, I. (2018) Marketing Innovation and Sustainable Competitive Advantage of Manufacturing SMEs in Ghana. Management Decision.
- Quayle, M. (2002) E-commerce: the Challenge for UK SMEs in the Twenty-first Century. International Journal of Operations & Production Management. Vol.22 (10), pp.1148–1161.
- Ramanathan, R. (2010) E-commerce Success criteria: Determining which criteria Count Most. Electronic Commerce Research. [Online] Vol.10 (2), pp.191–208. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10660-010-9051-3> [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- Ramdani, B., Kawalek, P. and Lorenzo, O. (2009) Predicting SMEs' Adoption of Enterprise Systems. Journal of Enterprise Information Management. Vol.22 (1/2), pp.10–24.
- Ramdansyah, A. D. and Taufik, H. E. R. (2017) Adoption Model of E-Commerce from SMEs Perspective in Developing Country Evidence – Case Study for Indonesia. EUROPEAN RESEARCH STUDIES JOURNAL. Vol.XX (Issue 4B), pp.227–243.
- Reasoner, N. (2020) 5 Digital Marketing Predictions for a post-pandemic Economic Recovery [Online]. Think with Google. Available: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-gb/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/post-pandemic-economic-recovery/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Rebiazina, V. A., Smirnova, M. M. and Daviy, A. O. (2020) E-commerce Adoption in Russia: Market- and store-level Perspectives. Russian Management Journal. Vol.18 (1), pp.5–28.
- Resciniti, R. and De Vanna, F. (2019) A Literature Review on Firms' Internationalisation through e-commerce. Mercati & competitività - Open Access. [Online] Vol.0 (1). Available: http://ojs.francoangeli.it/_ojs/index.php/mcoa/article/view/7636 [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].

- Reuber, A. R., Knight, G. A., Liesch, P. W. and Zhou, L. (2018) International entrepreneurship: the Pursuit of Entrepreneurial Opportunities across National Borders. Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.49 (4), pp.395–406.
- Reuschke, D. and Mason, C. (2020) The Engagement of home-based Businesses in the Digital Economy. Futures. p.102542.
- Riaz, M. U., Guang, L. X., Zafar, M., Shahzad, F., Shahbaz, M. and Lateef, M. (2020) Consumers' Purchase Intention and decision-making Process through Social Networking sites: a Social Commerce Construct. Behaviour & Information Technology. pp.1–17.
- Ribau, C. P., Moreira, A. C. and Raposo, M. (2016) SME Internationalization research: Mapping the State of the Art. Canadian Journal of Administrative Sciences / Revue Canadienne des Sciences de l'Administration. Vol.35 (2), pp.280–303.
- Rich, R. C. (2018) Empirical Political Analysis : Quantitative and Qualitative Research Methods. New York, Ny: Routledge.
- Riemenschneider, C. K. and McKinney, V. R. (2016) Assessing Belief Differences in Small Business Adopters and Non-Adopters of Web-Based ECommerce. Journal of Computer Information Systems. Vol.42 (2), pp.101–107.
- Rigby, C. (2021a) As Stores reopen, Are Shoppers Returning – and What Are the Implications for Online sales? [Online]. InternetRetailing. Available: <https://internetretailing.net/themes/as-stores-reopen-are-shoppers-returning--and-what-are-the-implications-for-online-sales-23038> [Accessed 16 Apr 2021].
- Rigby, C. (2021b) Trading across EU Borders after Brexit [Online]. InternetRetailing. Available: <https://internetretailing.net/research-articles/trading-across-eu-borders-after-brexit> [Accessed 17 Apr 2021].
- Rigby, C. (2021c) Online Sales Grew across All Categories in locked-down February to Take a Record Share of Retail Sales [Online]. InternetRetailing. Available: <https://internetretailing.net/industry/online-sales-grew-across-all-categories-in-locked-down-february-to-take-a-record-share-of-retail-sales-22932> [Accessed 20 Apr 2021].
- Riquelme, H. (2002) Commercial Internet Adoption in China: Comparing the Experience of small, Medium and Large Businesses. Internet Research. Vol.12 (3), pp.276–286.
- Ritala, P., Golnam, A. and Wegmann, A. (2014) Coopetition-based business models: The case of Amazon.com. Industrial Marketing Management. [Online] Vol.43 (2), pp.236–249.

- Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019850113002150>
[Accessed 15 Jun 2021].
- Ritz, W., Wolf, M. and McQuitty, S. (2019) Digital Marketing Adoption and Success for Small Businesses. Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing. Vol.13 (2), pp.179–203.
- Robbins, S. P., Judge, T., Millett, B. and Boyle, M. (2017) Organisational Behaviour. Sydney, N.S.W. Pearson Australia.
- Rogers, E. M. (1995) Diffusion of Innovations, 4th Edition. New York: Free Press.
- Rosenow-Williams, K. and Kortmann, M. (2013) Islamic Organizations in Europe and the USA : a Multidisciplinary Perspective. Houndmills, Basingstoke, Hampshire: Palgrave Macmillan.
- RR (2020) Online Retail : UK, Europe & N. America : the Centre for Retail Research
Online Retail : UK, Europe & N. America : the Centre for Retail Research [Online]. Retailresearch.org.
Available: <https://www.retailresearch.org/online-retail.html> [Accessed 3 Dec 2020].
- Ruivo, P., Oliveira, T. and Neto, M. (2015) Using resource-based View Theory to Assess the Value of ERP commercial-packages in SMEs. Computers in Industry. Vol.73, pp.105–116.
- Sabanoglu, T. (2021) eBay: Number of Users 2021 | Statista [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/242235/number-of-ebays-total-active-users/>
[Accessed 3 Jun 2021].
- Saffu, K., Walker, J. H. and Hinson, R. (2008) Strategic Value and Electronic Commerce Adoption among Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in a Transitional Economy. Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing. Vol.23 (6), pp.395–404.
- San-Martín, S. and Jiménez, N. (2018) A Typology of Firms Regarding M-Commerce Adoption. Mobile Commerce. [Online] pp.550–565. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/gateway/chapter/183307#pnlRecommendationForm> [Accessed 8 Dec 2020].
- Sapienza, H. J., Autio, E., George, G. and Zahra, S. A. (2006) A Capabilities Perspective on the Effects of Early Internationalization on Firm Survival and Growth. Academy of Management Review. Vol.31 (4), pp.914–933.
- Sarasvathy, S. D. (2001) Causation and Effectuation: toward a Theoretical Shift from Economic Inevitability to Entrepreneurial Contingency. The Academy of Management Review. Vol.26 (2), p.243.

- Sarasvathy, S., Kumar, K., York, J. G. and Bhagavatula, S. (2014) An Effectual Approach to International Entrepreneurship: Overlaps, Challenges, and Provocative Possibilities. Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice. [Online] Vol.38 (1), pp.71–93. Available: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1111/etap.12088> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Saunders, M., Lewis, P. and Thornhill, A. (2019) Research Methods for Business Students. 8th ed. New York: Pearson.
- SBA (2021) Small Business Administration [Online]. Small Business Administration. Available: <https://www.sba.gov/search?q=SME> [Accessed 15 May 2021].
- Scarborough, N. (2014) Effective Small Business management. Pearson.
- Scarborough, N. M. and Cornwall, J. (2015) Entrepreneurship and Effective Small Business Management. Upper Saddle River, New Jersey: Pearson Education.
- Scarborough, N. M. and Cornwall, J. R. (2019) Essentials of Entrepreneurship and Small Business Management. New York, Ny Pearson Education.
- Schaper, M. (2014) Entrepreneurship and Small Business. Milton, Qld.: John Wiley and Sons Australia.
- Schellenberg, M., Harker, M. J. and Jafari, A. (2017) International Market Entry Mode – a Systematic Literature Review. Journal of Strategic Marketing. Vol.26 (7), pp.601–627.
- Schmitt, G., Mladenow, A., Strauss, C. and Schaffhauser-Linzatti, M. (2019) Smart Contracts and Internet of Things: A Qualitative Content Analysis using the Technology-Organization-Environment Framework to Identify Key-Determinants. Procedia Computer Science. [Online] Vol.160, pp.189–196. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050919316758> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Schmitz, A. J. (2016) Building trust in ecommerce through online dispute resolution [Online]. Elgar Online: The online content platform for Edward Elgar Publishing. Available: <https://www.elgaronline.com/view/edcoll/9781783479917/9781783479917.00031.xml> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Schu, M., Morschett, D. and Swoboda, B. (2016) Internationalization Speed of Online Retailers: A Resource-Based Perspective on the Influence Factors. Management International Review. [Online] Vol.56 (5), pp.733–757. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11575-016-0279-6> [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].

- Schweizer, R., Vahlne, J.-E. and Johanson, J. (2010) Internationalization as an entrepreneurial process. Journal of International Entrepreneurship. [Online] Vol.8 (4), pp.343–370. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007%2Fs10843-010-0064-8> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Scott, C. and Avalos, M. (2020) 5 Digital Marketing Predictions for a post-pandemic Economic Recovery [Online]. Think with Google. Available: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-gb/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/post-pandemic-economic-recovery/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Scuotto, V., Nicotra, M., Del Giudice, M., Krueger, N. and Gregori, G. L. (2021) A microfoundational perspective on SMEs' growth in the digital transformation era. Journal of Business Research. [Online] Vol.129, pp.382–392. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296321000539?casa_token=r8BbW1hKAsIAAAAA:PZwxqY6EqmpOL7r7AOJEMGIU2w-sGZ7QJgvuHPaB2qdeZLb2ufqFZSfz494cUMQa6Jld9pj3#bi005 [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Seggie, S. H. (2012) Transaction Cost Economics in International Marketing: a Review and Suggestions for the Future. Journal of International Marketing. Vol.20 (2), pp.49–71.
- Seitz, G. (2005) International Income Taxation of Cross-Border Electronic Commerce Transactions - a United States-German-New Zealand Case Study. SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Sestino, A., Prete, M. I., Piper, L. and Guido, G. (2020) Internet of Things and Big Data as Enablers for Business Digitalization Strategies. Technovation. [Online] Vol.98, p.102173. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0166497220300456> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Seyal, A. H. and Rahman, M. N. A. (2003) A Preliminary Investigation of E-commerce Adoption in Small & Medium Enterprises in Brunei. Journal of Global Information Technology Management,. Vol.6 (2), pp.6–26.
- Shah Alam, S., Khatibi, A., Ismail Sayyed Ahmad, Mohd. and Bin Ismail, H. (2008) Factors Affecting E-commerce Adoption in the Electronic Manufacturing Companies in Malaysia. International Journal of Commerce and Management. Vol.17 (1/2), pp.125–139.

- Sharma, V. M. and Erramilli, M. K. (2004) Resource-Based Explanation of Entry Mode Choice. Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice. Vol.12 (1), pp.1–18.
- Shaver, J. M. (2012) Do We Really Need More Entry Mode studies? Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.44 (1), pp.23–27.
- Shemi, A. P. and Procter, C. (2013) Explaining Contextual Factors Affecting e-commerce Adoption Progression in Selected SMEs: Evidence from Botswana. International Journal of Management Practice. Vol.6 (1), p.94.
- Shen, Z., Puig, F. and Paul, J. (2017) Foreign Market Entry Mode Research: a Review and Research Agenda. The International Trade Journal. Vol.31 (5), pp.429–456.
- Shi, P., Yan, B. and Zhao, J. (2018) Appropriate Timing for SMEs to Introduce an Internet-based Online Channel under Uncertain Operating costs: a Real Options Analysis. Electronic Commerce Research. [Online] Vol.20 (4), pp.969–999. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10660-018-9311-1> [Accessed 11 Feb 2021].
- Sillitoe, B. (2020) 5 Ways eCommerce Can Help Reverse Physical Retail Space Vacancies - IMRG [Online]. Imrg.org. Available: <https://imrg.org/blog/5-ways-ecommerce-can-help-reverse-physical-retail-space-vacancies/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Silverman, D. (2016) Qualitative Research. Los Angeles: Sage.
- Similarweb (2021a) Yell.com Traffic Ranking & Marketing Analytics | Similarweb [Online]. Similarweb. Available: <https://www.similarweb.com/website/yell.com/#overview> [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].
- Similarweb (2021b) Ebay.co.uk Traffic Ranking & Marketing Analytics | Similarweb [Online]. Similarweb. Available: <https://www.similarweb.com/website/ebay.co.uk/?competitors=amazon.co.uk> [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].
- Similarweb (2021c) Amazon.co.uk Traffic Ranking & Marketing Analytics | Similarweb [Online]. Similarweb. Available: <https://www.similarweb.com/website/amazon.co.uk/?competitors=ebay.co.uk> [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].
- Simpson, M. and Docherty, A. J. (2004) E-commerce Adoption Support and Advice for UK SMEs. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.11 (3), pp.315–328.

- Sin, K. Y., Osman, A., Salahuddin, S. N., Abdullah, S., Lim, Y. J. and Sim, C. L. (2016) Relative Advantage and Competitive Pressure Towards Implementation of E-commerce: Overview of Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs). Procedia Economics and Finance. [Online] Vol.35, pp.434–443. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S221256711600054X> [Accessed 25 May 2021].
- Sinkovics, N., Sinkovics, R. R. and Bryan-Jean, R. (2013) The Internet as an Alternative Path to internationalization? International Marketing Review. Vol.30 (2), pp.130–155.
- Skeldon, P. (2021) 50% of UK Shoppers to Continue Purchasing Clothing Online despite Shops Reopening [Online]. InternetRetailing. Available: <https://internetretailing.net/covid-19/50-of-uk-shoppers-to-continue-purchasing-clothing-online-despite-shops-reopening-23011> [Accessed 16 Apr 2021].
- Skudiene, V., Auruskeviciene, V. and Sukeviciute, L. (2015) Internationalization Model Revisited: E-marketing Approach. Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences. Vol.213 (213), pp.918–924.
- Şlusarciuc, M. (2015) The Economic Potential of Crossborder Areas. Opportunities and Threats. Procedia Economics and Finance. Vol.32, pp.801–808.
- Smith-Doerr, L., Lounsbury, M. and Ventresca, M. J. (2003) Research in the Sociology of Organizations, Vol. 19: Social Structure and Organizations Revisited. Contemporary Sociology. Vol.32 (6), p.710.
- Sorescu, A., Frambach, R. T., Singh, J., Rangaswamy, A. and Bridges, C. (2011) Innovations in Retail Business Models. Journal of Retailing. Vol.87 (1), pp.S3–S16.
- Sousa, P. R. de, Barbosa, M. W., Oliveira, L. K. de, Resende, P. T. V. de, Rodrigues, R. R., Moura, M. T. and Matoso, D. (2021) Challenges, Opportunities, and Lessons Learned: Sustainability in Brazilian Omnichannel Retail. Sustainability. Vol.13 (2), p.666.
- Srivastava, S., Singh, S. and Dhir, S. (2020) Culture and International Business research: a Review and Research Agenda. International Business Review. [Online] Vol.29 (4), p.101709. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0969593120300470?token=C3BF8F23FE E113BDAC2C015ECFD8A4DBE4C47E5D5E0A57835BEC76AE809E0324A3C50D6D9113 2418D8BC8133A96B08D5> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].

- Statista (2020a) Amazon in the United Kingdom (UK) | Statista [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/study/66168/amazon-in-the-uk/> [Accessed 3 Dec 2020].
- Statista (2020b) Stores of DIY Retailers Great Britain 2020 | Statista [Online]. Statista. Available: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/454008/leading-diy-retailers-by-number-of-stores-uk/> [Accessed 20 Feb 2021].
- Steel, G. (2021) Going Global – Going digital. Diaspora Networks and Female Online Entrepreneurship in Khartoum, Sudan. Geoforum. [Online] Vol.120, pp.22–29. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0016718521000038> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Stewards, C. (2020) 5 Digital Marketing Predictions for a post-pandemic Economic Recovery [Online]. Think with Google. Available: <https://www.thinkwithgoogle.com/intl/en-gb/consumer-insights/consumer-trends/post-pandemic-economic-recovery/> [Accessed 27 Apr 2021].
- Stjepić, A.-M., Pejić Bach, M. and Bosilj Vukšić, V. (2021) Exploring Risks in the Adoption of Business Intelligence in SMEs Using the TOE Framework. Journal of Risk and Financial Management. [Online] Vol.14 (2), p.58. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/1911-8074/14/2/58> [Accessed 9 Mar 2021].
- Stojkovic, D., Lovreta, S. and Bogetic, Z. (2016) Multichannel Strategy - the Dominant Approach in Modern Retailing. Ekonomski anali. [Online] Vol.61 (209), pp.105–127. Available: <http://www.ekof.bg.ac.rs/wp-content/uploads/2014/04/417-1.pdf>.
- Stroud, N., Minahan, C. and Sabapathy, S. (2009) The Perceived Benefits and Barriers to Exercise Participation in Persons with Multiple Sclerosis. Disability & Rehabilitation. pp.1–7.
- Strzelecki, A. (2019) Key Features of E-Tailer Shops in Adaptation to Cross-Border E-Commerce in the EU. Sustainability. [Online] Vol.11 (6), p.1589. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/11/6/1589> [Accessed 29 May 2021].
- Sui, S. and Baum, M. (2014) Internationalization strategy, firm resources and the survival of SMEs in the export market. Journal of International Business Studies. [Online] Vol.45 (7), pp.821–841. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/jibs.2014.11> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Sullivan Mort, G. and Weerawardena, J. (2006) Networking Capability and International Entrepreneurship. International Marketing Review. Vol.23 (5), pp.549–572.

- Susanty, A., Handoko, A. and Puspitasari, N. B. (2020) Push-pull-mooring Framework for e-commerce Adoption in Small and Medium Enterprises. Journal of Enterprise Information Management. Vol.33 (2), pp.381–406.
- Susanty, A., Puspitasari, N. B., Caterina, A. D. and Jati, S. (2020) Mapping the Barriers for Implementing Halal Logistics in Indonesian food, Beverage and Ingredient Companies. Journal of Islamic Marketing. Vol.ahead-of-print (ahead-of-print).
- Sussan, F. and Acs, Z. J. (2017) The Digital Entrepreneurial Ecosystem. Small Business Economics. [Online] Vol.49 (1), pp.55–73. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11187-017-9867-5> [Accessed 17 May 2021].
- Sutanonpaiboon, J. and Pearson, A. M. (2006) E-Commerce Adoption: Perceptions of Managers/Owners of Small- and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Thailand. Journal of Internet Commerce. Vol.5 (3), pp.53–82.
- Swanson, E. B. (1994) Information Systems Innovation among Organizations. Management Science. Vol.40 (9), pp.1069–1092.
- Tabares, A., Chandra, Y., Alvarez, C. and Escobar-Sierra, M. (2020) Opportunity-related Behaviors in International Entrepreneurship research: a Multilevel Analysis of antecedents, processes, and Outcomes. International Entrepreneurship and Management Journal.
- Taher, M. (2012) Resource-Based View Theory. In: Integrated Series in Information Systems. New York: Springer.
- Taherdoost, H. (2018) Development of an Adoption Model to Assess User Acceptance of e-service technology: E-Service Technology Acceptance Model. Behaviour & Information Technology. Vol.37 (2), pp.173–197.
- Tan, Z. (alex) and Wu, O. (2006) China: overcoming institutional barriers to e-commerce [Online]. Cambridge University Press. Available: https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/2E49A026F62514F4D6947CD6BC607F25/9780511488603c6_p209-246_CBO.pdf/china_overcoming_institutional_barriers_to_ecommerce.pdf [Accessed 17 Feb 2021].
- Tan, Z. (alex) and Wu, O. (2006) China: overcoming institutional barriers to e-commerce [Online]. Cambridge University Press. Available:

https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridge-core/content/view/2E49A026F62514F4D6947CD6BC607F25/9780511488603c6_p209-246_CBO.pdf/china_overcoming_institutional_barriers_to_ecommerce.pdf
[Accessed 17 Feb 2021].

Tan, Z. (alex) and Wu, O. (2021) China: Overcoming Institutional Barriers to e-commerce. Global e-Commerce. [Online] pp.209–246. Available: <https://experts.syr.edu/en/publications/china-overcoming-institutional-barriers-to-e-commerce> [Accessed 24 Apr 2021].

Tarafdar, M. and Vaidya, S. D. (2006) Challenges in the Adoption of E-Commerce Technologies in India: the Role of Organizational Factors. International Journal of Information Management. Vol.26 (6), pp.428–441.

Tarhini, A., Elyas, T., Akour, M. A. and Al-Salti, Z. (2016) Technology, Demographic Characteristics and E-Learning Acceptance: a Conceptual Model Based on Extended Technology Acceptance Model. Higher Education Studies. Vol.6 (3), p.72.

Tatarinov, A. A. (2019) Measuring Digital Economy in National Accounts. Voprosy statistiki. Vol.26 (2), pp.5–17.

Teegen, H. (2000) Examining Strategic and Economic Development Implications of Globalising through Franchising. International Business Review. Vol.9 (4), pp.497–521.

Teo, T. S. H. and Ranganathan, C. (2004) Adopters and non-adopters of business-to-business Electronic Commerce in Singapore. Information & Management. Vol.42 (1), pp.89–102.

Terpstra, V. and Yu, C. J. (1990) Piggybacking: a Quick Road to Internationalisation. International Marketing Review. Vol.7 (4).

Thaichon, P., Phau, I. and Weaven, S. (2020) Moving from multi-channel to Omni-channel retailing: Special Issue Introduction. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. p.102311.

Thimm, H. H., Rasmussen, K. B. and Gohout, W. (2016) Website Quality and Performance Indicators Including Ratio Numbers – A Study of German and Danish SME Companies. Journal of Business. [Online] Vol.1 (3), p.22. Available: <https://journalofbusiness.us/index.php/site/article/view/39> [Accessed 15 Jun 2021].

Thomas, B. C., Williams, R., Thompson, P. and Packham, G. (2013) Use of the Internet and SME Characteristics to Expand Scale and Geographic Scope of Sales. International

- Journal of Technology Diffusion. [Online] Vol.4 (3), pp.1–37. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/article/use-of-the-internet-and-sme-characteristics-to-expand-scale-and-geographic-scope-of-sales/97135> [Accessed 13 Jun 2021].
- Thomas, B., Miller, C., Packham, G. and Simmons, G. (2009) The Role of Web Sites and E-Commerce in the Development of Global Start-Ups. Electronic Business. [Online] pp.1002–1022. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/role-web-sites-commerce-development/9332> [Accessed 13 Jun 2021].
- Tiessen, J. H., Wright, R. W. and Turner, I. (2001) A Model of e-commerce Use by Internationalizing SMEs. Journal of International Management. Vol.7 (3), pp.211–233.
- Tolstoy, D. and Agndal, H. (2010) Network resource combinations in the international venturing of small biotech firms. Technovation. [Online] Vol.30 (1), pp.24–36. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S016649720900090X> [Accessed 27 May 2021].
- Tolstoy, D., Jonsson, A. and Sharma, D. D. (2016) The Influence of a Retail Firm’s Geographic Scope of Operations on Its International Online Sales. International Journal of Electronic Commerce. Vol.20 (3), pp.293–318.
- Tolstoy, D., Nordman, E. R., Hånell, S. M. and Özbek, N. (2020) The Development of International e-commerce in Retail SMEs: an Effectuation Perspective. Journal of World Business. [Online] p.101165. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1090951620300936> [Accessed 28 Nov 2020].
- Tolstoy, D., Nordman, E. R., Hånell, S. M. and Özbek, N. (2021) The Development of International e-commerce in Retail SMEs: an Effectuation Perspective. Journal of World Business. [Online] Vol.56 (3), p.101165. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1090951620300936> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Tornatzky, L. G. and Fleischer, M. (1990) The Process of Technological Innovation. Massachusetts: Lexington Books.
- Tran, L. T. T. (2021) Managing the Effectiveness of e-commerce Platforms in a Pandemic. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.58, p.102287. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698920312959>.

- Tumolo, M. (2001) Business-To-Business Exchanges. Information Systems Management. Vol.18 (2), pp.54–62.
- Turban, E., Outland, J., King, D., Lee, J. K., Liang, T.-P. and Turban, D. C. (2018) Electronic Commerce 2018 : a Managerial and Social Networks Perspective. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
- Tushman, M. L. and Anderson, P. (1986) Technological Discontinuities and Organizational Environments. Administrative Science Quarterly. [Online] Vol.31 (3), p.439. Available: <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/be4f/b1ad3317228b60938d83aca27b496fbc5d4.pdf> [Accessed 29 Oct 2019].
- Uma Sekaran and Bougie, R. (2019) Research Methods for Business : a skill-building Approach. Hoboken, Nj: John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Vakulenko, Y., Shams, P., Hellström, D. and Hjort, K. (2019) Service Innovation in e-commerce Last Mile delivery: Mapping the e-customer Journey. Journal of Business Research.
- Valarezo, Á., Pérez-Amaral, T., Garín-Muñoz, T., Herguera García, I. and López, R. (2018) Drivers and Barriers to cross-border e-commerce: Evidence from Spanish Individual Behavior. Telecommunications Policy. [Online] Vol.42 (6), pp.464–473. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308596117304986> [Accessed 28 Nov 2020].
- Van Looy, A. (2021) A Quantitative and Qualitative Study of the Link between Business Process Management and Digital Innovation. Information & Management. [Online] Vol.58 (2), p.103413. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378720620303517> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Van Maanen, J., Sørensen, J. B. and Mitchell, T. R. (2007) The Interplay between Theory and Method. Academy of Management Review. Vol.32 (4), pp.1145–1154.
- Veal, A. J. and Ticehurst, G. W. (2005) Business Research Methods : a Managerial Approach. Frenchs Forest, Nsw: Longman.
- Venkatesh, V. and Bala, H. (2008) Technology Acceptance Model 3 and a Research Agenda on Interventions. Decision Sciences. Vol.39 (2), pp.273–315.
- Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. D. (2000) A Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model: Four Longitudinal Field Studies. Management Science. [Online] Vol.46 (2),

- pp.186–204. Available:
<https://pubsonline.informs.org/doi/abs/10.1287/mnsc.46.2.186.11926>.
- Venkatesh, V., Morris, M. G., Davis, G. B. and Davis, F. D. (2003) User Acceptance of Information Technology: toward a Unified View. MIS Quarterly. [Online] Vol.27 (3), pp.425–478.
- Verhoef, P. C., Kannan, P. K. and Inman, J. J. (2015) From Multi-Channel Retailing to Omni-Channel Retailing. Journal of Retailing. [Online] Vol.91 (2), pp.174–181. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0022435915000214?casa_token=8cFxQQFdCq4AAAAA:LpTt1xmuFzBVTt95EZxYlfANoXqRLPwXaUH7lql_qf1P_W5-RQYePcR5c5IkQbDp1ATJt-vTXJA [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- Vizard, M. (2013) Jaguar Launches Virtual Shopping Experience [Online]. www.cioinsight.com. Available: <https://www.cioinsight.com/it-news-trends/jaguar-launches-virtual-shopping-experience> [Accessed 18 Feb 2021].
- Vodafone UK News Centre (2021) 100,000 Small Businesses to Get Free Digital Skills Training from Vodafone [Online]. Vodafone UK News Centre. Available: <https://newscentre.vodafone.co.uk/press-release/enterprise-nation-free-digital-skills-training-100000-small-businesses/> [Accessed 10 Jun 2021].
- von Briel, F. (2018) The future of omnichannel retail: A four-stage Delphi study. Technological Forecasting and Social Change. [Online] Vol.132, pp.217–229. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162518302026?casa_token=tJ6v5_eGHtUAAAAA:nLUV9hwkw7ZBBPj2MZgr4bqxcZEBEZhHVIj3ibZFFMGEBJNWQq00RkBREUuTHFA4n0Hah3ID [Accessed 14 Jun 2021].
- Wach, K. (2014) Market Entry Modes for International Businesses [Online]. ResearchGate. Available: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/267040494_Market_entry_modes_for_international_businesses [Accessed 25 Jun 2021].
- Wagner, G., Schramm-Klein, H. and Steinmann, S. (2018) Online Retailing across e-channels and e-channel touchpoints: Empirical Studies of Consumer Behavior in the Multichannel e-commerce Environment. Journal of Business Research.
- Walmart (2021) Walmart Expands Its eCommerce Marketplace to More Small Businesses [Online]. Corporate - US. Available:

- <https://corporate.walmart.com/newsroom/2020/06/15/walmart-expands-its-ecommerce-marketplace-to-more-small-businesses> [Accessed 18 Jun 2021].
- Wang, H. and Hou, J. C. (2011) Drivers and Inhibitors of E-Commerce Adoption in Small and Medium Sized Enterprises. Advanced Materials Research. Vol.225-226, pp.929–932.
- Wang, J. (2014) Opportunities and Challenges of International e-Commerce in the Pilot Areas of China. International Journal of Marketing Studies. Vol.6 (6).
- Wang, S. and Wang, F. (2020) Network prominence and e-store performance in social marketplace: A nuanced typology and empirical evidence. Electronic Commerce Research and Applications. [Online] Vol.43, p.100991. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1567422320300685> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Wang, X., Lu, J., Ow, T. T., Feng, Y. and Liu, L. (2021) Understanding the Emotional and Informational Influence on Customer Knowledge Contribution through Quantitative Content Analysis. Information & Management. [Online] Vol.58 (2), p.103426. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0378720620303645> [Accessed 11 Mar 2021].
- Wang, Y. Chai, Y. Liu and Y. Xu (2015) Qualitative Analysis of Cross-Border E-Commerce Based on Transaction Costs Theory [Online]. undefined. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Qualitative-Analysis-of-Cross-Border-E-Commerce-on-Wang-Chai/c1d15fc5c0b75732c4426982ccf984e769e532f9> [Accessed 6 Jun 2021].
- Wang, Y.-S. (2008) Assessing e-commerce Systems success: a Respecification and Validation of the DeLone and McLean Model of IS Success. Information Systems Journal. [Online] Vol.18 (5), pp.529–557. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1365-2575.2007.00268.x> [Accessed 7 Mar 2021].
- Warleta, G. M., Ventisca, M. D.-B. and Gallo, M. P. (2016) Importance and Role of Retail Brands in a Non-Food Market. Handbook of Research on Strategic Retailing of Private Label Products in a Recovering Economy. [Online] pp.416–442. Available: <https://www.igi-global.com/chapter/importance-and-role-of-retail-brands-in-a-non-food-market/157665> [Accessed 1 Mar 2021].

- Washtell, F. (2019) High Street Overhaul as “perfect storm” Hits [Online]. This Is Money. Available: <https://www.thisismoney.co.uk/money/markets/article-6638043/High-Street-overhaul-perfect-storm-hits.html> [Accessed 20 May 2021].
- Watson, M. and Shove, E. (2008) Product, Competence, Project and Practice. Journal of Consumer Culture. Vol.8 (1), pp.69–89.
- Wedawatta, G. and Ingirige, B. (2016) A Conceptual Framework for Understanding Resilience of Construction SMEs to Extreme Weather Events. Built Environment Project and Asset Management. Vol.6 (4), pp.428–443.
- Wedawatta, G., Ingirige, B., Jones, K. and Proverbs, D. (2011) Extreme Weather Events and Construction SMEs. Structural Survey. Vol.29 (2), pp.106–119.
- Welch, C. (2000) The Archaeology of Business networks: the Use of Archival Records in Case Study Research. Journal of Strategic Marketing. Vol.8 (2), pp.197–208.
- Welch, C. and Piekkari, R. (2006) Crossing Language boundaries: Qualitative Interviewing in International Business. Management International Review. Vol.46 (4), pp.417–437.
- Westhead, P., Ucbasaran, D. and Binks, M. (2004) Internationalization Strategies Selected by Established Rural and Urban SMEs. Journal of Small Business and Enterprise Development. Vol.11 (1), pp.8–22.
- Whinston, M. D. (2003) On the Transaction Cost Determinants of Vertical Integration. Journal of Law, Economics, and Organization. Vol.19 (1), pp.1–23.
- Williams, C. C. (2004) A Lifestyle choice? Evaluating the Motives of Do-it-yourself (DIY) Consumers. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.32 (5), pp.270–278.
- Williams, C. C. (2008) Re-thinking the Motives of do-it-yourself (DIY) Consumers. The International Review of Retail, Distribution and Consumer Research. Vol.18 (3), pp.311–323.
- Williams, C., Du, J. and Zhang, H. (2020) International Orientation of Chinese Internet SMEs: Direct and Indirect Effects of Foreign and Indigenous Social Networking Site Use. Journal of World Business. Vol.55 (3), p.101051.
- Williams, M. D., Rana, N. P. and Dwivedi, Y. K. (2012) A Bibliometric Analysis of Articles Citing the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology. In: Integrated Series in Information Systems. New York: Springer.

- Wilsdon, J. and Miller, P. (2002) Digital Futures: an Agenda for a Sustainable Digital Economy. In: Digital Futures: Living in a Networked World. London: Earthscan, p.3.
- Wolf, M. and McQuitty, S. (2011) Understanding the do-it-yourself consumer: DIY Motivations and Outcomes. AMS Review. [Online] Vol.1 (3-4), pp.154–170. Available: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s13162-011-0021-2> [Accessed 23 Feb 2021].
- Wolf, M. and McQuitty, S. (2013) Circumventing Traditional Markets: an Empirical Study of the Marketplace Motivations and Outcomes of Consumers' Do-It-Yourself Behaviors. Journal of Marketing Theory and Practice. Vol.21 (2), pp.195–210.
- Work, S. (2011) How Loading Time Affects Your Bottom Line [Online]. Neil Patel. Available: <https://neilpatel.com/blog/loading-time/?wide=1> [Accessed 2 Jun 2021].
- Wu, J.-H. and Wang, S.-C. (2005) What drives mobile commerce? Information & Management. [Online] Vol.42 (5), pp.719–729. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S0378720604000904?via%3Dihub> [Accessed 24 May 2021].
- Wu, L. (2019) Website interactivity may compensate for consumers' reduced control in E-Commerce. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.49, pp.253–266. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S096969891830609X> [Accessed 14 Jun 2021].
- Wu, X. and Gereffi, G. (2019) Amazon and Alibaba: Internet Governance, Business Models, and Internationalization Strategies [Online]. undefined. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Amazon-and-Alibaba%3A-Internet-Governance%2C-Business-Wu-Gereffi/31a4a02529e95788bfb025f23db96dea627475f2> [Accessed 3 Jun 2021].
- Xia, Y. and Zhang, G. P. (2010) The Impact of the Online Channel on Retailers' Performances: an Empirical Evaluation. Decision Sciences. [Online] Vol.41 (3), pp.517–546. Available: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1111/j.1540-5915.2010.00279.x> [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- Xie, C., Bagozzi, R. P. and Troye, S. V. (2007) Trying to prosume: toward a Theory of Consumers as co-creators of Value. Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science. Vol.36 (1), pp.109–122.

- Xuhua, H., Chosniel Elikem, O. and Akaba, S. (2019) Effects of Business to Business e-commerce Adoption on Competitive Advantage of Small and medium-sized Manufacturing Enterprises. Economics & Sociology. Vol.12 (1), pp.80–99.
- Yahia, I. B., Al-Neama, N. and Kerbache, L. (2018) Investigating the drivers for social commerce in social media platforms: Importance of trust, social support and the platform perceived usage. Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services. [Online] Vol.41, pp.11–19. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0969698917301315> [Accessed 19 Jun 2021].
- Yamin, M. and Kurt, Y. (2018) Revisiting the Uppsala Internationalization Model. International Marketing Review. Vol.35 (1), pp.2–17.
- Yell (2021) Yell Business - Digital Marketing Services [Online]. Yell Business. Available: https://business.yell.com/?utm_source=yell.com&utm_campaign=yell.com-header-top-left-link&utm_medium=referral [Accessed 8 Jun 2021].
- Yrjölä, M., Saarijärvi, H. and Nummela, H. (2018) The Value Propositions of multi-, cross-, and omni-channel Retailing. International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management. Vol.46 (11/12), pp.1133–1152.
- Yu, Y., Wang, X., Zhong, R. Y. and Huang, G. Q. (2017) E-commerce Logistics in Supply Chain Management. Industrial Management & Data Systems. Vol.117 (10), pp.2263–2286.
- Zaheer, S. and Zaheer, A. (2005) Trust across Borders. Journal of International Business Studies. Vol.37 (1), pp.21–29.
- Zahra, S. A. (2020) International Entrepreneurship in the Post Covid World. Journal of World Business. Vol.56 (1), p.101143.
- Zakari, M. (2020) International Financial Reporting Standard (IFRS) Adoption and Its Impact on Financial Reporting: Evidence from Listed Nigeria Oil and Gas Companies. Asian Journal of Finance & Accounting. Vol.9 (1), p.464.
- Zhang, C. and Zheng, X. (2021) Customization Strategies between Online and Offline Retailers. Omega. [Online] Vol.100, p.102230. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0305048319304955?casa_token=sD0zKZLL2bUAAAAA:6vSR99ZKuAfg8qpiR0aQBLE7gGqtMHCO8HobUaMkYEwGdDXIEcbue1rot9MfDOv3QOm0KgMZ [Accessed 8 May 2021].

- Zhang, K. Z. K. and Benyoucef, M. (2016) Consumer Behavior in Social commerce: a Literature Review. Decision Support Systems. [Online] Vol.86, pp.95–108. Available: https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923616300458?casa_token=wS89K92-bCIAAAAA:hqYhnCJvguvAjCpvg_fhHM6_6RiFQfWT5Ax7j5of3YZjITOYE-oWPkE0SUQdkFYXWyd9gOEYxw [Accessed 17 Jan 2021].
- Zhang, P., He, Y. and Shi, C. (Victor) (2017) Retailer’s Channel Structure choice: Online channel, Offline channel, or Dual channels? International Journal of Production Economics. [Online] Vol.191, pp.37–50. Available: <https://reader.elsevier.com/reader/sd/pii/S0925527317301585?token=8B1E522497705BB9A478FBF51539851861C90B8AB13D7C2EEE25AFF14C15CA8E1A3482C2443731884D5E20F9DD244971&originRegion=eu-west-1&originCreation=20210508033912> [Accessed 8 May 2021].
- Zhen, X., Xu, S., Shi, D. and Li, Y. (2019) When Should a Retailer Introduce a Third Party Platform Channel under Spillovers from Offline to Online Sales? SSRN Electronic Journal.
- Zheng, Q. (2014) Model Path of E-Commerce Adoption in SMEs. Advanced Materials Research. Vol.933, pp.907–911.
- Zhichao, X., Han, Y., Yongfeng, Z. and Qingyao, A. (2020) E-commerce Recommendation with Weighted Expected Utility. arXiv e-prints. [Online] p.arXiv:2008.08302. Available: <https://ui.adsabs.harvard.edu/abs/2020arXiv200808302X/abstract> [Accessed 9 Feb 2021].
- Zhu, K., Kraemer, K. and Xu, S. (2003) Electronic Business Adoption by European firms: a cross-country Assessment of the Facilitators and Inhibitors. European Journal of Information Systems. Vol.12 (4), pp.251–268.
- Zhu, K., Kraemer, K. L. and Dedrick, J. (2004) Information Technology Payoff in E-Business Environments: an International Perspective on Value Creation of E-Business in the Financial Services Industry. Journal of Management Information Systems. Vol.21 (1), pp.17–54.
- Zhu, K., Kraemer, K. L. and Xu, S. (2006) The Process of Innovation Assimilation by Firms in Different Countries: a Technology Diffusion Perspective on E-Business. Management Science. Vol.52 (10), pp.1557–1576.

Zhu, K., Kraemer, K. L., Gurbaxani, V. and Xu, S. X. (2006) Migration to Open-Standard Interorganizational Systems: Network Effects, Switching Costs, and Path Dependency. MIS Quarterly. Vol.30 (), p.515.

Zikmund, W. G., Babin, B. J., C, J. and Griffin, M. (2013) Business Research Methods. Mason, Ohio: South-Western.

Chapter 10: Appendixes

10.1. Appendix 1: Participant information sheet

Research Project Title:

Surviving the Challenges of 21st Century Retailing – Proposing a Way Forward for Independent DIY Retailers in the UK Using e-commerce.

2. Invitation

You are being invited to take part in this research project. Before you decide to do so, it is important that you understand why the research is being done and what it will involve. Please take time to read the following information carefully and discuss it with others if you wish. Ask us if there is anything that is not clear or if you would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not you wish to take part. Thank you for reading this.

3. What is the purpose of the project?

This research aims to propose a way forward for the independent DIY retailers in the UK by examining their e-commerce adoption challenges, practice and opportunities.

This project builds on research carried out by researchers and academics over the decades in different industries and settings. However, this study focuses on how independent DIY retailers can adopt and sell e-commerce platforms to the domestic and international markets through e-commerce sites.

4. Why have I been chosen?

You have been chosen as an experienced independent DIY retailer and have ample experience in DIY retailing. Therefore, we believe this study will be benefited from your knowledge and experience. Moreover, the whole Independent DIY retail industry will be benefited from your experience.

5. Do I have to take part?

Your participation is entirely voluntary; it is up to you to decide whether or not to take part. If you choose to take part, you will keep a copy of this information sheet, and you should

indicate your agreement to the online consent form. Of course, you can still withdraw at any time. You do not have to give any reason.

6. What will happen to me if I take part?

You will be requested to participate in a face-to-face interview, telephone or via Skype or Zoom interview at your convenience. If you wish, I can visit your store or any place that is convenient for you. You may also want to agree to a follow-up interview to find out more about your approach.

7. What do I have to do?

Suppose you agree to participate in the interview. In that case, you will be asked your industry-related questions regarding the challenges your business faces and your opinion on how to overcome those challenges. There are no other commitments or lifestyle restrictions associated with participating.

8. What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

Participating in the research is NOT anticipated to cause you any disadvantages or discomfort. The potential physical and/or psychological harm or distress will be the same as any everyday life experience.

9. What are the possible benefits of taking part?

Whilst there are no immediate benefits for those participating in the project, it is hoped that this study will have a beneficial impact on academia that will describe and clarify the independent DIY retailers' challenges to survive and grow potentially. This research will focus on how independent DIY retailers adopt e-commerce and sell locally and globally.

Thus, the British independent DIY retail industry will be benefited in terms of moving online and sell at home the international market. Thus, the overall British economy will be benefited.

10. What happens if the research study stops earlier than expected?

Should the research stop earlier than planned and you are affected in any way, we will tell you and explain why.

11. What if something goes wrong?

If you have any complaints about the project in the first instance, you can contact me personally.

If you feel your complaint has not been handled to your satisfaction, you can contact the University of West of Scotland and my first supervisor, Dr Julia Fallon, to take your complaint further.

12. Will my taking part in this project be kept confidential?

All the information that we collect about you during the research will be kept strictly confidential. You will NOT be able to be identified or identifiable in any reports or publications. Your institution will also NOT be identified or identifiable. Any data collected about you, or your company will be stored in a form protected by passwords and other relevant security processes and technologies.

Data collected may be shared in an anonymised form to authenticate by the research Supervisor, Dr Fallon. These anonymised data will not allow any individuals or their institutions to be identified or identifiable in any manner.

13. Will I be recorded, and how will the recorded media be used?

The interview will be recorded for audio ONLY without mentioning your or the institutions' name or identity. You will be informed and supplied with a consent form for your permission. If you wish not to be recorded, your valuable comments and information will be noted for further research and analysis.

14. What type of information will be sought from me, and why is this information collection relevant for achieving the research project's objectives?

You will be asked about the e-commerce adoption challenges, practice in your business.

15. What will happen to the results of the research project?

Results of the research will be published in a thesis form. You will not be identified in any report or publication. Likewise, your institution will NOT be identified in any report or

publication. If you wish to be given a copy of any reports resulting from the research, please ask us to put you on our circulation list.

16. Who is organising and funding the research?

As a self-funding doctoral researcher, I am Md Ashraf Hossain, funding for the course in order to complete a Doctor of Business Administration Degree from the University of the West of Scotland.

17. Who has ethically reviewed the project?

This project has been supervised by Dr Julia Fallon and ethically approved by the University of the West of Scotland's Research Ethics Committee in accordance with the UWS ethical research guidelines.

18. Contacts for further information

Md Ashraf Hossain, DBA student, UWS- London Campus. email:

[REDACTED]

Dr Julia Fallon, DBA- Supervisor, UWS- London Campus. email: [REDACTED]

Thank you for taking part in this research.

Regards

Ashraf

10.2. Appendix 2: Consent Form

Interviewer's Name: Md Ashraf Hossain

DBA candidate at the University of the West of Scotland. London Campus, 235 Southwark Bridge Road, London, SE1 6NP.

Participant's Name:

Dear Respondent

You have been asked to participate in research titled "Surviving the Challenges of 21st Century Retailing – Proposing a Way Forward for Independent DIY Retailers in the UK Using e-commerce".

This study aims to understand the challenges facing by independent DIY retailers in the UK. Furthermore, this study aims to provide recommendations on how independent DIY retailers can sell in the foreign market through e-commerce platforms.

If you agree to participate, you will be asked to participate in a 45-60-minute tape-recorded interview. You are also being asked for your permission to audiotape the interview, but if you wish NOT to be recorded, please be notified that, only notes will be taken.

Please be informed that the findings of this study may be published. Your identifications in any means will NOT be included.

Your consent is being given voluntarily. Please be assured that you may refuse to participate in the entire study or any part of the study at any time.

When you sign this form, you will receive a signed and dated copy of this form for your record.

A participant information sheet is supplied to you for more information. Please feel free to contact should you have any further question regarding this study.

Regards

Md Ashraf Hossain

Email:

.....
Participant's Signature

.....
Date:

.....
Investigator's signature

.....
Date:

10.3. Appendix 3: Ethics Approval Letter

15/01/2021

Dear Md Ashraf Hossain,

Your application 13904: SMEs Internationalisation Through E-commerce - British Independent DIY Retailers., submission 13213, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC. You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Dr D Turner

10.4. Appendix: Defining SMEs.

SMEs are defined differently in different parts of the world. However, in most countries, SMEs are determined based on the number of employees, yearly turnover, and the balance sheet at the end of the year. For example, SMEs are defined in the UK and EU based on three categories: staff headcount, yearly turnover, and balance sheet total. Under this umbrella term, SMEs are segmented into three categories: medium, small, and micro-size businesses independently owned, not a subsidiary of any large company (European Commission, 2016; OECD, 2021).

SMEs in the UK: Criteria for SMEs

Micro Entities: a company is categorised as a micro business if it has any two of the following

- A turnover of £632,000 or less.
- £316,000 or less on its balance sheet.
- Ten employees or less.

Small Companies: a company is categorised as small if it has any two of the following.

- A turnover of £10.2 million or less.
- £5.1 million or less on its balance sheet.
- 50 employees or less.

Medium-size business: a company is categorised as small if it has any two of the following.
(Companies House, 2017)

- A turnover of £36 million or less
- £18 million or less on its balance sheet.
- Average employees 250 or less

SMEs in the EU:

Microbusiness: a business with fewer than ten employees and a balance sheet of up to €2 million or yearly turnover of up to 2 million.

Small Business: a small business has fewer than 50 employees or up to €10 million in turnover or balance sheet total.

Medium-size business: a business with less than 250 staff and a turnover of up to € 50million or a balance sheet of up to €43 million.

Table 40: Category of Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) by EU and the UK.

Category of Small and Medium Enterprise (SME) by EU and the UK.

Company category	Staff headcount	Turnover	or	Balance sheet total
Medium-sized	< 250	≤ € 50 m		≤ € 43 m
Small	< 50	≤ € 10 m		≤ € 10 m
Micro	< 10	≤ € 2 m		≤ € 2 m

Source: Adapted from European Commission (2016) and OECD (2021)

10.5. Appendix: The current state of IT adoption among retail SMEs

The current state of IT adoption among retail SMEs

Leading tech company Dell Technology introduced the Digital Transformation Index (DTI) in 2016, and they publish DTI report every two years and last published in 2020. This highly sophisticated report is based on more than 4300 companies in 13 different categories, including companies from the retail and consumer category and 18 other countries from America, Asia Pacific, and the EU.

This report investigates the barriers of digital transformation and categorised companies into five different categories based on their digital transformation circumstances. First of all, digital laggards those who have limited investment and initiatives and no plan for digitalisation. Then Digital followers- companies feel the need for digitalisation but have very little investment and initiatives for digitalisation. Digital followers are the ones who are actively planning and making an effort and investment towards a gradual digitalisation. Then, digital adopters with a mature digital goal make a significant investment in innovation and digitalisation. Finally, digital leaders, these companies are at the height of digitalisation and a functioning digital organisation. The report illustrates that businesses are inching towards digitalisation across the world. Significantly, companies are forced to adopt at least some sort of digitalisation in 2020 due to the COVID19 pandemic. (DTI, 2020)

Figure 27: Digital Transformation Index comparison.

Source: Adopted from Dell Technologies (2020).

The report found that lack of resources and budget, 30% of businesses surveyed, lack of skill and in-house expertise (24%) and slow economic growth are the critical reasons for digital transformation and technology adoption. Furthermore, government regulations and legislative changes (23%) and lack of institutional or government support (17%) for digitalisation also hinder digitalisation and e-commerce adoption. However, in 2020, pandemic related disruption pushed businesses to embrace technology at least to some extent, which raises the concern for data privacy and security (31%), and strong government legislation regarding GDPR is limiting the technology adoption, and digitalisation as many small businesses are not able to comply with the regulations for data protection.

10.6. Appendix: The current state of digital transformation

The current state of digital transformation among SMEs in selected countries

Technology adoption among businesses is far greater in developing countries than in developed countries (DTI,2020; OECD;2020). Research shows that in 2018 and 2020, Indian business digitalised more than the Netherlands, Sweden and Japan. In 2016, among SMEs, the UK was one of the poor-performing countries in technology adoption, ranked by DTI (2016).

In 2020, businesses worldwide had emphasised technology adoption due to pandemic pressure when most businesses remained shut, while technology and digital platforms provided alternatives for survival. The state of IT adoption in the UK and other selected countries are given below.

Figure 28: Digital technology adoption in the UK and other countries in 2020.

Source: Author's construct, data extracted from DTI (2020).

10.7. Appendix: DIY Retail market in the UK.

Figure 29: Market forecast of DIY/hardware specialist 2014-2024.

Source: Adapted from Mintel (2020).

DIY Retailing, which includes electrical, home improvement, gardening, and household, is one of the British economy's critical sectors. Over the last decade, it grew steadily from £11.6 billion in 2014, and Mintel (2020) forecasted that it would reach £13 billion in 2024 will maintain the same growth. The best-case scenario could go up to £16.6 billion (Latest available data by ONS (2021)).

10.8. Appendix: Leading DIY stores and Brands in the GB

Figure 30: Leading DIY retailers in GB in 2020, by stores number.

Leading DIY retailers in Great Britain in 2020, by number of stores

Great Britain: leading DIY retailers 2020, by number of stores

Source: Adopted from Statista (2020).

The number of DIY specialised stores grew steadily in the UK over the last decade. However, this number increased by only 501 stores in the previous 12 years, totalling 6119 stores, including specialists, non-specialist and independent retailers. The increase mainly came from specialist DIY retailers such as B&Q, Homebase, Screwfix, Toolstation, The Range, etc.

Kingfisher group's B&Q and Screwfix held the largest DIY market share in the UK, having 297 and 687 stores, respectively. Argos and Wilko lead the non-specialist DIY with 570 and 419 branches across the UK.

However, the number of independent DIY retailers are in continuous decline. For example, in 2019, only 7% in-store and 2% online sales of the total DIY sales came from independent retailers, decreasing yearly (Mintel, 2017, 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021). It is due to the less

footfall in the high street (CRR,2021; Deloitte,2021), unfavourable policies by the local authority (Dickinson, 2021), no or limited parking facilities on the high street (Bamfield, 2014).

10.9. Appendix: Online DIY market

Compared to other consumer categories, DIY is one of the UK's least mature categories in e-commerce (Mintel,2020). Online DIY turnover crossed £2.1 billion in 2020 (latest available data) and grew by 14.7% like-for-like. However, DIY retailing is gaining substantial development in the UK. Significantly lighter end of the market is top-rated and popular online across the channels due to the delivery suitability. It is speculated that the bigger-ticket items that are not suitable for delivery hinder DIY online retailing. Customers are intended to purchase bigger-ticket items from in-store. However, this does not justify when other large consumer items such as home appliances and furniture that are even larger have more online market penetration, 18%. However, during the pandemic, when most people had to remain home due to lockdown or social distancing, online sales skyrocketed in every category, and DIY online sales increased. This trend will continue throughout the coming years as customers are more comfortable with online ordering and delivery (Mintel,2020).

Underdeveloped digital offerings among specialists contribute to the slow development of market penetration alongside the size and nature of the DIY products. Although prominent market players, particularly specialists, are focusing and investing heavily in the digital channel, they are still catching up with the online channel.

As a result, it is no surprise that non-specialists (Sainsbury, Tesco), pure Online players (Amazon, eBay), generalists retailers such as Argos, Wilko filled the void and led the online DIY market. These retailers are favoured for their product range, the convenience of delivery and collection and price offerings.

Online competition is getting intense in recent years, being a highly competitive market (BIRA,2021). Amazon has consolidated itself as a market favourite for DIY in the past three years (Mintel,2020). Of all the competitors, Amazon outweighs all others in the inconvenience factor, particularly for amazon prime members who enjoy next-day delivery. This was even more significant during COVID lockdown throughout 2020 and onwards, while most big box DIY retailers remained closed or restricted due to social distancing (Amasanti, 2020).

The sharp growth of online retailing:

Online retailing is booming in the UK and across the world. 18.4% of total retail merchandise sold in the UK through the online channel in 2018. However, online retailing has seen a sharp growth during the pandemic and reached an all-time high; 36.1% of the total retail sale came through online in February 2021 (ONS,2021). This shift of sales in online cannibalised brick-and-mortar retailing (CRR,2020; Martins, 2021).

10.10. Appendix: Online market share of DIY retail sales

Figure 31: Total online sales as a % of total DIY retailing.

Source: Adapted from ONS (2021).

Economist Intelligence Unit (EIU) (2021) predicted that the online retail sale would cross over 25% of total retail sales, compared to 10% in 2019 globally. Though this overall online growth could slow in 2021, some categories will grow steadily. DIY and household category is one of them (Mintel,2020). In the UK, online retail sales grew exponentially in February 2021 compared to the same period in 2020; nearly half, 48%, of the online retail sales came from pure online players who don't have physical stores (ONS,2021; IR,2021). This shows that a solid online presence is a key to growth for retailers. Most importantly, DIY and Household store category have seen a sharp rise in online retail sales with 180% year-on-year growth in February 2021 compared to February 2020 (Dalglish, 2021; ONS, 2021; Rigby, 2021c).

Bhattacharyya (2021) affirmed that there would be winners and losers in a hyper-competitive sector during this digital market transformation, depending on the retailers' ability to move online and get new customers. However, while the businesses race to capitalise, the opportunities from the online shift, many businesses will fail to achieve profitability in the digital race. Moreover, Companies need to understand consumers behaviour and trend using

the latest technology to explore the market potential while managing the competition and regulatory barriers and cybersecurity (Bhattacharyya, 2021; IR, 2021).

10.11. Appendix: Global spending on DIY in e-commerce

Figure 32: Most popular online shopping categories worldwide in 2018.

Share of internet users who have purchased selected products online in the past 12 months as of 2018

Most popular online shopping categories worldwide 2018

Source: Adapted from Statista (2018), the latest available data worldwide.

In 2018, 57% of Internet users globally purchased fashion-related products, making clothing the most popular online shopping category worldwide. Footwear ranked second with 47% coverage of online purchases. Online Shopping In 2018, there were a total of 258.9 million digital shoppers in the United States. This figure is expected to rise to more than 307 million shoppers in 2023, reaching 79.2 and 90.8 per cent of US internet users, respectively. The fastest-growing e-commerce categories are food and beverages, with a CAGR of 12.7% between 2017 and 2023, compared to average industry growth of 8.7%. Online Retail in the US Overall, US customers were satisfied with electronic retailing as a whole, with online retailing scoring 82 out of 100 points on the US Customer Satisfaction Index (ACSI) from 2018. Years later, in which it scored the highest online retailer, customer satisfaction with Amazon dropped to 82/100 points, staying in line with the industry average. In February 2019, Amazon accounted for nearly half of the US retail e-commerce market, and eBay, in second place, didn't even hit double digits.

10.12. Appendix: Digital marketing tools from Yell.com

Figure 33: digital marketing tools from Yell.com.

Don't miss out on these FREE tools

Business Listing

Get listed on Yell.com - UK's No.1 online business directory*

Get a FREE listing

Reputation Report

Find out what customers see when they search for your business online

Run a FREE scan

Website Checker

Do search engines like Google and Bing love your website? Find out now

Check my website

*For all types of local businesses - Similarweb 2019

Compare the options

Feature	Free Listing	Starter	Prominence
	£0	£10/month	From £10/month
Prominence / Position	None	Above Free Listing	Wider range of options to target desired locations and categories
Listing on Yell.com	✓	✓	✓
Listing on Yell app	✓	✓	✓
Listing on Amazon Alexa devices (Echo, Echo Show & Alexa built-in devices)	✓	✓	✓
Listing on Apple location services (Maps, Siri, Spotlight)	✓	✓	✓
Listing on Bing (Maps and Cortana virtual assistant)	✓	✓	✓
Update and manage on the go	✓	✓	✓
Analytics dashboard	✓	✓	✓
Number of categories	1	1	unlimited. Choose from 2,500 options
Enhanced design	✓	✓	✓
Additional locations	✓	✓	✓
Call Counter telephone number	✓	✓	✓

Source: Screenshots taken from yell.com.

10.13. Interview Transcript: Respondent A7

Ashraf: I would like to welcome you and express my gratitude for participating in today's interview. I am Ashraf Hossain. I have already explained the purpose of this study and provided you with an information sheet and a consent form that details the interview procedure and how collected data will be handled. However, I would like to reiterate in short. Your participation in this interview is voluntary, and you were not paid or forced by any means to participate in this interview. This conversation will be recorded and kept confidential for the transcription of the interview and further analysis for the research. You and your business details would be kept anonymous, and any details will not be published that identifies you or your business. However, the recording may be shared with the research supervisor upon request. I would also like to assure you that you can withdraw at any time or refuse to answer any question that you do not feel like answering.

Ashraf: Do I have your permission to record this interview?

Respondent: Yes, please. That's absolutely fine.

Ashraf: How many stores do you have?

Respondent: One store in the East London area.

Ashraf: How many employees do you have?

Respondent: *I've got five full-time employees and me.*

Ashraf: Do you sell online or have your own website?

Respondent: *Yes, we sell on eBay and Amazon, and we also have our own website. But the website is not performing well compared to eBay and Amazon.*

Ashraf: How long are you in the DIY business?

Respondent: *I have been in this business for the last 13 years. Actually, I was working for a DIY store after leaving school. I worked there for more than ten years. Then, I started my own business.*

Ashraf: How long are you selling online?

Respondent: *I think, If I am not mistaken, I started selling on eBay and amazon in 2013, so it's been seven years, I would say.*

Ashraf: Would you please share your experience of how did you start selling on e-commerce?

Respondent: *When I started my store, back then, online was not that much popular. People used to come to the store, and business was good; until 2013, I was doing okay in business. I would say that around 2013, this online started booming. Everyone was rushing to join online, especially Amazon, then eBay came. People used to come to the store and compare prices with eBay and Amazon. Then I started looking for how to start because I didn't have much idea about this e-commerce thing. One of my friends was selling clothes on e-bay. So, I was interested in how he is doing it actually. Then I asked him, and he gave me some ideas and searched on google, which helped me also.*

Ashraf: Thank you very much.

What sort of technology do you have, like a computer, printer etc.?

Respondent: *Right now, I got two computers, one printer and I got internet.*

Ashraf: Have you faced any challenges in adopting e-commerce, and how did you overcome them?

Respondent: *Oh, it was difficult in the beginning. Everything was new to me, and I was not a tech guy, though I knew about computers and learned the process with time. As I said, I had help from my friend, and whenever I had difficulties, I used to consult with him. I didn't like all these hassles, but I had to keep the business going, and I was much young back then.*

I had a problem with account opening because I didn't know how to do that. Then learn how to fulfil the order and post them. I would say one thing Google and YouTube helped me a lot. Though I got some bits of help from my friends, they are busy. So, I just couldn't keep bothering them. So, instead, I learned from the internet.

Ashraf: What was your motivation to sell online?

Respondent: *I would say it was hype at that time. People were talking about e-commerce, and Amazon and eBay were booming. So, I saw it as an opportunity for my business.*

Ashraf: So, can we say that you saw the advantages of e-commerce, which affected their adoption decision?

Respondent: *Yes, you can say that, but I knew e-commerce would help my business, but I knew little about what will happen. I just wanted to do something for my business.*

Ashraf: What do you think about EC technology and how it affected e-commerce adoption decisions?

Respondent: *As I said, it was not straightforward to start. I didn't know how these things worked. Then I thought I would do it and just begin to random search on google how to start selling on e-bay, and I found some videos and some documents explaining some of that. I saw the video, and I found it a bit difficult, honestly. Due to these difficulties, I lost interest in it because of too many things, like listings and updated listings. After that, I went to my friend, and he showed me the listing area and showed me listing my product. Even after, I was like waiting for another 3 to 4 months. It's like I took some time to make the decisions.*

After, I was like, okay, let's do that. So, I got my personal account, so I tried to make it with my personal account at the beginning. But my friend said, do it with a business account. As I already have a business so registered with a business account on e-bay.

Ashraf: What would you say about independent retailers like you are facing these difficulties with e-commerce technology to adopt to e-commerce and sell there?

Respondent: *I would say there's no excuse not to learn anything, you know, pretty much with YouTube all the sorts of resources out there that, you know, there's pretty much you can learn what you need to set your business up and to develop it. You see, I would consider myself, so I know a bit of a lot. A lot of different things, you know what I mean. These days e-commerce costs peanuts. You can literally buy any software cheaper than your iPhone, but it was a different ball game when we started ten years ago.*

Ashraf: What do you think of the e-commerce adoption cost? How do you think that influenced or affected your adoption decision?

Respondent: *I think money is no problem, I was ready to invest, but I was concerned about when to get my money back. The cost of set up, like a computer, printer and other materials was not a problem for me I didn't think much about that. But I couldn't hire someone to do this for me as that was expensive, and I just couldn't hire someone without knowing that I would be making money.*

Ashraf: You said you could not do it initially by yourself, and you didn't hire anyone to do that; why didn't you employ someone who has more technical and e-commerce skills or train your staff?

Respondent: *Look, I already told you, I didn't know whether this online business would work out or not. Besides, I personally look after my business, and I have control over my business. Even if I have money, how will I trust my employee if I don't know what they are doing? And why I will spend my money to train my staff, they may leave the job after training.*

Ashraf: As you mentioned, you now sell on e-commerce marketplaces like eBay and Amazon, and you have a website too. How are these channels performing currently?

Respondent: *For us, it's eBay, we are doing better than Amazon, and our website is not doing much, not even 5% of our total online sales. I would say eBay is giving at least 70% online sales at this moment. We have done everything with our website, but people are not buying from our website. This is just a waste of time and money. So now, I am focusing on eBay only. Amazon is another headache. You have to remember that eBay is not competing with us. It's just business like me who is selling there, but they compete with us on Amazon.*

Ashraf: Apart from this, do you face any other challenges with these online channels?

Respondent: *Creating a product is quite a time consuming with eBay and with our own website. Getting the pictures right, putting the titles in, putting the descriptions in, the barcodes in, the weights, the postage, etc. When we started to sell on Amazon, literally, it was so easy for us as a third-party seller to begin listing our products on Amazon. It was almost too easy. You literally just type your barcode of the product into Amazon. And you could have that product listed for sale within minutes. Because obviously, Amazon is based around that product catalogue. So, if the product that you're selling exists in Amazon's product catalogue, you can literally list it for sale in seconds. If the product isn't listed in Amazon's catalogue, you have to put the same work to create that product as you would on your website and eBay.*

But because the majority of products that we were selling were not proprietary products, you know, they were direct from manufacturers, and wholesalers, a lot of the products that we were selling, were already on Amazon. And so, we got ourselves into a situation where we put too many products on Amazon too quickly. So, anyway, there is another problem with amazon: you most of the items they have the photos and description, and you do not have any control over them, but on eBay, you can write your description and add your own images.

Apart from this, they both take the customer side always, and some customers take advantage of this. Also, the commission is ridiculous, especially on Amazon. They have many changes, and they dominate the price and terms and conditions. I wish I could avoid Amazon, but there is no choice. They are too big, and people buy from them.

Ashraf: How do you process your order like order fulfilment? And what are the challenges do you face?

Respondent: *It's very much manual and traditional that I like to follow. When anything sells, I get notifications on my phone and eBay and Amazon dashboard. I have RM Click and Drop business account, and all my bills are integrated into the Click and Drop. Orders automatically go there, and we print postage labels according to the parcel size and weight. Then, at the end of the day, we drop them at to post office. Sometimes, we use UPS, Hermes, and other services if they are large and heavy items.*

It's crucial to check the item before you send to customers because reviews matter on these sites and customer are really sensitive. Most customers leave an honest review, but few customers leave bad reviews for the slightest issue.

Ashraf: Do you get bad reviews often, or it is rare?

Respondent: *Ahhhh, basically, we try to solve it before customers put bad reviews if they communicate with us for any issues. Things happen when you buy online. Maybe or it is not exactly what they want or anything else. If customers contact us, we try to solve the problem, most cases we offer replacement or money back. But in some cases, customers don't want to communicate, of even we try to resolve it, they still leave a negative review. What you can you do? This is a part of the business.*

Ashraf: Since you are selling on e-commerce platforms, and you mentioned there are challenges. I would like to ask you, what are the advantages you are enjoying?

Respondent: *Of course, it's better for us, otherwise why we would sell there. Without these sales, we would've been out of business long ago. As you know, store sales are not that fantastic, and people mostly buy online these days. Mainly, we had an excellent business online during the lockdown. Our sales grew up by at least ten times. Still, eBay and amazon pay for the wages and rents for my business. Also, I can buy more and get a better rate. For some items, you just need six pcs in a month for the store, but you cannot just buy six things. You need to buy more for wholesale discount. Importantly, now I can buy more from the suppliers using their credit and pay off*

before time because online money circulates fast. I usually have 30-45 days credit terms. But I sell those items few times within this time and get paid and pay later to the suppliers. The market is competitive, so you must take everything into account.

Ashraf: Is it helping your competition as you said it is a competitive market?

Respondent: *Honestly speaking, yes. The guy across the road sells the same stuff, but I can tell they are doing like us. Our price is better than them. I can tell you their cost price is at least 20-30 % higher than us because they buy from cash and carry. If you buy from the company directly, they are at least 20% cheaper than cash and carry. We can directly purchase from the company because we can clear them quickly.*

Ashraf: How about online competition?

Respondent: *It's a different game where you are competing with big guys like B&Q Homebase. Still, it is profitable. For me, I just sell a little cheaper than the store and charge for the postage.*

Businesses are born with competition, so there is no way to get rid of it. However, I think you got to know how to minimize the competition. So obviously, customer retention is a big part that helps to reduce competition, because if you keep the good quality product and provide a quality customer service, customers would love to come back to you."

Ashraf: Is there any other benefits of selling on e-commerce?

Respondent: *I have five staff and myself. I actually don't need that many people only for the store. If it is not online sales, I would've cut down to 2 staff only and myself. We may need another team for picking and packing. So, this is a blessing for us. People are getting a job. It's a good sign, and I am happy that I can keep my staff.*

Ashraf: Thank you very much.

I am just wondering, have you tried any other marketplaces, mainly social media like Facebook, Instagram or Gumtree?

Respondent: *I don't like Gumtree because once I was cheated by them in 2014 around house rent issues. I don't like them. It's my opinion. But, I know about the Facebook*

marketplace. I have an account on Facebook. I saw people sell a lot of things on Facebook. But I really don't feel like selling on Facebook. I don't think people would buy DIY items from Facebook. Maybe later.

Ashraf: Thanks for your time, though. I know how busy you are. I have some more questions. If you allow me, I can ask.

Respondent: *Please go on.*

Ashraf: As you said, you struggled in the beginning to start e-commerce. Have you received any support from any companies or institutional support to start e-commerce or progress in training or information?

Respondent: *To be honest, no. I didn't know whether any such support was available. I needed some training, but I didn't know any of them. It would be better if we get such training. As I said, we are not doing well on our website. I don't know what to do. I cannot hire any big people to do that for me. If I knew how the website works, that would've been better. It's only Google and YouTube I get help, but you know it's not easy as they say there.*

Ashraf: Thank you.

Ashraf: I would like to address one more area. Are you selling to the international market using e-commerce?

Respondent: *Yes, I do.*

Ashraf: That's interesting. How do you do that?

Respondent: *We just list on eBay and Amazon they offer to their customer at international markets. We send them like any other orders. We get at least 10% of our orders from all over the world. Mostly from eBay.*

Interestingly, I get more orders from Germany. Though I charge extra postage costs for international I orders, still, people buy. I think they love British products.

Ashraf: Do you do anything different to sell internationally?

Respondent: *I don't think so. We just list like normal on eBay and Amazon. For eBay one good thing is if you sell anything internally, you can just send it to the eBay in the UK like domestic delivery, rest is their headache. they charge customers postage, taxes and everything. Amazon is little different, because we don't do FBA, so We have to send them to customer by ourselves. But it's easy, we book via RM international standard, and they deliver.*

I must say, it was easy before like selling in the UK. No little bit more paper works, but I can manage that.

Ashraf: Do you get order from cross-border markets on your website?

Respondent: *Ha ha.. (laughing). We don't get order from the UK let alone cross border markets. Never received any order from outside of the UK.*

Ashraf: What do you think of all these channels and what should be the starting point for business like you who want to start e-commerce?

Respondent: *I would say, in my experience, eBay should be the priority for the new seller. It has little formality to start with, people with little knowledge can start, but Amazon is complex and require many formalities. Plus, selling abroad is easy on eBay. I wouldn't recommend website to begin with. First, they need to learn the process of everything related to e-commerce, then they can start website.*

Ashraf: Is there any point that you would like to add overall?? About eBay or your business?

Respondent: *Ok. I like to add about payment process of e-bay. Payment comes through PayPal. I spend 6 months to feel comfortable with PayPal. Because you can't sell without PayPal people do not rely on you and PayPal also charge for it. I really don't understand why they charged like 50p or 1 pound without doing anything except keeping our money. I don't think that small businesses are happy with that.*

Ashraf: Thank you for your valuable comments and opinion. We are almost at the end of the interview. I have to ask you some personal questions that are related to this study. Though, you can refuse to answer if you do like to answer.

What age group you put yourself? Like 20 to 30 or 30 to 40 or 40 to 50.

Respondent: *Its alright. I am 35 years old.*

Ashraf: Well. That's very much straightforward answer for me.

What is your education label?

Respondent: *I completed my bachelor s degree after that I started my business.*

Ashraf: Do you think your education helps you to run it business.

Respondent: *For businesses basically, it is my personal opinion, it is important how interested you are and how hungry you are for making money is important rather than how many degrees you have. Its all about willingness to lean and do things and you have to extremely patient about it because you will not get at top very easily. you have work hard and wait for right time. So, I would say my education helps me learn things, but I don't think so it is that much important.*

Ashraf: Thank you very much. This is the end of our interview today. I really appreciate your time and valuable opinion. I will transcribe this recording for further analysis purpose. Would you mind if I contact you again for any further clarification? If you have any further question about the interview, you can contact me on the contact details given on the information sheet. I may send the transcription to you for your authorisation to make sure that I have recorded and understood the accurate statements of you.

Respondent: *It's alright. You have my number and email. You can contact me, no problem. Good luck to your research.*

Ashraf: Thank you. You have a lovely day. Stay safe.

Thank You